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ALLINTERACT

Report 1:

“How social actors benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education”

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1. Introduction

ALLINTERACT, Widening and diversifying citizen engagement in science is a Horizon 2020 project that aims on the one hand, to create new knowledge about how to transform potential citizen participation in science into actual engagement in scientific research with social impact and on the other hand to discover new ways to engage societal actors in research, including young citizens (16-29 years old) and vulnerable groups that have traditionally been marginalized from science (e.g., low socioeconomic background, ethnic and religious minorities, women, LGBTQI). In order to achieve this twofold overall objective, six specific objectives were established. This report aims to respond to objective O1) to identify in both, face to face interactions and social media interactions, how societal actors, including young citizens and vulnerable groups, benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education. This is done in the framework of two Sustainable Development Goals –Quality Education and Gender Equality – and with a mixed method approach, by using a literature review, analytics of social media, communicative focus groups and a survey.

2. Methodology

The methodology of this report is grounded on four data collection techniques: a literature review, analysis of social media, communicative focus groups and a survey. Regarding the first technique, the literature review aims to explore how citizens' benefit from scientific research with a focus on gender and education. It has been conducted by retrieving articles published in top-ranked journals indexed in Journal Citation Reports and Scopus and the analysis includes the benefits regarding the social impact, the policy impact and the scientific impact. A total of 75 articles have been included in the final sample and reviewed in depth. As for the analysis of social media, it includes the Social Media Analytics (SMA) which aims to collect interactions among users on diverse social networks and analyse this data quantitatively and qualitatively and the Social Media Communicative Observation (SMCO), which aims to explore the impact on citizens' participation and awareness of introducing scientific evidences in social media interactions. Regarding SMA, it has followed a twofold strategy, including bottom-up and top-down approaches. It has been implemented on Twitter Facebook, Reddit and Instagram. The final sample has included a total of 19,194 messages. The SMCO has been conducted on Facebook and Reddit for 6 months and on the evidence-based platforms Sappho and Adhyayana for 15 months, with a total sample of 21,322 members. Third, ALLINTERACT consortium has implemented 12 Focus Groups (FG) (6 on gender/6 on education) with women, including youth and vulnerable women, LGBTI+ individuals, students, parents and teachers in Italy, Spain, United Kingdom, Finland, Portugal and the Netherlands. These FG collected the voices of society regarding the benefits of scientific research. Finally, a survey has been conducted with 7507 participants from 13 European countries (with a balanced number of EU members, considering their relative size and geographical area) in order collect quantitative data about how citizens' benefit from scientific research and the impact of interactions with science.

3. Results

The main results point to four contributions: 1) Research with social impact has co-creation at the core of the intervention, 2) Egalitarian dialogue involving all sectors of society contributes to the social impact of research, 3) Interactions with science contribute to the identification of scientific evidence

and hoax in gender and education and 4) Social media is an effective agora to share and discuss about science.

Research with social impact has co-creation at the core of the intervention

The literature review concluded that actions that give importance to the co-creation of knowledge that combine scientific evidence and local knowledge provided by communities achieve greater impact in education in diverse educational contexts, including schools, high schools, universities, and informal learning centres. Therefore, in order to build fair and sustainable societies, researchers should create spaces for the co-production of knowledge and the interaction between scientific knowledge provided by universities and experience-based knowledge provided by citizens. Some examples in this regard can be found in SMA, where the messages that contained real examples of social impact of research consisted of actions promoted by NGOs involving all members of communities and were explicitly linked to the achievement of SDGs, or Wikipedia, as an accurate and reliable encyclopaedia that has its basis on certified scientific sources and co-creation of knowledge. Another example is found in the FG, where participants remarked that Dialogic Scientific Gatherings - one of the Successful Educational Actions that is based on the co-creation of knowledge through reading and discussing scientific works- promoted scientific literacy among participants, as well as interest towards science, empowerment and self-confidence. In addition, Dialogic Scientific Gathering promoted the participation in scientific events (gatherings, talks or conferences) in the associations/schools, encouraged teachers to make new scientific activities inside their school and improve the atmosphere among teachers of the same school.

Egalitarian dialogue involving all sectors of society contributes to the social impact of research

Existing scientific evidence analysed in the literature review points that changes in legislation improve education for all when they have two key characteristics: are based on scientific evidence in the field of education and give high priority to the engagement of an egalitarian dialogue with community members. Therefore, the scalability and transference of educational practice depends on the characteristics of the dialogue shared during the process between all stakeholders. In the same direction, on SMA, a common finding across social networks and strategies is that within the examples of real cases of social impact of research there were messages that share the impact achieved by specific actions in the promotion of women political participation, black women health, access to water, financial and technical women empowerment, and COVID-19 gender labour gap, among others. These messages provided examples of how NGOs, partnerships of NGOs, educational settings, companies, citizens' platforms and universities in dialogue with communities benefit from specific research outcomes that were improving citizens' lives and responding to the challenges of society. Another related example is obtained from the qualitative data of the FG, where participants expressed that the egalitarian dialogue shared in the Scientific Dialogic Gatherings encourages people to be curious, to increase the knowledge of scientific vocabulary and provides the motivation for people to transform their environment, while improving the educational practices of the teachers.

Interactions with science contribute to the identification of scientific evidence and hoax in gender and education

Qualitative data from the FG support this finding. Participants expressed that the use of social media for research dissemination purposes was very important, as it contributes to teach people how to identify verified content from fake news. Quantitative data from the survey points to the same

direction. The results show that interactions with science increase both, people who identify a hoax statement as a hoax and the proportion of respondents who identify an evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, contributing to the identification of evidence and hoaxes. One example of the identification of scientific evidence and hoaxes can be found in SMA, especially on Twitter and Reddit where users are more likely to interact with those messages that are based on scientific evidence than with those without it.

Social media is an effective agora to share and discuss about science.

The analysis of social networks enabled to identify how researchers succeed at reaching citizens when sharing their research on social media and also how users adopt scientific concepts and arguments and discuss about scientific topics on the different social networks. Although the four analysed networks (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and Reddit) have different characteristics and purposes, all of them are used for any of these purposes. In addition, citizens value scientific contributions on social media, use them in discussions on social media and in some cases ask for scientific evidence, showing that they value scientific research when this research achieves social impact that truly improve their lives. In the same vein, women participants and especially youth express in the FG that they learn and benefit from the scientific, political and social impact of scientific research via social media. In addition, participants mentioned that social media may boost scientific research due to the conversations running through different timelines and platforms. In this sense, they are perceived as an input for researchers about the topics that interest social media users and population in general, and which could result in new researches or studies. For this reason, scientific research should use social media in order to disseminate results. Quantitative results from the survey also support this finding as identified that following someone on social media who often publishes about science is the most effective interaction with science in the promotion of scientific literacy and identification of evidence and hoaxes. Finally, participants in the SMCO expressed that social media allowed them to reflect, argue, motivate them to learn more and to engage in virtual dialogue with other users about what they have found in scientific articles, their experiences, or their point of view.

4. Conclusions

This report explored how citizens benefit from scientific research in gender and education, by identifying what elements facilitate (transformative dimension) and what obstacles hinder (exclusionary dimension) the targeted impacts in order to overcome them and achieve scientific, political and social impact. Therefore, among the main elements that facilitate scientific, political and social impact there are co-creation of scientific knowledge, egalitarian dialogue with all sectors of society (including those that have traditionally been excluded from science), interactions with science and social media interactions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The overall task of WP1 of the ALLINTERACT project is to explore how societal actors, including young citizens and vulnerable groups, benefit from the social impact of scientific research in regard to the SDGs of Quality Education and Gender Equality.

In order to respond to this objective, a series of tasks have been conducted, namely a Literature Review, Social Media Analytics, Focus Groups and a Survey. Different Consortium partners have been involved in the aforementioned tasks and analyses that integrate this report coordinated by the University of Barcelona.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview

In response to O1, the literature review on how social actors benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education was conducted. The methodology followed in retrieving literature reviews in both fields, the results of the literature review, and the main conclusions are presented below, respectively. Findings of this literature review inform the design and development of the social media communicative intervention, which is presented in Chapter 3 of this report, the focus groups, which are presented in chapter 4, the survey which is presented in chapter 5, as well as of the interventions and policy recommendations which will be presented in other deliverables of the project.

2.2 Citizens' benefits from research impact in gender

2.2.1 Overview

This section provides information regarding the literature review of how citizens' benefit from the social impact of research on gender, corresponding to ALLINTERACT's O1. With this aim, a systematic literature review has been conducted in Scopus and the Web of Science scientific databases. In addition grey literature has been searched to complete the task. Section 2.2 of this report includes the methodology followed in this literature review, with a focus on gender, the results obtained and the main conclusions. The results were analysed and grouped into three categories: the social, political and scientific impact of research on gender from which citizens have benefitted. The results inform the design and development of the focus group in gender which is explained in chapter 4, as well as the survey (chapter 5), the interventions and the policy commendations which will be presented in other work packages of the project according to the aim they contribute to. Researchers from ISCSP-ULisboa and UB have participated in the elaboration of this section.

2.2.2. Methodology

The aim of this literature review is to explore existing social science research regarding how citizens benefit from scientific research in gender. To do that, scientific literature in the research area of Social Sciences published between 2010-2021 in journals indexed by Scopus and the Web of Science scientific databases was identified. Article is the document type set when searching for literature in Scopus and the Web of Science. Searches in both databases were conducted in English. In addition, impact factors were also been considered when conducting literature searches. Specifically, Q1 and Q2 journals for the searches made on Web of Science, and Q1 journals for the searches made on Scopus. To complete the task, grey literature has also been searched.

The following combinations of keywords were used to do the articles' research in Scopus and Web of Science:

- 1) gender and social impact of research
- 2) gender and social impact of gender research
- 3) social benefits of research on gender
- 4) social benefits of gender research
- 5) science social impact and gender inequalities
- 6) science social impact on / and gender
- 7) "scientific evidence" AND gender policy
- 8) evidence-based policy AND gender
- 9) gender-based AND polic* AND scientific evidence
- 10) "social impact" AND "gender-based"
- 11) "social impact" AND gender AND intervention

Regarding Web of Science database, searches were made following a specific procedure:

- Firstly, a general search of the keywords on all the indexes belonging to the Web of Science Core Collection.
- Secondly, a specific search of the keywords on Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI).
- Thirdly, a specific search applying the data range exclusion criteria.
- Fourthly, a specific search applying the "article" and "journal" criteria.
- Fifthly, a specific search selecting only a list of the main Social Sciences areas.
- A final selection applying "Q1" and "Q2" exclusion criteria.

In the case of Scopus, searches were made as follows:

- Firstly, keyword searches were made applying the first filter: "Article, Abstract, Keywords".
- Secondly, a specific search applying the data range exclusion criteria.
- Thirdly, a specific search applying the "Social Sciences" criteria.
- Fourthly, a specific search applying the "article" and "journal" criteria.
- A final selection applying "Q1" exclusion criteria.

Figure 2.1. Methodology process for the literature review on gender

A total of 285 articles resulted after the searching on Web of Science database and Scopus, of which 234 were out of scope, 11 were discarded due to lack of journal impact, 24 due to lack of evidence of impact of research and 3 were repeated. In addition, 21 additional articles were added from searches on education or topic “b”.

A final sample of 34 articles matched the selection criteria for topic a, and thus were reviewed and selected for the analysis. Selected articles were classified in 3 categories: 1. Benefits from social impact, 2. Benefits from political impact, and 3. Benefits from scientific impact. For each of these the transformative dimension (i.e. what facilitates the targeted impact) and the exclusionary dimension (i.e. obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted impact) have been identified. Data has been classified according to the established categories (1-3) and dimensions as outlined in the Work Plan M1-M7 (see the following table).

Table 2.1. Analysis grid

TOPIC a) How citizens’ benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which have contributed to the advancement of science with social impact)</i>
Transformative Dimension			

Exclusionary Dimension			
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Next, within the different categories, the following subcategories were identified

Table 2.2. Categories and subcategories of the analysis on gender

Categories	Subcategories
Benefits from social impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Overcoming of gender violence b. Promotion of women empowerment
Benefits from political impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Overcoming of gender violence b. Policy recommendations
Benefits from scientific impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Influence of gender-diverse authorships in the scientific impact of research b. The gender pay gap c. The role of gender conceptualization in the emergence of inequalities d. Proposal and conceptualization of research methodologies that include the gender perspective

2.2.3 Results

34 articles were identified about how citizens benefit from the social impact of research in gender. The results were classified according to the type of impact produced in “benefits from social impact”, “benefits from political impact” and “benefits from scientific impact”, as presented in figure 2.2:

Figure 2.2. Proportion of articles in each category (Gender)

2.2.3.1. Benefits from social impact

Social impact refers to the way the results of research benefit citizens' lives. Therefore, this impact is achieved when, once the results of research have been published and disseminated, they improve citizens' lives in relation to the objectives of society, such as the Sustainable Development Goals. In this line, the articles analysed contained examples of how research in the field of gender can improve citizens' lives. This way, the articles can be categorised in 2 groups, depending on the type of social impact that provide: a. The overcoming of gender violence, and b. the promotion of women empowerment.

a. Overcoming gender violence

Article in subcategory a.Overcoming gender violence, included studies that contribute to the overcoming of gender violence in different contexts, including high schools (Duby et al., 2021; Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Merodio et al., 2020; Rodrigues-Mello et al., 2021), universities (Puigvert et al., 2019) and the media (Pulido et al., 2021). The article within this category can be grouped in 2 subgroups: those presenting evidence of interventions aimed at the prevention of gender violence and those presenting evidence about breaking the silence about gender-based violence in universities.

Regarding the former, interventions for the prevention of gender-based violence, four articles provide scientific evidence of the social impact achieved by these programs (Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Merodio et al., 2020; Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Vidu et al., 2020; Racionero-Plaza et al., 2021; Rodrigues-Mello et al., 2021) have been identified. All the articles have some characteristics in common that are the cornerstone of the impacts achieved. This way, all programs proposed evidence-based interventions based on the following aspects (Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Merodio et al., 2020; Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Vidu et al., 2020; Racionero-Plaza et al., 2021; Rodrigues-Mello et al., 2021):

1. The claim that love and attraction are social, and therefore their patterns can be changed through socialisation,
2. The language of desire that empties violence of attractiveness, and
3. The identification of different types of masculinities, including New Alternative Masculinities (NAM).

This way, although all programs include unique characteristics, they are all grounded on the scientific contributions of preventive socialisation of gender violence. Some of the differences between interventions are related to the structure of the sessions. While the study conducted by Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Vidu and colleagues (2020) was centred in the reading of the book *Radical Love* and the intervention from Rodrigues-Mello et al. (2021) was designed around the Spanish version of the movie *Three Steps above Heaven*. Other interventions included seven sessions, in which topics such as infidelity, consent, the dominant coercive discourse, the social nature of love or new alternative masculinities (Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Merodio et al., 2020; Racionero-Plaza et al., 2021). The main impacts achieved by these articles are related to the awareness-raising about the existence and impacts of the coercive dominant discourse (Racionero-Plaza et al., 2021; Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde,

Merodio et al., 2020), the emergence of feelings of disgust or disappointment towards violent men (Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Vidu et al., 2020 ; Rodrigues-Mello et al., 2021), an enhance of the attraction towards egalitarian masculinities (Racioner-Plaza, Ugalde, Merodio et al., 2020; Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Vidu et al., 2020), a better identification of gender-based violence (Racionero-Plaza et al., 2021) and the rejection of violent relationships and giving better advice to their friends (Racionero-Plaza, Ugalde, Merodio et al., 2020; Racionero-Plaza et al., 2021). Finally, a common issue across all these studies is that they share scientific evidence with the participants and encourage discussion among participants based on the scientific evidence provided, contributing to the co-creation of knowledge.

The second subgroup gathers articles which present evidence on breaking the silence about gender-based violence in universities and includes its impact on health (Aubert & Flecha, 2021), on journalism (Pulido et al., 2021) and on Spanish universities (Puigvert et al., 2019). The research conducted by Puigvert and colleagues (2019) explored the social impact of the first research that aimed to break the silence about gender based violence at Spanish University, using the Communicative Evaluation of Social Impact (CESI). The dialogic spaces created under the Communicative Evaluation of Social Impact enabled the sharing of narratives from university stakeholders in which they provided evidence of the social impacts at personal and university levels. Through this Communicative Evaluation of social Impact, the authors concluded that the research that broke the silence about gender violence at Spanish universities achieved social impacts related to the creation of appropriate conditions for the reporting of gender violence, the overcoming of the fear of reporting, the establishment of solidarity relationships with and among the victims and the awareness-raising about gender violence at universities.

In a similar vein, another of the articles aimed to explore the health and well-being consequences of Isolating Gender Violence (IGV) on gender violence survivors and people who supported them, through three narratives of gender violence survivors (Aubert & Flecha, 2021). According to the authors, these three narratives enabled for the first time, to identify the impact of IGV on survivors of gender violence. On the one hand, in the exclusionary dimension, the authors found that gender violence and IGV negatively impacted health (physically and psychologically) and well-being of survivors. On the other hand, in the transformative dimension, because of the support received, survivors could process a formal complaint and mitigate the consequences of gender-based violence. In this vein, survivors stated that thanks to the support received by their advocates, they were able to cope with the situation and to become successful survivors.

Finally, in the article by Pulido and colleagues (2021), the authors explored the impact of the documentary "Voices against Silence" (Golden Globe Award at the 2018 World Media Festival, Hamburg), through the Social Impact of Social Media methodology and 14 interviews. "Voices against Silence" is a documentary about sexual violence in Spain through victims' voices. Among the cases included in the documentary, there is a case about sexual harassment at university, specifically about the first collective complainant of a professor. The documentary also reports the second order sexual harassment suffered by advocates who support the survivors. By collecting citizen' voices on social media (Twitter and Facebook), researchers concluded that the documentary contributed to increase

the visibility of sexual violence and gave a Voice to survivors, addressing revictimization and overcoming Second Order Sexual Harassment.

b. Promotion of women empowerment

Three of the selected articles focus on the promotion of women empowerment. According to Humphries et al. (2012), the potential of participatory agricultural platforms goes beyond agriculture. To understand the broader social impacts of participatory agricultural platforms and the relationship between participatory agricultural platforms and empowerment, Humphries et al. (2012) examined the gendered impacts of a long-term farmer research project in Honduras. When the article was published, the authors explained that the project had been ongoing for 18 years. From an exclusionary point of view, barriers preventing women from making informed decisions were: lack of opportunities to participate in economic development initiatives and organisations; local masculinity limiting their freedom; traditional family roles for women; and their limited access to knowledge. However, the results of the study also showed that women increasingly made more informed decisions after participating in the programme, they perceived they had more friends, they left the house more often, they were more able to present and talking in group, they knew their own rights better, they learned to be timely and organised and they had more confidence to join other organisations and to collaborate with others. Moreover, men's pride in the self-confidence and accomplishments of their wives who participated in the project can also confirm the project's contribution to gendered change. All these support the role of the participatory agricultural platforms in opening spaces for overcoming gender inequalities and providing support for empowerment. Among the key elements that enabled the success of this programme were: an inclusive environment where women felt valued, the provision of opportunities for women to engage in their communities to provide tangible improvements in food security, and the solidarity built between women and men within the programme.

Another article in this line reported a participatory community-wide intervention that aimed to change gender perceptions, to raise awareness about gender inequalities and to improve school opportunities for girls in rural Ethiopia (Visser et al., 2021). In order to do so, the intervention included a community approach characterised by the participation of different stakeholders, such as students, parents, teachers and other school staff. A total of 30 schools participated in the study that lasted 3 years. During this time, researchers assessed gender perceptions of girls, their parents and their teachers through interviews and group discussions. The interventions included 1) actions for schools, such as capacity-building trainings for teachers to include gender-sensitive curriculum or gender action committees for female teachers to address girls' necessities, among others; as well as 2) interventions for girls, such as provision of sanitary pads and separate toilets, additional classes in core subjects or counselling groups about reproductive health and gender issues. As a result of the intervention, researchers found impacts in schools, such as the inclusion of parents in decision-making processes or tutorial classes for girls, among others; teachers' attitudes that encouraged girls' educational opportunities, increased parental support and improvement of girls' self-esteem.

Finally, another article in this regard was the study conducted by DUBY and colleagues (2021), which included an intervention for young women in South Africa focused on sexual and reproductive health.

The intervention included peer-group clubs about gender equality that aimed to boost girls' self-esteem and empowerment, as well as to create supportive networks in safe spaces, with the final objective of improving girls' wellbeing and mental health. The interventions were conducted in 5 South African districts. To explore the impacts of these interventions, researchers conducted 57 in-depth interviews and 19 focus group discussions with 185 participants, and also in-depth interviews with teachers (N=10), facilitators (N=14) and implementers (N=13) and 2 focus groups with 14 facilitators. As a result of the interventions, the authors reported an increase of girls' self-esteem and empowerment, the creation of supportive and peer networks and an improvement of girls' wellbeing due to the emotional support and guidance provided. According to the authors, the key elements of the intervention that made these impacts possible were peer support and emotional support, the provision of safe spaces, the community approach of the intervention and the possibility to interact with positive role models.

2.2.3.2. Benefits from political impact

The second category is related to the political impact of research, which can be defined as the transference of the results of research to institutions, administrations, organisations, policymakers and citizens, who use these results to design policies or to improve plans, actions and programs.

a. Overcoming of gender violence

The main examples of the political impact of research in gender equality were related to the overcoming of gender violence. The first impact in this regard is found in the article from Vidu and colleagues (2021). This article provided evidence of the impact achieved by the research that broke the silence about gender violence at Spanish universities. The political impact of this research includes the evidence-based legislation of the second-order violence (SOV) in the Catalan Parliament for the first time in history, which was legally defined as "the physical or psychological violence, retaliation, humiliation, and persecution exercised against people who provide support to victims of sexist violence" (p. 9). This advance in legislation is aligned with the scientific research that identified the necessity of public policies that give protection to the people who can overcome the silence about gender violence. The second article about the political impact of research in gender violence was conducted by Puigvert and colleagues (2019) and explained how, as a result of a scientific research that broke the silence about gender violence at universities, researchers and policymakers discussed scientific findings and contributions related to the preventive socialisation of gender-based violence, which created opportunities to address gender violence in universities. One example in this regard was a change in legislation approved in 2007, which required that Spanish Universities had to have equality units and protocols for the prevention of sexual harassment.

b. Policy recommendations

Additionally, there are also several examples of articles that, although they do not provide evidence of the political impact of research; they provide recommendations for policymakers, governments, companies and professionals for the elaboration of gender evidence-based policies or programs. These recommendations can be grouped in 1) recommendations for the overcoming of gender

violence and 2) recommendations for the promotion of gender equality in companies, research teams and firms.

The recommendations for the overcoming of gender violence included diverse contexts. First, in the university context, Ruiz-Eugenio et al. (2020) analysed the preferences for sporadic and stable relationships of female university students. Their results pointed to the existence of a coercive dominant discourse that links attractiveness with violent behaviours. Specifically, when female students were asked about the type of man that they would choose for hooking up, 28.42% chose a man with violent behaviour. On the contrary, when they were asked for the type of man for a stable relationship, only 5.78% chose that type of man. The authors conclude that these results dismantle the idea that gender-based violence occurs only in stable relationships and therefore, they recommend the inclusion of gender violence in sporadic relationships in campaigns and programs that aim to prevent gender violence to young women. According to the authors, these campaigns and programs should base their action on scientific evidence and thus, reverse the dominant coercive discourse that links attractiveness with violence.

Second, another article that provided recommendations for the prevention of gender violence and sexual exploitation was elaborated by Melgar et al. (2021) and addressed the trajectories of sex-trafficked minors in Morocco and Spain. As a result of their research, they identified that recruitment processes had two common elements. On the one hand, girls arrive in a city in an irregular situation and on the other hand, they used to have low educational levels and poor work experience. Based on these results, the authors state that in order to address these challenges, it is required to implement primary prevention measures and programmes to promote successful educational trajectories for girls in their countries of origin.

Regarding the second subgroup “recommendations for the promotion of gender equality”, some of the articles analysed the impact of gender-diverse teams in efficiency and firm performance to provide evidence for the elaboration of evidence-based gender policies. This is the case, for example, of the study conducted by Valls Martínez and his colleagues (2020). Previous studies indicated the relationship between female directors and corporate social performance is positively correlated. To delve further into this topic, Valls Martínez and colleagues (2020) explored the impact of women on boards on the corporate social performance of their companies and compared the behaviour of the US and European markets. They considered American companies which were included in the S&P 500 index and European companies included in the Euro Stoxx 300 index. The findings indicated that gender diversity on the board benefits corporate social responsibility performance and, in turn, that promoting gender equality benefits, not only women at individual level, but society as a whole. This provides evidence for policymakers to strengthen gender policies. Similarly, Zhang’s study (2020) presents findings from a more global perspective. In their case, they examined data from 35 countries and 24 industries around the world to analyse the relationship between gender diversity and firm performance. The authors understand normative acceptance of gender diversity as the acceptance, in shared organisational norms and values, of practices and strategies as appropriate, useful and desirable. The results showed that this normative acceptance of gender diversity could increase market valuations and revenue in a country or industry. According to the authors, this happens

because when gender diversity is normatively accepted, all workers are more likely to accept it in their workplace and to adopt open attitudes in their interactions that promote that women feel valued and respected. However, due to the differences in institutional approach to the acceptance of gender diversity (normative or regulatory), the relationship between gender diversity and firm performance varied significantly across countries and industries. In this line, in those countries with a normative approach towards the acceptance of gender diversity, this diversity is valuable, and investors and workers perceive that it can improve productivity and decision-making processes. On the contrary, in those countries with a regulatory approach to gender diversity, women are more likely to suffer discrimination and negative stereotyping, which hinders their opportunities to positively contribute to firm performance. That highlights the role of social context in the relationship between gender diversity and firm performance.

Other studies focused on Research & Development (R&D) teams make similar recommendations. For instance, Xie and his colleagues (2020) focused on the effect of gender diversity within research R&D teams on firms' innovation efficiency, in the Chinese context. They used data on manufacturing firms in one of China's coastal provinces and the information on companies registered in the province with annual sales of more than 5 million yuan. The study showed that gender diversity in R&D teams had a positive relation with innovation efficiency. Specifically, when R&D teams incorporate gender diversity, they produce high-quality innovations, better communication throughout the innovation process and innovations that bring more social benefits for communities. In addition, although large and well-performing firms typically had good innovation efficiency, R&D team size was negatively related to innovation efficiency. Therefore, one of the conclusions of the study was that having R&D teams with a great number of employees was not a key element to guarantee high innovation efficiency. In light of this evidence, the authors suggested that policymakers should provide more societal support for women as they are essential to the development of innovation capacity. In a similar way, the study of Zouaghi (2020) explored how the diversity dimension (gender, skills and education) in R&D teams interacted to drive innovation. The results indicated that the diversity variables (gender, skills, and education) had positive relationships with product and process innovations.

In the same line, Kamerlin and Wittung-Stafshede (2020) identified the key elements behind the success of a Gender Initiative for Excellence called Genie, in order to provide recommendations for further programs. Genie's objective is to promote excellence at the university with the promotion of gender equality and the representation of female faculty. This initiative achieved good results, such as the provision of tools, the support to female scientists and awareness-raising of gender inequalities in academia. After analysing the initiative, the authors identified 3 key elements that made possible the success and could increase replicability: 1) Genie was a bottom-up initiative coordinated by university staff and not by administrators, 2) it had external funding and 3) its long lifespan contributed to introducing permanent changes.

Other recommendations regarding policy were aligned with the promotion and engagement of women in STEM. While one of the studies included the exposure of women to counter stereotypical experiences (Di Bella & Crisp, 2016), the other highlights the importance of role models (van Veelen

et al. 2019). On the one hand, Di Bella and Crisp (2016) adopted a perspective based on the promotion of women in STEM rather than in the analysis of what prevents women from pursuing a STEM career. Therefore, their orientation toward social transformation brought them to the conclusion that gender equality in STEM fields is not only a matter of building a fair society, but it brings cognitive benefits for women as well, as this exposure can be protective, and it can encourage women's flexibility in STEM fields. As a conclusion, the authors stated that policymakers and universities should highlight in their programs and policies that women's choice to enrol and pursue a STEM career brings benefits to them other than the degree itself. Therefore, these policies should pay special attention to all other benefits, which include more resilience to stereotypes or better cognitive flexibility, among others. Still regarding STEM, van Veelen and colleagues (2019) investigated how being a woman in male-dominated STEM sectors constituted a source of threat to social identity. In their study, they included 177 female and 630 male STEM graduates in the Netherlands. Their results point to the importance of the representation of women in the STEM sector because when women are represented in STEM fields, they experience less threat in their gender identity and therefore, they are more likely to engage at work and to feel career confidence. In light of this evidence, the authors argue that STEM organisations should improve gender equality, both in terms of increasing female representation and eliminating negative gender stereotypes.

Finally, the article by Reidl and colleagues (2020) presents the results of a literature review on typologies of welfare state and gender equality regimes to provide key characteristics for the differentiation of gender equality regimes and evaluation regimes in Research, Technology Development and Innovation (RTDI). Their article analysed to what extent the welfare state and gender equality regimes and the evaluation culture of the seven EFFORTI countries (Austria, Hungary, Germany, Spain, Denmark, France and Sweden) corresponds to the Social-Democratic typology or the conservative/traditional-family type, which provides less opportunities for women in the labour market and, especially, in RTDI. For each of the seven EFFORTI countries, five context areas were analysed: (1) the structure and performance of the research and innovation system; (2) gender equality policies in the labour market and; (3) welfare policies related to reproductive work and childcare; (4) the governance and existing policies of gender equality in RTDI, and (5) the evaluation culture and policy especially in the field of gender equality in RTDI. Their results concluded that context factors like legal regulations addressing gender equality in the RTDI sector, employment conditions in RTDI and horizontal and vertical segregation in RTDI could influence the effects of gender equality activities. Therefore, and considering that the seven EFFORTI countries varied clearly in respect to gender equality, policies to promote gender equality need to be planned, implemented and evaluated taking into account the different welfare regimes and evaluation regimes in RTDI, including legal regulations addressing gender equality in the RTDI sector, employment conditions in RTDI and horizontal and vertical segregation in RTDI. In a similar vein, Beaudry and Larivière (2016) studied what factors (including gender) influenced the probability of receiving more citations in scientific papers. Their findings indicated the influence of gender discrimination and, therefore, they argued that science policy should continue ensure gender-balanced research environments in order to avoid discrimination towards women, as well as gender bias. Therefore, science policies should encourage women to enter and pursue research and scientific careers.

2.2.3.3. Benefits from scientific impact

This category includes studies that contain examples of the knowledge and recognition of the results of research by the scientific community. Therefore, articles about the dissemination that takes place when researchers share the results of research beyond academia and these results reach institutions, NGOs or citizens, are also included. The articles included in this category present evidence on the four following topics: a) the influence of gender diversity in the scientific impact and productivity, b) the gender pay gap, c) the role of gender conceptualization in the emergence of inequalities, and d) the proposal and conceptualization of research methodologies that include the gender perspective.

a. Influence of gender-diverse authorships in the scientific impact of research

In order to make visible the scientific advancements promoted by women in all fields, several authors aimed to explore how gender diverse authorships affected the scientific impact of research in terms of citations and scientific recognition. In this regard, Nielsen and colleagues (2019) conducted a study combining bibliometric and content-focused approaches in more than 25,000 papers to examine the potential relationship between gender diversity and management research outcomes (in terms of citation impact and research focus). The regression models suggested that there was no discernible effect of team gender diversity on the scientific impact. In addition, one of their findings pointed out that women were highly represented in social and human-centred management fields, whereas men were overwhelmingly present in more technical and operational fields. This study concluded that gender diversity may influence research outcomes but that this influence is not easily captured or measured in terms of citations or publication rates. Therefore, the authors stated that gender diversity in authorships was not a useful predictor of how many citations a paper will receive over time. Lynn et al. (2019) also explored the impact of gender on citations in social science disciplines (economics, political science and sociology). To do that, they reviewed about 10,000 articles on gender and citations published during the period 1983–2003. In line with Nielsen and colleagues (2019), their results also indicated that gender was not a useful predictor of how many citations a paper will receive over time.

Following this line, Beaudry and Larivière (2016) explored factors affecting the propensity to receive more citations and whether the effects of these factors varied by gender. Nevertheless, they found that although women collaborated with the same number of co-authors as men and targeted similar Impact Factor journals, their articles are less cited than those of their male colleagues. In addition, female health scientists who published more articles as middle-ranked authors were relatively less cited than their equivalent male colleagues. On the contrary, no gender effect was found in the natural sciences and engineering, where women are still a minority. Considering that women account for a comparatively larger proportion of researchers in the health fields, Beaudry and Larivière (2016) suspected that their lower relative citation rate was possibly due to gender discrimination. They also argue that more research was required to truly measure the societal impact of one's research. In the same direction, Aguinis and colleagues (2018) intended to understand the reasons for a gender productivity gap in STEM and other scientific fields, specifically among star performers. With this aim, they conducted 3 studies, which included 1) 3,853 researchers who published 3161 articles on

mathematics, 2) 45,007 researchers who published 7,746 articles on genetics, and 3) 6,337 researchers who published 3,796 articles on mathematical psychology. The results of the three studies were consistent and pointed to the existence of a substantial greater gender productivity gap among star performers in favour of men, as well as to the underrepresentation of women in high productivity levels. This way, as productivity and scientific performance levels increased, so did the underrepresentation of women. The results could contribute to understanding possible reasons for the existence of gender productivity gaps, including: gender differences in citation rates, gender discrimination or gender-based differences in the access to scientific careers.

This topic was also studied by Eagly and Miller (2016), who focused on the status of contemporary female psychologists to explore if women will predominate in the next generation of eminent psychologists. In order to do so, they based their analysis on *h* index, which is the number of a researcher's publications that have been cited at least *h* times. Variables considered in this review include: quantity and impact of publications and gender bias in publication metrics. The results showed that women published less than men in terms of quantity and impact of publications in most fields. Their publications were also cited less per article than men.

Another article in this first category explored the underlying impact of gender on science ethics and its influence on scientific productivity. In this vein Ecklund and Di (2017) examined how physicists perceived the impact of gender on science ethics. A total of 121 US and UK academic physicists participated in this study through semi-structured interviews. Researchers divided participants' attitudes toward gender and ethics into three categories: 1) participants who believed that gender had an influence on individual-level science ethics ($n=27$) and think that female scientists addressed ethical issues in a female way, while male scientists addressed ethical issues in a male way. Among them, 9 participants thought that the different ways in which ethical issues were handled led to different levels of competition between male and female scientists in academic physics, and that feminized ethical approaches may harm research productivity of female physicists. 2) participants who considered gender discrimination itself as a ethical problem ($n=42$) and 3) participants who were "gender blind" and did not think in the existence of gender stratification in the scientific community ($n=52$). As a conclusion, the authors argued that men and women have different ways of addressing physicist research. While men tend to engage in scientific competition, women are more likely to address science in a "feminine" ethical way, characterised by being more cautious with data and conclusions. According to the authors, this difference may be one of the underlying causes behind the gap in scientific productivity between men and women.

b. The gender pay gap

The second subcategory brings new evidence around the existence and magnitude of gender pay gap. This way, the study of Maume et al (2019) aimed to determine the extent to which the managerial pay gap was explained by gender differences in worker endowments and differences in the characteristics of labour markets that rewarded workers. In order to do so, they included an analysis of secondary data of 916 managers aged 25-64 from the 2010 European Social Survey. The results found that employer devaluation of women was responsible for the majority of the gender pay gap, especially in countries without mandatory quotas. Gender differences in skills, human capital, work attachment,

family situation, employment location had little impact on gender gap in managerial pay. Therefore, it was implicit discrimination against female managers that led to gender gap in managerial pay. In a similar direction, Stockdale and Nadler (2013) focused on three major areas: Sociology, Economy, and Psychology to clarify the role of these social-science disciplines in gender inequalities, including gender wage gap and occupational segregation. To do that, the authors reviewed disciplinary and ideological perspectives in these areas drawn primarily from studies focused on United States samples. They argued that although the gender wage gap and occupational segregation were separate phenomena, they were closely linked. In other words, according to the authors, men and women tend to be classified into masculine-typed jobs or feminine-typed jobs, and those occupations that are mostly occupied by women tend to gain lower incomes than those occupied by men. This evidence shed new light on the analysis of the factors behind gender occupational inequalities that can nurture further research.

c. The role of gender conceptualization in the emergence of inequalities

The third subcategory refers to the role of linguistics and gender-related concepts in the emergence and overcoming of inequalities. In this regard, prior research pointed out that the use of gender-fair linguistic forms instead of masculine linguistic forms had an important impact on mental representations. Horvath et al. (2015) investigated the simultaneous emergence of beneficial and detrimental effects of gender-fair language in Italian and German on the social perception of professional groups. A total of 195 Austrians and 196 Italians completed the online questionnaire. The results showed that gender-fair language could have both positive effects (such as increasing women's visibility) as well as negative effects (such as the polarisation of male-female differences in pay). In the same line, Rittenhofer and Gatrell (2012) reviewed and analysed theoretical and policy literature on gender perspective within the EU between 1998 and 2011. According to the authors, the vague definition of "inequality" in the gender mainstreaming literature hindered the implementation of gender mainstreaming in organisational practice. Another article that analyzed the gender conceptual framework was the research conducted by Gay-Antaki (2020) in the field of climate. The author delineated the mechanisms by which some meanings of gender (like gender balance) dominated over others (like gender equality). To do that, the author participated in the Conference of the Parties (COP) workshop and in the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and also completed interviews and participant observation using climate and UN documents. The paper suggested that feminist geographies of climate change had the potential of promoting global conversation about gender and climate change, of forming new coalitions and techniques and of finding equitable outcomes in the face of climate change.

d. Proposal and conceptualization of research methodologies that include the gender perspective

Finally, in the fourth category there were three articles that include how research should address gender perspective in order to become more equitable. The first article was elaborated by Puigvert and colleagues (2019) and its scientific relevance is based on 1) the provision of ground-breaking data about the silent reality of gender violence at Spanish universities and 2) the conceptualization of a new methodology based on the co-creation of knowledge, the Communicative Evaluation of Social Impact (CESI). This methodology is characterised by the inclusion of all the diversity of voices in the

evaluation of the social impact of research and contributes to collecting evidence of the transformations achieved as a result of a research process. This way, the article brings new knowledge about how researchers can overcome resistance and overcome inequalities through research using the CESI.

The second article proposed a research methodology to assess the engagement of women in STEM fields (London et al., 2011) in order to capture and identify the factors that contribute to the success and engagement of women in STEM. In order to do so, they proposed the Experience Sampling Methodology (ESM) is a data collection methodology that has been broadly used in fields such as social sciences or clinical personality but underutilised in the assessment of the engagement of women in STEM. The ESM is a methodology in which researchers use repeated participants self-reports to measure and sample behaviours, moods, recall events, emotions and experiences within a period of time or around specific events. Authors argued that this methodology could bring several benefits to gender research, such as realism, the reduction of memory call distortions or the accuracy in the measure of day-to-day experiences in which women felt threatened or marginalised, among others. Therefore, researchers concluded that “ESM could be used at the institutional level and become part of a university’s policy or normal programming” (p. 525) and it also can be used to evaluate existing policies or intervention programs which aim to maintain or boost academic engagement for women in STEM fields. The other study in this category included the study conducted by Bürkner (2012), which explored the impact of the intersectionality approach on migration research. The author concluded that the intersectionality approach could promote the empirical reconstruction of gender-related exclusion in migrations as well as help immigrant studies liberate from conceptual constraints and better understand the emergence of individual and collective social positions.

2.2.4 Conclusion: Citizens’ benefits from research impact in gender

After the analysis of the selected articles, the main conclusion points to the importance of the inclusion of diverse voices and perspectives in co-creation processes. This way, gender equality is relevant, not only for the women themselves who become actively involved in all spheres of society, but also for society as a whole who benefits from the improvements and advances that are promoted. In this line, across the three categories, the studies that achieved more social, political, or scientific impact were those interventions, policies or research that gave high priority to scientific evidence and to the inclusion of diverse voices.

Citizens’ benefits from the social impact of research in gender

Within the impacts generated by research and from which citizens benefit, one can find social impact. The analysis conducted in this report shows that research achieves greater social impact when all the voices are included. This way, the analysis of the identified articles pointed to two main achievements: the overcoming of gender violence and women empowerment. From these, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Effective evidence-based programs on preventive socialisation of gender-based violence place co-creation of knowledge at the core of the intervention. In all programs, researchers: shared

scientific knowledge with participants and engaged in an egalitarian dialogue with them, encouraging citizens' participation in science.

2. In the line of overcoming gender violence, the creation of networks of support and solidarity with the victims of gender violence and with those advocates who stand by their side contribute to breaking the silence. This way, victims can become successful survivors and avoid revictimization as well as isolating gender violence.
3. Programmes aimed at the promotion of women empowerment also drew on the creation of networks of support and solidarity in safe spaces and the inclusion of the voices of all stakeholders and community members.

Citizens' benefits from the political impact of research in gender

Regarding the political impact, it is important to note that although policies and legislations are necessary for the overcoming of gender violence, not all policies are equally effective. Therefore, the analysis of the political impact of research must provide the key elements that contribute to the success of these gender policies. In this line, in this literature review there were two pioneer legislations in the field of gender violence that supposed a step forward and that achieved significant impacts. The analysis of these policies concludes that:

1. Policies designed taking into account the scientific evidence in the field reach social impact. In this line, the two pioneer legislations were grounded on years of scientific research in the line of the prevention of gender violence. This way, the accumulation of scientific knowledge oriented towards social transformation enables political and legal changes that contribute to the reduction of gender inequalities.
2. Policies oriented towards social transformation and the overcoming of inequalities support the victims of gender violence and avoid their revictimization. The main recommendations in this line point to the necessity of including sporadic relationships in the campaigns for the prevention of gender violence in youth.
3. Policies promoting gender-diverse teams in research teams and companies are not only a strategy to promote justice and gender equality, but also bring benefits to society in terms of innovation, creativity and performance.

Citizens' benefits from the scientific impact of research in gender

Finally, the scientific impact of research addressed several topics, including the influence of gender-diverse teams in scientific research, the gender pay gap, the role of gender-related concepts in the emergence of inequalities and methodologies that include gender perspective. The following contributions can be drawn:

1. Research increases its scientific impact when it is orientated towards social transformation.

2. Research considering gender inequalities aimed at promoting social transformations sheds light on aspects that not only contribute to the improvement of how research is designed and implemented, but also the results are better aligned with the interests of citizens.

2.2.5 Reference

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2.3 Citizens' benefits from research impact in education

2.3.1 Overview

This section of Report1 gathers the state of the art regarding how citizens' benefit from the social impact of research on education, contributing to the achievement of ALINTERACT's O1. The results inform the design and development of the focus groups on education, which are explained in chapter 4, as well as the survey on education, which is presented in chapter 5, the interventions and the policy commendations which will be conducted in other work packages of the project. To that end, a systematic literature review has been conducted through an extensive identification of scientific contributions published during 2010-2020 in journals indexed in the scientific database of Scopus. To complete the task, grey literature was also searched. The following sections gather the methodology followed in this review, the results obtained and the main conclusions. In this line, the report identifies the social, political and scientific impact of research on education from which citizens have benefitted. Researchers from RUG and UB have participated in the elaboration of this section.

2.3.2 Methodology

This literature review aims to explore existing social science research regarding how citizens benefit from scientific research in education. For this reason, a literature review was conducted to identify worldwide scientific contributions on the topic. Studies indexed in the scientific database of Scopus were searched and retrieved for the analysis. Sources have been selected seeking an interdisciplinary approach, both regarding the journals' and the articles of selection. For this literature review, the following combinations of keywords were used:

- 1) Societal impact of research AND education
- 2) Social benefits of science AND education
- 3) Science social impact on / AND inequalities
- 4) Science social impact on / AND education
- 5) "political impact" AND education
- 6) evidence-based AND education* AND social impact
- 7) successful AND educational AND vulnerable
- 8) successful AND educational AND impact
- 9) "social impact" AND education AND inequalities
- 10) "societal impact" AND education
- 11) "social impact" AND education AND school

The inclusion criteria of the literature we used is: 1) Subject area is Social Sciences, 2) the writing language is English, 3) the document type is article, 4) the keyword is education when available, 5) the publish year of these literature were during 2010-2021, 6) the source type is journal and 7) the journal is indexed in Journal Citation Reports (Q1 or Q2) or Scopus (Q1)

Figure 2.3. Methodology for the literature review on education

The literature search yielded 784 potential articles, of which 598 were discarded because they were out of scope, 54 due to the journal impact, 92 due to the lack of evidence of scientific, political or social impact and 5 due to repetition. One article published in a journal indexed in Scopus (Q2) was not discarded due to lack of journal impact because the article has been cited by 17 articles indexed in JCR. Additionally, 7 articles from the research on gender or on topic “b” were added as deemed relevant for the topic. One report was identified in the search for grey literature, but its content felt out of the scope of this report. Finally, 41 articles were included in the analysis.

For the analysis, the data retrieved from the 41 was organised in three following categories:

- 1) benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors).
- 2) benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors).
- 3) benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).

For each of these categories, the transformative dimension (i.e. what facilitates the targeted impact) and the exclusionary dimension (i.e. obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted impact) have been identified. Data has been classified according to the established categories (1-3) and dimensions as outlined in the Work Plan M1-M7 (see the following table).

Table 2.3. Analysis grid

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which have contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i>
Transformative Dimension			
Exclusionary Dimension			

Next, within the different categories, the following subcategories were identified

Table 2.4. Categories and subcategories of the analysis on education

Categories	Subcategories
Benefits from social impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Successful Educational Actions for all children b. Educational research for the promotion of quality education for minority students c. Effective educational practices in the university context d. Interventions oriented to the promotion of community welfare
Benefits from political impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Changes in legislation on education b. Scalability and transference of educational practices --- Gathered policy recommendations
Benefits from scientific impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Engagement of ethnic minorities in science b. School actions to improve educational achievement c. Factors influencing educational achievement d. The relationship between scientists and society

2.3.3 Results

The 41 articles which were retrieved regarding how citizens' benefit from research in education were classified according to the type of impact produced in "benefits from social impact", "benefits from political impact" and "benefits from scientific impact". After analysing the identified articles and categorising them into the above mentioned categories, the following results were found:

Figure 2.4. Proportion of articles in each category (Education)

2.3.3.1. Benefits from social impact

The articles categorised within this section include how citizens benefit from the social impact of research on education. This impact is achieved when, once the results of the research have been published, disseminated and shared, they improve citizens' lives in relation to the objectives of society, such as the Sustainable Development Goals. The articles included in this category present scientific evidence on the impact of research on education, and have been organised in the following subcategories: a. Successful Educational Actions for all children, b. educational research for the promotion of quality education for minority students, c. effective educational practices in the university context, and d. Interventions oriented to the promotion of community welfare.

a. Successful Educational Actions for all children

A large number of studies within the first category are related to the Successful Educational Actions (SEAs) which were identified by the research project INCLUD-ED from the 6th Framework Program (Girbés-Peco et al., 2015; Rios González et al., 2019; Duque et al., 2020). Some of the articles analysed the impact of the transformation of schools into Learning Communities that implement the SEAs (Girbés-Peco et al., 2015; Flecha, 2013; Flecha et al., 2011). The main contributions in this regard point out that, besides improving educational achievement and social cohesion, Schools as Learning Communities have also a significant impact on the community, contributing to the reduction of poverty (Girbés-Peco et al., 2015; Gatt & Armeni 2013), the improvement of health status (Flecha, 2013; Flecha et al., 2011) and the promotion of employment opportunities (Gatt & Armeni, 2013). In addition, several articles analysed the impact of a specific SEA, including Interactive Groups, Dialogic Gatherings, Dialogic Model of Violence Prevention, and the Extension of Learning Time.

As defined in the analysed articles, Interactive Groups are ones of the SEAs identified by the research project INCLUD-ED and are grounded on the principles of dialogic learning. IGs consist of an inclusive

reorganisation of the classroom, characterised by the creation of heterogeneous groups in terms of abilities, gender, background, etc. with an adult volunteer (Diez-Palomar et al., 2020). IGs draw upon the basis that the more and more diverse dialogue is promoted in class, the higher learning children achieve (Valls & Kyriakides, 2013). For this reason, volunteers come from beyond the school and include parents, other relatives, neighbours, retired people, university students, among others. The studies about IG consisted of 10 case studies (Duque et al., 2020), 3 schools from the United Kingdom and Italy with 167 children (Diez-Palomar et al., 2020) and 2 primary schools and one high school from Spain (Valls & Kyriakides, 2013). Regarding the participants, the three studies included children participating in the IG, and Duque and colleagues (2020) and Valls and Kyriakides (2013) also included teachers, parents and volunteers. Among the main impacts identified there are an increase of engagement and motivation towards learning (Valls & Kyriakides, 2013; Diez-Palomar et al., 2020), better learning opportunities for all children including those with special needs (Duque et al., 2020; Valls & Kyriakides, 2013) or higher learning expectations (Duque et al., 2020), among others, which promote higher levels of performance and achievement (Valls & Kyriakides, 2013; Diez-Palomar et al., 2020; Duque et al., 2020). In this line, the study of Gatt and Armeni (2013) also revealed the impact of schools practising community involvement on schools' neighbouring communities in their health. They found that language learning courses for community members within schools enabled participants to understand the health services available, and nutrition courses enhance the knowledge about healthy lunches or snacks for children.

The second SEA identified in this review is Dialogic Gatherings (DGs), which consists of the creation of a dialogic environment where participants engage in egalitarian dialogues around a classical work from the universal literature in the case of Dialogic Literary Gatherings (Ruiz-Eugenio et al., 2020) and around a scientific text in the Dialogic Scientific Gatherings (Buslón et al., 2020). The key elements of the DGs are the egalitarian dialogue shared among participants, the inclusion of all the diversity of voices and the exchange of arguments instead of power claims (Ruiz-Eugenio et al., 2020; Diez-Palomar et al., 2020). Several of the analysed articles include the impacts of different dialogic gatherings on participants. For example, regarding the Dialogic Literary Gatherings, their main impacts are related to an improvement on educational achievement and instrumental learning (Ruiz-Eugenio et al., 2020; Duque et al., 2020) and a transformation of participants attitudes towards reading and learning (Diez-Palomar et al., 2020). In addition, when the Dialogic Literary Gatherings were implemented during lockdowns, they brought significant impacts on participants' wellbeing, such as the promotion of safe spaces to share feelings and interact when the schools were closed (Ruiz-Eugenio et al., 2020). Another example of dialogic gatherings is Dialogic Scientific Gatherings, which have shown to promote scientific literacy among participants (Buslón et al. 2020). Specifically, the dialogic scientific gatherings enhance the access of all people to scientific knowledge, foster analytical and critical thinking and promote evidence-based decision-making as well as solidarity and active citizenship.

Finally, within the Dialogic Gatherings, the last education action identified in the literature review are the Dialogic Pedagogical Gatherings. These are an evidence-based action for in-service teachers based on the principles of dialogic learning. Therefore, the Dialogic Pedagogical Gatherings are an action characterised by the collective reading and discussion of evidence-based pedagogical texts that fulfil

the criteria of “successful stories”, transferability to other contexts and universal relevance. In the Dialogic Pedagogical Gatherings, participants share an egalitarian dialogue around the reading and co-create new knowledge to transform and improve their educational practice in education. Roca-Campos and colleagues (2021) aimed to explore the impact of in-service teacher training and identified the impact of this Successful Educational Action on students’ achievement and school results for those students whose teachers participated in the Dialogic Pedagogical Gatherings. In order to do so, they implemented 6 techniques (focus groups, semi-structured interviews, document analysis, participant observation, in-depth interviews and questionnaires) over a period of 5 years. Their results conclude that the participation of teachers in the Dialogic Pedagogical Gatherings has a significant impact on students, mainly in their learning outcomes and in social inclusion. When teachers transferred to their schools what they had learned in the Dialogic Pedagogical Gatherings, there was an improvement in students’ learning and in school social cohesion.

Another of the Successful Educational Actions identified on this review is the Dialogic Model of Violence Prevention, the study conducted by Roca-Campos and colleagues (2021) explored the impact of the Zero Violence Brave Club in the decreasing of school violence. The Zero Violence Brave Club is an evidence-based intervention that draws upon the Dialogic Model of Violence Prevention and that is grounded in the basis that those children who report violence suffered by a peer and stand always on the victim's side are brave. In their research, Roca Campos and colleagues implemented the Zero Violence Brave Club in 7 schools in Spain, which were diverse in terms of population, geographical context, and background. As a result, authors conclude that the Zero Violence Brave Club decreased school bullying thanks to the creation of a culture of zero tolerance to violence. Specifically, the authors point to the importance of shedding light on the existing violence in order to break the silence, to the promotion of those friendship relations that protect children from violence since early childhood and to the necessity of making violence less attractive. Finally, the article concludes that most of the interviewees perceived an increase in peer empowerment as agents of change that denounce violence and stand on the victim’s side.

Finally, the last of the Successful Educational Actions found in this analysis is the Extension of Learning Time (ELT), which consists of providing additional learning activities and educational support beyond the school time, with the objective of ensuring educational success for all. Thus, the activities conducted during ELT are based on egalitarian dialogue and social transformation, among others (Salvadó et al., 2021). In this vein, the article from Salvadó and colleagues (2021) compiled a specific experience of ELT that consisted of the implementation of scientific workshops for vulnerable students in order to improve their participants’ science identity and science capital, as well as their educational aspirations. For this reason, they conducted 7 workshops about human paleoecology, physics and chemistry with 86 children at risk of social exclusion. Among their results, the authors found some barriers that hinder vulnerable children’s scientific aspirations, which were included in the exclusionary dimension. These barriers were related to the feeling that the profession of scientist is too demanding, their unawareness of the process to become scientists and their preferences for other professions. However, their research found positive impacts in the improvement of knowledge about scientific disciplines, as well as in science identity, which were included in the transformative dimension. In this line, participants developed an inclusive science identity that enabled them to see

themselves as girls and ethnic minorities who could become scientists, promoting higher scientific and educational expectations.

b. Educational research for the promotion of quality education for minority students

As shown in the previous subsection, Successful Educational Actions improve students' achievement and school cohesion for all students, including minority groups, in different contexts. However through the literature review some of the articles identified reported on interventions that are not within the Successful Educational Actions per se, but that share common aspects with them and are succeeding in the promotion of quality education for minority students, including Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (Claridge et al., 2018), African American communities (Tumiel-Berhalter et al., 2011) or Aboriginal students (Henderson et al., 2015) among others. The articles in this subcategory were grouped in 1. after-school programs for minority students, and 2. factors that hinder or promote educational success for minority students.

Several after-school programs for minority students were identified in the search. A common aspect these share with the Successful Educational Actions is that these are based on extending the learning time for children, which as, abovementioned, has a positive effect on children's academic outcomes. For instance, some of the articles analysed explore how different out-of-school activities and programmes have an impact on children's educational achievement and professional readiness. For instance, the Summer Academic Research Experience for minority students explored by Kabacoff and colleagues (2013) aimed to offer challenging, enriching and academically rewarding activities through an academic internship. This initiative was promoted by the John Hopkins School of Medicine and included working closely with doctoral and postdoctoral researchers who became their mentors. Among the main impacts achieved by this initiative, the authors remarked an increase in research skills, an improvement in writing performance and the gain of professionalism skills such as speaking in public, responsibility, punctuality, etc. According to the authors, the key to the success of this action is that it includes a research component, a professionalism component, and an academic component.

In the same line, the study performed by Lacy and colleagues (2012) analysed the impact of a series of out-of-school initiatives in the promotion of diversity in dental schools. This program was implemented by the Texas A&M Health Science Center Baylor College of Dentistry and aimed to offer academic enrichment and to raise awareness and attraction to dental careers in underrepresented minority students. The activities organised within this program included projects at elementary schools, field trips and summer enrichment programs, among others. After the implementation of these initiatives, the college gained a significant number of underrepresented minority students in dental careers. The initiative strengthened students' biomedical and scientific background, improved their academic performance and scores, and enhanced their study skills, which increased the enrolment of diversity students in dental school. For many students, improving their scores was key to encouraging them to pursue dentistry. Also in the medical field, Henderson and colleagues (2015) examined the impact of an outreach initiative for Aboriginal students, launched by The University of Calgary's Cumming School of Medicine, to address systemic barriers experienced by low-income and minority students to accessing medical school. The initiative included summer science camps and

community presentations encouraging potential applicants in high school. The participants were junior and senior high school students, who attended a half-day program in classes or summer science camps of 15-25 junior high school students. The results showed that mini-medical schools increased health literacy among target populations. In addition, the authors also found an increase in medical school admission for minority students who meet the requirements as an impact of the implementation of the programme.

Some of the other interventions identified were focused on interventions for sustainable development. In this line, Trott (2020) examined how an after-school program impacted children's climate change knowledge as well as how children experienced their growing climate change awareness. Participants were 55 children aged 10 to 12 from different primary and secondary schools in the USA. They were white, Hispanic/Latinx, biracial or multiple ethnicities, and Asian/Pacific Islander, and most of the participants come from low-income families. The programme included educational activities exploring the existing links between climate change, local ecosystems, and human behaviour, as well as the development of family action plans and the design and implementation of a community action project. The results showed that after participating in the program, children's certainty about climate change, time to think about climate change as well as their climate change knowledge had increased. Following the program, their understanding of climate change exceeded the average knowledge level of average USA teens and adults. The findings of this study point at the potential for informal after-school settings to provide young people with spaces to learn and actively engage in climate change overcoming, and for children to be intergenerational communicators to circulate climate change knowledge.

Beyond extended learning time, other studies focused on external factors that hinder or promote their academic success. In this line, a study (Claridge et al. 2018) revealed the obstacles hindering the academic achievement of Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME) medical students. Semi-structured interviews and focus groups with 41 medical students and 8 staff in the UK. Their results show that ethnically defined social networks and informal transfers of knowledge can isolate minorities from useful academic information and affect their academic performance. Authors also suggested that students with increased family responsibilities, or students who commute because they live with family members find themselves in disadvantaged positions by being unable to participate in social and academic activities. Some black students mentioned that they faced discrimination in exams, especially those involving examiner observation. As a conclusion, authors argue that both conscious and unconscious discrimination may negatively impact the BAME students' abilities in their examinations and coursework choice.

In a similar vein, Serbin and colleagues (2013) conducted a study to investigate an important transition in student academic achievement: from primary education to secondary education. Specifically, they conducted a prospective longitudinal study to examine predictors of success in transitioning from primary (grades 5 and 6) to secondary education (grades 7 and 8) in 127 Quebec youth. Demographically, the participants who were involved in this study came from families below the population average in several indicators of social and economic functioning. The results showed that many of the children participating in this study did not perform as expected in their elementary school,

and after transitioning to secondary school, their academic performance deteriorated. The hierarchical regression analysis offered transformative ways to improve the academic achievement of vulnerable children by indicating that the more support parents provide to their children in terms of academic and social skills, the more opportunities for success in the transition to secondary education. These imply that interventions targeting literacy skills, parental support, and social skills during the transition from primary to secondary education benefit vulnerable adolescents.

c. Effective educational practices in the university context

Some of the articles included in this review focus on effective educational practices in the university context. One study in this regard was conducted by Weinberg and colleagues (2018) and explored the impacts of a specific experience of research for undergraduate students. The authors drew upon the premise that through innovative, interdisciplinary and engagement-oriented research experiences, undergraduate students become aware of the social impact of science. This awareness strengthened their academic career and encouraged persistence in STEM careers, especially in students from underrepresented communities. In this program, which lasted 9 weeks, participants met local scientists with local scientific knowledge and experience, studied Participatory Action Research methods with university professors, built relationships with indigenous community members and combined traditional ecological knowledge with scientific knowledge. This experience enabled participants to learn about the process of generation of knowledge, raising their awareness about the role of community members, the importance of co-creation and local knowledge and the necessity of interdisciplinary research. In addition, it allowed students to translate knowledge into action, empowering community, and engaging community members in science.

Another study in this regard focused on reciprocal learning programmes between western and eastern universities and educational centres (from Canada and China) (Howitt, 2019). This initiative consisted of the creation of a partnership for pre-service teachers and educators in similar subjects in Canada and China, with the objective of sharing professional dialogues about the lesson planning and content, as well as establishing collaborations between communities. In ten years of implementation, 12 educational institutions, 100 educators, 25 administrators, 6000 students and 150 parents participated in the program. The implementation of the program brought several benefits, such as more effective teacher practices, awareness of globalisation processes, value for traditions and cultures and deeper levels of knowledge. According to the author, these impacts were possible thanks to the personal commitment of professionals from both universities, the multidimensional partnerships and educators desire to learn.

d. Interventions oriented to the promotion of community welfare

Finally, some of the articles analysed focused on educational interventions oriented to the promotion of community welfare. For instance, the study of Tumiel-Berhalter et al. (2011) described the participatory process used in the development of the Good For The Neighborhood program (GFTN), a program implemented by the Independent Health Foundation (IHF) with 4 underserved minority communities within Western New York. These communities included two predominately African American communities, a predominantly Puerto Rican community and a Seneca Nation of Indians

community, all of them with percentages of population living in poverty that went from 14%-40%. For the success of this program, IHF identified community partners in targeted areas who agreed to host GFTN monthly and assist with promotion and health education activities. The Formative evaluation of the GFTN program suggested that residents perceived the positive impact of the programme. The awareness of health issues in the community was raised, and healthy behaviour changes were promoted. This program showed that strong community partners, allowance of time for trust and respect to develop, and continual reassessment to ensure programming meets the needs of the community were key elements for the success of this community-based program.

More broadly, and presenting research results from a transnational study, Gatt and Armeni (2013) show a series of impacts of community involvement in education of both the children and the community itself. Regarding health, authors found that language learning courses for community members within schools enabled participants to understand the health services available, and nutrition courses enhance the knowledge about healthy lunches or snacks for children. In the field of housing, community participation within schools promoted the creation of associations and solidarity networks within the community and enabled the exchange of information about the housing and banking system. The benefits in the field of employment, included volunteering work and courses within the school to help families to increase their employment opportunities by equipping them with skills, competences and hands-on experience. Sometimes, families found employment in the school itself, serving as role models to other community members. Finally, the benefits in social participation of community members included the participation of families in decision-making processes and their contribution in the implementation of school activities.

2.3.3.2. Benefits from political impact

This section includes articles in which citizens benefit from the political impact of research, which is related to the transference of the results of research to institutions, administrations, organisations, policymakers and citizens, who use these results to design policies or to improve plans, actions and programs. Several examples of the political impact of scientific research in education were found. These examples can be grouped in two subcategories: a. changes in legislation on education and b. scalability and transference of educational practices. In addition, several articles were found that, although did not bring examples of the political impact of research, they are somehow related to this issue.

a. Changes in legislation on education

The first subcategory included one article about how the FP5 project “WORKALO, the creation of new occupational patterns for cultural minorities: the gypsy case” fostered the unanimous recognition of Roma on the part of the European Parliament (Álvarez et al, 2020). This project was pioneer in the co-creation of innovative strategies for social and economic development and social cohesion in Europe, between researchers and citizens, including Roma citizens. This dialogic public policy had two key elements. One the one hand, it placed the egalitarian dialogue with the Roma people at the core of the intervention and on the other, it was evidence-based.

b. Scalability and transference of educational practices

The second subcategory contained several examples of how, as a result of scientific research on education, those educational practices and actions that had shown to improve academic results and contribute to overcome inequalities were scaled-up and transferred to other contexts. In this line, the article elaborated by Vieites and colleagues (2020) explored the scalability and transference of the Successful Educational Actions identified by the INCLUD-ED project to 139 schools from 50 clusters in Portugal, using dialogic methods for citizen engagement in research. In order to do so, they collected data from document analysis, communicative observations, and interviews, to conclude that the egalitarian dialogue shared between schools and researchers and among schools and government was essential to implement the actions and ensure replicability. According to the authors, the key elements of this dialogue were that 1) it was based on scientific evidence, 2) it aimed to improve the educational quality for all and 3) it was an egalitarian dialogue. Besides, Duque and colleagues (2020) provided an example of how research identified the benefits of interactive learning environments for students with disabilities and, consequently these educational actions were transferred to a great number of mainstream schools with children with disabilities as well as to special schools.

Gathered policy recommendations

Some of the articles analysed did not provide evidence of the political impact of research, but issued policy recommendations that are of relevance to this topic. More precisely, contributions from these articles relate to the effect of policies on the quality of education and educational recommendations for policymakers.

Regarding the effect of policies on the quality of education, some of the articles focused on social policies and on educational policies. For instance, Merry et al (2020) used the welfare regime and social stratification theory to examine the national education performance in 35 OECD countries that were involved in the PISA 2015 assessment. The results indicated that policies that aimed to guarantee citizens basic needs and securities were more positively associated with educational achievement than the amount of spending, which implied that the quality of the welfare policy is more influential than the amount of funding. For example, authors found that the proportion of high-achieving students was superior in nations with stronger policies devoted to the protection of income loss during unemployment.

Focusing on educational policies, the study conducted by Freeman and Steidl (2016) aimed to explore the impact of segregation policies in school. They investigated the association between school segregation policies and racial disparities in the application of school discipline, which included expulsions and suspensions. Participants included black and white students from 585 schools in 40 districts. The results suggested that racial inequalities were present in many forms and that the efforts to establish racial integrated schools did not release districts from the establishment of policies to raise awareness about racial inequalities in school discipline. For this reason, the authors indicate that districts and policies should address this issue and should implement awareness-raising actions targeting racial disparities in education, as well as create policies and practises to reduce racial

inequalities, and train professionals to assess unequal disciplinary patterns and to raise awareness about racial bias at classroom and administrative levels.

In order to overcome these inequalities, several studies analysed how to improve the quality of education. This is the case, for example, of the literature review about education for sustainable development (ESD) in early childhood education, conducted by Bascopé (2019). Education for Sustainable Development implies putting sustainability at the core of educational practices, interacting with the economy, society, environment and education. Based on the results, the author proposed three recommendations for ESD practises: 1) to be action-integrative, which refers to educating children to become agents of change, active stakeholders and problem-seekers and solvers that impact their communities through participatory processes, 2) to be community-based, which includes learning from and about the community and promoting spaces for co-construction of knowledge and solutions with the community, and 3) to be value-oriented, which includes giving high priority to the development of those values that promote democratic societies, such as diversity, equity and social justice.

Finally, the study conducted by Netshakhuma (2021) analysed the alliance of archive, library and museum (ALM). ALM are alliances between Archives, Libraries and Museums based on community-education, aimed at building alliances that provide children and families with access to specialised high-quality learning activities and community engagement. Their main functions include: 1) creating a learning space where people can feel comfortable to engage in formal and non-formal learning, 2) offering opportunities for intergenerational and community learning and 3) developing not only individuals' skills and knowledge, but their confidence and values. A total of 10 practitioners participated in the study and were interviewed. Results showed that most South Africans did not access or visit ALM because they lacked the access to resources or because they thought that ALM contained only information about a specific historic period or population group. The results of this study provide recommendations to enhance the access and use of ALM, including adopting pro-active measures to encourage communities, providing relevant resources to communities, or providing scholarships to youth so that they could access ALM, among others..

2.3.3.3. Benefits from scientific impact

The articles included in this category refer to the knowledge and recognition of the results of research by the scientific community. Therefore, this section also includes the dissemination that takes place when researchers share the results of research beyond academia and these results reach institutions, NGOs or citizens. The articles in this section included the creation of knowledge about how to improve education were classified in three subcategories: a. engagement of ethnic minorities in science, b. school actions to improve educational achievement, c. factors influencing educational achievement and d. the relationship between scientists and society.

a. Engagement of ethnic minorities in science

In the first subcategory, several articles included the creation of knowledge about how to increase the access and engagement of minority students in STEM. One example in this regard is the study

conducted by Ghee et al (2016) which aimed to examine the impact of research engagement, skill development, and mentorship aspects of a summer research program on students' persistence in the STEM pathway. The program consisted of exposing undergraduate students to the graduate school research site, with the support of a mentor. The results indicated that the summer experience even though students' consideration of research careers outside academia remained relatively unchanged, the summer experience improved students' understanding of the graduate school application process and graduate school life. Therefore, this study sheds light in new ways to help students from underserved populations in their transition from high school to college. Similarly, the study by Gibau (2015) explored the experiences of underrepresented minority (URM) graduate students in the biomedical sciences of a large, midwestern, urban university. The students who participated in their study reported both positive and negative experiences in the program. Regarding the exclusionary dimension, authors reported that the environmental and curricular adjustments made participants feel challenged and female participants experienced difficulties in maintaining academic standing and financial aspects. However, as for the transformative dimensions, participants reported that they had benefited from the summer research experience as well as mentorship, social and professional support, and career definition. In this line, the study concludes that support and solidarity among underrepresented minority students are key elements to help them to succeed in their STEM paths.

Also in line with science, another of the analysed articles explored new ways of contextualising science materials to take into account cultural and social background in order to increase the access to science education for ethnic and culture minority students (Sánchez Tapia et al., 2018). Their recommendations included the use of traditional knowledge in scientific concepts to engage adult members of the community in the classroom, the development of critical consciousness, the use of technology into the curriculum materials or the evaluation of inaccurate evidence-based explanations, among others. The inclusion of these contextualization principles helped students learn about western science and promoted their understanding of challenging scientific concepts. This way, the study provided new evidence of the impact of including cultural background in science materials, as a great support towards science learning for indigenous students.

b. School actions to improve educational achievement

The second subcategory refers to school actions to improve educational achievement and includes articles that provide scientific knowledge of what actions can be implemented within the educational context to improve education. Among the identified actions, there were courses for families, student evaluation activities, lifelong learning and the use of Information and Communication Technology .

Regarding family participation, the article by Gatt and Armeni (2013), presented in the section devoted to the benefits of the social impact of research, drew upon the INCLUD-ED project from the FP6 of the European Commission in order to reveal how those schools with a community-involvement approach contributed to increase social cohesion and improved educational achievement. The specific educational practices included language courses for immigrant families, courses about health, or to gain work related skills and competences and the participation of the community in school activities as volunteers. Their findings unveil that schools practising community involvement can really become

the schools of the future, acting as a central point of reference to communities and particularly to those groups who need most help to integrate in society.

As for student evaluation, Warren (2020) used a quasi-experimental design to conclude that direct evaluation activities in lab reports and indirect evaluation activities in lecture, homework, and exams may produce epistemic gains for students. Specifically, the article provides new evidence of the impact of evaluation activities on 1) structure of scientific knowledge, which is the idea that scientific knowledge is structured in consistent ideas and information, principles and models, 2) structure of science, which includes the notion that science is collaborative and consistent, 3) real-life applicability, which refers to the utility of scientific knowledge outside university and 4) ability to learn, which is related to beliefs about if learning abilities are innate or social and, therefore if they can be cultivated.

Scientific contributions on the improvement of education also reflect on the importance of lifelong training. In this line, the paper of Zwanikken et al (2016) explored the impact of the master public health (MPH) program in graduates and their peers and supervisors. The study remarked on the importance of further education. Specifically, the results showed that graduates are considered to be able to make significant contributions to their workplaces and are often influential at the national level and most impacts are in line with public health education goals.

Finally, some studies reflected on the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). For instance, regarding multimedia, Issa and colleagues (2011) studied the impact of multimedia design principles in superior learning in undergraduate medical students. Their results proved that multimedia design effectively improved medical students' short-term retention. Still, from their results they could not determine the impact these multimedia principles that were applied had on learning transference. Also about ICT, the study by Carrasco-Sáez and colleagues (2019) points out that the education system does not explicitly incorporate into the curriculum enough skills to help students manage and interact in both face-to-face and virtual environments. To that end, the authors develop an instrument for the study of Personal Learning Environments (PLE). PLE refer to the strategy that individuals create themselves to promote their autonomous learning in a digital ecosystem. The results show how this instrument can contribute to rebuilding the role of students in regard to open learning, the management of data, and knowledge management and transference.

c. Factors influencing educational achievement

The third subcategory refers to the effects of different issues in educational achievement, and includes studies that analysed the effects of residential mobility and the different roles during peer discussions in order to provide new knowledge about what practises and actions can be implemented to increase the quality of education globally.

The longitudinal study conducted by Sweet et al (2019), which investigated the impact of residential mobility on educational outcomes for students. After following a single cohort of pupils over an eleven-year time period, they found that residential mobility had a negative impact on educational achievement. Thus, this study offers a new knowledge of understanding the processes of residential mobility across the educational life course.

Another study analysed students' roles during peer discussions in order to find how to create classrooms with egalitarian interactions between boys and girls and also among underserved or international students (Eddy et al., 2015). One of their results stated that students' experiences and characteristics could predict their response on the value of peer discussions. This way, boys were more likely to prefer the leadership or explainer role, girls were more likely to prefer to be collaborators, and underserved American, Asian-American and international students were all more likely to prefer listening roles. The authors concluded that the knowledge gained in this study could be used to promote peer discussions in class and increase equity in participation in large active-learning biology courses.

d. The relationship between scientists and society

Finally, the last subcategory contained articles about the relationship between scientists and society and referred to the role of university and academia in current societies. In this line, if higher education institutions or universities structure their teaching, research, and operational tasks to be sustainable, sustainable development could be improved (Nölting et al, 2020). Therefore, it is necessary to promote a transfer of knowledge developed in universities to practice. Using a mixed methodology, Nölting and colleagues (2020) noted that higher education institutions (HEI) needed to combine transfer and sustainable development more systematically. In their article, they provided new knowledge about the conceptualization of transfer for sustainable development, which is characterised, among others, by the inclusion of knowledge provision from HEIs to society, interaction between HEIs and society, and the promotion of spaces for co-production of knowledge with HEIs and citizens.

In a similar vein, Cook and Overpeck (2019) wrote a review for climate experts who are not satisfied with the outcomes of current interactions with the public, aimed at modifying the public's societal responses to climate change. In this vein, the authors point out how such efforts are not deterred by citizens' indifference or ignorance, but explain the lack of success on the experts' aim to prompt a behavioural change in the public. Accordingly, the authors highlight that current strategies are only successful with citizens who are already open to the information shared with them and ready to act, but not to citizens who are doubtful, live in precarious conditions or prefer not to consider the negative outcomes of climate change. Based on these, authors urge experts to establish an open relationship with their audience by clearly presenting their intentions and including citizens in the co-creation of solutions to reach the priorities collaboratively established by all parties.

Finally, and considering the growing importance of ethical issues in science and in society, McDonald and Pan (2020) conducted a study that aimed to explore how science students perceived responsibility, bias and ethics in artificial intelligence. They found that unless students were explicitly encouraged to do so, they were not inclined to think deeply about the impact of AI design on the privacy and well-being of others. Therefore, the authors suggested that Information and Computer sciences curricula should integrate identity-related ethics, through discussions and extrapolation to raise empathy about vulnerable and intersectional identities.

2.3.4 Conclusions: Citizens' benefits from research impact in education

Based on the analysis of the selected articles, the main conclusion that can be obtained is the importance of the inclusion of diverse voices and of community involvement in the promotion of quality education for all. Throughout the three categories, the studies that achieved more social, political or scientific impact were those that placed community participation at the core of the intervention, policy or research.

Citizens' benefits from the social impact of research in education

The analysis conducted in this literature review suggests that research achieves greater social impact when educational interventions are designed with a community-approach that values and includes all the voices. This way, the analysis of the identified articles pointed to four achievements: Successful Educational Actions for all children, educational research for the promotion of quality education for minority students, effective practices in the university context and interventions oriented to the promotion of community welfare. From these, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Actions that give importance to the co-creation of knowledge that combine scientific evidence and local knowledge provided by communities achieve greater impact in education in diverse educational contexts, including schools, high schools, universities, and informal learning centres.
2. Community-based interventions promote reciprocal learning and the transference of knowledge into action. In addition, when communities actively participate in educational practices, it brings several benefits in schools (such as an increase of school coexistence and parental support) and beyond (including improvements in health, employment or housing).
3. Programs that promote high quality education and support beyond school time, including summer and afterschool programs promote the overcoming of educational inequalities that affect children and youth from ethnic minorities or underserved populations.

Citizens' benefits from the political impact of research in education

Policies play a key role in the overcoming of educational and social inequalities. However, not all policies are equally effective and that funding is not a useful measure of the quality or the success of the implemented policies. In this line, the analysis of the main political impacts of research in education points to two main milestones: changes in legislation in education and the scalability and transference of educational practices. In addition to these milestones, there are several recommendations for policymakers that can reduce educational inequalities. The main conclusions in this regard are:

1. Changes in legislation that improve education for all have two key characteristics: they are based on scientific evidence in the field of education and they give high priority to the engagement of an egalitarian dialogue with community members.

2. The effectiveness of the scalability and transference of educational practice depends on the characteristics of the dialogue shared during the process between all stakeholders. The main features of the dialogue that foster political impact are that it is based on scientific evidence, it is egalitarian and based on arguments and not on power claims, and its aim is to improve education for everyone.
3. Recommendations for policies also point to the need to educate children to become agents of transformation and active citizens who seek solutions for the problems of society
4. Community-oriented policies often create spaces where citizens can engage and participate in co-creation processes and also, give high priority to the inclusion of values such as diversity, equity and social justice.

Citizens' benefits from the social impact of research in education

As for the scientific impact of research in education, the analysis shed light about the importance of scientific educational research in the advancement of current societies. Among the main topics covered by the analysed articles were: the engagement of ethnic minorities in science, school actions to improve educational achievement and the relationship between scientists and society. The main conclusions in this regards were:

1. Educational research aimed at social transformation promotes the creation of new knowledge about how to engage and foster the participation of ethnic minorities in science
2. Universities should play an active role in current societies and promote the transference of knowledge beyond the walls of academia.
3. In order to build fair and sustainable societies, researchers should create spaces for the co-production of knowledge and the interaction between scientific knowledge provided by universities and experience-based knowledge provided by citizens.

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3. SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYTICS

3.1 Overview

As detailed in the DoA (p.10) in March 2021 (M6) the Social Media Analytics tasks of the project started. According to the GA (p.138) this analysis aimed to:

“provide information about how citizens interact in social media, focusing on the areas of gender and education (O1, O2, O3 & O4). For this analysis, social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Reddit will be considered. The focus will be on how citizen participation in science can be enhanced through online awareness-raising initiatives which link social advancements to the scientific research which led to them.”

For this purpose, ALLINTERACT consortium has followed the Social Impact in Social Media methodology (Pulido et al., 2018)¹, which consists of the identification of quantitative and qualitative evidence of the potential or real impact of research shared on social media.

This chapter of Report 1 contains the Social Media Analytics for topic a) How citizens’ benefit from scientific research.

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1 Methodology for the Social Media Analysis

SMA sought to reach citizens’ voices, paying special attention to vulnerable groups and young citizens. For this reason, different social networks were included in this analysis. Considering that each social network has specific characteristics, Table 3.1 compiles the main characteristics of each social network that were taken into account before the SMA.

Table 3.1. Characteristics of the selected social networks

Network	Options	Characteristics
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¹ Pulido, C. M., Redondo-Sama, G., Sordé-Martí, T., & Flecha, R. (2018). Social impact in social media: A new method to evaluate the social impact of research. *PLoS one*, 13(8).

Facebook	Pages	Most Facebook pages are not individual initiatives, but they belong to organisations, associations, media or campaigns. Citizens like or follow these pages, so they can see in their home page the contents shared by these pages. When pages share their content, citizens interact with this content through likes, sharing or comments, so this is one way to access citizens' voices	
	Groups	Public	Public groups include the voices of citizens, as all those users who are members of the group can post in the group and interact with the shared content. Users who are not part of the group can find the group (as long as the group is visible) and can see the content and interactions shared within the group, but they can only interact with the content through likes (they cannot publish a new post or comment in existing posts)
		Private	Allinteract will not access private groups
	Individual profiles	<p>One option to search what individual citizens post in their timelines is to browse by hashtags (e.g. #gender). The results will show only those posts containing the hashtag, which are public, including pages and those citizens with a public Facebook profile.</p> <p>NOTE: It is important to ensure that the results obtained through this search are representative of society, because the use of hashtag is not broadly normalised yet and most users do not post using hashtags. In fact, the use of hashtags is more common in pages or institutional profiles than in individual profiles.</p> <p>NOTE: Most citizens do not have their profiles in a public option, so it is difficult to get the whole picture in a search using hashtags.</p> <p>The second option is to use the keyword instead of the hashtag (without the #) in the browser and refining by "publications". However, the results in this search show only publications containing the keyword posted by your friends or</p>	

		public pages. Therefore, this is not a real alternative, as it is impossible to see the whole picture in these results.
Twitter	Individual profiles	The search can be carried out through hashtags and the results will show all public posts posted by individuals using the hashtag. Interactions with other citizens can be analysed through RT, comments or likes
Instagram	Individual profiles	The search can be carried out through hashtags and the results will show all public posts posted by individuals using the hashtag. Interactions with other citizens can be analysed mainly through likes. This social network is the most visual of all and users share pictures with hashtags and sometimes, a brief description. Therefore, it contains less written interactions among users.
Reddit	SubReddit	<p>When you conduct a search in Reddit, you can obtain results by posts and communities/users. As reddit does not use #, the posts results show all posts that use the keyword in every public reddit.</p> <p>When the search is refined by communities, you obtained all communities that mention that word (sorted by relevance, new... and filtered by period of time). In the communities, users share posts and comment posts about different topics. Some communities have categories to filter the posts (e.g: by topic, type of post, location...)</p>
	Individual users	Individual users can join Reddit communities and post or comment existing posts

Source: ALLINTERACT SMA protocol

The procedure carried out for the SMA is based on the ALLINTERACT Social Media Analytics Protocol (Flecha & Pulido, 2021) and summarised in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. ALLINTERACT SMA procedure

According to this protocol, the SMA has followed a twofold strategy:

- **Top-Down:** this approach consists in the definition of keywords related to gender/education and the topics of the project to contrast if these topics are expressed by citizens in their opinions, comments and post expressed in social media.
- **Bottom-Up:** this approach consists in the identification of topics that emerge from those keywords and hashtags most used by citizens in twitter. Then the emerging topics are contrasted with the topics defined by the project and analyse if they cover all aspects proposed by the project and/or there are some additional issues that were not covered initially by the project.

The analysis of the selected messages for topic a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research was also based on the SMA protocol, as can be detailed in the following Table 3.2.

Table 3.2. Analysis grid for Topic a) How Citizens' benefit from scientific research.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which have contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i>
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* Transformative/exclusionary dimension

The categories and dimensions of the analysis were defined as detailed in Table 3.3:

Table 3.3. Definitions of dimensions and categories for topic a.

Dimensions	Transformative dimension: includes those messages that evidence what facilitates the social/political/scientific impact mentioned in the message.
	Exclusionary dimension: includes those messages that show obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted social/political/scientific impact.
Categories	Scientific Impact: refers to the knowledge and recognition of the results of research by the scientific community. It includes the dissemination of scientific results, that happens when researchers share the results of research beyond academia and these results reach institutions, NGOs or citizens. (Reale et al., 2018) ² .
	Political impact: is related to the transference of the results of research to institutions, administrations, organisations, policymakers and citizens, who use these results to design policies or to improve plans actions and programs (Soler-Gallart, 2017) ³ .
	Social impact: is achieved when once the results of research have been published, disseminated and transferred, they improve citizens' lives in relation to the objectives such as the Sustainable Development Goals (IMPACT-EV, 2015) ⁴

3.2.2. Methodology for the Social Media Communicative Observation

The SMCO has aimed at further exploring which awareness-raising initiatives are succeeding at enhancing citizen participation in science, in regard to the SDGs of quality education and gender equality, with gender also being considered transversely throughout all SDGs.

Posts identified in mentioning successful awareness-raising initiatives were further explored, in order to identify which of them refer to actions that succeed as well in engaging citizens in active science

² Reale, E., Avramov, D., Canhial, K., Donovan, C., Flecha, R., Holm, P., ... & Van Horik, R. (2018). A review of literature on evaluating the scientific, social and political impact of social sciences and humanities research. *Research Evaluation*, 27(4), 298-308. <http://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvx025>

³ Soler-Gallart, M. (2017). *Achieving social impact: sociology in the public sphere*. Springer. <http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60270-7>

⁴ IMPACT-EV. (2015). Research Briefing. Social Impact of Research. Recuperat de http://impact-ev.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/research_briefing.pdf

participation. Researchers reviewed them one by one and classified them following the above-mentioned categories (Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research, Awareness-raising initiatives succeeding at engaging citizens in scientific participation, including the Open Access movement, awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences, and policies that promote awareness-raising actions and citizen engagement in science). The success rate of the identified initiatives was also calculated.

3.2.2.1. Selection of the Facebook and Reddit Groups

This research has selected the social media groups/pages taking into account the most used words when talking about gender and education identified in WP1. Based on these words, groups were searched for on the social networks Facebook and Reddit. Specifically, 61 groups were searched, 29 for gender and 32 for education (see Table 3.4.).

Table 3.4. Table summarising the groups that were pre-selected and subsequently contacted for gender and education:

Social Media	Pre-selected Groups Gender	Pre-selected Groups Education
Facebook	CAMPAIGN AWARENESS AGAINST GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE & GENDER INEQUALITY!, UNI-Mentors in Violence Prevention, The Feminism Platform, Gender equality in the Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement, ETUC Gender Equality, Global Youth Movement Against Gender Based Violence, LGBT Advocacy, EMPOWER EQUALIT. CHILD RIGHT AND GENDER EQUALITY SUPPORT, Gender-based Violence Campaign Group., Gender Based Violence SOLUTIONS, Gender Equity and Reconciliation International, Equality 4 Women, LGBTQ+ Protest Group	Parents for children's education / Parents union from all around the world, School teacher and administrator educational resources, Child Care' Development, Education & Parenting, Our Voice: Communities for Quality Education Group, International Special Needs Teachers/ Learning Support Teachers, Amazing Educational Resources, Special Education Community, Quality Early Childhood Education and Care, PARENTS, TEACHERS AND STUDENTS FORUM, All Teachers' Unity Platform, Teachers and Students, Teachers Throwing Out Grades, The Quality Education Project, Special Education Community, FAME - Families Against Mis-Education.

Reddit	<p>r/feminism, r/feminisms, r/FeMRADebates, r/PurplePillDebate, r/bisexual, r/SRSFeminism, r/AskFeminists, r/Equality, r/TwoXChromosomes, r/AskWomen, r/relationships, r/SexualHarassment, r/GenderIssues, r/MeToo, r/LGBTeens, r/women</p>	<p>r/education, r/ScienceTeachers, r/ApplyingToCollege, r/teaching, r/science, r/Teachers, r/college, r/parenting, r/ParentTeacherGroups, r/ECEC, r/FutureTeachers, r/ScienceEducation, r/highschool, r/specialed, r/Teacher, r/Children.</p>
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We contacted the administrators of these groups to participate in the research, of which four replied, two of them decided to participate. However, it was not carried out because they did not provide the ethical consent created to participate in the research.

In parallel, the research team decided to create and search for other social media groups/pages. In the area of gender, five groups on Facebook and five on Reddit were created and selected again, while in the area of education, 5 Reddit groups were created and 5 Facebook groups/pages were contacted where scientific evidence in education was already being discussed.

Table 3.5. shows the names of the gender groups and in which language they are spoken in the group.

Table 3.5. Facebook and Reddit groups created on gender:

Facebook			Reddit		
Selected Groups	Language	Origen	Selected Groups	Language	Origen
Contra el acoso que reciben quienes apoyan a las víctimas / VG Aisladora	Spanish	Created	r/Contra_SOSH	Spanish	Created
Against the harassment of victim supporters / IGV	English	Created	r/Against_SOSH	English	Created
Our right to fall in love	English	Created	r/OurRigthToFallInLove	English	Created
Grup de Dones Sherezade: Dialogant el Feminisme	Catalan	Selected	r/genderviolence	English	Created

Social Impact Science Platform	English	Created	r/science_gender_sappho	English	Created
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The table below lists the names of the education groups and in which language the group speaks.

Table 3.6 Facebook and Reddit groups or pages created about education:

Facebook			Reddit		
Selected Groups	Language	Origen	Selected Groups	Language	Origen
Comunidades de Aprendizaje. Schools as Learning Communities	Spanish	Selected	r/GruposInteractivos	Spanish	Created
Tertulias Literarias y Musicales Dialógicas	Spanish	Selected	r/InteractiveGroups	Spanish	Created
Actuaciones Educativas de Éxito. Comunidades de Aprendizaje	Spanish	Selected	r/TertuliasDialogicas	Spanish	Created
Comunidade de Aprendizagem / Comunidad de Aprendizaje	Spanish	Selected	r/DialogicGatherings	English	Created
Inclusividad NEE en CdA. Inclusion SEN in Schools as Learning Communities	Spanish	Selected	r/EducacionInclusiva	Spanish	Created

In these groups, posts were written in relation to the results of the Allinteract research, in which users could interact with the content. The groups were also used to provide information and consent for those who wished to participate. The selected groups were informed, and consent was obtained from the administrators and the users whose comments were analysed.

3.2.2.2. Selection of Social Impact Platforms Forums

Allinteract research has been involved since the beginning, in October 2020, in the creation of two Social Impact Platforms, one in gender and the other in education. So, the Allinteract team at the University of Barcelona has decided to incorporate these in the current SMCO analysis.

These platforms are led by the Research Group in Sociological Theory and Impact of Research (TSIR). The two platforms are non-populist participatory platforms, available to everyone, both to consult and to contribute. They are contributing to deepen, on the one hand, in the development of sociological theory at the international level and, on the other hand, to the analysis and improvement of the social impact of research.

These platforms are built with a bottom-up approach that brings together not only researchers and practitioners, but all citizens, both to consult and to contribute. These participatory instruments are committed to promoting an egalitarian dialogue based on validity claims and the sharing of scientific evidence with all citizens. Thus, these platforms are Open Access platforms available to everyone. Any citizen who wants to participate will be able to sign in and contribute. Participation will be totally voluntary.

These platforms are:

- SAPPHO scientific evidence platform is focused on Gender SDG.
(<https://socialimpactsience.org/gender/>)
- ADHYAYANA scientific evidence platform is focused on SDG Quality Education, from a multicultural perspective. It will deepen, on the one hand, the development of sociological theory at the international level and, on the other hand, it will contribute to the analysis and improvement of the social impact of research.
(<https://socialimpactsience.org/education/>)

The research team contacted the platforms' administration team to inform them of the selection and obtained consent. We also contacted the people selected for the study and obtained consent (Online consent form <https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=qzwxosOxOk-7ESFXRH3btA8lqcPRmYtGj4JVP3l6T1ZUQ1VIVkFIMUVGN1hCN1hHQ1pBQjITMjE4Ry4u>)

3.2.2.3. Data Collection

The information collected has been carried out from May 2021 to December 2021 (6 months) for the social networks Facebook and Reddit. While the information from the Social Impact Science forums has been collected from October 2020 to December 2021 (15 months).

A total of 21,322 members made up the 20 groups selected/created (10 in gender and 10 in education) and the two Social Impact Science Platforms. **A total of 1383 posts related to the research objective**

have been made, which have had **3,397 interactions (reactions and sharings)** and **576 comments** have been made.

3.2.2.3.1. Data collection on gender

In the field of gender, a total of 885 posts have been made in relation to the research on Facebook, Reddit and Social Impact Science on Sappho. Of the 3,171 members who are part of the groups/pages or forums have interacted (reactions and sharings) 1882 times and made 158 comments.

Details are given below:

Facebook Gender

In relation to the 5 Facebook groups/pages, **486 posts** related to the results of the research project have been published and a total of **600 members have joined**, of which **1875 have interacted and made 38 comments**.

Table 3.7. Detailed table of the gender-related Facebook groups/pages studied.

Facebook				
Group/Page	No. of members / followers	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
Contra el acoso que reciben quienes apoyan a las víctimas / VG Aisladora	110	106	400	3
Against the harassment of victim supporters / IGV	77	110	175	10
Our right to fall in love	25	45	71	2
Grup de Dones Sherezade: Dialogant el Feminisme	65	10	20	0
Social Impact Science Platform (Gender)	323	215	1,209	23

Reddit Gender

In the case of Reddit, 5 sub-communities were created, of which **a total of 313 posts** were made about the project and a total of **45 members took part, of which 7 interactions and 4 comments were made.**

In January 2021, when we looked at this data again, we realised that Reddit administrators had deleted around 276 comments in January 2022. So, there are currently 37 public comments left in 2021.

Table 3.8. Detailed table of Reddit groups on gender.

Reddit				
Group	No. of members	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
r/Contra_SOSH	13	98 (6)	3	2
r/Against_SOSH	12	98 (7)	2	2
r/OurRighToFallInLove	8	65 (6)	0	0
r/genderviolence	3	22(14)	1	0
r/science_gender_sappho	9	30 (4)	1	0

Social impact Platform Gender

The **2,526 members** of the platform have made **86 related posts** of which other members have made **116 comments** in which they discuss the scientific evidence on gender. People have contributed reflections, scientific articles, experiences, or statistical data.

Table 3.11. Detailed table of members, comments, and feedback on SapPho Platform.

SapPho Platform		
No. of members	No. of Post	No. of Comments
2,526	86	116

3.2.2.3.2. Data collection on education

In the field of education, **a total of 498 posts** have been made in relation to the research on Facebook, Reddit, and Social Impact Science on Adhyayana. Of the **18,151 members** who are part of the groups/pages or forums have interacted (reactions and sharings) **1,515 times** and made **418 comments**.

Facebook Education

In the 5 selected Facebook groups/pages on education, about **90 posts** related to the results of the research project have been published. There are **17,527 members** in these groups, of which **1506 interactions and 8 comments** have been made.

Table 3.10. Detailed table of the education Facebook groups/pages surveyed.

Facebook				
Group/Page	No. of members/ followers	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
Comunidades de Aprendizaje. Schools as Learning Communities	4,947	28	338	1
Tertulias Literarias y Musicales Dialógicas	1,107	7	30	0
Actuaciones Educativas de Éxito. Comunidades de Aprendizaje	2,617	35	972	7
Comunidade de Aprendizagem / Comunidad de Aprendizaje	8,631	8	135	0
Inclusividad NEE en CdA. Inclusion SEN in Schools as Learning Communities	225	12	31	0

Reddit Education

In the case of Reddit, 5 sub-communities were created, of which **a total of 203 posts** were made about the project and a total of 49 members took part, of which **9 interactions and 3 comments** were made.

Table 3.12. Detailed table of Reddit groups on education.

Reddit				
Group/Page	No. of members	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
r/GruposInteractivos	13	72	3	0
r/InteractiveGroups	9	70	2	2
r/TertuliasDialogicas	12	55	1	1
r/DialogicGatherings	9	45	3	0
r/EducacionInclusiva	6	33	0	0

*These Reddit groups are no longer accessible.

In January 2022, when we looked at this data again, we realised that the Reddit administrators have removed the five sub-communities.

Social Impact Science Adhyayana

The **575 members** of the platform have made **133 related posts** of which other members have made **407 comments** in which they discuss the scientific evidence on gender. People have contributed reflections, scientific articles, experiences, or statistical data.

Table 3.12. Detailed table of members, comments, and feedback on Adhyayana Platform.

Adhyayana Platform		
No. of members	No. of Post	No. of Comments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

575	133	407
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3.2.2.3.3. Final Research Sample

For the final analysis, the first 5 posts on education and 5 on gender that are related to scientific evidence were selected. Finally, **76 comments were analysed (20 on gender and 56 on education)**.

3.2.2.4. Social Media Communicative Observation - Analysis

The analysis of the Social Media Communicative Observation consisted in exploring the effects of introducing scientific evidence in the interactions.

The selected groups have been studied in detail using the software MAXQDA2020, in order to explore which of the selected actions have succeeded at enhancing participation in science.

The comment threads were listed according to the order of appearance (E1, E2, E3,...), while listing the participants (1, 2, 3...) who made contributions that were related to the object of study. Finally, **57 comments were analysed (21 on gender and 36 on education)**.

The messages have been categorised by the following selected actions and we have identified for each category the transformative and the exclusionary dimensions. The categories we have analysed are: 1) Aim of the enhancing-participation action; 2) Promoting organisation (i.e., aim; private/public); 3) Level of intervention (i.e., local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down); 4) Field of intervention; 5) Participants (targeted and real); 6) Type of participation (i.e., role of participants); 7) Level of access to scientific evidence; and 8) Social impact.

For each of these categories, the transformative dimension (i.e., what facilitates the implementation of the targeted actions) and the exclusionary dimension (i.e., obstacles hindering the implementation of the targeted actions) were identified.

The SMCO analysis has consisted mainly of a review one by one of the posts, classifying them and identifying and selecting the actions that succeed in active science participation. The consent form has been obtained from the participating members of the analysed posts.

Then we have identified the changes in the debate after the scientific evidence was introduced in the discussion.

Once data has been categorised, we have calculated the correlation between the two variables "citizen awareness of the social impact of research" and "citizen engagement in science".

3.3 Results

From the 21,289 messages extracted, 2,091 messages (966 in gender and 1,125 in education) were discarded from the analysis, as detailed in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2. Selected and discarded messages in gender and education

The main reasons for discarding posts were:

- Broken links or lack of access to the content, which made impossible the categorization
- Not being related to areas of study that are gender and education
- Not falling in the scope of topic a, or not showing how citizen benefit from science

Therefore, the final analysis included a total of 19,198 messages, distributed as presented in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3. Distribution of the messages included in the analysis.

3.3.1 SMA - Citizens' benefits from social impact in gender

Following the ALLINTERACT SMA protocol, the SMA in gender has implemented a twofold strategy, including a **top-down approach**, described in section 3.3.1.1 and a **bottom-up approach**, described in section 3.3.1.2.

3.3.1.1 Top-Down strategy - gender

As above-mentioned, the top-down strategy was conducted in **(1) Twitter, (2) Facebook, (3) Instagram and (4) Reddit**. Due to the different characteristics of each social network, they were analysed separately. For each network **quantitative** and **qualitative findings** are presented. The qualitative findings section provides evidence on the **scientific impact, political impact and social impact** reflected in the analysed social media posts.

1) Twitter

The SMA in Twitter included the analysis of the hashtags #Equality, #Gender, #GenderEquality, #WomenRights and #HeForShe, with a total of 5,464 tweets. More than 9 out of 10 of the tweets (91.42%) obtained at least one retweet, being 21.42 the average number of retweets obtained.

Quantitative findings

More than half of the tweets (56.31%) were examples of how citizens benefit from the social impact of research, more than one third (35.61%) from the political impact of research and an 8.07% from the scientific impact of research (Figure 3.4):

Figure 3.4. Distribution of categories in Twitter Top – Down (gender)

The following Figure 3.5 shows that almost all tweets were classified into the transformative dimension, but a 3.09% of the messages within the social impact category were exclusionary. These exclusionary tweets were messages that claimed to be using science or that were using scientific concepts to blame all men for gender violence or to discourage men from the fight against gender-based violence:

Figure 3.5. Distribution of dimensions in Twitter Top – Down (gender)

Regarding the use of scientific evidence, the following figure represents the distribution of the used sources across all categories (Figure 3.6).

The scientific category was the category where more tweets containing any type of scientific evidence were found (34.92% of certified scientific evidence and 40.36% of supposed scientific evidence). In the other categories, the total amount of scientific sources was 36.43% in the political impact and 23.98% in the social impact. Most of these sources did not come from journals indexed in Scopus or JCR but from official reports about the prevalence of gender-based violence instead. Finally, Figure 3.7 presents the proportion of tweets in each category that provide real and potential examples of the impact of research.

Figure 3.6. Distribution of scientific evidence in Twitter Top – Down (gender)

Figure 3.7. Distribution of potential-real impacts in Twitter Top – Down (gender)

As shown in Figure 3.7., there is an important difference between categories. Whereas in the scientific impact category more than 9 out of 10 (96.37%) of the tweets were real examples of the impact of research, less than a 13% of the messages in the other categories (12.85% in the political impact and 12.64% in the social impact) were real examples of how scientific research had benefited citizens.

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

In all the hashtags analysed in this social network there were examples of real scientific impact of research. The formats for the dissemination of scientific contributions to the society were diverse, ranging from scientific articles or reports to talks, workshops, press articles or podcasts, among others. The topic covered by these messages were also wide, including equality in a broad sense (not only in terms of gender, but also ethnicity, age and disabilities, among others), scientific contributions in the field of gender, or the close relation between gender and other areas, such as Artificial Intelligence, climate change, energy, agriculture, poverty, mobility, urbanism, or water facilities, among others. There was also a group of tweets that shared a specific example of scientific impact that was how the European Commission had distinguished a research project about gender equality in STEM communication with a good-practice mention.

Another group of tweets included potential examples of the scientific impact of research because they were disseminating and sharing information about a research project in process, which could provide scientific impact in the future.

b. Political Impact

A lot of tweets were classified as evidence of political impact of research, including both real and potential examples. Regarding the potential impact, there were examples of social denounces, awareness-raising, recommendations, campaigns, commitments and the convention of the UN on the Status of Women:

- **Social denunciation:** these messages included denunciations promoted by different social actors, including citizens, companies, NGOs, political organisations, associations, expert groups, financial institutions and governmental organisations. These actors used reports, videos, campaigns and interviews to denounce the inequalities that women face in diverse areas, such as pensions, poverty, leadership, labour, COVID-19 pandemic, policymaking, political participation and gender violence, among others. Some of these messages targeted policymakers and governments and demanded actions against violence against women and racism, as well as equality departments in governments and organizations.
- **Awareness-raising:** These messages included press articles, interviews, webinars, workshops, reports, videos and open letters to world leaders that aimed to raise awareness about diverse topics, such as women leadership, urbanism, climate, labour and education. Most of these tweets were promoted by NGOs, governmental organisations, companies, parliaments and police forces.
- **Recommendations:** these tweets included recommendations for the advance of gender equality in diverse fields, such as urbanism, labour, energy, artificial intelligence, mobility, climate, feminist policies and sanitation, as well as for the overcoming of sexual harassment and violence against women. These recommendations were provided by governmental organisations, NGO and networks of NGOs, researchers, companies and partnerships of companies, associations and governments and provided their recommendations through different formats, including press articles, policy briefs, handbooks, webinars and round tables, among others.
- **Campaigns:** these messages included information about both, official campaigns, such as UN campaign He For She and campaigns led by citizens. The main messages of these campaigns was to include men in the fight against gender inequalities and to promote legal actions to criminalize sexual harassment.
- **Commitments:** these messages included commitments made by governments, NGOs and enterprises to implement policies and actions to fight racism and gender inequalities and to promote feminist foreign policies and recovery plans for the COVID-19 pandemic.
- **65th Commission on the Status of Women:** This event, organised by the UN, was held between March 15th and 26th. There were diverse messages mentioning this convention, including information of the event, links to access and join the convention, interventions of speakers or conclusions of the convention. Some of the messages were encouraging participation of citizens with a focus on democracy, religious diversity, intergenerational inclusion, participation of women in politics and presence of women in technology. The interventions of speakers shared quotes expressed by experts, policymakers or representatives of NGOs in the panels and sessions organised within the 65th CSW. Some of the topics of the 65CSW that were present in Twitter were tax justice, religious diversity, the impact of desertification on women, poverty, women in leadership and democracy.

On the other hand, the examples of real political impact included actions, legislations, transference of scientific results to other contexts and visibilization of successful cases:

- **Actions:** these messages included the implementation of diverse actions such as voting sessions in parliaments about LGBT rights, increases in budget and inversions, the implementation of Gender Equality Plans, programs of enterprises, mining companies and prizes for companies that implement equality policies.
- **Legislations:** in this group there were tweets with current laws, modification of the laws and advances in laws related to gender. The main topics covered by these legislations were gender curriculum in educational centers, equal pay, equality plans, violence against women and equal rights.
- **Transference:** the transference of research results to other contexts included initiatives of community participation and implication of different social actors (including neighbours, families and policymakers) in school decision-making spaces and processes. Other examples included the implementation of an evidence-based action, the Safe Zone in companies to fight against violence against LGBT community or the use of geospatial technology to promote gender equality.
- **Visibilization of successful cases:** there were several examples of cases that had successfully implemented policies to overcome gender inequalities. Some examples included countries that had implemented feminist foreign policies, cities that had implemented measures to ensure safe and equitable mobility in terms of gender and the testimonies of pioneer women in the field of politics.

c. Social Impact

The examples of potential social impact of research included awareness-raising and support initiatives, resources and recommendations, services and programs, actions in process of implementation, and campaigns:

- **Awareness-raising and support:** these messages included examples of initiatives led by representatives of all sectors of society, including citizens, policymakers, NGOs, international governmental organisations, companies, schools, political parties, associations, youth organisations, and associations of experts and professionals in different fields. Some of the more common formats chosen to raise awareness were press articles, campaigns, reports, conferences, podcasts, videos, and webinars. The topics of the awareness-raising messages were diverse and often included mentions to the SDGs. There were specific topics related to gender such as glass ceiling, LGBT rights, bystander intervention as a key element for the overcoming of gender-based violence, child sexual abuse, harassment in social media, gender pay gap and the importance of men as allies in the feminist movement. In addition, there were messages that were focused on the interdependence of gender with other areas, such as education, labour, sport, health, mobility, climate change, agriculture, water sanitation, drug consumption and stigma, artificial intelligence and ethnicity.
- **Resources and recommendations:** these messages were mostly provided by NGOs, universities, and enterprises and were related to the promotion of mental health, the overcoming of racism, the increase of women in leadership or in technology and the promotion of financial equality. Some

of these recommendations were included in official reports and used tools provided by governmental international organisations.

- **Services and programs:** These services and programs were led by NGOs and enterprises and included the promotion of educational programs in different countries focused on the education of girls as a key factor for social transformation.
- **Actions in process of implementation:** these actions were mainly led by NGOs although some of them were initiatives promoted by companies and enterprises. Most of the messages mentioned how the actions were contributing to the SDG 5 of Gender Equality and in some cases, they also referred to other SDGs. The main topics of these actions were gender equality, nutrition, internet connectivity and women empowerment.
- **Campaigns:** these messages included both official campaigns (e.g. #HeForShe or #ChooseToChallenge) and citizens-driven campaigns, including fund-raising initiatives. Besides the overcoming of gender-based violence, the topics of these campaigns girls empowerment, LGBT rights, sexual health and sexual harassment.

Finally, the real examples of social impact of research included use of scientific concepts, science advances, impact of actions and visibilization of successful cases:

- **Use of scientific concepts:** these tweets were shared by individual users and contained visual material to explain the differences of concepts, such as equity and equality, inclusion and integration or sex, gender and sexuality.
- **Science advances:** these messages included tweets from companies and individual users sharing press articles about scientific contributions in the field of artificial intelligence, the overcoming of gender bias in data science, climate adaptation and technology innovations.
- **Impact of actions:** there were messages that share the impact achieved by specific actions in the promotion of women political participation, black women health, access to water, financial and technical women empowerment, and COVID-19 gender labour gap, among others. These messages provided examples of initiatives carried out by NGOs, partnerships of NGOs, enterprises, citizens' platforms and universities. Several of these actions promoted by NGOs mentioned how their actions had contributed to the SDG5 Gender Equality. It is important to highlight a group of tweets that mentioned the impact of the Beijing Declaration on the fight against gender-based violence.
- **Visibilization of successful cases:** These examples of tweets were mainly promoted by NGOs and shared successful stories of girls who could serve as role models. There were also examples of villages that had overcome female genital mutilation, colleges awarded with prizes related to equality and diversity, or the presence of women in Mars Missions. Other messages that were present in this group were those of testimonies of bystander intervention, reports from the UN with advances in the SDGs and programs of NGOs related to health and access to clean water.

2) Facebook

The SMA in Facebook using a top-down strategy consisted of the analysis of the pages Never Alone, NOH8 Campaign, World Wide Women, Women Rights News and Equality Now. According to their descriptions, the aim of the two first pages is to raise awareness about sexual abuse in the first case and LGBT discrimination in the second. The other three are pages where news related to gender issues and women rights are shared. A total of 139 messages, including posts and comments were included in the final analysis. It is important to mention that in Facebook pages there are two types of messages: posts and comments. Posts are shared by the own page, which is administered by specific users and comments are shared by individual users who can interact among them around the issue proposed in the post.

Quantitative findings

Almost all the messages (93.53%) were included in the social impact category and the rest in the political impact category. This analysis did not find any message related to the scientific impact of research (see Figure 3.8):

Figure 3.8. Distribution of categories in Facebook (gender)

The analysis of the dimensions found that the majority of the messages were transformative (Figure 3.9). The messages that were included in the exclusionary dimension were messages that were using scientific data or statistics in a way that discourage men from joining the feminist movement or the fight against gender violence.

Figure 3.9. Distribution of dimensions in Facebook (gender)

Regarding the presence of scientific sources in these Facebook pages, the analysis found that more than two thirds of the messages did not contain any mention of scientific evidence, besides showing how citizens benefit from scientific research. As detailed in Figure 3.10, among those users that mentioned scientific evidence, there was scarce presence of certified scientific evidence. In most cases users claimed to be basing their arguments in science using expressions such as “Studies say that” or “According to science” but provided no reference of these studies. It is important to remark that, in some of these cases there were answers from other users that asked for and demanded these studies.

Figure 3.10. Distribution of scientific evidence | Facebook (gender)

Finally, Figure 3.11 shows the presence of real and potential impact of research. It is especially relevant the percentage of real social impact of science (63.08%) that corresponds to the use of scientific contributions in the debates that citizens shared in the social network:

Figure 3.11. Distribution of potential-real impacts in Facebook (gender)

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

There were no messages categorised as evidence of scientific impact in the analysed Facebook pages.

b. Political Impact

Only 8 messages were classified as evidence of political impact. Some of them were real examples of political impact and included comments with press articles echoing campaigns promoted by citizens and policymakers. Those messages with potential evidence of political impact included comments sharing news about citizens' mobilizations to claim changes in legislation.

c. Social Impact

Most of the messages were examples of social impact of research, including both real and potential examples of social impact. The examples of real social impact included on the one hand, how citizens adopted and used science concepts in their discussions with other users, explaining for example, how gender is biological and gender is a social construct. On the other hand, there were examples of citizens exchanging arguments based on scientific contributions to controversial issues, such as the trans* debate. Although citizens exchanged contrary perspectives, those that advanced in the debate were the ones including scientific contributions and evidence.

Regarding the potential examples of social impact, there were messages and debates that raised the awareness about issues such as, LGBT rights, sexual abuse, suicide and the importance of breaking the silence against gender violence. It is important to mention a specific debate about the implication of men in the feminist movement, in which some users that claimed that all men are potential abusers and others that defended that men are essential to overcome gender violence and that there are men and women who support the abusers and men and women who support the victims.

3) Instagram

The SMA in Instagram included the hashtags #womenempowerment, #domesticviolence, #womenrights, #feminism and #genderequality and a total of 386 posts. Due to the characteristics of the social network, the analysis in this case considered as unit of analysis the whole post, including the text and the image.

Quantitative findings

All messages were categorised into the established categories, as presented in Figure 3.12:

Figure 3.12. Distribution of categories in Instagram (gender)

More than eight out of ten of the posts (85.49%) were examples of social impact of research, followed by examples of political impact (13.99%). In contrast, the percentage of posts showing examples of scientific impact was extremely low (0.54%). A reason behind this high presence of social impact posts is that Instagram was a social network where citizens denounce facts and raise awareness on current issues related to violence against women or gender inequality. Although most of the posts were categorized within the transformative messages, 1.85% of the political impact posts and 2.42% of the social impact posts (see Figure 3.13) were considered exclusionary because use contributions of science in gender issues to blame all men or to discourage men from joining the feminist movement.

Figure 3.13. Distribution of dimensions in Instagram (gender)

Unlike other networks, in Instagram there were 7 cases of contradictory messages in one post. These posts mainly contained a transformative text claiming that the overcoming of gender violence needs both, men and women, with an exclusionary photo representing how all men are potential abusers and cannot be trusted. Instagram provided another interesting finding related to the number of likes that got transformative and exclusionary posts. The following Table 3.13 represents this finding in the three hashtags where both transformative and exclusionary posts were found:

Table 3.13. Differences in the number of likes obtained across dimensions.

	Average n of likes in transformative posts	Average n of likes in exclusionary posts
#womenrights	34.02	55.00

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

#feminism	44.29	13.71
#genderequality	41.70	9.00

In two of the three hashtags, those posts that were discouraging men from joining the feminist movements, or that were blaming all men of gender-based violence obtained less likes than those that fostered social transformation.

The use of scientific evidence was not common in Instagram posts, as shown in Figure 3.14:

Figure 3.14. Distribution of scientific evidence in Instagram (gender)

Most of the messages did not contain data or any reference to a source. In some cases, in order to make the magnitude of the problem of violence against women visible, citizens use statistics and figures about the number of victims of gender violence, but they did not mention the sources where this data came from. As Instagram is not a social network for engaging debates and discussions with other users, there were no cases of citizens asking for studies or scientific evidence to other users.

Regarding the proportion of posts with real or potential evidence of the impact of research, the analysis showed that the posts contained mainly examples of potential impact of research (Figure 3.15)

Figure 15. Distribution of potential-real impacts in Instagram (gender)

The scientific impact category included only two posts that disseminated scientific studies. The proportion of messages with real examples of the impact of research was 9.26% in the political impact category and 4.55 in the social impact category. This high proportion of potential impact of research was related to the use of Instagram mainly to denounce and raise awareness about recent cases of gender violence. Citizens used this social network as a space to show citizens' mobilisation, to break the silence against gender violence to promote bystander intervention and to support or stand up for the victims. In all these cases, citizens were benefiting from advances that were possible due to extant research in gender issues that has been key for the empowerment and mobilisation of citizens.

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

Only two posts in Instagram were classified in the category of scientific impact of research. One of them was the invitation to a dissemination event related to ornithology and the other shared a scientific article published in Harvard Business Review to promote discussion around women in business.

b. Political Impact

Within the political impact category there were examples of posts that contained potential impact of research, mostly through sensibilization initiatives, citizens' mobilizations and initiatives to promote changes in legislation:

- **Sensibilization:** These messages aimed to raise awareness about the importance of advances in the fight against gender violence, such as the Istanbul Convention, to share information about conventions of the United Nations, such as the 65th session of the Commission on the Status of Women or to denounce violations of women's rights.
- **Citizens' mobilizations:** These posts share initiatives promoted by citizens from different parts of the world to protest about specific issues. Some examples of this type of messages included posts that showed citizens surrounding the Australian Parliament to claim political actions against gender-based violence or demonstrations of citizens asking for more mechanisms to report gender-based violence.
- **Initiatives to promote changes in legislation:** These messages included letters from NGOs addressed to world leaders to call for action about gender inequalities and also campaigns started by NGOs or citizens to change current legislation related to gender violence.

The real examples of political impact included reforms in the legislation, the implementation of programs and services and the transference of the results of research.

- **Reforms in legislation:** Some of these posts were examples of how citizens' mobilizations and claims had promoted changes at political level. The topics of these legislations included gender parity, abortion and equal rights.
- **Implementation of programs and services:** This group included examples of projects to protect the victims of gender-violence, such as safe houses for women who had suffered gender violence or protection orders for the victims.
- **Transference:** In this group there were some examples of how enterprises had transferred the results of research to design products and apps in issues related to conception, pregnancy and fertility.

c. Social Impact

Some of the examples of potential social impact found in Instagram included awareness and resources:

- **Awareness:** this group included different initiatives that aimed to denounce gender violence and raise awareness about gender inequalities. There were examples of webinars, videos, citizens' campaigns and visual content such as images and infographics. Although most of these initiatives were led by citizens, the presence of awareness material provided by NGOs and enterprises was also noticeable. The main topics covered in these messages were consent, sexual abuse, gender gap, rape, gender inequalities, trans* rights and topics related to recent cases of violence. In this line, the key messages turned around Asian hate in the US, the Not All Men debate (if all men are guilty of gender violence or if they can be part of the solution) and debates around clothes and consent.
- **Resources:** Most of the resources were related to gender-based violence and included, among others information about how to identify different forms of abuse, safe helplines available 24 hours a day and seven days a week for women who are suffering gender violence and information for citizens about the hand signal of help. These posts were promoted by diverse actors, including individual citizens, associations, enterprises, NGOs, and governments among others. In this line it is important to mention an initiative driven by a partnership between the government and pharmacies that had converted pharmacies into help points for victims of gender-based violence.

The examples of messages containing real evidence of social impact of research were grouped in use of scientific concepts and visibilization of successful cases:

- **Use of scientific concepts:** These posts included images and texts that use and explain scientific concepts related to gender roles and the LGBT community.
- **Visibilization of successful cases:** These messages included posts with videos of citizens sharing their testimonies of how they succeeded both personally and professionally after having suffered gender violence or sexual harassment. The aim of these videos was to provide positive role models to girls and women suffering gender violence.

4) Reddit

The SMA in Reddit included the analysis of posts and comments included in 5 communities: r/PurplePill, r/bisexual, r/FEMRADebates, r/Feminism and r/Feminisms. A total of 166 messages including posts and comments were analysed within this topic. It is important to mention that in reddit communities there are two types of messages: posts and comments. Nevertheless, and unlike social networks such as Facebook, both types of messages are shared by individual users who can propose specific topics for the debate, ask for advice or share news with other members of the community. A total of 166 messages were analysed in this social network.

Quantitative findings

As detailed in Figure 3.16, most of the messages (89.16%) were analysed as examples of social impact of research.

Figure 16. Distribution of categories in Reddit (gender)

Most of the messages within all the categories were examples of how citizens were using scientific research to improve their lives and those of people around them, but some of the messages claimed to be using science and hindered social transformation. These messages were included in the exclusionary dimension (see Figure 3.17):

Figure 17. Distribution of dimensions in Reddit (gender)

As detailed in this figure, all the exclusionary messages were found within the social impact category (12.84%). These messages provided examples of citizens using scientific arguments in debates around gender issues to revictimize survivors, blame all men and discourage them from the feminist movement. There were also some posts from citizens doubting science and considering science as relative and non-reliable because they considered that all women lied in the studies.

Regarding the use of scientific evidence, it is noticeable that in all cases, more than 30% of the messages included a reference to a scientific source, both indexed and non-indexed in JCR and Scopus (Figure 3.18).

Figure 3.18. Distribution of scientific evidence in Reddit (gender)

Unlike other networks, in Reddit discussions, people used studies, statistics and data from research to base and reinforce their arguments. Several of the debates turned around issues that are controversial also within the scientific community, such as gender roles, trans*, contraception or consent, among others, but users used scientific arguments to reply to other users, to base their comments, to refute previous arguments and to reinforce other comments. It is also important to mention that there were also users who steered the debate towards an evidence-based debate, asking other users for scientific references or asking them what studies they were basing their claims on.

Finally, regarding the presence of examples of real and potential examples of the impact of research, Figure 3.19 represents the proportion of each type within the three categories:

Figure 3.19. Distribution of potential-real impacts in Reddit (gender)

As shown in Figure 3.19, all messages within the scientific impact category were real examples of dissemination of scientific research to the Reddit community. In the social impact category, the proportion of real examples is of 43.92% whereas in the political impact category is of 25%. In both categories, those messages included in the potential group were mainly focused on raising awareness about different gender issues and those messages in the real group provided examples of how citizens have interiorized scientific advances and are able to engage discussions basing their arguments on scientific claims.

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

On Reddit, only 10 of the analysed messages contained examples of scientific impact of research. The most common form of scientific impact evidence was through press articles provided by users in their comments. The main topics covered by these messages were the gender bias in Artificial Intelligence and the prevalence of gender violence worldwide. There were also examples of users recommending books about feminism from authors such as bell hooks.

b. Political Impact

Only 8 messages were included in the political impact category and they contained awareness-raising messages about the positive impact of the presence of women in parliaments and governments and also links to articles from the UN about the political needs worldwide.

c. Social Impact

As above mentioned, more than half of the messages in the social impact category were examples of potential social impact of research. These posts and comments, which were all shared by individual users, aimed to raise awareness about specific gender issues. The more common topics were how education is key to overcome gender violence, debates around what is feminism and what is femininity, the importance of taking action and becoming active bystanders in situations of gender

violence and discussions about whether the presence of men in the feminist movement is beneficial or detrimental.

Regarding the examples of potential social impact of research, there were three types of comments: the use of scientific concepts and data, the use of scientific arguments to the debate and specific actions.

- **Use of scientific concepts and data:** In this type of messages, there were tweets using and explaining scientific terminology and statistics. One interesting example of this type of messages that was found frequently, were examples of users explaining the differences between the concepts sex and gender, using contributions from science in this debate.
- **Use of scientific arguments:** In the analysed communities it was common to find comments with debates among users about the topic of the post. In most of these debates, users provided scientific arguments and evidence to refute other comments, to strengthen their perspective and to advance in the discussion. It is important to mention the widespread use of science in these debates. Although the shared perspectives were often contradictory and controversial, users were basing their claims on scientific studies. These debates were usually about issues that can be controversial, such as gender roles, trans* identity, femininity, patriarchy and homophobia.
- **Specific action:** There were a group of messages about an initiative led by a company that consisted of withdrawing from their stock all books and materials that defined homosexuality of LGBT as mental illnesses and disorders.

3.3.1.2 Bottom-up strategy - gender

1) Twitter

The SMA in Twitter with a bottom-up approach included hashtags that were retrieved from the daily trending topics in all European countries. In this line, it includes the hashtags #IStandWithLinda, #EqualPayDay, #WiMINConference21, #ReclaimTheStreets and #EnoughisEnough and a total number of 3,183 tweets. Almost 9 out of 10 of the tweets (89.57%) were retweeted at least once, obtaining an average of 80.10 retweets.

Quantitative findings

The classification of tweets in the three established categories found that more than eight out of ten (82.09%) of the tweets are examples of social impact of research, followed by political impact (16.43%). On the contrary, the proportion of tweet regarding the scientific impact of research is only of 1.48% (Figure 3.20):

Figure 3.20. Distribution of categories in Twitter Bottom – Up (gender)

As mentioned before, the hashtags were selected from the daily trending topics in European countries related to gender issues. For this reason, the hashtags are directly related to recent events, such as cases of gender-based violence, social mobilizations and vigils organized to denounce these murders and the commemoration of the Equal Pay Day in Germany, which was on March 18th. In their tweets, citizens echo these events to call for action or to raise awareness among the general population. Most of the tweets were examples of how research contributions have overcome or could overcome social inequalities. However, as represented in Figure 3.21, some of the tweets contained examples of exclusionary messages.

Figure 3.21. Distribution of dimensions in Twitter Bottom – Up (gender)

The category where more examples of exclusionary tweets were found is the political impact category, with a 2.1%. These tweets came, mainly from the hashtag #EqualPayDay, in which there were users who distrusted statistics and science and claimed that this initiative was politically biased.

The following Figure 3.22 shows the distribution of the use of scientific evidence in all the categories. The category where more scientific evidence was found was political impact (64.63%), followed by social impact (40.60%) and scientific impact (29.79%).

Figure 3.22. Distribution of scientific evidence in Twitter Bottom – Up (gender)

The use of data, statistics and evidence was widespread across all hashtags and categories. However, the sources of the data were mostly official reports about the cases of gender violence or about the gender pay gap, and not scientific articles from journals indexed in JCR and Scopus. In the case of the scientific impact, the non-certified scientific evidence came from the hashtag #WiMINConference21, which was the hashtag used in a conference about the presence of women in medicine in Ireland. In this case, the sources used came from the interventions of speakers and experts on the field who intervened in the conference. These sources were not included as scientific evidence because the tweets did not mention any source.

Finally, the tweets in all the categories were distributed according to the presence of real or potential examples of the impact of research, as shown in Figure 3.23:

Figure 3.23. Distribution of real – potential impacts in Twitter Bottom – Up (gender)

Except in the scientific impact category, most of the tweets (93.69% in political impact and 96.44% in social impact) were examples of potential political or social impact of research but did not provide evidence of the impact achieved. This trend was not found in the scientific impact category, where more than two thirds of the tweets (68.09%) were examples of real dissemination of scientific results to both, experts on the field and society as a whole. Those tweets with potential scientific impact were

tweets that despite announcing the WiMINConference, a space where the results of research were shared, were not sharing scientific results.

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

This bottom-up analysis included the hashtags selected from the daily trending topics in all European countries. Among these hashtags, there was the #WiMINConference 2021 that was related to the Women in Medicine conference, a conference held on March 13th and organized by the network Women in Medicine in Ireland, an organisation to increase the visibility of women in medicine and to encourage girls to become doctors and medical professionals. As the data collection period coincided with the celebration of the conference, most of the posts were related to this event. In this line, the tweets included quotes from the interventions of experts and researchers in the conference, examples of slides of different sessions and the conclusions of the conference, among others. It is important to mention that, although the attendees of the conference were mainly experts, researchers and professionals in the medical field, disseminating and promoting these messages from social media, enabled to reach different sectors of society.

b. Political Impact

Another remarkable event that took place within the data collection period was the celebration of the Equal Pay Day in Germany. This initiative is devoted to denouncing the existing pay gap between men and women and is celebrated annually on the day to which women workers would work for free if they were paid the same salaries as men. Since in 2021, Equal Pay Day in Germany was celebrated on March 18th, most of the tweets within this category are related to this topic.

Some of the messages included examples of potential political impact of research and contained social denounce, awareness-raising, campaigns and recommendations:

- **Social denunciation:** these tweets were mainly promoted by policymakers, NGOs, workers unions and mobilizations of citizens. Some of them included the user's stance against the pay gap, statistics about wage differences between men and women and how, besides formal work, women deal with childcare and education at home.
- **Awareness-raising:** these tweets were promoted by policymakers, political parties and governmental institutions and aimed to spread awareness about the impact of gender pay gap and also about the factors that promote these inequalities.
- **Campaigns:** the tweets sharing campaigns and mobilizations were promoted by NGOs, foundations, citizens' platforms and individuals and claimed the application of new policies and laws to reduce and overcome gender pay gap.
- **Recommendations:** there was also a group of tweets with recommendations from the EU and policymakers to reduce wage inequalities.

Those messages that included real examples of political impact included prizes and bonifications for companies, enterprises and institutions with gender wage parity. These bonifications were initiatives promoted by governments and NGOs. There were also some examples of how the implementation of specific laws and political measures in countries such as Iceland and Sweden had reduced gender inequalities in remuneration.

C. Social Impact

In this category there were messages that included the real and potential social impact of research. In the potential impact group, there were awareness-raising messages and social denounces:

- **Awareness-raising:** These messages included topics such as the prevalence and magnitude of gender-based violence, the necessity of including men in the fight against gender discrimination, the importance of becoming an active bystander and intervening in cases of violence, the factors behind gender pay gap and the presence and stereotypes of women in medicine. These tweets were mainly shared by NGOs, citizens' platforms or individual users.
- **Social denounce:** These messages covered themes that included recent cases of gender-based violence in different countries, messages against the revictimization of rape survivors and victims of gender violence and sexual harassment, and the impact of gender pay gap in women with disabilities. Although some of these examples were initiatives driven by NGOs or platforms, most of the messages included examples of citizens mobilising against recent news related to these inequalities. In this line, three of the hashtags (#ReclaimTheStreets, #EnoughIsEnough and #IStandWithLinda) were examples of citizens-led initiatives.

Finally, real examples of social impact of research included tweets of citizens supporting and standing up for the victims of gender-based violence and sexual harassment, results of companies that succeeded in the elimination of gender pay gap and testimonies of citizens. In this last case, it was particularly remarkable one example of a conversation between a mother and her teenage son, in which they talk about consent in sexual relationships.

3.3.2 SMA - Citizens' benefits from social impact in education

The SMA in education, as well as in gender, has followed a twofold strategy, including a **top-down approach**, described in section 3.3.2.1 and a **bottom-up approach**, described in section 3.3.2.2.

3.3.2.1 Top-Down strategy - education

As above-mentioned, the top-down strategy was conducted on **(1) Twitter, (2) Facebook, (3) Instagram and (4) Reddit**. Due to the different characteristics of each social network, they were analysed separately. For each network **quantitative** and **qualitative findings** are presented. The qualitative findings section provides evidence on the **scientific impact, political impact and social impact** reflected in the analysed social media posts.

1) Twitter

The SMA in Twitter using a top-down strategy consisted of the analysis of the hashtags #PublicEducation, #School, #Students, #Learning and #Education. A total of 4525 tweets were included in the final analysis. Almost all of the tweets got at least one Retweet (98.69%), with an average of 35.20 retweets per post.

Quantitative findings

The tweets were analysed following Table 2 and were assigned a category (scientific, political or social impact), as shown in Figure 3.24.

Figure 3.24. Distribution of categories in Twitter Top – Down (education)

Figure 3.24 shows that almost two thirds (65.97%) of the tweets contained evidence of social impact, followed by tweets with evidence of scientific impact (20.46%) and finally political impact (13.56%). The hashtag including a higher percentage of scientific impact tweets was #Learning (35.97%), as included dissemination of science-related issues, such as machine learning or artificial intelligence. #PublicEducation was the hashtag where users shared a higher proportion of messages with political impact (52.27%) as the scope of the hashtag includes political campaigns, reforms and mobilizations. Regarding social impact, the higher percentage of tweets was found in the hashtag students with a 78.84%. All tweets were also assigned a dimension (exclusionary or transformative), as shown in Figure 3.25.

Figure 25. Distribution of dimensions in Twitter Top – Down (education)

All the 925 messages containing evidence of scientific impact of research and all the 613 messages of political impact provided examples of how citizens benefit from the impact of research and, therefore, were analysed as transformative. In the case of tweets of social impact, 23 messages (0.77%) were exclusionary, as they claimed to be using science to promote actions that could bring negative consequences to citizens, such as eliminating the use of face masks or focusing education only in children's wellbeing and not in learning.

Regarding the use of scientific evidence, there are differences between the different categories, as presented in Figure 3.26:

Figure 3.26. Distribution of scientific evidence in Twitter Top – Down (education)

The higher percentage of scientific evidence was found in tweets related to scientific impact, with a 59.20%, including those tweets with evidence obtained from a scientific article from JCR or Scopus and those tweets with scientific evidence obtained from other sources, such as reports or books. However, more than one third of the tweets in the social impact category included evidence from a non-indexed source, mainly reports from international organisations that users included in their messages to reinforce their arguments. It is also important to remark that, in the analysed hashtags, there were almost no messages demanding the use of scientific evidence to other users, which could be related to the very few debates among users.

There are also differences between categories in the presence of real evidence or a potential impact of research. In this case, as presented in Figure 3.27, in the category scientific impact more than 9 out of ten (93.95%) are real examples of the impact of scientific research, whereas in social impact, the presence of evidence of real social impact of research is 14.32% and in political impact a 41.1%.

Figure 3.27. Distribution of real – potential impacts in Twitter Top – Down (education)

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific impact

As mentioned before, all the messages were transformative examples of the impact of scientific research. Those messages that were related to a real scientific impact of research included the dissemination of scientific concepts to researchers and experts and also to the general public. The most common forms were scientific articles, books and conferences, but also dissemination formats targeting citizens in a more specific way, such as fun facts, reports, talks, apps or press releases. The rest of the messages related to potential scientific impact of research contained mainly recommendations of books, invitations to scientific conferences and research projects in process.

The themes covered by these messages were diverse, ranging from the use of digital technology and artificial intelligence in education to studies about the impact of COVID-19 pandemic in education.

b. Political Impact

The messages that contained a real political impact of research included the implementation of programs or services and the transference of the results of research to different contexts. In this line, there were several initiatives across all hashtags that included the application of virtual reality and artificial intelligence to fields such as, education, health, sports, marketing or energy.

However, more than half of the messages were related to a potential political impact. This group included campaigns and petitions aiming a change at the political level, proposals or recommendations to policymakers, meetings or initiatives of dialogue between governments and other stakeholders to advance in legislations, pilots or future transferences of the results of research and awareness-raising actions or social mobilizations to claim political change.

In this group of potential impact, there were campaigns and petitions related to recent news that promoted a protest response from citizens and targeted governments and policymakers. Some of the petitions or campaigns demanding academic freedom, more budget for schools and safety measures

and COVID-19 vaccines for teachers, or broke the silence against sexual harassment in educational centers, violation of democracy and human rights and educational gaps produced or increased by the pandemic. The recommendations were normally addressed to policymakers or schools and aimed to create safe schools for ethnic minorities, to implement safety measures against the spread of the virus or to share evidence-based toolkits for STEM education. Those messages containing pilots or future transference of the results included possible future applications of artificial intelligence in education, pilots of collaborative experience between schools and industry and workshops to promote the transferability of good practises to schools. Finally, there were examples of campaigns and social mobilizations of citizens, NGOs and associations that aimed to draw the attention of policymakers and international organisations. The main issues covered by these campaigns were political participation, the effects of COVID-19 in children's access to education, inclusive education, college dropout and education for refugees.

c. Social Impact

Like the other categories, this category was divided into two groups. On the one hand, those tweets including real examples of social impact of research and, on the other hand, tweets where users benefited from research to implement actions or initiatives that could bring further and potential social impact.

In the group of messages with real examples of social impact of research there were implemented actions or programs that have provided benefits to citizens, the visibilization of successful cases and stories and the use of scientific arguments in debates among citizens. First, the implemented actions and programs included how the implementation of eco-friendly practises had improved school recycling, the increase of youth literacy in poor countries because of the implemented actions, programs aiming to provide meals and milk to vulnerable children and experiences of how the sense of belonging of immigrant students increased thanks to volunteering in their communities. In this case, it is necessary to highlight the important role of NGOs, as most of the shared experiences were promoted or implemented by them. Second, the visibilization of successful cases and stories narrated positive experiences that could also inspire others. This is the case, for example, of experiences of cultural diversity in schools, how some schools managed to continue providing quality education despite the lockdowns and individual trajectories of people who overcome the difficulties to achieve their dreams and could become role models. Finally, there were tweets and threads where users discussed about specific topics, such as bullying, the presence of women in STEM or sexual harassment in the academia using statistics and scientific arguments and concepts.

The group of messages with examples of potential social impact included examples of social mobilisation and awareness-raising actions, trainings, recommendations and resources.

- **Awareness-raising actions:** included examples of initiatives implemented by NGOs, enterprises, schools or the army in order to prevent drugs consume, racism, HIV, youth violence, learning loss or sexual abuse and to make students aware of slavery, the importance of sexual consent, climate change or the right to education, among others.
- **Trainings:** there were also tweets that shared trainings for teachers, families, students or citizens in general. Some of these trainings were held by enterprises and others were initiatives emerged

from schools. The main topics covered by these trainings were technology, codification, robotics and informatics.

- **Recommendations:** another group of tweets included recommendations for teachers or parents with strategies to promote children's mental health, effective teaching, increase motivation, and reduce the spread of the virus in the classrooms.
- **Resources:** there were tweets with examples of resources that teachers and parents could use in schools or at home to promote instrumental learning (mathematics, literacy, science or technology, among others) or to address racism and other forms of inequalities in schools.

2) Facebook

The SMA in Facebook using a top-down strategy consisted of the analysis of the pages Teacher2Teacher, WeAreTeachers, Edutopia, MindShift, and Education Week. The first two pages are spaces of dialogue among teachers and educational professionals; whereas the other three are pages where educational news are shared. A total of 620 messages, including posts and comments were included in the final analysis. It is important to mention that in Facebook pages there are two types of messages: posts and comments. Posts are shared by the own page, which is administered by specific users and comments are shared by individual users who can interact among them around the issue proposed in the post.

Quantitative findings

On the one hand, the majority of the messages (94.68%) contained examples of a real or potential social impact of research, as detailed in Figure 3.28.

Figure 3.28. Distribution of categories in Facebook (education)

On the other hand, all messages in the categories scientific and social impact, as well as more than 90% of the messages of political impact corresponded to the transformative dimension, as provided examples of benefits of scientific research (Figure 3.29).

Figure 3.29. Distribution of dimensions in Facebook (education)

Regarding the use of scientific evidence in the messages, the use of certified scientific evidence was more widespread in messages within the scientific impact category, as they were examples of dissemination of scientific research. However, it is relevant to mention that in most of the discussions shared in these pages, users tended to base their arguments on press articles or blogs that mention scientific studies, although these studies were not indexed in JCR or Scopus. Figure 3.30 represents this result:

Figure 3.30. Distribution of scientific evidence in Facebook (education)

It is also important to clarify that, although the vast majority of the messages were assigned in the social impact category, very few of these messages included evidence of a real social impact or of a real improvement in the quality of education. This trend was also found in the political impact category, as presented in Figure 3.31. This was not the case of scientific impact because, as mentioned before, the 7 messages within this category shared and disseminated the findings of a specific study.

Figure 3.31. Distribution of potential-real impacts in Facebook (education)

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

Seven messages were categorised as evidence of scientific impact. All these messages were examples of dissemination of the results of research. Four of the messages were posts shared from the Facebook page with a link to a blog article about a specific topic, which included results of studies, among other sources. The aim of these posts was to share the research with teachers and other individuals and to promote a discussion around the results. The other three, were examples of how users respond to an existing post, sharing the results of a research. It is especially important to highlight one of these comments, which contained the link to a certified scientific evidence (an article from JCR or Scopus). In general, the topics of the shared studies included students' mental health, COVID-19 and project-based learning.

b. Political Impact

The posts and comments in this category included examples of transference of the results of research to other contexts (real political impact), as well as awareness-raising messages and recommendations (potential political impact). The more representative messages containing examples of transference included comments of teachers expressing that they had conducted a specific activity focused on numeracy and literacy in kindergarten, implementing action aligned with the recommendations of research of teaching letters and numbers at early ages. However, teachers did not express in those comments if the activity had achieved positive results and, therefore, could not be categorised as a social impact of research. There were also other examples that included the vaccination plans for teachers or how a school included the voices of the community in the decision-making processes about the school curriculum.

Regarding examples of potential political impact, there were awareness-raising messages aiming changes at political level. These posts and comments turned around the impacts of COVID-19 in education and some of them were focused on the increase of the educational gap and the others on the increase of poverty and vulnerability. Although most of the messages encouraged action to overcome these inequalities, a few of them claimed to be using science to discourage possible actions

that would address learning loss or to recommend not to use face masks and were included in the exclusionary dimension. Finally, there are examples of recommendations, including posts and comments with recommendations to create safe conditions in schools and to reduce the screen time in online learning.

c. Social Impact

The social impact category was the category that included more messages and contained both, messages with potential social impact and with real social impact of science. Regarding potential social impact, there were examples of resources, awareness-raising and debates about teaching practises.

- **Resources:** these messages included ideas of activities linked to instrumental learning (mathematics, reading methods, science), strategies to ensure quality hybrid teaching or to build a sense of community and resources to implement mindfulness and to prevent racism. The resources also included recommendations of books and apps for teachers and parents. Almost all the messages were posts shared from the Facebook pages and aiming to equip teachers with resources and strategies.
- **Awareness-raising:** there were messages that raised awareness about inclusive practises in schools, the importance of reading, racism, the importance of additional time engaged in high-quality learning, and also about issues related with the pandemic, such as the impact of COVID-19 and online learning or mental health.
- **Debates:** these messages did not include posts shared but Facebook pages, but comments of the users. In these comments, users, who were mostly teachers and/or parents, discussed educational methods related to reading and finger-counting. Despite the existence of scientific literature about these topics, users based their arguments on their own experiences, without providing any reference to scientific research. These debates show how citizens benefited from science without being aware of the contributions of research that are behind these methodologies.

The examples of messages containing real evidence of social impact of research were grouped in three groups: the visibilization of successful cases, the implementation of actions and the use of science in the debates:

- **Visibilization of successful cases:** these messages included testimonies of people from migrant origin or ethnic minorities that had succeeded in their educational trajectories and had become teachers, serving as role models for other students. Other experiences were shared about how online learning had positively impacted the educational trajectory of children with autism.
- **Implementation of actions:** in this group there were examples of implemented strategies that had enabled safe conditions in schools in times of COVID-19 and testimonies of how evidence-based reading methods had positively impacted children from different schools.
- **Use of science:** these messages included users making use of scientific terminology (mainly related to psychological disorders) in their discussions, users asking for reliable studies to other users

and references to studies about neuroscience or about how the socioeconomic context does not determine academic success.

3) Instagram

The SMA in Instagram using a top-down strategy consisted of the analysis of the hashtags #QualityEducation, #StopBullying, #ScienceEducation, #Learning and #Education. A total of 595 posts were included in the final analysis. Due to the characteristics of the social network, the analysis of Instagram includes not only the content of the post, but also the image.

Quantitative findings

All posts were categorised into the established categories and the findings showed that almost two thirds (62.18%) of the posts corresponded to the social impact category, followed by a 37.14% of messages in the scientific impact category. Only 4 messages were included in the political impact, as presented in Figure 3.32.

Figure 3.32. Distribution of categories in Instagram (education)

However, it is especially noticeable that more than three quarters parts of the posts within the scientific impact category came from the hashtag #ScienceEducation, where a lot of messages with dissemination of science were found. In general terms, the analysis of Instagram revealed a high presence of posts that showed how citizens benefit or could benefit from the social impact of science. Regarding the analysis of the transformative or exclusionary dimension, the results showed that only a 1.08% of the posts within the social impact category were assigned the exclusionary dimension, whereas the rest of the posts were transformative (Figure 3.33).

Figure 3.33. Distribution of dimensions in Instagram (education)

Those posts included in the exclusionary dimension were found in the hashtag #StopBullying. These posts were benefitting from scientific contributions in the fields of psychology, education or behavioural studies, among others, to raise awareness of the negative consequences of bullying but offer no alternatives other than the use of violence or suicide. A relevant consideration regarding these exclusionary messages is that none of them included any reference to scientific evidence. The use of scientific evidence from journals indexed in JCR or Scopus in Instagram is not widespread and when users include some reference in their posts, they are mainly statistics included in the image or the citation of official reports to reinforce the argument of the post. Some examples in this line are the percentage of students suffering bullying, the increase of Asian hate crimes in the US or the effects of bullying in children. Figure 3.34 represents the use of scientific evidence in the analysed hashtags:

Figure 3.34. Distribution of scientific evidence in Instagram (education)

Figure 3.34 shows how most of the posts do not include any scientific evidence. The proportion in the political impact is a little bit higher than in the others because it only included 4 posts. The use of certified scientific evidence in Instagram was limited to the scientific impact category, where users shared with the community recent advances and discoveries. In the social impact category, citizens used statistics and data to denounce situations of bullying and violence, however, they did not detail the source where the data came from. As people in Instagram do not join discussions with other users,

it is not common to find examples of people demanding scientific evidence to other users. Finally, it is important to look at the differences in the real and potential impact between categories, which are presented in Figure 3.35:

Figure 3.35. Distribution of potential-real impacts in Instagram (education)

In line with the analysis of other social networks, the higher presence of real impact of research was found in scientific impact, because this category included the dissemination of scientific research and concepts to the general public. In the social impact category, this trend was not found, and citizens used scientific research to promote initiatives that could bring improvements in society, but no evidence of the impacts achieved was provided.

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

All the posts within the scientific impact category have one characteristic in common: they use social media to disseminate scientific advances and reach the general public. As mentioned in section 2, the period for the extraction of data collection was March 4th - March 17th. Therefore, it included March 14th, which is Science Education Day in several countries, including the USA and India. This is one of the underlying reasons why most of the posts within this category contained the hashtag #ScienceEducation.

Within this category, there were posts that directly disseminated the results of recent scientific research. These posts were promoted by research organisations and shared the latest experiments and advances of research teams using technical language. Another group of posts aimed to share specific information about different areas of science in an appealing and humorous format for society. An example of this kind of posts are the “Molecule of the day”, scientific glossaries, “Fun facts” or “Science facts” and games and ideas about how to explain complex scientific concepts to children. Most of these posts were promoted by NGOs, enterprises, and citizens’ organisations. The third identified group was related to recent news and discoveries and included posts from official accounts. In this group, the most common topics were related to Mars NASA missions and New Zealand

earthquakes. Finally, there were messages that besides sharing scientific concepts, aimed to bring science closer to citizens. Some of these posts raised awareness about specific topics and others promoted scientific activities held by museums. In this line, the main topics were health issues such as Parkinson, diabetes or viruses and the main promoting users were citizens' organisations, NGOs and museums.

b. Political Impact

Only 4 posts were included within this category, and they aimed to raise awareness and promote political change at different levels. The topics of these posts were energy consumption, policies for the promotion of higher education among refugee students and gender violence. All the posts were citizen-lead initiatives.

c. Social Impact

In this category, there were different types of posts in the potential and real impact groups. On the one hand, in the potential groups, most tweets aimed to raise awareness about a specific issue, to share recommendations or resources and methodologies.

- **Awareness-raising:** The tweets that raised awareness were found in all the hashtags, although there were differences on the topics of the messages depending on the hashtag. In this direction, the hashtag #StopBullying included topics that denounced Asia hate and school bullying, explained the negative consequences of bullying, and encouraged to break the silence and to take action against bullying and violence. The hashtag #QualityEducation mostly contained posts related with the SDG and the other hashtags included diverse topics, such as inclusive access to education, the importance of early childhood education and care or the impacts of COVID-19 on education. These tweets were mostly promoted by NGOs, testimonies of individual citizens, schools and enterprises.
- **Recommendations:** There were also posts with recommendations of books or actions to implement in schools. These recommendations were promoted by individual citizens and included topics such as bullying, health issues, basic skills or recycling, among others.
- **Resources or methodologies:** These posts included ideas or proposals of literacy, numeracy and science activities for schools and families and were mainly promoted by schools and enterprises. In some cases, the posts were promoted by schools and aimed to engage other schools in implementing the resources or methodologies.

On the other hand, the posts with real evidence of social impact included the visibilization of successful cases and implemented actions. The visibilization of successful cases narrated stories of individuals who overcame the difficulties and successfully accessed or completed their educational trajectory. This kind of post was promoted by NGOs that work for the promotion of quality education for all children. The posts with implemented actions included the results of science projects at higher education level, experiences of schools that apply science or scientific concepts in their activities and experiences that promote student retention. Most posts were promoted by schools and NGOs.

4) Reddit

The SMA in Reddit included five communities: r/Teachers, r/Teaching, r/ApplyingToCollege, r/Science and r/Education. Three of these communities are mostly constituted by teachers or educational professionals that share debates related to their professional experience. One of the other communities is formed by students and the other includes citizens from all sectors and countries. It is important to mention that in reddit communities there are two types of messages: posts and comments. Nevertheless, and unlike social networks such as Facebook, both types of messages are shared by individual users who can propose specific topics for the debate, ask for advice or share news with other members of the community. A total of 966 messages were analysed in this social network.

Quantitative findings

First, all messages were classified into the established categories, as presented in Figure 3.36. Almost 9 out of 10 of the messages (89.44%) contained examples of how citizens benefit from the social impact of research. The scientific impact and the political impact category were found in 6.94% and 3.62% of the cases.

Figure 3.36. Distribution of categories in Reddit (education)

It is noticeable that 59 of the 67 messages in the scientific impact category came from the subreddit r/science, pointing out that the dissemination of scientific research was not among the main objectives and priorities of Reddit users in the other four communities. The analysis of the messages according to the established dimensions showed that the messages belonging to the transformative dimension was more frequently found across the three categories, as shown in Figure 3.37:

Figure 3.37. Distribution of dimensions in Reddit (education)

Those messages that were classified as exclusionary included scientific data in their comments but based their arguments on their personal opinions or experiences and not the provided data. It is important to mention that Reddit communities give users the opportunity to vote and downvote other users' comments. In this line, Table 3.14 shows the differences in the average punctuations obtained in each community when comparing the exclusionary and transformative dimensions:

Table 3.14. Differences in the average punctuation across dimension

	Average Transformative Dimension	Average Exclusionary Dimension
r/science	48.16	-3.71
r/education	59.83	-
r/Teachers	9.98	3.25
r/Teaching	12.70	4
r/ApplyigToCollege	4.75	-1

Regarding the use of scientific evidence, a significant proportion of Reddit users shared some scientific sources in their discussions (61.19% in the scientific impact category and 30.56% in the social impact category). The Figure 3.38 shows the distribution of scientific sources across categories:

Figure 3.38. Distribution of scientific evidence in Reddit (education)

As described in Figure 3.38, it was important the proportion of users that demanded scientific evidence or discussed the reliability of the provided studies (8.96% in the scientific impact and 7.99% in the social impact). In this line there were cases in which users replied providing non-scientific sources and, in these cases, the general response of the community was negative, and they discredited the sources. In this case, it is important to highlight an interesting result found in two of the analysed communities: *r/science* and *r/teachers*, where users voted or downvoted the comments differently depending on the use of sources to provide arguments. Table 3.15 shows the differences found in this regard:

Table 3.15. Differences in the average punctuation depending on the use of scientific sources.

	Average in <i>r/science</i>	Average in <i>r/teachers</i>
No scientific evidence	23.95	9.10
Certified scientific evidence	238.55	3
Supposed scientific evidence	25.04	20.08
Demanded scientific evidence	19.89	7.5

In both cases, it is important that if users provided scientific sources to base their arguments, the community valued the contributions positively. In addition, in *r/science*, the punctuation obtained was significantly higher if users provided scientific evidence from a journal indexed in Scopus or JCR.

Finally, Figure 3.39 shows the presence of real and potential examples of the impact of research in each category. In this line, it is important to remark the proportion of real social impact examples (70.63%).

Figure 3.39. Distribution of real – potential impacts in Reddit (education)

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

Those messages containing evidence of scientific impact of research were mainly the dissemination of scientific studies. In some cases, these studies were shared as a post to promote debates around a specific issue and in other cases, were links to scientific articles provided in the comments. The main topics of the shared studies were genetics, behavioural sciences, cannabis consumption in pregnancy, the effects of cannabis cultivation in the environment, and the relationship between toddlers and technology.

b. Political Impact

In this category there were examples of potential political impact, which aimed to denounce or raise awareness about specific topics in schools. In this line, there were, for example, criticisms of a bonification program in schools that did not work properly and about the presence of racism attitudes and behaviours in educational centres.

There were also examples of the transference of scientific research to the school context. This transference included initiatives of mentorship in school, play-based learning and the promotion of dialogical decision-making spaces for teachers. However, users did not provide evidence of how the implementation of these evidence-based initiatives had improved education and learning and, for this reason, these initiatives were analysed as examples of transference and not of real improvement.

c. Social Impact

Some examples of social impact of research showed a potential social impact that could benefit citizens and were mainly awareness-raising messages, messages asking for advice or help and resources:

- **Awareness-raising:** there were posts and comments provided by users that aimed to make other users aware of topics such as HIV, consent in affective and sexual relationships, or sexual harassment in different contexts.
- **Advice and help:** As mentioned before, due to the characteristics of Reddit, all messages shared in the communities were shared by individual users. In this line, it was common to find posts where a user exposed a situation and ask for help or advice to other users. In most cases, they were teachers asking for advice to other teachers and professionals. Some of these users asked for advice specifying that they need evidence-based advice, and community members answered providing advice based on scientific arguments and contributions. The main topics addressed in these situations were students with disruptive behaviours, and the diagnosis of specific disorders.
- **Resources:** some of the messages included users providing examples of resources to enhance reading, promote gamification or ensure a quality online education.

Regarding the real examples of social impact of research, there were examples of the use of scientific concepts and data and of the use of scientific arguments to the debate:

- **Use of scientific concepts and data:** Reddit users usually used scientific terminology in their debates and discussions. In this line, there were important differences between the analysed communities. Whereas in four of the studies communities the terminology was mostly related to educational psychology and child development, in the fifth community the topics were diverse, ranging from drug consumption and pregnancy to environmental sciences or genetics.
- **Use of scientific arguments:** In the analysed communities it was common to find comments with debates among users about the topic of the post. In most of these debates, users provided scientific arguments and evidence to refute other comments, to strengthen their perspective and to advance in the discussion. It is important to mention the widespread use of science in these debates. Although the shared perspectives were contradictory and controversial and some of them defended for example drug consumption during pregnancy or breastfeeding, users were basing their claims on scientific studies. These debates were usually about issues that can be controversial, such as drug consumption in pregnancy, the legalisation of drugs, or racism. It is important to mention that in most cases, users shared scientific evidence in order to make other users aware of the scientific data, and to allow them to build an opinion based on scientific contributions.

3.4.2.2 Bottom-up

1) Twitter

The SMA in Twitter using a bottom-up strategy consisted of the analysis of the hashtags #books, #Wikipedia, #FutureOfEurope, #DigitalDecade and #Schools. A total of 3,151 tweets were included in the final analysis. Approximately three-quarter parts of the messages (75.69%) were retweeted at least once, with an average number of 174.11 retweets per post.

Quantitative findings

All the retrieved tweets were categorised in the established categories, as presented in Figure 3.40:

Figure 3.40. Distribution of categories in Twitter – Bottom-Up (education)

More than half of the tweets (54.84%) were assigned the category of social impact of research, followed by the scientific impact (33.70%) and the political impact (11.46%). However, there were important differences among the analysed hashtags. For example, most of the scientific impact tweets came from the hashtags #books, which included tweets sharing scientific books, and #wikipedia, which included tweets that aimed to disseminate knowledge contained in this encyclopaedia. In contrast, the hashtags #DigitalDecade and #FutureOfEurope contained mainly tweets classified as political impact, as these hashtags were related to political events at European level. In addition, all tweets were classified into two dimensions: exclusionary and transformative, as detailed below (Figure 3.41)

Figure 3.41. Distribution of dimensions in Twitter – Bottom-Up (education)

In total, less than a 1% of the messages were included in the exclusionary dimension (1.11% in the political impact and 0,80% in the social impact category). These tweets classified as exclusionary included people sharing fake news and people disapproving Wikipedia as an accurate and reliable encyclopaedia. Regarding the presence of scientific evidence, it is important to mention that an important part of the users mentioned scientific evidence in their tweets, although the cited sources

were not always indexed in JCR or Scopus. The case of #wikipedia was very meaningful, as it allowed citizens to observe how citizens disseminated scientific concepts and engaged in discussions about scientific concepts, citing Wikipedia articles that contained certified scientific evidence. Figure 3.42 represents the distribution of scientific evidence among categories:

Figure 3.42. Distribution of scientific evidence in Twitter – Bottom-Up (education)

As above-mentioned, the use of scientific evidence (including both certified and non-certified sources) was of 87,95% in scientific impact, 40,72% in political impact and 59,20% in social impact. The most common sources for scientific evidence that are not indexed in JCR or Scopus are Wikipedia articles with references to other scientific journals, official and international reports and scientific books. This is the case of the hashtag #books, which mainly included recommendations to books about science or scientific advances, but which were not considered certified scientific evidence as they are not peer-reviewed scientific journals indexed in Scopus or JCR.

In line with previous findings, there was an important difference in the presence of real and potential impact between the three analysed categories. Those messages within the scientific impact category disseminate scientific contributions and, for this reason, correspond to a real scientific impact. In the other two categories, the presence of evidence of real political or social impact is approximately a 30%, as shown in Figure 3.43:

Figure 3.43. Distribution of real-potential impacts in Twitter – Bottom-Up (education)

Qualitative findings

This section describes the main qualitative results found within categories, including the main topics, actions described and target groups.

a. Scientific Impact

The category of scientific impact included three types of tweets. First, there were tweets that shared science books, mainly about computation, coding, informatics, and technology. These tweets were promoted by both, individual users and enterprises. Second, there were tweets that disseminated information about scientific discoveries, historical facts and research contributions through Wikipedia articles and were promoted by individual users. Third, there were tweets that shared the results of the calculations of the risk of the spread of COVID-19 in different contexts, the infection rates or studies about the impact of COVID in education and school dropout.

b. Political Impact

The messages in this category were divided in two groups, those tweets that could bring potential political impact and those that correspond to real evidence of political impact. In the group of potential political impact there were messages with information about the communication of the European Commission regarding the digital transformation of Europe and the Conference on the Future of Europe. This information was mainly shared by official accounts or by policymakers and also included quotes and fragments of the interventions of different policymakers in these events. Finally, there were examples of different tweets with citizens' initiatives that wanted to expose the lack of inversion in schools, the inequalities between different types of public educational centres or the negative impact of a law on trans kids, among others.

The messages with real evidence of political impact, included the actions within the Digital Decade program and within the Conference on the Future of Europe, both programs promoted by the European Commission. These tweets were mainly shared by official and institutional accounts. Another group of tweets aimed to provide recommendations to educational centres about distance learning, inclusive language and safety measures against the virus. Finally, there were messages with news and information about a specific law or policy, mainly press articles.

c. Social Impact

In the social impact category tweets were also classified in two groups: those tweets that included real evidence of social impact and those that could bring to a potential social impact. In this second group there were awareness-raising tweets, resources, social denunciations and visibilization of successful trajectories.

- **Awareness-raising:** most of these tweets included awareness-raising messages about the impact of COVID-19 in learning, the digital gap and the importance of connectivity. Some of these messages were addressed to policymakers and enterprises or related to the European program.
- **Resources:** these messages included the recommendation of books about scientific contributions from different disciplines and fields and also about how to look for and enrol in educational

centres, universities or colleges. The vast majority of these tweets were shared and promoted by individual citizens.

- **Social denunciations:** the messages containing social denunciations were shared by different users, including individual citizens, NGOs and press. All denunciations were related to educational centres and were mainly found in the hashtag #schools. The main topics of these denunciations were the demolition of schools, mass abductions of students in Nigeria schools and racism or messages related to the Black Lives Matter movement.
- **Visibilization of successful trajectories:** These messages were mainly found in Wikipedia and use articles in this encyclopaedia to share successful trajectories of different people in order to provide successful role models to society. These tweets included the biographies of scientists, writers and social activists, among others.

Regarding the tweets in which users shared evidence of real social impact, there were actions, visibilization of successful cases, use of scientific contributions to the debate and value of Wikipedia:

- **Actions:** Some tweets shared examples of specific actions that had enabled improvements in citizens' lives. These tweets were shared by individual users and the two more frequent topics were COVID-19 vaccinations to teachers and the impact of the hand signal of help for victims of gender-based violence-
- **Visibilizations of successful cases:** these tweets were mainly promoted by NGOs and citizens and explained how some people had succeeded in their educational trajectory despite the difficulties. Two examples were especially remarkable for the amount of retweets that were achieved. The first one narrated the story of a twelve-year-old girl who started teaching their neighbours when the schools closed due to the pandemic and the second one shared the case of the first Indian girl who passed the exams to enrol in a prestigious college.
- **Use of scientific contributions to the debate:** these tweets were all shared by individual users and were replies to existing debates about all types of topics. Unlike in Facebook or Reddit and due to the characteristics of Twitter, these messages did not contain all the debate shared among users, but the reply someone provided to another tweet. These tweets contained the tags to the other users who had participated in the debate, the argument or the contribution to the debate and the source, which was mostly a link to a Wikipedia article with scientific evidence.
- **Value of Wikipedia:** there were also discussions where users exchanged their views about the Wikipedia encyclopaedia, and its value, accuracy and reliability. In these debates, there were users defending both sides. However, it is important to remark that those users that claimed that Wikipedia was not a trustworthy source did not provide any argument and they attacked the encyclopaedia and all the people who use Wikipedia. On the other side, users who defend Wikipedia mentioned the presence of certified scientific evidence at the end of each article, the collaboration of citizens from different contexts in the elaboration of the articles and the possibility to modify the content as soon as science published new discoveries. In these debates, the tweets arguing against Wikipedia were classified as exclusionary, whereas the tweets basing their claims in arguments were considered transformative.

3.3.3 Social Media Communicative Observation

The following are the results obtained from the Social Media Communication Observation on gender and education issues. The comments analysed in this SMCO show that users participating in the groups/pages or platforms have benefited from knowing the scientific evidence, especially the results on education and gender.

The virtual participation of the participants has increased their scientific knowledge. At the same time, it has allowed them to reflect, argue, motivate them to learn more and to engage in virtual dialogue with other users about what they have found in scientific articles, their experiences, or their point of view.

Through their comments, we observe that users indicate that they have benefited from the scientific evidence, not only by increasing their knowledge but also because it has allowed them to question their practises and apply the scientific evidence to their environment.

Comments in relation to policy impacts have appeared less frequently and refer to how policies benefit from scientific advances.

In relation to comments on the benefits of scientific impact (i.e., scientific research that has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact), they have had more presence in social media. Users have pointed out how scientific theories and evidence have had an impact on their environment, which favours scientific progress in both education and gender.

Table 3.16. Results of the TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research.

<u>TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research</u>		
<i><u>Benefits from social impact (i.e., direct benefits for social actors)</u></i>	<i><u>Benefits from political impact (i.e., evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</u></i>	<i><u>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e., scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</u></i>

	<p><u>E1.5: However, even though it is known that participation is fundamental, given that it promotes the development of different skills in children, as mentioned by Kuutti et al. (2021).</u></p>	<p><u>E1.11: The easiest option for the education system has been to create special schools, thus grouping children with disabilities together. In this way they create a feeling of isolation, thus creating more differences between them. Looking at the statistics and the well-being of children with disabilities, such separations are not beneficial. However, (according to Colmenero, MJ., Pegalajar, MC. and Pantoja, A.) 428 teachers working in special schools claim that by using inclusive practises the results are more positive.</u></p>	<p><u>E2.14: In my school, which is a learning community, we have seen how through the creation of egalitarian dialogic spaces (based on Freire's theory) inequalities and power relations between the various agents of the educational community are reduced. For example, this is realised through joint working committees made up of diverse people from the community, where the arguments of validity and not the position held, is what guides the relationships, putting the focus on improving the lives of the students.</u></p>
	<p><u>E1.7: In relation to the comment made above, we believe that it is important to promote inclusive education for all students, given that this will allow them to develop the necessary tools for optimal performance in the educational sphere. This, in turn, will allow for development in social areas, promoting occupational participation. Inclusive education allows students to have equal opportunities in the education system.</u></p>		<p><u>E4.12: A successful educational action that includes the so-called "bystander intervention" is the Zero Violence Brave Club. This action is applied in more and more schools worldwide with significant improvements to stop bullying and achieve children's well-being.</u></p>
	<p><u>E2.16: I believe that by combining the teacher's explanatory part with a part in which the student participates in dialogue, successful learning and less school failure are more likely to be achieved</u></p>		<p><u>E1.1: Another factor that favours academic success is the interactive groups in special education schools, which have been qualified by the European Union as ESAs (Successful Educational Actions).</u></p>

	<p><u>E1.18: From the scientific evidence I am involved in researching, but also from my own experience, I can affirm that Bourdieu's reproductionist model is surpassed every day from different corners of the world, from different neighbourhoods, from different families, like mine, and from so many educational communities that work hard to offer a quality education, a transformative education like the one my parents wished for me.</u></p>		<p><u>E2.16: Oliver, E. and Gatt, S. conducted a study on the subject, analysing the learning outcomes of interactive groups of heterogeneous learners who were guided by adults who accompanied them in their learning.</u></p>
	<p><u>E5.1: Indeed, teacher expectations influence academic success, and this also includes students belonging to ethnic groups - the higher the expectations, the higher the achievement, and the lower the expectations, the lower the achievement. Flanagan, Cormier and Bulut (2020) show this in their research using 140 teacher surveys, even when teachers do not report different behaviour, they report lower expectations for indigenous students.</u></p>		<p><u>E2.12: Freire was ahead of the social sciences as a whole when he included the dialogic perspective, among other writings, in his Pedagogy of the Oppressed (Freire, 2018). Many schools and projects have improved results with dialogic perspectives that have had Freire as one of their references.</u></p>
	<p><u>E3.21: The other day I was lucky enough to be with Sara at the same Tertulia and the evidence was overwhelming: no to ideas based on discrimination against people.</u></p>		<p><u>E2.13: In my school we implement Successful Educational Actions such as Interactive Groups and Tertulias Dialógicas which are dialogical learning spaces based on principles such as equal dialogue and solidarity. Thanks to principles such as these, safe and collaborative spaces are created in which all children have the opportunity to learn while developing the best values and feelings. We see how they not only behave in this way during the activity but define and characterise all their interactions.</u></p>

	<p><u>E4.23: Previous researchers have shown that many school-based anti-bullying programmes are effective. A previous meta-analysis (Gaffney, Ttofi & Farrington, 2019) found that intervention programmes are effective in reducing bullying perpetration by approximately 19-20% and bullying victimisation by approximately 15-16%. Gaffney, H.,Ttofi, M.M.& Farrington,D.P.(2021).What works in anti-bullying programs?Analysis of effective intervention components. Journal of school Psychology, 85, 37-56.</u></p>	<p><u>G4.58: "Childhood exposure to violence and likelihood of adult perpetration of violence, particularly for boys"; please, if you have found this kind of evidence in some of the article you sent in your message, I would kindly like to ask you to point out which is this evidence and in which articles can be found. I have found correlations, but not causal relationships. I have also found statements about causal relations, but without support of scientific evidence. I was a victim of gender violence and I could transform myself into a survivor thanks to the help of men and women, some of whom had been exposed to violence when they were children. Children with exposure to violence are victims; projecting into them the suspicion that they will become perpetrators is revictimization. Besides, this projection also creates difficulties for the solidarity we need from them to transform ourselves from victims to survivors.</u></p>
	<p><u>E3.15: Today, after participating in a Pedagogical Dialogue on the article by López de Aguilera and Soler-Gallart (2021) "Ausubel's Significant Learning and Educational Segregation", I have decided to share my own transformative experience. I studied in EGB and at that time no practices of content reduction were applied, nor were any children removed from the classroom for social reasons, such as coming from an uneducated family or from a dysfunctional family.</u></p>	<p><u>G5.158: Bystander Intervention is one of the evidence based interventions that has proven to reduce and prevent violence in all its forms at educational institutions from schools to universities. Its approach focuses on the empowerment of the witnesses to speak up and report the possible violence and harassment situations as an effective action to protect the victims.</u></p> <p><u>Now, evidence goes beyond demonstrating the efficacy of the program to prove that Bystander Intervention does not only have immediate effects in the short term but also in the long run.</u></p>

	<p><u>E4.22: The role of bystanders against bullying. All members of the group are in agreement on this issue, as we believe that bystanders are an indispensable source to end bullying and all that goes with it.</u></p>	<p><u>G1.152: I usually listen to different public debates that romantic relationships are the root of gender violence. But when I checked the scientific evidence, there is clear evidence that depends on the people that you choose to be involved, if they are violent the relationship will be violent independently if the relationship is a sporadic or long term relationship. And the people that you consider attractive depend on the type of socialization process experienced as it explained in the following article: Gender Violence Among Teenagers: Socialization and Prevention published in the most important international scientific journal on Violence Against Women.</u></p>
	<p><u>G1.153: In my personal experience, romantic love has in no way been a root of gender violence. I have a very romantic relationship with my girlfriend and after several years together she has never felt involved in a violent relationship according to her.</u></p> <p><u>Now, according to the evidence that I know, the root of gender violence are the social interactions that make us desire and choose violent people. To back this assertion I share a peer reviewed paper below</u></p>	<p><u>E1.5: As mentioned in the discussion, peer support and communication are factors that foster social inclusion and the reduction of educational inequalities, thus favouring academic success. In view of this, it is important to emphasise social participation as a relevant occupation in the educational context.</u></p>
	<p><u>G1.154: Romantic relationships are not the root cause of gender-based violence, but they can be decisive in helping to prevent future violent relationships. In my personal experience I had a long and romantic relationship with my first girlfriend, many years later she told me that due to that relationship we had, she has been able to clearly distinguish violent attitudes in boys who have claimed to have a relationship with her</u></p>	

	<p><u>G2.15: There is evidence of the SOSH that exists in universities and the permissive dynamics installed in them towards this violence that can even make the victims feel guilty for thinking that they are the ones who have caused this situation. These university contexts where this type of violence is permitted make the victims feel isolated by their peers which leaves them even more unprotected. I totally agree that it is urgent to defend those who support the ending of the sexual violence that still persists in universities.</u></p>		
	<p><u>G5.15: I work in a school and on a daily basis, I can see that through the implementation of the dialogical model of conflict prevention the intervention of witnesses has increased both to stop direct aggression and to tell or look for help when they find out or see something. Children are safe to intervene and no longer look the other way or encourage the aggressor because they know that protecting and acting is courageous and they will not be alone. Coexistence has improved, reducing the intensity of the violence and managing to stop it from the first moments.</u></p>		

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusionary Dimension

3.5 SMA Conclusions - Citizens' benefits from social impact

Finally, this section presents a summary of the main findings regarding the SMA.

Main Findings between social networks

- Facebook and Reddit were the social networks where users could interact more with other users. For this reason, it was more common to find discussions and debates between users or users asking for help and advice.
- Whereas in Facebook, the administrators of the page shared the posts (e.g. press articles and blog entries), in Reddit all users are invited to post and propose a topic for the debate.
- In Twitter and Instagram there were not examples of community discussions. However, in Twitter, there were interactions between users, mainly through comments replying to previous messages.

Main Findings between strategies

- Although some differences were found between the Top-Down and Bottom-Up strategy, the most significant differences were found across different social networks.
- The selection of hashtags following a twofold strategy (top-down and bottom-up) brought different results.
- On the one hand, hashtags obtained from the bottom-up strategy were related to specific recent events and news and exemplified the response of citizens and society to these events.
- On the other hand, hashtags obtained from the top-down strategy were related to more general topics and included, not only the voices of citizens but also NGOs, governments, policymakers, companies, experts and associations, among others.

Main Findings between categories

- A common finding in all social networks was that most of the messages in the scientific impact category, contained real examples of the impact of research.
- This trend was not usually found in the political and social impact, where in most cases there is no evidence of the real impact of research. In these cases, it was more common to find examples that could bring to a potential impact of research.
- The examples of real social impact of research were mostly related to how citizens were able to incorporate the advances provided by scientific research in their lives and to use this knowledge in discussions.
- There were also examples of real impact of research that consisted of actions promoted by NGOs and were explicitly linked to the achievement of SDGs.

*Main Findings between **dimensions***

- In all social networks, citizens tend to share transformative examples of how citizens' benefit from research. The proportion of exclusionary messages ranged from 0 -12.84% .
- Specific results were found in Reddit, where users tended to downvote more exclusionary comments, and Instagram, where exclusionary posts earned less likes than transformative posts.
- The social network where more exclusionary messages were found is Reddit, with 12.84% of the posts in social impact (gender) and 11.43% of the posts in political impact (education).

*Main Findings in the **use of scientific evidence***

- In general, the use of certified scientific evidence was not frequent in the analysed messages.
- Twitter was the social network where more results obtained from official reports from NGOs or international governmental organisations are included in the messages.
- In Instagram, citizens' use of scientific evidence was mainly through the provision of data or statistics about the cases of bullying or gender-based violence. Usually, the sources where the data came from were not provided.
- In those social networks where users engaged in discussions among them (Facebook and Reddit), it was more common to find users asking for scientific evidence.
- In Reddit, users tended to vote the comments differently depending on the source provided. Therefore, comments with no evidence obtained the lowest punctuations, and comments with evidence from Scopus or JCR the highest. Although if the source provided was not from JCR or Scopus it was punctuated higher than no sources.

Main findings of the Communicative Observation of Social Media

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research

- The virtual participation of the participants has increased their scientific knowledge
- The virtual participation has allowed them to reflect, argue, motivate them to learn more and to engage in virtual dialogue with other users
- Users have benefited from the scientific evidence, not only by increasing their knowledge but also because it has allowed them to question their practises and apply the scientific evidence to their environment.
- Users have pointed out how scientific theories and evidence have had an impact on their environment, which favours scientific progress in both education and gender.

4. FOCUS GROUPS

4.1 Overview

All partners have worked keeping in mind that a Focus Group (FG) “is a group of individuals selected and assembled by researchers to discuss and comment on, from personal experience, the topic that is the subject of the research” (Powell & Single, 1996, p. 499)⁵.

Focus groups in gender include the selection of different profiles of participants: Women (including vulnerable women) from a women’s group; Members of an LGBTQI group; Women (including Young women) from a women’s group. Focus groups in education include the selection of different profiles of participants: Parents; Teachers; Students.

The section is divided into three parts: **The first one**, methodology of the focus, which explains the main characteristics of the implementation and analysis of FG; **the second section**, which focuses on the results of the FG on gender and education; and the final section, where we present the conclusions obtained on the “Topic A) How citizens’ **benefit** from scientific research” from the research.

4.2. Methodology: Focus Group

The focus groups conducted by the UOXF, ISCSP-ULISBOA, UNIMIB, UB, UH, and RUG followed the guidelines established in the Focus Group protocol of the projects, as well as the individual and collective protection measures based in the country due to the COVID-19 pandemic. 4.1.1. Implementation of the Focus groups

Table 4.1. Distributed of the focus groups among partners of the Consortium:

Gender			Education		
Profile of participants	Partner	C/E	Profile of participants	Partner	C/E
Women (including vulnerable women) from women’s group	UOXF	C/E	Parents	UB	C/E
Member of LGBTQI group	ISCSP-ULisboa	C/E	Teacher	UH	C/E
Women (including Young women) from a women’s group	UNIMIB	C/E	Students	RUG	C/E

⁵ Powell, R. A., & Single, H. M. (1996). Focus groups. International journal for quality in health care, 8(5), 499-504.

All participants have received written and oral information about the project and have signed a consent document, translated into the national language, to participate in the project. The guidelines are set out in terms of format, language and time in Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participants.

The methodological procedure used for each of the population groups studied is detailed below:

4.2.1.1. Gender

- **Women (including vulnerable women) from women’s group**

In line with the objective of the ALLINTERACT project to widen and diversify citizens’ engagement in science, participants were recruited via the Public and Community Involvement, Engagement and Participation leads at NIHR Oxford Biomedical Research Centre and the NIHR Applied Research Collaboration for Oxford and the Thames Valley with a specific focus on including participants from diverse ethnic groups. One participant required English language translation, which was provided by their family member. Several participants identified themselves as neurodiverse.

Altogether, 33 people expressed interest in participating in FGs. Based on the availability of the majority of the participants, 18 people were invited to participate in two FGs, one participant declined an invitation, and one participant did not attend. As a result, 16 people participated in two FGs.

During recruitment, potential participants were asked if they would be potentially interested in participating 1) in an intervention aimed at raising citizens awareness in order to promote and diversify citizens engagement in science, and 2) in a followed up focus group. Only those who indicated their potential interest in participating in the intervention were allocated to the Experimental Group. Those who did not indicate their potential interest in participating in the intervention were allocated to the Control group.

In line with the Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participants, all potential participants signed a consent form to participate in the FGs and prior to that had an opportunity to ask researchers questions regarding their potential participation.

The socio-demographic characteristics of the participants and their pseudonyms are detailed in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2. Socio-demographic characteristics and pseudonyms of participants, UOXF.

Focus Group number and type	Pseudonym	Age	Race/ethnicity
FG1 (Experimental)	P1	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)

FG1 (Experimental)	P2	51-60	Mixed (White and Black Caribbean, White and Black African, White and Asian, any other Mixed background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P3	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P4	20-30	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P5	51-60	Black or Black British (Caribbean, African, or any other Black background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P6	20-30	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P7	51-60	Other
FG1 (Experimental)	P8	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P9	70+	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P10	20-30	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)
FG 2 (Control)	P11	70+	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)
FG 2 (Control)	P12	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P13	70+	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P14	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)

FG 2 (Control)	P15	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P16	20-30	Black or Black British (Caribbean, African, or any other Black background)

- **Member of LGBTQI group**

The Gender Team at University of Lisbon was in charge of conducting two FG sessions, one for an Experimental Group and one for a Control Group. Regarding the Experimental Group, 7 people voluntarily participated in the session, while the Control Group was composed by 8 people.

WP2 followed the recommendation provided by Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participant, based on high standard criteria: a free and voluntary participation and avoidance of any kind of coercion which may have a negative impact on their involvement during the FG. Also, researchers from the WP2 informed the participants that they will not receive any type of reward for their time and presence during the session, as well as the confidentiality on the information analysis and dissemination of results.

Tables 4.3 and 4.4 include the information from participants of the two FG conducted at this stage. This process has followed the guidelines set out in the Deliverable D4.8. Anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.

Table 4.3. Pseudonymous participant in Focus Group – Experimental Group conducted by ISCSP-ULisboa.

Focus Group	Pseudonym	Role
FG1 – EG	P1	Participant
FG1 – EG	P2	Participant
FG1 – EG	P3	Participant
FG1 – EG	P4	Participant
FG1 – EG	P5	Participant
FG1 – EG	P6	Participant
FG1 – EG	P7	Participant
FG1 – EG	F1	Facilitator
FG1 – EG	F2	Facilitator

Table 4.4. Pseudonymous participant in Focus Group – Control Group conducted by ISCP-ULisboa.

Focus Group	Pseudonym	Role
FG1 – CG	P1	Participant
FG1 – CG	P2	Participant
FG1 – CG	P3	Participant
FG1 – CG	P4	Participant
FG1 – CG	P5	Participant
FG1 – CG	P6	Participant
FG1 – CG	P7	Participant
FG1 – CG	P8	Participant
FG1 – CG	F1	Facilitator
FG1 – CG	F2	Facilitator

Topics addressed in both sessions were taken from the list included in Allinteract Protocol, according to the objectives in which ISCP-ULisboa has been working throughout the project: a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research.

Both facilitators welcomed participants and explained the stage of the project in which FG are being conducted. Facilitator 1 (F1) had the role of carrying the conversation along the session and invited participants to express their opinions regarding the topics. F1 encouraged an egalitarian intervention from all participants and promoted an open dialogue.

According to the Focus Group Protocol, FG sessions were conducted in the country's official language (Portuguese), in order to assure comprehension and interaction among participants. However, according to the instructions provided by the Central Team, opinions from participants included in this report were translated into English. The records of the FG, as well as the full transcripts of both sessions, have been stored by the CIEG-ISCP, who collected the data in the dispositive approved by our ethical board.

- **Women (including Young women) from a women's group**

The UNIMIB team had to carry out two focus groups involving "women/including young women" that are part of a national association dealing with gender/feminist issues.

After a careful analysis of the Italian associative landscape, the UNIMIB team selected "Casa delle donne", because of its long history of feminist activism (more than 30 years), in particular on gender violence. It is a "social promotional association that looks without discrimination at the aspirations and needs of women of all ages and sexual orientations, who (...) live in our city (Milan). The association

is linked to other women’s associations (...) that share our goals to fight gender-based violence, promote talents and enhance women's knowledge”⁶.

UNIMIB team selected this association for two main reasons: 1) this association involves women not only of various ages, but also with different characteristics in terms of nationality, education, socio-economic status, job *etc.*; 2) the association is based in different Italian cities; therefore, it was possible to guarantee a geographical mix.

We illustrated the project’s goals, the methodology, the research expectations to the main stakeholders of this association. We indicated the criteria for correctly selecting our participants: we searched people with different ages, with a particular attention to young women (20-29 years old), as indicated by the Protocol; people with different education, so preferably not all people with a degree or a master’s degree (coherently with the spirit of the project that wants to engage social disadvantage people or people that historically don’t participate to science). We excluded people with STEM education and academics for the same reasons.

We contacted “Casa delle donne di Milano”, “Casa delle donne di Pisa” and, finally, “Casa delle donne di Parma”. They are located in the North and in the Center of Italy. We contacted “Casa delle donne di Roma” too, but we didn’t select any participants from there, because the participants’ characteristics didn’t match with our criteria. We selected these cities because they are representative of the Italian small/medium/large cities, and they have a different but relevant history in terms of feminist activism.

A very long and meticulous work has been done both to find people interested in the participation in our project and to compose balanced groups.

At the end of the selection’s process, we had a list of 17 people; we composed our final groups with 10 people: 5 for the first FG (the experimental group) and 5 for the second FG (the control one). We excluded 5 people because of their characteristics; the other 2 didn’t accept to participate for personal reasons. In the following table (Table 4.5) we resume all the women’ characteristics.

Table 4.5. Characteristics of the participants in the focus groups.

Focus Group (n. 1/n. 2)	Participant’s initial name	Characteristics (nationality, age, education)	Association (geographical area)	Group (experimental/ control)
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⁶ The quotation is taken from: <https://www.casadonnemilano.it/chi-siamo/>

“Casa delle donne” is present in different Italian cities.

Focus Group 1 (FG1)	L.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	I	Italian; 20-29 years; high school diploma	Casa delle donne Parma	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	T.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	E.	Italian, but with foreign parents; 40-50 years; 8 th grade diploma	Casa delle donne Milano	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	P.	Italian; 60-70 years; high school diploma	Casa delle donne Milano	EG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	G.	Italian; 20-29 years; high school diploma;	Casa delle donne Parma	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	M.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Parma	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	C.	Foreign origin; 40-50 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Milano	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	S.	Italian, 50-60 years old; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	A.	Italian; 50-50 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	CG

Selected participants have received written and oral information about the project. UNIMIB team informed that participants did not receive any type of reward, and the participation did not suppose a cost for them. Researchers communicated that all participants will be informed about the evolution of the ALLINTERACT project. All the participants signed an informed consent document. All participants' informed consent documents are uploaded in a specific folder on the ALLINTERACT workspace.

In line with the national directives in terms of collective safety, the UNIMIB team carried out the FGs online through the WEBEX platform. We conducted the two focus groups in Italian in the following dates:

- Focus Group 1: On Tuesday, the 12th October 2021 from 10.00 to 11.30 a.m. (without a pause); since we didn't finish to discuss all the stimuli, we scheduled another brief meeting on Wednesday the 20th October from 1.30 to 2.00 p.m.
- Focus Group 2: on Thursday, the 14th October 2021 from 6.30 to 8.00 p.m. (without pause).

The UNIMIB team conducted all the FGs in Italian to guarantee the full participation of people. In each of the FGs there were two researchers (Prof. Carmen Leccardi and Dr. Zenia Simonella) who played the role of facilitators of the discussion. The researchers presented themselves. One of the two

researchers briefly illustrated: a) the goals of the FGs; b) the possibility for each participant to freely express her opinion without fear; c) the ethical principles related to the protection of all FGs' participants in terms of privacy/anonymity. The other researcher conducted the FGs proposing the selected pool of stimuli (on gender topic) that were reported in the Protocol Document. Every researcher was in charge of involving all the participants, in particular those who participated less to the discussion.

All focus groups and interviews have been audio/video-recorded and literally transcribed. These recordings are uploaded in a specific folder on the ALLINTERACT workspace.

4.2.1.2. Education

- **Parents**

At the University of Barcelona, we conducted one the one hand four in-depth interviews with family members of vulnerable groups who have taken part in Scientific Dialogue Gatherings and two FG with families (15 mothers exactly, and 3 teachers accompanying them). These families did not used to participate in scientific activities. Thus, it will be these families that we will carry out the implementation of the scientific activities carried out by the project.

Here below are the pseudonyms and roles of the participants in the FG and interviews so far. This process has followed the guidelines set out in the Deliverable D4.8. Anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.

Table 4.6. Pseudonymous participant in focus groups and interviews undertaken by UB.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	RoI
Interview 1 (I)	Maria	Family
Interview 2(I)	Sofia	Family
Interview 3 (I)	Cristina	Family
Interview 4(I)	Francisca	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Elena	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Laura	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Angela	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Laia	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Nerea	Family

Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Estefania	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Carolina	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Matilde	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Carmen	Teacher
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Lucia	Teacher
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Hayat	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Mariana	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Mariya	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Silvia	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Esther	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Victoria	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Josefa	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Diana	Teacher

FG and interviews have followed five sections: 1) Identification of how societal actors benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education.

One of the interviewers will have the role of facilitator of the focus groups and will be in charge of giving turns to participants who want to intervene in the discussion. The facilitator will always prioritize those participants who have intervened less in order to ensure egalitarian participation. The facilitator will also encourage everyone to join the conversation and ensure an egalitarian dialogue among participants, in which participants intervene to provide validity claims instead of power claims.

- **Teachers**

In this topic the UH team has implemented two focus groups held with educators/teachers. Likewise, the Barcelona team conducted two FG with teachers (17 people) who have taken part in Scientific Dialogue Gatherings.

Here below are the pseudonyms and roles of the participants in the FG with teachers.

Table 4.7. Pseudonymous participant in focus groups undertaken by UB.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Rol
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Antonia	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Dolores	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Sara	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Antonio	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Javier	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Miguel	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Elena	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Raquel	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Alejandro	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Lucia	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Juan	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mateo	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Alba	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mónica	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Laura	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Jesús	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Emilio	Teacher

- **Students**

At the University of Groningen, we conducted two FG with undergraduate students (12 people). All the people participated voluntarily throughout the process, and we followed the recommendation provided by Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participant, which is based on high standard criteria: all conversations between researchers and potential participants about the possibility of participating in the research occurred in a place where the participants felt comfortable and safe to avoid any possible coercion and to ensure that the decision was taken with absolute freedom. Researchers have informed that participants did not receive any type of reward, and the participation did not suppose a cost for the participants. Researchers have also explained the possible risks and benefits of participating. The recruitment process was never

conducted by someone who may have an unduly influence on potential participants. The language employed ensures comprehension for the participant.

Table 4.8. Pseudonymous participant in focus groups and interviews undertaken by RUG.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Rol
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Lucas	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Julia	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Yara	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Kostas	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Kelly	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Liam	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mary	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mateo	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Sophie	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Eleni	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Anika	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Emma	Student

One of the interviewers will have the role of facilitator of the focus groups and will be in charge of giving turns to participants who want to intervene in the discussion. The facilitator will always prioritize those participants who have intervened less in order to ensure egalitarian participation. The facilitator will also encourage everyone to join the conversation and ensure an egalitarian dialogue among participants, in which participants intervene to provide validity claims instead of power claims.

4.2.2. Data collection

All focus groups and interviews have been audio-recorded and literally transcribed, substituting all names for pseudonyms for scientific use for later analysis. Later on, these were translated into English. The records of the FG have been stored by each partner who collected the data in the dispositive approved by the ethical board on their institutions.

4.2.3. Analysis

The Allinteract team has followed the dimensions and initial categories that emerged from project topics (a-e):

Table 4.9. Definitions of dimensions and categories for Focus Groups.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Dimensions	Transformative dimension includes those messages that evidence what facilitates the social/political/scientific impact mentioned.
	Exclusionary dimension includes those messages that show obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted social/political/scientific impact.
Category	a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research

4.3. Results of the Focus Groups: TOPIC a) How citizens benefit from scientific research

4.3.1. Results on Gender

The results obtained by gender are presented below:

- **Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group**

Respondents reported direct benefits to themselves mainly in terms of improved medical treatments, improved health information, but also in terms of access to scientific information for educational purposes.

In terms of political benefits, respondents mentioned using scientific information and participating in research as part of their advocacy efforts on behalf their ethnic community and patient group.

In terms of benefits from scientific impact, respondents referred to the development of Covid-19 vaccines and understanding gender and ethnic differences in Covid-19.

Respondents also provided examples of the barriers that prevent citizens from benefiting from scientific research. These included a language barrier for people whose first language is not English, the level of education, ethnicity for people who belong to ethnic minorities, gender as women were historically excluded or underrepresented in science as participants or researchers, and a lack of funding to take scientific evidence into practice in state schools.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872395

	<p>“one thing I was thinking about prior to this meeting was actually sciences entertainment. We always used to watch... the Christmas lectures... there was a brilliant television program called Rough Science, which I think is available on YouTube, where groups of scientists were set projects to do with little or no equipment... And I also listen to Inside Health and Inside Science and More or Less on Radio 4 as well.” P13 FG2</p>	<p>“I am autistic myself, so my heart was kind of racing because inevitably when I'm in a group, there's always a family member or someone who has someone a bit like me. I get nervous not knowing what I'm going to hear because often the experience I have is that people talk for us and not with us. And this is what led me to join the research community in 2016 because I thought, how can I change things because that's the scientific community and the general population has so many misconceptions about autism and learning disabilities.”</p>	<p>“I know we all know about it, but we're now being told that the virus affects men and women in a different way. Different ethnic groups are affected in a different way.” P14 FG2</p>
	<p>“Having read Caroline Criado's book [Invisible Women] on the way in which society is biased against women... If people actually read it, it's probably more widely known than it was. She's very good on that.” P13 FG2</p>		
	<p>“...we need more bilingual, either through audio or visual or written awareness of research, importance of reach such and how researchers make sure that it's safe and effective as much as possible. And she said, then there will be more engagement from people from her community.” P9, FG1</p>		
	<p>“I would say it's not nothing to do with education. I think it's the trust, the mistrust, because I said I come from Africa, Nigeria and Pfizer was in Nigeria. Once that had a lot of damage to a clinical trial, they were doing even way before I knew anything about clinical trials. So immediately you mentioned clinical trial to an African. The first thing they tell you is, Oh, they're using us as guinea pig.” P5 FG1</p>		
	<p>“I think the trouble is that the criteria for people to be included in what you call clinical trials are very excluding of pregnant women, of black women or or, as they put it. They don't exclude black people. They're not allowed to do that. But they say whose first language is not English, which an awful lot of black people.” P8 FG1</p>		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>"I think women have traditionally been second class citizens when it comes to medical research, I think particularly over things like pain, where nearly all research is conducted on men... There's so much anxiety about harming unborn children that anybody of potentially pregnant age tends to be excluded." P3 FG1</p>		
	<p>"...as a woman, I mean, not many years ago, autism was exclusively a male condition. Notice how I say condition and not disorder. It was because women couldn't be autistic." P2 FG1</p>		
	<p>"I'm aware of some research that was done to look into how and how to improve the school's environment for children. And one of the difficulties there of getting it implemented, of course, is funding. And so, you know, private schools can take that research and do whatever they like with it and improve the work the school environment for their students. But in state schools, that funding isn't available..." P1 FG1</p>		
	<p>"I think thinking of it the opposite way is I think an awful lot of people now are getting so much wrong information on social media." P14 FG2</p>		
	<p>"I've got a few here barriers to benefiting from research, I think could be just things like lack of awareness of the research, maybe lack of means to actually participate in the research, maybe the feeling that they don't have anything worthwhile to contribute. And that might be because they don't really understand the research process or maybe the need or importance for research and also maybe a perceived lack of skills. Maybe people think that you need to have a degree to be able to understand it or, you know, some sort of qualification or experience in the subject area. I'm trying to think of my own family. What would you know, the younger members of my family in particular that would maybe prevent them from accessing research or participating in it" P15 FG2</p>		
	<p>"They don't teach analytical thinking in school, particularly nowadays... what I think is needed is teaching kids to read a website critically and just to feel confident." P13 FG2</p>		
	<p>"it's not only gender, it's ethnicity as well. So a lot of research, if you look at things like BMI [Body Mass Index]... is done on white Americans and it has no bearing whatsoever on our other groups. Even the white Europeans, it doesn't have any bearing on it." P11 FG2</p>		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>"when I was at school, it was always I never felt any sense of that women wouldn't be, you know, valid contributors to research and science. But it was the case that the girls, in the girls grammar school I went to, we did biology and to do chemistry and physics, we had to go to lessons at the boys school. So there was that historic sort of. And things like engineering and so on were never on the radar." P12 FG2</p>		
	<p>"And let's not forget that African people are the most genetically diverse people on earth. So science is not doing research any favours in excluding them, willingly or not." P2 FG1</p>		

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

- **Member of LGBTQI group**

In general, participants of the Control Group (CG) positively evaluated the opportunity to participate in the Focus Group, as they were able to share thoughts, opinions, critics and ideas about how citizens benefit from scientific research. They also see a major importance not only in scientific research and its relation to academia, but mainly in how results are communicated and disseminated to the population in general. In this sense, three key aspects can be mentioned as key findings: first, although Internet and social media have made access to information so much easier compared to previous years, it is important that people know how to identify real facts from fake news. Second, in relation to this point, participants also referred to the importance of Education in the process of creating critical thinking and also teaching people how to differentiate proper research from other kinds of information. And third, participants identified that most of the time scientific research and its results remain circulating in a small group of people – researchers mainly – who has the same knowledge and vocabulary, making difficult for regular people to have access to those results. Therefore, they highlighted the importance of making this information more understandable and accessible for the entire society.

Table 4.11. Results of the member of LGBTQI group on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research. Control Group.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research				
		Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)	Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);	Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).
<p>Case 1: There are examples in Instagram of how citizens benefit from research to promote social campaigns or activism. For example, the use of the hashtag #stopbullying is related to social protests against racism and school violence and also makes visible the need of breaking the silence and becoming active bystanders against violence.</p>	TD*	<p>P1: "(...) a funny thing happened with me and Facebook, which is a social network that was once much more relevant than today, but I use it basically to read articles. I think the algorithm is already well trained and the people I have in my network, so I usually when I get on there it's because I'm in time, because I'm a person publishing articles, publishing relevant content and a lot of times they have studies behind it."</p> <p>P4: "I think that already having somehow some kind of engagement of a population not so specialized in scientific content is a first step already successfully achieved."</p> <p>P2: "I work with social media directly and I notice that recently when doing research for certain inspirations regarding publications, it is very common to integrate pieces that are more linked to activism or more linked to documentation and sharing of studies, of statistics."</p>	<p>P3: "(...) on Facebook I use a lot, I see a lot of hashtags about female empowerment, about social causes, because that's what I study."</p> <p>P4: "(...) my social media are also a bit oriented in that sense. I have Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter... and I feel sometimes that the information is a bit oriented towards my specific tastes, as it is natural. I work on issues of gender violence and LGBTI issues, and so using the hashtags and the kind of messaging is common and is often from governmental organizations and also non-governmental organizations."</p>	<p>P2: "(...) a great benefit that scientific research has is the possibility of referencing and then referencing the main text. And in that sense, scientific research itself has benefits in relation to sharing information without any kind of scientific or analytical debate that can be confirmed later. That is, if I share a statistic that has a study behind it, I can confirm whether that study is legitimate or not or whether it's been accepted, whether it's been revised and all that. However, there is also a lot of... sometimes out of malice, sometimes out of the need to make things more attractive, the need to create a little bit of a pretty, attention-grabbing version of the study. That is, if I have a statistic that is eye-catching, has a phrase that is quite interesting, something that can be shared on the news, that can be shared on social media, it also ends up turning almost a little bit so that the research is shared or that has something eye-catching that can be shared, because sharing a study that doesn't have a definitive conclusion and that calls for further revision in the future, is not very interesting to the vast majority of people, and therefore will not be the target of a post on social media, of a hashtag of that kind of disclosure. I think that's a bit of the tightrope we find ourselves on in scientific dissemination."</p>

	<p>P4: "(...) it is also up to the development maybe of critical thinking, of critical reflection, to question the sources and theirs, the media because these bubbles, as P2 was saying, they are going to be naturally fed by those who govern these networks. We want them to then make sense to us and to be close to us and to prove what we say, on a psychological level it's normal."</p> <p>P3: "(...) I think very much that these things that bring that social movement, yes, they end up producing content, more content, they end up motivating research (...)"</p> <p>P1: "(...) I am careful, but it is an effort, right? And then I wonder how much we are... how difficult it is to navigate, to give access without forgetting to transmit, along with the information, what makes that information reliable, right? I think there are two sides to giving access to information. Here is the information and you can trust it because it was well done, it was done this way, this way and this way."</p> <p>P6: "(...) in my view of all this I think it also goes through the issue of education and how we are educated even in the schools themselves, right? I mean, we entered school and at least I got a little bit at the end of high school with this whole boom of Instagram and Facebook and we are not taught, that is, there is no talk about it for the younger ones. And so... I had a pretty negative experience myself because of this. That is, this kind of dissemination of kind of information, in this case of misinformation, and I think it's all about how to educate, educate to see, educate to research, educate also to know where the information and the misinformation is."</p>		<p>P8: "(...) the sharing of content, whatever kind it is, is always going to continue to exist and expand, so I think it's very relevant that scientific research tries to keep up, tries to occupy as much space as possible to try to diminish the space of the other things that may arise that are less credible and that, in fact, the vast majority of people will not have the ability to discern."</p> <p>P3: "(...) obviously using social media to try to reach more people is an obvious, necessary path. We are in the century of information, in a globalized world, the information comes very fast and is disseminated very fast, so the science, right, the academy, the scientific media do not use this to popularize, to be able to show people what is happening, it is a shot in the foot."</p>
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	<p>ED*</p> <p>P3: "Besides these disclosures of scientific training, there is also a lot of misinformation. I don't know if it is connected with the question you asked, but there are many facts that are not, in fact, verified and are widely disseminated and when you see them, they are saying that the cure for cancer is drinking five liters of water a day and everyone starts drinking, making eternal viral trends of drinking five liters of water a day to not get cancer. I don't know if it is exactly what you want to know, but besides this scientific production, I... these hashtags also have this other side of fake news, things are not clarified and the masses end up consuming them."</p> <p>P3: "(...) the important hashtags are part of my life as a researcher, as a social media user, the I also believe that sometimes it can lead to misinformation. Not that it has to do with the hashtags, but there you go, it happens because that's what's being published on the net."</p> <p>P4: "I think it's a good tool, but also as P3 pointed out, it has its downsides and sometimes when that information is not verified or not from reliable sources, that cascading effect of sharing a hashtag can become somewhat harmful."</p> <p>P2: "(...) I think that it is not only proven, because we know that as a business model social media will always try to integrate the content with which we will interact in order to spend more time on them, but I also think it has to do a bit with the extremism that we have seen recently and the possibility of these communities' extreme certain ideas and promote only certain views of things. As we talked a little bit about misinformation, the idea that there aren't then</p>		<p>P5: "We end up seeing ourselves on social media, what we think ends up being validated by the hashtags that you've liked in the past and you'll see that huge amount of content from those same people again. I use Twitter and Instagram more and on Twitter I follow accounts more from journalists, scientists, more because of the pandemic, and on Twitter it's very fast when they change the hashtags."</p> <p>P5: "For you to get out of that bubble is something you have to actively do, you have to go after other sources. It's not the social network that's going to lead you to those other sources."</p> <p>P3: "(...) I think that another point that we have to observe is that the problem is not... okay, it may be that at the time the language, the form of disclosure was a problem and maybe it still is today, because the academy, I think, I see it like this, is still going through that process of approaching society, of calling society, of not looking at society as an object of study, but of looking at society as an inseparable part, as an important part that validates why study, you know?"</p> <p>P3: "(...) A second point that I think we have to pay attention to is that there's no point in me making a video, or making YouTube content, Instagram content, with stories, with glow, with whatever, if people are not taught to look, if people are not taught to value Science. People are not taught."</p> <p>P3: "(...) in my experience as a teacher and everything else, the school, in a certain way, is also made to be able to reproduce the same discourse of the social, capitalist, modern world, of the logic of work. At least in a public school in a peripheral neighborhood in Brazil. So, those people that attend that school are not taught to think, to research, they are taught to work. You go, work from eight to 18, Monday to Monday, one day off a week and that's it. So, this education model doesn't include an incentive to read, an incentive to critical thinking, an incentive to research. So, do you think that this person, when he/she goes to the social media, is going to write an article? Is he going to be worried about knowing whether what is written or not? No. And like this: it's not entirely their fault either, it's also the fault</p>
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	<p>topics that lead us to confront ideas around some people that are unreachable with certain information, because they're never going to give the necessary engagement with that publication and that way they're not going to be more available to receive other kinds of content. That's something that, in my case, is a concern."</p> <p>P3: "(...) If I'm always in the circle, for example, of fake news, I'll never get out of that circle. I will not walk in the circle of fake news to read an article from the BBC, to read an article, I don't know, from a newspaper, a scientific newspaper, whatever, because that is not my reality either. It is also there to think about a reality as that is also a social symptom in his reality, the access to information, how he consumes information. So, when we talk about social media, there are all these entanglements, the network itself, the media, who is consuming, what is the profile of the person who consumes, what is her background, academic, scientific, life background, because probably that background will directly influence what she is seeing in her social media, right?</p> <p>P1: "(...) I'm very skeptical about consuming anything, even from friends, even from my bubble. Any data that is even remotely reminiscent of a statistic or a fact or a reality of society, I have a lot of reservations."</p> <p>P7: "(...) I think that Wikipedia has already occupied the space of launching many fake news, right? Also, just a comment, but from my point of view any information that we read nowadays, we need to</p>		<p>of the way they were molded, both as a general civil society, and in the school model that we are inserted".</p>
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	<p>know where it came from and understand who wrote it."</p> <p>P8: "(...) I think that if research and science don't occupy those spaces, that space will be occupied by other things. So, and I don't necessarily think it's bad... that is, it can be difficult, but I think it's positive that scientific content tries to make an adaptation to be more attractive, always referring to sources and what gives them some credibility."</p> <p>P7: "(...) it is also necessary to have this education: let's read the sources, let's understand where it came from, let's know who studied it, for example, who did a translation of... I don't know, of Freud, who was the translator, why did he speak those words. Because translations also have sayings and the information doesn't end up arriving exactly as it was transmitted by Freud, but it ends up being transmitted the way the translator understood it. And it's also a little bit bad from my point of view."</p>		
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*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

Table 4.11. Results of the member of LGBTQI group on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research. Control Group

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research		
	<p><i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i></p>	<p><i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</i></p>
		<p><i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i></p>

<p><i>Case 2: In many languages, the use of masculine forms has traditionally been used to refer to both women and men, although feminine forms are available, too. A cross-linguistic (Italian and German) study shows that word pairs help to avoid a male bias in the gender-typing of professions and increase women's visibility; at the same time, they decrease the estimated salaries of</i></p>	<p>TD*</p>	<p>P2: "It's extremely interesting that these studies are being developed in relation to the most demonstrable impact possible of language changes. It's extremely interesting."</p> <p>P7: "(...) what little I have been following about gender neutral I still keep thinking that we had to work more to make society aware of the difference itself and the gender that kind of that gender is equal to the other and not only in terms of dialectics but in terms of consciousness itself. Of course, dialectics will help create that awareness, but it wasn't just dialectics that they would have to look at."</p>	<p>P5: "(...) We have to change how we see the world, because if... or not, it is also by public policies also to decrease the difference in salaries and everything else."</p>	<p>P3: "(...) So there is not just a movement from one place, there is a movement from several places that together create these resistance movements. And then I totally think that Science has a connection, yes, that it can both validate these studies from the perspective of qualifying and quantifying them and also get people out on the street and get people thinking."</p> <p>P2: "(...) it is only through scientific research that we can foster more scientific research. That is, from studies other studies are formed, from research another research is formed, needs are identified for things that need to be further investigated. So, in that sense, I think it's very important that there continues to be research and publication about various subjects because only from that will there begin to be more and more research and more, greater development of certain areas."</p>
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<p><i>typically feminine professions. This potential payoff has implications for language policies aiming at gender-fairness. (Horvath et al., 2016).</i></p>		<p>P5: "(...) our language, our language is the reflection of how we see the world or the opposite, depending on the point of view. And in Portuguese we have masculine and feminine and if we use the word "doctor", the first person, the image that comes to our mind is a male doctor. It's not going to be a woman doctor, unless you speak "médica". And in Italian, it is even "worse", because there is no word "doctor", it is only "physician". Even if it is a woman, they will call it "doctor". And this reflects a lot of how society views that profession."</p> <p>P7: "(...) unconsciously our dialectics also affects how we see the world and stuff like that. I'm not saying that this kind of study is invalid, but I think we also have to worry not only about changing the dialectic itself, but raising people's awareness."</p> <p>P1: "(...) the transformation has to be first as collective culture or first as language, because one thing can pull the other. So, I think that what happens even... we talk a lot about representativeness, I think that more and more... Someone put a representation that did not exist for the first time before it was accepted, right? And this sometimes encourages this dialogue, this transformation. So, I think with language it's kind of like that too. There is a dialogue going on and to effect this dialogue into transformations, whether in language, in whatever, whether in the media, is fuel for other transformations as well, right? So, I think the two things go very closely together and I don't think there is one without the other."</p> <p>P7: "(...) I don't know if I spoke too differently, but that was it: to make people aware, not only of gender, but of the difference of the other, that it exists, but it is one accepting the other, like you don't care if you have a vagina or a penis, you are a person and that's it, it's over. And this ideology also has to be changed, right? Because besides gender also folks need to start understanding</p>		
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		<p>that... to throw away certain stereotypes of the kind... that have been formed over time."</p> <p>P3: "(...) the more you speak, the more people read and that knowledge people review, criticize and that criticism, that magazine, all that, generates pressure, generates a counterculture movement, a resistance movement that changes the system."</p> <p>P3: "(...) Machismo, racism, these are structural systems, so, for us to break this, it is not enough to just talk, just talk on the Internet, and that's it. This is a tool, it is a platform, but we have to join forces with other sectors too, right? I have to talk to the media, I have to protest, the media has to start embracing this."</p> <p>P3: "(...) we need to keep talking, keep writing and keep bringing people into this discussion, for the thing to keep growing and even further."</p>		
	ED*	<p>P3: "(...) there is no way that this is the only variable in this study over a period of time that the only thing that has been achieved is really the change in the linguistics used to refer to these types of jobs."</p>		<p>P2: "(...) When science and academia only create other... that is, if no other knowledge loop is created that is not disseminated and applied in public policies, then we are engaging in an unnecessary exercise. That is, it may be that all the researchers in my department agree and think my research is excellent, but if that has no influence whatsoever on... not only on Science and academia, but also on public perception, on public policy, on the whole process of shaping society, then for me it becomes a misstep."</p> <p>P5: "(...) Now, thinking about the... taking this to Brazil, but also here in Europe, in Hungary, in Poland, that we have governments that are anti-science."</p>

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

Participants of the Experimental Group (EG) were also very interested in participating in this Focus Group, not only because of the subject itself, but also for the opportunity for people who have been always excluded from scientific research in terms of opinion to be able to express their ideas and critics on the matter. In general, there was a consensus about the fact that some hashtags on social media may be related to scientific research or science. Some of the participants recognized to follow some hashtags, but mainly to quickly access to specific conversations or topics of their interest, but not for subjects related neither to science nor to scientific research in particular. However, they did recognize that social media can boost scientific research, mainly when there are

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some specific topics that create a major interest in social media users. In this sense, it appears as a tool for researchers of people in science to detect those subjects that may be target of deeper research. On the other hand, participants also addressed the fact that social media were created by private companies which have specific interests in terms of business and how to interact with users. In this sense, it calls the attention on how information is disseminated and the way this has an impact on the content consumed by people, which could be responding to those commercial or political interests. However, they agreed on the fact that social media is a powerful tool to promote activist causes, which could help science and scientific research to reach more people globally.

Table 4.12. Results of the member of LGBTQI group on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research. Experimental Group.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research				
		Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)	Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);	Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).
<p><i>Case 1: There are examples in Instagram of how citizens benefit from research to promote social campaigns or activism. For example, the use of the hashtag #stopbullying is related to social protests against racism and school violence and also makes visible the need of breaking the silence and becoming active bystanders against violence.</i></p>	TD*	<p>P7: "(...) I think that we have a social media movement where the debate it... many of the things that are being discussed in Brazil today are born within the social media. For example, when we are going to talk about issues related to racism, which I think is something that at least I know more about and that I am much more connected to, I notice and also... And also about LGBTQA+ issues, I think these are the points that draw my attention the most, that I am always there watching and trying to understand what is happening. I think that there is a very big movement of people realizing that people... it may start as a hashtag, but that this will be transformed into a very rich debate within universities, for example."</p>		<p>P7: "(...) in Brazil we notice a very large movement of studies that are born from the restlessness that arises from the Internet. For example, you will notice that some authors will gain notoriety, like Djamila Ribeiro, for example, it comes from a person who writes and that what she talks about through the lives and through all the movement that is made by some specific theme related to racism, that takes a path and makes people, for example, use a book, use her research and make developments on these themes that she brings within her speech, within this writing."</p>
		<p>P5: "(...) I think hashtags are very connected to the political issues of putting on the agenda that are necessary. Even the demarcation came, the issue of the demarcation of indigenous lands now had a hashtag that had to do with it. I saw many of my friends from Anthropology and within academia using the hashtag to talk about these issues related to indigenous issues. It reminded me a little bit of that as well."</p>		<p>P7: "(...) And if we also look at, for example, the contemporary academic production in Brazil and some specific courses, we will notice a lot of us making this connection with this universe of the Internet, a universe that is debated there and that many of the things that we think we need to talk about, will emerge there, especially in this period that we went through, where everyone was at home, so the Internet became a place where people need to debate."</p>

		<p>P6: "(...) my own use of social media are different in each of the social media I use. On Instagram, for example, it's just to share some activism things or things that are proper from, I don't know, tours, etcetera. On Facebook I share a lot of political things from Chile and also things that have to do with feminism and sexual dissidence. On Twitter it's just to vent myself personally about some anger I had about some specific issue as well. So, there they are... the hashtags I use are super distinct in each of these media."</p>		<p>P4: "(...) regarding the benefit that social media can bring to debates and research, I think that yes, there is no doubt that they add something, right? However, what I am wondering is what kind of methodologies can be used to use this information that exists in a communication medium, considering social media as a communication medium, what kind of methodology can be used to extract information. For example, at the level of hashtags, are we going to count hashtags? How do you do that?"</p>
		<p>P7: "(...) I think social media can be a trigger... I think they can be a trigger for a researcher to perhaps introduce or introduce or research more on a specific theme. Then we... I will remember, it came to my mind now too... I remembered, for example, when a movement of black women started in Brazil to talk about the loneliness of black women. And that was a movement in which several black women started to post in their networks how it was the situation of being a black woman and being neglected since childhood, right? That you are not chosen to be a school friend, that you are not chosen to date a specific figure, and there was a lot of talk about that. It was a moment in Brazil when a lot was said. And then several women started to write in their networks. And that started to create a movement of what, a movement of people writing about that, who then went looking for theoretical bases for us to try to explain why those women were writing about that in that specific period."</p>		<p>P4: "(...) when the media do a good job of disseminating science, it ends up being, in a way, scientific dissemination anyway. And so, I think that social media as a medium or as a vehicle for communication, should be used by those who work in academia or those who do research. I think it all makes sense to disseminate and inform people in the best way."</p>
				<p>P7: "(...) I think that the social media, they are nowadays doing something that wanting it or not it will have themes that will deal in more latent ways because of the speed with which everything passes there, that maybe we, because of the time we need to be able to research and get a specific production, we can't."</p>

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	ED*	<p>P1: "I'll be very honest. I didn't even know this was happening, because most of the activism that I see, unless I follow a specific page, for example ILGA or something like that, I don't tend to follow hashtags, but when there are like this big movements, like there was with Black Lives Matter, if we followed the hashtag, I would find more the voices of the people themselves who were on the ground and who could then provide information for academic studies and more in-depth things rather than exactly the institutions or the academics or direct references. It's always through third or fourth connections that a person gets there."</p> <p>P2: "(...) I had no idea that hashtags were linked to any scientific event or scientific study. I thought that hashtags were a way to compile information related to that topic. I really had no idea that, for example this #StopBullying was connected with any scientific or other study. I'm being taken by surprise."</p>		<p>P6: "(...) I think it has to do with what is the concept we handle about science issues because for me specifically, when we talk about science, I always think it's research about medicine, about new cells, etcetera, etcetera. So, I didn't conceive of the connection that scientific research has with social media."</p> <p>P2: "(...) That's sometimes the risk I see in spreading science on social media... because we don't always know, we're never sure if it's serious, if it's not serious, if we have to take it into consideration, if we don't have to take it into consideration, and I believe that most people can't do, or don't want to, don't have the predisposition to do sometimes what I do which is to go and really investigate if it's a credible article or not."</p>
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	<p>P1: "(...) we know that there is a lot of activism that is, in fact, informed. But, thinking again about the Black Lives Matter issue, when it was that issue of everyone sharing the black squares... while there were people actively on the ground asking them not to, because it was clogging up the hashtags and preventing people who needed information at the time and urgent information... dark places to scare, where to get water or food, etcetera, and they couldn't access that information because it was a bunch of people putting the little squares there and I don't know what. So, in other words, if a researcher was to look at those issues, my question was, would he get to those voices or would he just see the little squares. And I would think yes, it's actually a sign of social change, it's all very united, etcetera."</p> <p>P1: "(...) I have a lot of faith in social media, but at the same time these questions worry me because I think that often social media tends to be a little bit of a mirror of what already happens outside of social media, which is the same people who already have a voice, continues to screen and occupy the space. Every time there's a little bit of space for people who didn't already have it, it comes to be taken up again... I don't know."</p> <p>P2: "(...) I, in my opinion, don't specifically follow anything on social media to get some scientific benefit out of it. As they said earlier, I follow media and from there and from the media, from what they post, if it's something that I'm interested in on a scientific level, then I'll investigate it directly and not through social media."</p>		<p>P1: "(...) Science is slow to do. It's normal, isn't it? To be rigorous, etcetera, it has to follow certain precepts and certain steps, etcetera. And it often goes backwards too, it happens too. We've seen now with this whole Covid issue, things are being discovered that contradict others, that supposedly... it's normal, that's how science works. And then, on top of that, it's slow... the whole process. And publishers also a code gate keeping on articles and etcetera, so all science is slow. And social media doesn't live on slow stuff, does it? I think that's why there's also that difficulty..."</p> <p>P2: "(...) E depois esta questão dos ritmos e por vezes as próprias redes sociais não têm propriamente um formato profundamente compatível com os formatos académicos, que são coisas mais longas, mais... às vezes quase inacessível, tanto do ponto de vista monetário, como também do ponto de vista la linguagem, dos conceitos, etcétera, etcétera."</p> <p>P2: "(...) I think it would be good for people in the academic world to look more at the social media, but with solid systems and with extra care. But at the same time I also think that there should be more presence of the researchers and the institutions especially... I also don't want to put the emphasis only on the researchers, poor things, who already have more than enough work... I think that the institutions do very little to support their researchers in their presence in social media."</p>
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		<p>P2: "(...) in recent years we have started to see that a lot since a year and a half mainly, the scientific issue disseminated on social networks, there is always that other side of the coin of how much information or fake news that spreads much more easily than the... than a serious article, right? The serious article, in my opinion, has a harder time spreading in the social networks than a fake news, than a less serious article and so, maybe, sometimes I get to the point, I myself sometimes get to the point of not knowing if that information that has all the air of being very scientific and very serious and I don't know what, if it is truly to be taken into account or taken into consideration or not. Sometimes I get a little bit in this balance if it's a credible article, if it's not, how am I going to get it easily, because then I personally, when the article interests me, I go and investigate and find out if I believe it or if it's not."</p>		
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*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

Table 4.13. Results of the member of LGBTQI group on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research. Experimental Group.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i>
<p><i>Case 2: In many languages, the use of masculine forms has traditionally been used to refer to both women and men, although feminine forms are available, too. A cross-linguistic (Italian and German) study shows that word pairs help to avoid a male bias in the gender-typing of professions and increase women's visibility; at the same time, they decrease the estimated salaries of typically feminine professions. This potential payoff has implications for language policies aiming at gender-fairness.</i></p>	<p>TD*</p>	<p>P2: "(...) there are languages, namely English, that we can easily find a neutral gender to treat everybody, but speaking specifically of Portuguese, it is very complicated because "o", "a", "os", "as" are still binary. There is nothing there that defines non-binary people, you know? There would have to be a whole linguistic reformulation and creation of a neutral gender. And all that would entail a drastic change in education, I don't know... a whole brutal change..."</p> <p>P1: "(...) One thing that I think could help is to have gender issues and LGBT issues more framed with the curricula. So, start right in the university curricula, because we have this idea that these are new things and they're not. Just check on literature. Byren already used neutral pronouns to refer to people that his vision would be neutral or that we would call non-binary people. In other</p>	<p>P1: "(...) And I think it would be a good place for people like us to start having a voice and to start being able to also participate in these studies and after these studies, from then on, we are more visible in public policies, in political debates... right, in civil society in general, you know? We're not just that group that once in a while, okay, come on, we have to pay a little attention."</p> <p>P2: "(...) it seems to me that obviously this issue of creating a neutral pronoun is a political issue. However, we know that politics leans, lays practically on top of what science says. The day that science, in my view, the day that science starts to use a neutral pronoun, politics will eventually do the same. When there is no longer, as P1 said, especially in medical science, this sharp differentiation, because in the end the difference is not so great, when we are talking about an ear operation... in other fields it will be</p>

		<p>words, there is a whole history of the various LGBT communities throughout history, Sappho, etcetera, etcetera, within Literature, the Arts, of everything, and that is simply left out of the curricula. And I think that already just having contact with those testimonies in the curricula, I'm not even saying at the high school level anymore, but at least at the university level, could already start to be an incentive...".</p> <p>P1: "(...) that language issue is very complicated. I was just saying that I also think it would help to start thinking about these issues more generally if we had more contact with all these communities from the beginning, because then it helps us open the range to other issues."</p> <p>P1: "(...) I think that for there to be this awareness of the language issue, there first had to be a more general socialization about the experience of these people. That is... of people, at least I include myself in those people, of our history, of our existence. Because from the moment we stopped being concepts and started being people with culture, with history, etcetera, maybe the opening would be greater."</p>	<p>sharper, but there are things that are not so sharp, when science starts using a neutral pronoun or a gender-neutral form, politics and society will end up doing the same. That's my opinion. So, science has an important and fundamental role in my view."</p>	
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	ED*	<p>P1: "(...) despite the fact that we are in a Gender Studies thing, this is a criticism that I can also point out even in relation to Gender Studies still here in Portugal, and that they are... there is still very little research done on non-binary gender. When we talk about gender equality, in my head I think "good, genders equality", but in reality, it always tends to be a very binary thing, still. There's still very little stuff on non-binary stuff, etcetera."</p> <p>P2: "(...) I can say that I am non-binary, but you look at me and if I don't tell you that you are non-binary, you would treat me as a woman. It's normal, isn't it? Okay, gender is what we are, but inevitably it depends on how people treat us and how they interact with us. So, logically, these things will eventually also apply to me in theory, in practice, etcetera, but as a non-binary person I don't see myself at all in this kind of research, you know what I mean? In other words, I think there is still a long way to go in this direction, of making things non-binary in the various fields of intervention."</p>	<p>P1: "(...) I think that the very... not only the civil discourse and the political debate but also the academic debate itself here in Portugal, but I would say maybe... my experience is more with the British academia, but... now we are starting to talk more about non-binary issues and about trans people and etcetera, but we still talk very little and here in Portugal I feel a lot when we talk about gender equality policies, we are actually talking about the reality of cis women and cis men. Then I think it's the LGBT issues."</p>	<p>P2: "(...) All the studies and when we hear about it and when something happens or... and that the topic is gender equality, it's always binary, it's always male and female."</p> <p>P2: "(...) why is it that in Gender Studies or Gender Equality, when we talk about Gender Equality, we don't talk about Gender Equality, do we? because we know that there is inequality between cis men and cis women, yes, but we also know that there are inequalities between trans men and cis men, etcetera, etcetera. And these are gender issues. However, some are addressed as LGBT issues and some are addressed as gender issues. And I think academia does that a lot still, unfortunately."</p> <p>P5: "(...) besides the fact that we do not have much research in academia on issues of neutral languages and so on, there are no incentives for this and many times we are prevented from doing this, isn't it? For example, I already had a research project that did not go ahead, that I wanted to research on neutral language, neutral pronouns, but it did not go ahead because there was not enough bibliography about it, because there was not enough research about it. So, how could I carry out that research. So, but starting from that principle, this is never going to happen, right? If one can never start or never go ahead with this kind of research, because there isn't any, there never will be. I mean, it is something that ends in itself. And that's it, we need the incentive, we need to be allowed to basically</p>
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				<p>talk about it, and many times we are not. Like in my case."</p> <p>P6: "(...) that science also uses, that alienates science from ordinary people. I put it this way, because when one has an interest in some scientific topic, the terms they use sometimes are too far-fetched or too difficult to understand for ordinary people. So one puts the text aside and is left without reading to the end."</p> <p>P6: "(...) I read in the social networks also that we are the ones who make the language. It is not made by politicians; it is not made by scientists. The common people, we ourselves are the ones who are creating our own vocabulary. Then also as P5 says, there are no previous investigations about language issues or equality in language. One already has to start doing that, ask some professor or there will already be some kind of book that has already covered that topic."</p> <p>P1: "(...) I don't know if the academy can do much more. Maybe in the matter of fact checking, fact checking and things like that... but that... I mean, who's going to do that. And that then also raises labor issues, doesn't it? I mean, the researchers, the professors work very hard and on top of that they have to do fact checking... you know what I mean? I mean, I don't know, I think it always depends on the intervening parties. In fact, sometimes there are people who take scientific things and misinterpret them, either unintentionally or</p>
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				<p>on purpose, and then they have that evidence there, and then almost nobody takes the trouble to read the article properly. It's enough that the reference is there... I don't know."</p>
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*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

- **Women (including Young women) from a women's group**

Participants declare that they usually benefit from scientific research, especially on gender/feminist issues, because of their activism at "Casa delle donne". Furthermore, there are several references to COVID or to medical issues, for contextual (pandemic) or personal reasons (personal sickness).

They discuss about specific topics as the importance for them of the scientific sources, and how to select, to manage, and to diffuse articles, especially when people use social media to spread scientific information; another topic that emerged was the credibility of people who speak about science and the importance of having faith in scientists, all aspects that influence how they benefit from the scientific research.

All these aspects can be referred to the "transformative dimension", because they use research to generate a social impact; however, their interventions express some aspects related to the "exclusionary dimension" too. In fact, they underline socio-cultural obstacles related to the difficulty for ordinary people to deeply understand scientific research; furthermore, the raising of "non-scientific" streams that focuses on "personal experience" or "the spiritual side", filling a gap that scientists or doctors are not able to fill. Science is often viewed as rational and detached from humans, so this aspect is considered a big obstacle to foster the dialogue between "science and society" and to push ordinary people approaching scientific topics.

During the FGs, participants' interventions were related to social impact because they discussed about this topic in relation to their personal interactions during which they spread scientific information. On the contrary, we didn't notice "benefits from political impact" and "benefits from scientific impact" (except for one case).

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Table 4.14. Results of the Women (including Young women) from a women's group on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i>
TD*	I do it, that is take advantage of research and promote campaigns on gender-based violence, especially during specific dates such as on November 25 th or on March 8 th (A., FG_2).		We conceive science subjects as something boring that you have to study. I remember that... I am a filmmaker... in my first academic year, professors quoted from a book written by a filmmaker and a scientist explaining how neuroscience interacts with cinema. Many of us have read the book. It was interesting to investigate further ... how we could create/communicate using neuroscience. (G., FG_2)
	I follow the social campaigns related to feminism, or those that have to do with my work as a historian. I have always taken a critical approach, that is, looking at them through the lens of the researcher. So what I enjoyed was finding errors in some campaigns (e.g. March 8 is usually considered a party and not a day of struggle), or to criticize the distorted history of gender violence. The ones I supported had an impact on the people around me. (M., FG_2)		

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	<p>Most of my social activity is this: I don't share information about my personal life. If I read interesting articles, I re-share them, without commenting on them. (...) If I find something interesting that can stimulate conversation among people, friends, family, I share it.... I was part of a group of girls ... with whom we spread information about gender ... before we were called "Glimpses of gender" ... during the university we organized collective meetings in free classrooms but then, due to Covid, we moved to the social media space... so, yes, I use scientific papers, I use articles on gender culture, gender violence and I spread them (L., FG_1).</p>		
	<p>I talk with other people about various articles. Then, as E. said, at the "Casa delle Donne" we organize numerous meetings, even with those of "Nonunadimeno". We select sources and we read articles on gender/gender-based violence. (P., FG_1)</p>		
	<p>My experience is like that of L. Two years ago I approached "Casa delle donne" in Parma. I read and selected articles on gender, deciding what to publish. It was a task with a certain responsibility. I thought that ... our page started to have followers ... well ... we proposed articles that people would read ... it's a big job. (I., FG_1)</p>		
	<p>I had shared an article on autism. But I'm not going to check the sources. On the basis of my feeling, I share ... I am an ordinary person; I have no specific skills. Yes, I read articles on climate change, I am in favor of science... But I haven't really investigated scientific topics (E., FG_1)</p>		

	<p>In 1999, I had a sarcoma ... I have been under treatment and thanks to the doctors ... I still do follow up... I am an ordinary person. I don't know anything about science and research. (...) Thanks to them, I am alive today. If they hadn't made progress in research, I wouldn't have been here. There was another time when I shared an article from the Cancer Institute and there many people spoke to me because they knew about my past. So I talked about my experience (E., FG_1).</p>		
	<p>I usually follow the podcasts on neuroscience of a young Romanian boy. He became well known in two years ... now he has been hired by the Romanian Ministry of Education to do research and to go in the schools. Thanks to 25 minutes of neuroscience podcasts, he has a lot of success. It is useful, it is extraordinary. This has to do with the fact that he uses simple words. (...) The message is clear, it is full of scientific information, but it is at everyone's level. This isn't easy with neuroscience. The simplicity, the passion. The way of communicating the content (C., FG_2).</p>		
ED*	<p>I have the feeling that in this period, if not at the beginning of the pandemic, but just after ... in addition to the scientific discourse, which for me is very practical ... a path is being outlined that is also based on the feelings of the individual. And this is the reason why I do not blame those who do not need to go back to the (scientific) sources, because ... I speak for myself ... I often find myself listening to the opinion of people in the minority... let's say, and I didn't feel the need to go back to the origin. Because ... I find it very hard to explain ... it is a very deep feeling. Alongside the scientific discourse, this thing is emerging, which in my opinion is very big and is unusual (I., FG_1).</p>		
	<p>In my daily life I observe that we just don't know how to distinguish the valid sources from the false ones. It is normal for one to feel confused in this information flow which is getting bigger every day and therefore we do not know what to believe or we believe what seems easier, closer to our feelings and beliefs. (T., FG_1).</p>		

	<p>One point is “the salience of the single case”. It seems to me that it creates a link between emotionality and the strictest rationality ... the salience of the single case, that is ... "ah, this happened to my friend ... this happened to my mother" and people tend to remember more and to give more value to a more personal experience in which is easier to identify with than a very banal, impersonal article, which one might read while drinking coffee and to which she feels no emotional connection. For example, when talking about the side effects of vaccines, they stick to the single case narrative. On the other hand, I think that there is a much higher use of sources, but that we stop at this, at the sources. It is thought that the sources are enough to establish an opinion. It is not so. Those who have done a little research, I have done a minimum of it, I have done the master's degree ... here one realizes that behind the research there is not only the source, but also a sample, a statistic, there are years of study. It is not that if you throw me a statistic you are right: what sample did you use? It is not that the average citizen, since he relies on a source, can thus legitimize an opinion. I do not agree. There is a necessary reference to the competence, which is not knowledge, that is, if a doctor talks to me about sources and tells me that he has read several scientific articles, it is not the same as if I do, because I am not a doctor. I didn't follow the vaccine testing process, I don't know how the samples are selected, I don't know how the control group is done ... I don't know a whole series of steps ... and they don't have the same value. Indeed, the source becomes a negative tool, because through the sources people feel competent, but they are not. (...) If you don't have a method for reading those articles, you read them badly, or you read them as you want to read them, using a self-confirming bias of the beliefs you already have. Everyone reads what they want to read. Social psychology ... you know. How are you reading it? As a person who has an anxiety about that topic? What am I looking for when I read? The scientist asks these questions ... and the citizen? Am I free from confirming my prejudices? Science in the hands of the multitude risks becoming mush (L., FG_1).</p>		
	<p>There is a world of disinformation. I realize that scientific information is pressing, but it is difficult for normal people ... it is also difficult to understand how to find the sources. (P., FG_1)</p>		
	<p>There are the famous medical protocols. When medicine has to relate to the person, to the consequences a watertight container. If someone speaks to you of a hand, he speaks of a hand. He can't talk to you about the foot. There is no discourse on the whole person, on the soul. Science, in surgery, does not take into account the person. Science is lacking from a human point of view. (P., FG_1)</p>		

	<p>With all these social networks it is easier to be informed, but without any certainty about what we read, without any scientific knowledge. I see the source, it seems reliable, I read it. Then from there I move on to more and more and then I get lost in the sea of information. So, I try to go back and what I get is that I have a lot of doubts. It's just a superficial thing, it's not that I really have a scientific knowledge of various things, I have a bit of knowledge on some things, on my sector, less on others ... I find it to be an ocean of notions put out there (S. FG_2).</p>		
ED	<p>I can talk about my experience during linguistic high school: obviously full of girls... very intelligent. In general, we wanted to discuss issues with the teachers, only they didn't want to because they had to follow the program. They didn't want to discuss how to read the articles. In my opinion, adding an hour on how to use the tools... could be a good way to understand. (T., FG_2)</p>		

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

4.3.2. Results on Education

The results obtained by education are presented below:

- **Parents**

The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings respondents report that by participating in this activity they benefit from the research results, particularly on issues of education and prevention of gender-based violence. Their participation in the discussions increases the scientific knowledge of the participants, encourages them to be curious, increases their knowledge of scientific vocabulary, and motivates people to transform their environment. Family members who were not used to participating in scientific activities beforehand reported that: Science helps them to improve their health and their environment, improve in their work activities and motivates some of their children to want to become scientists. However, they find it difficult to know where to get information about science and how to differentiate science from non-science

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Table 4.15. Results of the parents on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i>
TD* TraTns	I Maria: It is different. I find it very different. I don't know how to explain it to you. In the scientific dialogic gatherings, there is more information. Everyone can contribute things that others have missed. It is not a single topic. It seems to me that in the Dialogic Gathering, the topic is more extensive.	I Maria: Of course, all citizens may not have scientific knowledge, but they know that things concern them scientifically, don't they? And they have ideas. (...) The European Union is working on this issue, so that people can have knowledge. Well, to have knowledge and to be able to participate in each of its measures.	I Maria: Every year, there are programs such as "Pint and Science", and we participate (Scientific Dialogic Gathering Group). We participate, and we contact them so that they can give us talks. That's what I was telling you before. And the thing about the moon, the stars and this, they put a telescope here in the palm tree and many people came.
	I Maria: I went to see quantum science topics. Quantum science explains that you can be in two places at the same time, isn't it very curious? You're here on earth, and you can be in space, right? And that's what they're applying... The scientist came afterwards to explain it to the people we went to see. (...) Now I understand the word, but when it turns up, I assimilate it, and I search for it. If a scientist comes to explain something, I'll remember something, but well, I'll keep the word that I didn't know before.		
	I Francisca: I think there is an interest. When we talk about climate change and all this, we are more agile to understand because everyone is involved. We know, and they tell us things, researchers who have worked here and there. I think more people than me don't understand enough either.		

	<p>I Maria: You have more references and if you are not very convinced, you are curious enough to go and look for it, and if you are not, then you are curious enough to look for it, and if you are not, then look, he is telling the absolute truth and that's it. Of course, he has more curiosity (she talks about the scientific gatherings).</p>	<p>have very much implemented R&D . My eldest son has done a lot of things with the company, from robotics to technology. At the beginning it was very much focused on individuals for the children of the workers</p>	
	<p>FG4 Silvia: Science helps me to create new recipes, because my daughter has an allergy problem.</p>		
		<p>as an incentive and many times the children of the workers have obtained scholarships. They also work with high schools.</p>	
	<p>FG4 Esther: I am in a community of moms, because my son has a problem. We talk and look at different ways to solve the problem. Moms say: look, this doctor has posted such and such a thing. Of course I participate, because I read it, I study it and I go to my child's family doctor and I say: look, this is what this is. Is this good for me or is this not good for me? Of course, it is something of yours that makes me involve you.</p>		
	<p>FG3 Angela: I work as a nursing assistant in a psychiatric center and many times we attend conferences related to the patient, to the workers or to the educators. The medical teams or psychologists are the ones who can give us some kind of tools to be able to better address the situations.</p>		
	<p>FG3 Bianca: The teacher who had our children started some talks about women scientists' projects for children, and now for example my daughter is following this path.</p>		
<p>ED*</p>	<p>FG4 Silvia: They (Specialists) told me that they will encourage my daughter's creativity and her desire to know, but of course I search and I can't find a way to encourage it.</p>		
	<p>FG3 Nerea: So where can I find this information and that it is real?</p>		

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- **Teachers**

The teachers interviewed in the focus groups carried out by the University of Helsinki on the topic a) How citizens benefit from scientific research muestran: On the one hand, the focus groups of the control group: Complex question. Need to focus on what we mean by science. And why are we getting the public involved? There are differences – for example between hard and soft science. Some science, such as medicine, has a human practical value. People can see the benefit. Social media is like that expression a stick has two ends! It provides easy access. People can access and put their views out there. Also for scientists it can be a help. But also how scientist are exposed to the public through it. They need training on this. Scientists are not used to this.

In the case of the experimental focus groups show that: Need to employ proper language to communicate. Academics and teachers sometimes are not good at this. We as teachers may need to change our mind shift. Should we deepen partnerships? I am working on Finnish Education export but the business community do not understand some of the language around this. I need to be careful on not take a normative approach. Importance of sharing resources My interaction and use of social media is limited. I am not sure it is always that useful.

In the case of teachers, in relation to the Scientific Dialogic Gatherings and interviewed by University of Barcelona, it also helps them be trained in the latest scientific evidence on education and gender, making them more enthusiastic and more confident in their work. These social benefits cause the participants in the scientific dialogues to get involved in research through congresses and doctoral theses, which helps to broaden scientific knowledge, especially in education. Concerning the political field, this is a topic that is more distant from the people interviewed. However, they mention how applying science in their associations and schools could increase the knowledge of policies on scientific issues and that the administration supports their initiatives.

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Table 4.16. Results of the teachers on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors)</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i>
TD*	FG1 Miguel: 150 people changed a lot in each session, so I think there have been a lot of people who were with their ideas, talking with themselves based on what they heard, which I believe to be very transformative.	FG1 Lucia: At the beginning of the trimester we do many meetings for new teachers and always there we invite families and the truth is that when parents feel that they are doing training as teachers is that you are empowered and that gives them validity, that that connection is empathy lasts us for the whole course and then it is already word of mouth. (These meetings are organised with the education administration)	FG2 Juan: I wanted to do my thesis many years ago and I abandoned it due to lack of motivation. Now I have taken it up again with full motivation, since I am in the Seminary. Personally, I am more and more curious and I don't believe anything anymore, I try to look for them, in fact we have also been doing pedagogical gatherings for teachers for two years, which also has a great impact.
TraTns	FG1 Antonia: another colleague who connected with the snog because she had a young daughter and this issue also concerned her now with the confinement.		
	FG2 Emilio: Now that I find it difficult to imagine another format of access to scientific literature, after reading it and then understanding it and being able to transfer it to the classroom. (He is talking about the Dialogic Scientific Gatherings).		

	<p>FG1 Sara: It is thanks to the reading of scientific articles that the dialogues arise. The big difference that I see with other meetings is what we read and how we work on it in the meeting. Then we can guarantee training in scientific evidence and we see the impact on so many people who have signed up, who are excited about what we read and how we do it, that there is sure to be a transformation.</p>		<p>FG2 Emilio: Some people from the seminar have encouraged us to participate in international research congresses such as CIMIE, for example, we can participate in them and each time we have understood how to make small contributions and some of us have been able to make some contributions from the classroom with all humility. Now, as with Juan with the thesis and, also, I am encouraged to participate in meetings with some people to start participating in science and, moreover, with the Sappho and Adhayana platforms.</p>
	<p>FG1: Marta: Well, it has helped me to be able to transfer scientific evidence to my place of work at the centre, to analyse what we were doing and what we were not doing in terms of scientific evidence and to improve this linkage of applying scientific evidence in education. So it has a direct impact on me. You really know in the centre what you are doing that is evidenced, and we still have things that are being done that are not evidenced. At least we have marked out the path that we need to follow to give the best education to students.</p>		
	<p>FG1 Miguel: I think it has helped both those of us who participated and the centres where we work to bring ideas that we could not have, that we could only transfer from the evidence. I am thinking about many of the articles and there are many things, but one of the things that happened, for example in our case is that after Gathering on Ausubel, we held an Ausubel Gatherings between two cloisters online from the same population, who were interested in sharing this type of evidence and I think that this has happened in many cases.</p>		
	<p>FG1 Raquel: about the impact on professional life in addition to what you say comes from the impact on the student body that is making it brutal and on the families. I am also very impressed by how this has transformed our staff room. And not just in the staff room of the high school where we work, but I dare say in the professional culture in Asturias. You often hear talk about whether this is evidence-based. The discussions are extended, as Miguel also said, beyond the discussions we used to have. That is, at the national level, within the Institute or within Asturias. In our seminar, topics or ideas that had been dealt with within the discussion groups came out, and this is a good thing, because it has an important impact. I would also like to add the impact that this cycle of gatherings has had on me personally, the satisfaction that this cycle of discussions has had on me as a professional, which is that I feel much more satisfied in terms of professional ethics and now I am developing this scientific culture among my colleagues and families.</p>		
ED*			

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*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

- **Students**

The focus groups of the students have allowed us to find out: benefits from the social impact such as research in education can create more equal opportunities for some children (e.g., coming from working families) and research in education might better support an individual on their everyday decisions and to decide which information they can trust or not. However, aparece algunas dificultades para que haya un beneficio pleno como : Research in education is conducted but not implemented in real life education so citizens do not get to benefit from that, Citizens do not have access to research because they do not have the right tools (e.g., databases to give them access to scientific papers), and/or time and motivation to study so much. Moreover, most scientific papers are written in English and not all people can read/ understand English. Likewise, It appear also that Citizens are sceptical about science and whether research is taking place to help society or for the purpose of profit, and citizens would benefit more from scientific research in education if research involved more actively the students and took into account real life education.

In relation to the benefits of policy impact respondents have shown a transformative dimension, namely that research in education can inform policies and therefore support citizens to make important decisions such as whether a child should go to a school for special needs education. TThey will also note an exclusionary Dimension, exactamente es Policies do not take into account the research in education.

The people interviewed in relation to the Benefits from scientific impact pointed out that research in education support a society to move forward as Transformative Dimension, while they pointed out that research in education should take more into account the students, teachers and rea life education instead of focusing only in publishing papers for the benefit of research. Real life education should benefit from research and vice versa as exclusionary dimensión.

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Table 4.17. Results of the students on TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research.

TOPIC a) How citizens' benefit from scientific research			
	<i>Benefits from social impact (i.e. direct benefits for social actors</i>	<i>Benefits from political impact (i.e. evidence-based policies which have led to benefits for social actors);</i>	<i>Benefits from scientific impact (i.e. scientific research which has contributed to the advancement of science with social impact).</i>
TD*	<p>Yara: Yes, I think what I started thinking about was the [dutch word] we have it in the Netherlands and as a researcher I do believe that research is important for citizens and that it can improve our lives. For example, the [dutch word] I know that from research, teachers in primary education are often like prejudiced by how they see children. For example, they have met their parents and they've seen their report cards from previous years and they often have like some kind of image about the child and his capabilities. And in the Netherlands, we have this [dutch word] that was designed by educational researchers that kind of measures somewhat objectively what the child can do and what level of education is most suited for the child. And it's often the case, if I am correct, that the teachers estimate it lower for some children for example from working class families. Then the [dutch word] will show. So, due to this test, we can create more equal opportunities somehow for these children. So, I think that is one of what research can do to give us a more objective measure of for example an education of what someone can do.</p>	<p>Julia: I was thinking about the corona crisis. Because of the scientific research that is done we know that social distancing works and that vaccinations can help and that is what I hope policy makers use to make like really big decisions about everyone in the country. So, if you don't have scientific knowledge, you don't have anything to... how to say it? You don't know what to do, I think. It's a lot of situations really important and on an individual level you have to like to decide whether a child has to go to a special needs education or not, then you have to base that on test that are valid and on scientific research that it's better for a kid to do that because it has a lot of</p>	<p>Lucas: I think research is the base for societies to move forward. Cause I think if they do no research, it kind of stops. And I think it's also important for, like, countries and, like, the societies within the countries to move forward, because if for example would stop doing research now, we would just, like, stay the way it is right now.</p>

		<p>consequences for someone, so I think that it's really important.</p>	
	<p>Julia: [...] what I was thinking about is that a lot of decisions that are made that have a big impact on the whole society and on a person on an individual level... well, when it's like based on scientific research you have a lot more certainty that you make the right decision instead of looking at opinions or... basing it on something else than scientific study. [...] personally, I found scientific research really important for me to decide what knowledge I have to take seriously and what knowledge I don't. So, I think that's the base</p>		
<p>ED*</p>	<p>Lucas: I think school education in Germany hasn't really changed in recent decades or there have been just very minor changes. So, I think when it comes to education in primary and secondary school, I think there is less research implemented. I think there is research done but there is less research implemented than for example in university studies. [...]So, I think there need to be more things implemented.</p>		<p>Mateo: I think in research, we are like in our bubble, and we need to, to publish in journals and this kind of thing, but this journal, is not, they are not in their real life. They don't read, for example, for this reason, I think Facebook, Instagram, I don't know, why this kind of stuff could help not only in papers, papers in journals, it's very important [...]</p>
	<p>Mateo: I don't want to be negative in this regard, but, I really think that science, scientific research is not reaching the citizens. Why I tell, why I tell this? Because, honestly, I think we are right now in a moment in which we, we believe what WE [emphasis] want to believe. [...] So, I think right now science is not (...) getting</p>	<p>Eleni: So at least in my department, mathematics, a lot of research happened for sure. But the policy was not really interest[ed] in research. So, there is the people</p>	<p>Anika: Yeah, because it's way easier to just talk about school and how it all takes place. But when you actually</p>

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	<p>to reach normal people. Besides, I think science is not in, for example, in, in apps for young people are on in these types of things. So, it's difficult to reach young people if you are not using in their media, the correct media. So, I think there are several factors that are getting the things more difficult for, for science to reach people.</p>	<p>who design curriculum and the design cool material, but [...] this material never reached the school classroom. So, another example: it was an idea some years ago that using technology in the classroom benefit the students. Good. So, they gave to all the first-year students, elementary school, if I remember correctly, some small laptops. Okay, the students got the laptops [but] no use, after that. [...] Teachers were not really educated on how to use these laptops in their classrooms. So, there is research on that. And for sure, there is literature on how to use a technology in your mathematical classroom, for example, but the teachers never really came into touch with a say, a literature. So, there is a gap.</p>	<p>come to a class, take a look yourself, you can see that it's really easy to say, "oh, yeah, they should just be more in interaction with all the kids. And it's not that hard" until you're in the class. And you can see it yourself that it's not that easy, as it's, as it said.</p>
	<p>Anika: Yeah, I think it's also because of the accessibility to the scientific research. Because when you study, at RUG, it's really easy to use Smartcat [a database], and to look up what you want to look up. But when you don't study at RUG or at any other school like that, it's not that easy to get the right information, or how do you get? How do you know if it's really true or not? And people these days, are questioning everything. [...] And it's, it's not easy to read for most of the time. Or it's in English, which can also be...[difficult] [...] or that you're not motivated to read it? Because it's too difficult.</p>	<p>Second, I don't, at least the teachers in Greece are not that young. [...] So, they were not really interested in learning something new, I apply something more</p>	<p>Moderator: Yeah. So, you think it should work both ways. So maybe the scientists should also go into the classroom? And, also the evidence should come into the classroom? So, it's two ways to it? Is that correct? Anika Yeah, exactly.</p>
	<p>Sophie: I think that we are very biased. From, from, from, the science, I think that there is a lot of good science. There's also a lot of bad science because, for example, publication by though a lot of research that is done, we never read. And I think like the media is really biased because they only publish what they want, what is good in their opinion. And there is also a lot researchers, there are only done to research because it's for their own benefits. And it's foreign and regions to earn money have to get money for their own... [profit] [...]. And I think with us, like a pure researcher, and that really wants to find a true, it's always good, and we can all benefit. And we can all benefit from it.</p>	<p>[...]and a problem is that most resources in English, okay, it's not in Greek. The language is an issue. [...] Most of the research is done in English. So, I think only countries that have as their primary language, English, benefit from all the research done. [...] I don't think language is a problem is that governments don't put enough stress into their teaching associations or whatever to get better. [...] there's there wouldn't be point of having research and education, and it just being published in, in articles, like Mateo said</p>	
	<p>Emma: And I just think that as a citizen, it is important to always maintain the critical view. Also, on media, because there's a lot of, like Sophie says, bias and framing. [...] So, my point is always remain a critical view on science, for example, medical science, and what the media tells you, you can do research yourself.</p>		
	<p>Mateo: So, in my, in my, in my opinion, at least in Spain, education is not taking into account a lot of things regarding to science. And for this reason, the students don't understand a lot of things that they, they all day, all of this happening a in our in our life</p>		
	<p>Anika: I think you have to make the students responsible as well, so that they feel part of what they're doing. Because otherwise it's there, it's just talking about not talking with and I think that's is as well with topics like science, or in general. As long as you're still talking about it, it's not going to be part of what they get, or</p>		

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	<p>it's it will stay far away in that way. So, I think it really helps to interact with the topics that they're doing, and that they feel they can change something as well.</p> <p>Assistant Moderator: What you mean is that people would benefit more from scientific research on education, if we actually included also the points of view of our students and the students in the research... Is that what you are saying?</p> <p>Anika: Yeah, exactly</p>	<p>earlier, if it doesn't get practiced, and the students, the citizens benefit from it. There is no like that it's you know, we spend so much money on research that at the end, is not being used.</p>	
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*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

4.4. Conclusions of the Focus Groups: TOPIC a) How citizens benefit from scientific research

Detailed findings by domain, gender and education are shown below.

4.4.1. Conclusions on Gender

The results obtained by gender are presented below:

- **Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group**

- Respondents reported a variety of ways through which citizens benefit from scientific research, such as improved medical treatments, improved health information, access to scientific information for educational purposes. Respondents also used scientific information as part of their advocacy efforts on behalf their ethnic community and patient group. The development of Covid-19 vaccines and the improved understanding of gender and ethnic differences in Covid-19 were the most significant example of scientific impact.
- Respondents also provided examples of the barriers that prevent citizens from benefiting from scientific research. These included a language barrier for people whose first language is not English, the level of education, ethnicity for people who belong to ethnic minorities, gender as women were historically excluded or underrepresented in science as participants or researchers, and a lack of funding to take scientific evidence into practice in state schools.
- Many participants described becoming aware of the impact of scientific research via social media. Participants of younger ages appeared to rely on social media more often than participants of older ages. Importantly, the Covid-19 pandemic has led to the use of Zoom and Teams by community activists for connecting communities with scientists internationally.
- Respondents discussed the need to acknowledge that that different generations get their information in different ways and agreed about the importance of social media and other digital information. Respondents acknowledged that for many citizens there could be a barrier to accessing scientific research digitally. Language appeared to be another important barrier. This included both people whose first language wasn't English and people who did not understand scientific language. One respondent suggested that getting rid of the terms "science" could help engage citizens in science. One responded acknowledge a lack of interest in scientific research among the younger generation.
- Based on their personal experience, respondents recollected and discussed a wide range of awareness-raising initiatives succeeding at engaging citizens in scientific participation. These included various university outreach activities, Open Days, Science Festivals, Women in Science Days, Science Museums, popular science

shows, Citizen Science websites, online lectures and talks, and numerous individual projects that sought to involve citizens as public contributors.

- Although participants spoke of such initiatives and their experiences rather enthusiastically, there was an agreement that people who participated in them were often the same type of people, or “the usual suspects”. Participants acknowledged a challenge in getting involved those people who are excluded from science or do not show much interest in science. The most salient barrier to widening participation was perceived to be a lack of plain English summary of research.
- The majority of participants believed that Open Access was useful and they gave examples of accessing Open Access journals and articles. However, participants agreed that Open Access alone was not sufficient because the overwhelming majority of citizens would not understand scientific terms and jargon and would find the amount of information overwhelming.
- Although participants acknowledged the importance of awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences, they were able to provide only a limited number of examples. In particular, these included actions by local authorities, universities, and professional associations. One participant also mentioned the adverse effects of such actions, namely pressure on women to participate in such actions.
- Participants recollected only a few policies that promote awareness-raising actions and citizen engagement in science. These concerned government policies to diversify data science and promote citizen involvement in research in the National Health Service.

- **Member of LGBTQI group**

Benefits from social impact

- Although is not common for some participants, it is perceived that social media have become a place where there are more content related to activism, studies and statistics.
- Participants still do not recognize social media as a well-used platform for research dissemination purposes.
- It was mentioned that social media may boost scientific research due to the conversations running through different timelines and platforms. In this sense, they are perceived as an input for researchers about the topics that interest social media users and population in general, and which could result in new researches or studies.
- In addition to the use of social media for research dissemination purposes, participants consider very important to teach people how to identify verified content from fake news. In this sense, teaching people critical thinking was

mentioned as one of the challenges in social media era. In this line, Education is a key element.

- Studies in areas such as language are well received and considered important for today's social challenges when it comes to LGBT issues, Gender Equality and Gender Studies.
- Science and scientific research are perceived as two key fields in which other areas, such as politics, rely on to address current social challenges. According to participants, they can help to make transformations that are needed nowadays.
- Science, scientific research and academia are considered of high value for society.
- For participants, it is important to make visible the contributions made for other Social Sciences, like Political Sciences, in a context in which the impact of Science and Scientific research is highly measured in terms of commercialization.
- It is perceived that Science and Academia is an elitist world, with studies and researches produced only for a reduced number of people. In this sense, participants believe that society in general needs to have more access to scientific results, but it is important to disseminate these results through an easy language.

Benefits from political impact

- Public policies can help to address societal challenges like salary differences between men and women.
- Participants found important and necessary to be part of studies in order to be more visible when it comes to public policies.
- Taking the example of the study on feminine and masculine language, participants believe that science can help politics to take these issues into consideration.

Benefits from scientific impact

- Scientific research has a validation that allows it to be accepted by society. And this is also helpful when it comes to talk about social movements.
- Participants believe that Science and Scientific research must occupy as much space as possible, in order to prevent fake news or not verified information to spread and reaching the population in general.
- Since social media is a place where people spend a lot of their time, Scientific Research should use them in order to disseminate results.
- The only way to foster more Scientific Research is through Scientific Research. In this sense, studies, researches and publications have a very important role.

● **Women (including Young women) from a women's group**

Benefits from social impact, Benefits from political impact, and Benefits from scientific impact

- The relationship with science of our participants is informed by both their daily life experiences — even those that pass through the bodies (e.g., a disease) — and their interest and curiosity towards scientific research, in particular when they are involved in political activism.

- Participants showed a different degree of awareness in relation to the issues addressed during focus groups. Particularly discussed among the various topics was that related to the impact of scientific research on their daily lives.
- Most of the participants are active to disseminate scientific results related to gender in their personal/professional networks or in those linked to "Casa delle donne". For this reason, they underline more "benefits from social impact" than "benefits from political impact" or "scientific impact".
- We report data for all the topics (a, b, c, d), except for topic e). However, some of them were interested in understanding more those European policies and projects that foster the dialogue between "science and society".
- Their interventions focused more on "the transformative dimension", but they were able to highlight both the obstacles to a full participation of citizens to science and the possible risks inherent to science communication.
- They made some suggestions about possible activities with the aim at favouring the dialogue between "science and society".
- During focus groups people fully participated in the discussion. Even if some of them were not familiar with some specific topics, they were interested in understanding more, asking questions about the results that we proposed in the form of stimuli. In this sense, the focus groups increased participants' awareness about the impact of scientific research.
- However, we observed a different degree of elaboration of our stimuli due to the different participants' socio-economic backgrounds and jobs. Our role, as researchers, was to constantly support those people who potentially could be in an uncomfortable condition during the focus group.

4.4.2. Conclusion on Education

The results obtained by gender are presented below:

- **Parents and Teachers**

Benefits from social impact

- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings encourages people to be curious, to increase the knowledge of scientific vocabulary and provides the motivation for people to transform their environment.
- Participating in Scientific Dialogic Gathering increases the awareness and interest about science results and their impact in both people involved and their environment.
- The teacher's participants in Scientific Dialogic Gatherings on education and gender boost to be trained in the latest scientific evidence, more enthusiastic, empowered teachers and more confident in their work.
- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings improve the educational practices of the teachers.
- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings can get involved in research through scientific congress and doctoral theses.
- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings can boost participants to make up new scientific events in associations, schools and other social movements.

- Knowing more science about education and gender offers argumentative tools to family members.
- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings with participating family members encouraged them to attend and to promote other scientific events (gatherings, talks or conferences) in the associations/schools.
- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings encourage teachers to make new scientific activities to other teachers and inside their school.
- Improve the atmosphere among teachers of the same school when they participate in these gatherings.
- Applying scientific evidence in the educational practices at the school increases family participation in the school or in other teachers' seminars.
- La ciencia de la salud tiene un gran impacto social, especialmente en las personas con problemas de salud.
- Occasional activities organised by schools or families may have an impact on or benefit some of the children and their families.

Benefits from political impact

- The participation in scientific events encourages people to know more about policies concerning science.
- The administration supports educational talks/conferences based on science.
- Companies' R&D policies can have a social impact on the families of their employees and on the educational establishments with which they are involved.

Benefits from scientific impact

- The Scientific Dialogic Gatherings can get involved in research through scientific congress, research process and doctoral theses.
- Increases the desire to be a scientist among the students (boys and girls) who participate in the Dialogic Gatherings.

● **Students**

Benefits from social impact

Transformative Dimension

- Research in education can create more equal opportunities for some children, e.g., coming from working families
- Research in education might better support an individual on their everyday decisions and to decide which information they can trust or not.

Exclusionary Dimension

- Research in education is conducted but not implemented in real life education so citizens do not get to benefit from that.
- Citizens do not have access to research because they do not have the right tools (e.g., databases to give them access to scientific papers), and/or time and motivation to

study so much. Moreover, most scientific papers are written in English and not all people can read/ understand English.

- Citizens are sceptical about science and whether a research is taking place to help society or for the purpose of profit. Additionally, they do not trust the media which is usually the source from which they are being informed about research.
- Citizens would benefit more from scientific research in education if research involved more actively the students and took into account real life education.

Benefits from political impact

Transformative Dimension

- Research in education can inform policies and therefore support citizens to make important decisions such as whether a child should go to a school for special needs education.

Exclusionary Dimension

- Policies do not take into account the research in education.

Benefits from scientific impact

Transformative Dimension

- Research in education support a society to move forward.

Exclusionary Dimension

- Research in education should take more into account the students, teachers and real life education instead of focusing only in publishing papers for the benefit of research. Real life education should benefit from research and vice versa.

5. SURVEY

5.1. Overview

The data from the survey provide us with valuable information to meet the objective of this report on the use of statistical data. Specifically, in ALLINTERACT survey, European citizens were surveyed in order to gather evidence for O1, but also for O2, O3 and O4. This report contains the main results for O1 “To identify in both, face to face interactions and social media interactions, how societal actors, including young citizens and vulnerable groups, benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education”. The exploitation of the data was divided into 5 blocks. A first block addressed the sociodemographic questions; a second block focused on questions related to education, a third block about gender questions and two final blocks with the analysis of the associations for education and gender.

5.2. Methodology

European citizens were surveyed in order to gather evidence for O1, but also for O2, O3 and O4, following what was established in the GA.

5.2.1. Survey technical sheet

SAMPLE

The survey was addressed to EU residents over the age of 16. Therefore, the total universe are residents in the 13 countries covered aged 16 and over. The final sample is constituted by the valid responses of 7507 individuals, distributed as follows:

- North of Europe
 - o Germany: 1000 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,10\%$)
 - o Finland: 703 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,70\%$)
 - o Ireland: 208 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 6,80\%$)
- Central Europe
 - o France: 1011 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,08\%$)
 - o Netherlands: 686 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,74\%$)
 - o Luxembourg: 200 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 6,93\%$)
- Southern Europe
 - o Spain: 999 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,10\%$)
 - o Portugal: 705 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,69\%$)
 - o Italy: 203 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 6,88\%$)
 - o Cyprus: 200 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 6,93\%$)
- Eastern Europe
 - o Romania: 693 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,72\%$)
 - o Slovak Republic: 694 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 3,72\%$)
 - o Croatia: 205 responses (Sampling error: $\pm 6,84\%$)

This way, the total sample was 7.507 individuals with a sampling error of $\pm 1,13\%$ for a confidence interval of 95.5% (2 sigma) and under the assumption of maximum uncertainty (where $P=Q=50\%$). The sample for each country was distributed in a proportional way by gender and age. Sampling weights were calculated

METHODOLOGY

A multichannel methodology was used to carry out the study, the most common being the survey online (CAWI methodology). The computer-assisted telephone survey (CATI methodology) has been used mainly in Luxembourg, where a panel was not available to guarantee a correct representativeness of the simple. The programming and validation of the questionnaire has been carried out by the subcontracted company UTE BILENDI-OPINOMETRE, as well as the supervision, recording, debugging, validation and creation of the database:

The company BILENDI has various systems of control that allow, among others, to avoid incorrect answers, as well as the control and verification of the speeds in all the answers. This system allows continuous surveillance and the blocking of any panelist if they provide useless information. Email accounts are for single use. In summary, the main security measures to guarantee the quality of the data obtained have been the following:

- Panel 100% *double opt-in*.
- Three "*strikes policy*": a three-strike policy was maintained for participants who respond too quickly or provide inadequate responses.
- Duplication technologies that have guaranteed that each participant responds only once
- A system that ensures panelist location IP addresses are validated.
- Without indiscriminate selection (*river sampling*).

All participants receive on average up to 10 survey invitations based on target group allocation, with rigorous control of the number of invitations sent for each individual to avoid over- or under-use.

5.2.2. Design of the questionnaire

UB, in collaboration with the KMC coordinator and UOXF, developed the questions to address topics (a-d) for both gender and education, considering all suggestions from different partners. Three sources of information were used in the development of the survey: 1) the literature review, 2) the Focus Groups and 3) the Social Media Analytics.

The questionnaire included 59 questions distributed in 6 sections:

- Section 1: This block is focused on topic a "How citizens' benefit from scientific research" and is constituted by 10 questions
- Section 2: This section is related to topic b "Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research" and contained 4 questions

- Section 3: This section is referred to topic c “Awareness-raising initiatives succeeding at engaging citizens in scientific participation, including the Open Access movement” and included 9 questions
- Section 4: This section aims to respond to topic d “Awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in sciences” and is formed by 13 questions
- Section 5: This section was added in order to explore how citizens responses vary (or not) as a response to interactions with science. This way it includes 8 questions about different ways in which citizens can interact with science and scientific research.
- Demographics: The final section collected information about demographic details and included 15 questions.

The master version was translated into the country languages by a professional translator which is familiar with survey work and then rechecked by members of the team and/or a second translation firm. The questionnaire had an approximate duration of between 25 and 32 minutes.

5.3. Section 1 - Sociodemographic questions

The total sample is 7507 cases, whose distribution by gender, as shown in the table below, shows 51.1% of women and 48.9% of men.

Table 1. Distribution by gender.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Wome n	3839	51,1	51,1	51,1
Men	3668	48,9	48,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The highest proportion of cases is found in the 35 to 49 age group, with 31.8%, followed by the 50 to 60 age group with 25.5%. We will pay special attention to young citizens as a group of particular interest, as reflected in objective one. Young people between 16 and 34 account for 24.6%, with the youngest (16 to 24 years) accounting for 7.8%.

Table 2. Distribution by age.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
16-24	582	7,8	7,8	7,8
25-34	1261	16,8	16,8	24,6
35-49	2385	31,8	31,8	56,3
50-64	1917	25,5	25,5	81,9
+65	1362	18,1	18,1	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The distribution of the sample by country shows how Germany, Spain and France are the most represented with 13,3% the first two countries and with 13,5% the third one. That means the 40,1% of the total sample.

Table 3. Distribution by country.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Germany	1000	13,3	13,3	13,3
Cyprus	200	2,7	2,7	16,0

Croatia	205	2,7	2,7	18,7
Slovakia	694	9,2	9,2	28,0
Spain	999	13,3	13,3	41,3
Finland	703	9,4	9,4	50,6
France	1011	13,5	13,5	64,1
Ireland	208	2,8	2,8	66,9
Italy	203	2,7	2,7	69,6
Luxemburg	200	2,7	2,7	72,2
Netherlands	686	9,1	9,1	81,4
Portugal	705	9,4	9,4	90,8
Romania	693	9,2	9,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The level of education indicates a low percentage of the population with slighter than lower secondary education, 18.6%. This same percentage in the case of the mother's level of studies increases to 51.7%. In turn, the percentage of the population with a master's degree or doctorate is 16.8%. The mother's level of studies is much lower in this case, at 6.1%. The highest percentage is found among those with upper secondary education, at 25.2%.

Indicate the highest course or educational level you have completed

Table 4. Distribution by level of education.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulated %
Educational development during early childhood or preschool education	100	1,3	1,3	1,3
Basic education	303	4,0	4,0	5,4
Lower secondary education	1000	13,3	13,3	18,7
Upper secondary education	1895	25,2	25,2	43,9
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	406	5,4	5,4	49,3
Short cycle tertiary education	446	5,9	5,9	55,3
Bachelor's degree or equivalent	1709	22,8	22,8	78,0
Master or equivalent	1080	14,4	14,4	92,4
Doctorate or equivalent	183	2,4	2,4	94,9
I do not know	221	2,9	2,9	97,8
Prefer not to answer	164	2,2	2,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

What level of education does (or did) your mother have?

Table 5. Distribution by mother's level of education.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Educational development during early childhood or preschool education	230	3,1	3,1	3,1
Basic education	2134	28,4	28,4	31,5
Lower secondary education	1518	20,2	20,2	51,7
Upper secondary education	1346	17,9	17,9	69,6
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	321	4,3	4,3	73,9
Short cycle tertiary education	325	4,3	4,3	78,2
Bachelor's degree or equivalent	611	8,1	8,1	86,4

Master or equivalent	357	4,8	4,8	91,1
Doctorate or equivalent	94	1,3	1,3	92,4
I do not know	407	5,4	5,4	97,8
Prefer not to answer	164	2,2	2,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The percentages for belonging to an ethnic minority group and a religious group are low, at 7% and 8.6%, respectively. Of those surveyed, 14.8% stated that at least one of their parents was born in another country. However, slightly more surprising is the percentage of people who claim to have disabilities or medical condition that limits their daily activities, reaching the 17,1%.

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group?

Table 6. Distribution by ethnic minority group.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	523	7,0	7,0	7,0
No	6439	85,8	85,8	92,7
I do not know	443	5,9	5,9	98,6
Prefer not to answer	102	1,4	1,4	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group?

Table 7. Distribution by religious minority group.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	645	8,6	8,6	8,6
No	6442	85,8	85,8	94,4
I do not know	328	4,4	4,4	98,8
Prefer not to answer	92	1,2	1,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Do you have a disability or medical condition that limits your daily activities?

Table 8. Distribution by people with disabilities.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	1284	17,1	17,1	17,1
No	5924	78,9	78,9	96,0
I do not know	194	2,6	2,6	98,6
Prefer not to answer	105	1,4	1,4	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Was one of his parents born in a foreign country

Table 9. Distribution by people whose parents were born in a foreign country.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
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Yes one of them	605	8,1	8,1	8,1
Yes, both	502	6,7	6,7	14,7
No, none of them	6213	82,8	82,8	97,5
I do not know	135	1,8	1,8	99,3
Prefer not to answer	52	,7	,7	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

In terms of employment, it is noteworthy that practically 20% of the people surveyed are retired. The level of unemployment stands at 5.8%. Also noteworthy is the 45.7% percentage of full-time employment among the participants.

What is your current employment status?

Table 10. Distribution by employment status.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Full time employee	3427	45,7	45,7	45,7
Part-time employee	637	8,5	8,5	54,1
Unemployed	438	5,8	5,8	60,0
Voluntarily unemployed	80	1,1	1,1	61,0
Student	302	4,0	4,0	65,1
Student with job	102	1,4	1,4	66,4
Retired, disabled	1478	19,7	19,7	86,1
Housewife	384	5,1	5,1	91,2
I do not know	86	1,1	1,1	92,4
Prefer not to answer	573	7,6	7,6	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Regarding employment, both in the present and the past. 21.6% of those surveyed have worked or are working in the education sector related to professions related to the education sector. Therefore, practically one out of every four persons surveyed works in education. This percentage decreases to 8.8% when referring to professions or job positions related to gender issues.

Practices (works) or has practiced (has worked in) any profession in the education sector

Table 11. Distribution by professional practices in the educational sector.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes (in the past)	1041	13,9	13,9	13,9
Yes (at the present)	577	7,7	7,7	21,6
No	5666	75,5	75,5	97,0
I do not know	145	1,9	1,9	99,0
Prefer not to answer	78	1,0	1,0	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Practices (works) or has practiced (has worked in) any profession or position in gender matters

Table 12. Distribution by professional practices in gender matters.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes (in the past)	376	5,0	5,0	5,0
Yes (at the present)	282	3,8	3,8	8,8
No	6618	88,2	88,2	96,9
I do not know	160	2,1	2,1	99,1
Prefer not to answer	71	,9	,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

30.2% of the people surveyed have a gross annual income of less than €1,043. Approximately one-third of the people surveyed have a net monthly income of at most one thousand euros.

Gross annual household income in euros

Table 13. Distribution by gross annual household income.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Less than 10562€	1202	16,0	16,0	16,0
Between 10562€ and 16043€	1069	14,2	14,2	30,3
Between 16043€ and 23.295€	1180	15,7	15,7	46,0
More than 23.295€	2654	35,4	35,4	81,3
I do not know	363	4,8	4,8	86,2
Prefer not to answer	1039	13,8	13,8	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

5.4. Section 2 – Education

This section aims to identify how citizens benefit from scientific research in education. To do so, we have structured this part of the report in 4 sections 1) scientific evidence and hoax in education (2 questions), 2) educational expectations (1 question), 3) family participation in schools (1 question) and 4) segregation and diversity (2 questions).

5.4.1. Scientific evidence and hoax in education

To analyze the impact of the interactions on the perception or recognition that respondents may have of the survey to distinguish between scientific evidence and hoax, we have introduced two phrases in the questionnaire: one of them is scientific evidence, while the other is a hoax. The sentences are:

- The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities
- The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income.

In both cases, respondents are asked if those two statements are scientific evidence and hoax, or if they do not know. The results are distributed as follows:

Table 14. Distribution of respondents' answers to the two statements related to education

The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities.			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Scientific evidence	2404	32,0	32,0
Hoax	3226	43,0	43,0
I do not know	1709	22,8	22,8
Prefer not to answer	168	2,2	2,2
Total	7507	100,0	100,0
The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Scientific evidence	4383	58,4	58,4
Hoax	1445	19,2	19,2
I do not know	1562	20,8	20,8
Prefer not to answer	117	1,6	1,6
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

On the one hand, approximately one third (32%) of the respondents think that the statement “The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities” is a scientific evidence, compared with the 43% of those who consider that it is a hoax. On the other hand, almost 6 out of 10 (58.4%) of the participants consider that the statement “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational

success for students from families with low levels of income” is scientific evidence, while 19.2% think that it is a hoax.

Figure 1. Distribution of respondents' answers to the two statements related to education

RESPONES BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

If we look closer at this data across vulnerable groups, we find that the proportion of respondents who identify scientific evidence and hoaxes varies across vulnerable groups. This way, in the statement “The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities” the proportion of respondents who identified it as a hoax ranges from 35.81% to 47.77%. The group that are most likely to identify this hoax are youth aged 16-24, followed by LGBTI+ (45.1%) and women (43.22%), compared to religious minorities (35.81%), ethnic minorities (39.01%) and people from low SES (39.85%).

Table 15. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities” across vulnerable groups

The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families.								
Schools cannot overcome inequalities								
	Woman	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES ⁷	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Scientific evidence	31,40	25,49	29,55	36,64	35,40	43,98	42,64	32,02
Hoax	43,22	45,10	47,77	40,76	39,85	39,01	35,81	42,97
I do not know	23,30	25,49	20,10	20,38	22,59	15,11	19,69	22,77
prefer not to answer	2,07	3,92	2,58	2,22	2,16	1,91	1,86	2,24

⁷ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year.

TOTAL 100,00 100,00 100,00 100,00 100,00 100,00 100,00 100,00

The following figure represents these results:

Figure 2. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities" across vulnerable groups

On the contrary, the proportion of respondents that identifies the scientific evidence ranges from 52.94% (LGBTI+) to 63.48% (ethnic minorities). In this case, ethnic and religious minorities, as well as youth aged 16-24 are more likely to identify the statement "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education" as scientific evidence, whereas women and LGBTI+ are less likely to identify this statement as scientific evidence (56.88% and 52.94%)

Table 16. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education" across vulnerable groups

The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education								
	Woman	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Scientific evidence	56,88	52,94	63,23	61,54	60,46	63,48	63,41	58,39
Hoax	19,87	15,69	15,29	18,48	17,57	20,65	18,14	19,25
I do not know	21,81	27,45	18,90	18,48	20,61	14,15	16,74	20,81
prefer not to answer	1,44	3,92	2,58	1,51	1,37	1,72	1,71	1,56
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

These results are represented in the following figure:

Figure 3. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you heard of any initiative that encourages citizen participation in science?" across vulnerable groups

Therefore, the proportion of people who identify scientific evidence and hoaxes in education varies across vulnerable groups. Youth aged 16-24 are more likely to identify which statement is scientific evidence and which is a hoax.

IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered "yes" to interaction 1 and "yes, often" and "yes, rarely" in interaction 2.

We can observe as a result of citizens' interactions with science, there is an increase in the proportion of those who think that the statement "The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities" is scientific evidence as well as in those who identify it as a hoax. This result is found generally, across all vulnerable groups and interactions with science. One hypothesis behind these results

may be that interactions with science provide citizens with skills and knowledge that made them feel more confident to answer this question. This way, as we can see, generally the percentages of people who answer that they do not know or that refuse to answer decrease more than 15%. If we look specifically at vulnerable groups, we can observe people from low SES are the group that benefits the most of interactions with science, with increments of 9.55% (interactions 1), 12.64% (interaction 2-often) and 11.35% (interaction 2-rarely) in the identification of the statement as a hoax.

To go through the findings a bit more systematically, the first interaction (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families) increases the proportion of people from all vulnerable groups who think that the statement is scientific evidence, compared with the total of respondents within the vulnerable group. This way, the percentages range from 33.33% (LGBTI+) to 51.17% (ethnic minorities). Also in this interaction, there is an increase in the proportion of women (47.12%), youth (48.73% in youth aged 16-24 and 42.86% in youth 25-34) and people from low SES (43.66%) who identify the statement as a hoax. In these three groups the proportion of those who identify the statement as a hoax is higher than the percentage of those who think it is an evidence-based statement, unlike in ethnic and religious minorities, where we can find the opposite trend. The results from the LGBTI+ community are limited by the small size of the sample (n= 12).

Regarding interaction 2, we can see that in this case, the proportion of respondents who think that the statement is scientific evidence increase in all groups except for LGBTI+ and youth aged 16-24. Also in this case, the reduced number of responses from LGBTI+ people (n=7) limits the analysis. In addition, the proportion of those who identify the statement as a hoax increase in almost all vulnerable groups. This way, among those who follow on social media someone who often publishes about science (interaction 2-often), the proportion ranges from 35.44% (religious minorities) to 54.93% (youth aged 16-24) and among those who follow someone who rarely publishes about science, from 39.71% (religious minorities) to 50.43% (youth aged 16-24). Also in this interaction, in all vulnerable groups except for ethnic and religious minorities, the proportion of people who identify the statement as a hoax is higher than the percentage of those who think it is an evidence-based statement.

Table 17. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities”, by vulnerable groups

		The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities							
		Woma n	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Scientific evidence	35,89	33,33	33,50	41,13	41,24	51,17	50,53	37,79
	Hoax	47,12	25,00	48,73	42,86	43,66	37,89	33,22	45,42
	I do not know	15,55	33,33	17,26	14,53	13,44	10,16	14,84	14,93
	Rejected	1,44	8,33	0,51	1,48	1,66	0,78	1,41	1,87
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2	Scientific evidence	36,38	14,29	28,17	37,63	42,90	52,78	53,80	35,74
	Hoax	48,56	71,43	54,93	48,08	44,89	36,81	35,44	49,04

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	I do not know	13,03	14,29	15,49	12,20	9,94	7,64	8,23	12,96
	Rejected	2,03	0,00	1,41	2,09	2,27	2,78	2,53	2,26
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Scientific evidence	38,31	14,29	28,70	40,39	40,31	44,33	45,59	36,73
	Hoax	44,60	57,14	50,43	43,35	44,38	40,21	39,71	47,33
	I do not know	15,13	28,57	19,13	13,30	14,38	13,40	13,24	14,19
	Rejected	1,96	0,00	1,74	2,96	0,94	2,06	1,47	1,75
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
	Decreases more than 15%	Increases		Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened					
	Decreases less than 15%	Increases more than 50%		Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who publishes about science... [often/rarely]					

The following figure represents the percentage of respondents within each vulnerable group who correctly identify the statement as a hoax, across all analysed interactions. This way, we can observe how in women, youth and people from low SES, all interactions with science increase the proportion of people who identify the statement as a hoax, but the impact is more accentuated among those who follow on social media someone who often publishes about science. As abovementioned, ethnic and religious minorities show different trends and the results from the LGBTI+ community are limited due to the reduced number of responses (see section 4). Finally, the impact of interactions is more visible in people from low SES and youth aged 25-34, as they are the group with higher increments in the percentages of identification of the statement as a hoax.

Figure 4. Percentage of respondents who identify the statement “The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities” as a hoax, across vulnerable groups

In addition, the differences between those who think that schools cannot overcome inequalities and those who identify the statement as a hoax follow a similar tendency across interactions. This way, the highest difference is obtained in youth 16-24 (in all interactions) and the lowest in ethnic and religious minorities.

Figure 5. Increases in the identification of the statement “The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities” as scientific evidence and hoax (primary axis) and difference between “scientific evidence” and “hoax” (secondary axis), across vulnerable groups and interactions

Regarding the evidence-based statement “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education” all interactions with science increase the proportion of people from vulnerable groups who identify the statement as scientific evidence.

In this case, we can observe that in interaction 1 (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families), the proportion of people from all vulnerable groups except for youth aged 25-34 who think that the statement is a hoax increases. In addition, the increase among those who think that the statement is a hoax is higher than the increase among those who correctly identify the statement as scientific evidence. This finding suggests that the impact of this interaction with science is more related to the promotion of self-confidence (which is associated with an increase in the percentages of “scientific evidence” and “hoax” and a decrease of “I do not know” and “prefer not to answer”), and on the contrary, it has less impact on the identification of scientific evidence and hoaxes. Nevertheless, in this interaction the proportion of people who identify the statement as evidence-based is higher than the proportion of those who think it is a hoax, across all vulnerable groups. This way, between 61.80% (women) and 68.47% (youth aged 25-34) correctly identify the statement as evidence-based. The results from the LGBTI+ community are limited by the small size of the sample (n= 12) (see section 4).

The results obtained from interaction 2 point that the frequency in which scientists post scientific content on social media has an impact in citizens’ identification of scientific evidence

and hoaxes. Thus, among citizens from vulnerable groups that follow on social media someone who often publishes about science, the proportion of identification of the scientific evidence ranges from 67.85% (women) to 72.82% (youth aged 25-34), while among those who follow someone who rarely publishes about science, from 66.21% (women) to 69.57% (youth aged 16-24). This result suggest that the most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science. Unlike interaction 1, following someone on social media who publishes about science, in general, does not increase the proportion of respondents who think that the statement is a hoax. The only exceptions in this vein are youth aged 16-24 and people from low SES, that although they also increase the proportions of respondents who think that the statement is a hoax, these increases are notably lower than the increases in respondents who correctly identify the statement.

Table 18. Distribution of respondents who answered YES to the interaction questions and answers to the question “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education”, by vulnerable groups

The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education									
		Woman	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Scientific evidence	61,80	75,00	68,02	68,47	65,71	64,84	63,25	65,57
	Hoax	22,46	0,00	16,75	18,47	21,00	21,88	19,43	19,78
	I do not know	14,88	16,67	13,20	12,56	12,24	12,50	15,90	13,65
	Rejected	0,86	8,33	2,03	0,49	1,06	0,78	1,41	1,01
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Often	Scientific evidence	67,85	85,71	66,90	72,82	71,31	71,53	70,25	70,35
	Hoax	18,61	0,00	15,49	18,47	18,47	18,06	17,72	17,74
	I do not know	13,03	0,00	16,20	7,67	8,81	9,03	10,76	11,04
	Rejected	0,51	14,29	1,41	1,05	1,42	1,39	1,27	0,87
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Scientific evidence	66,21	71,43	69,57	66,50	68,44	67,01	65,44	68,32
	Hoax	17,88	14,29	15,65	17,73	18,44	20,62	19,12	17,88
	I do not know	14,54	14,29	9,57	14,78	12,50	11,34	13,97	12,54
	Rejected	1,38	0,00	5,22	0,99	0,63	1,03	1,47	1,26
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Decreases more than 15%	Increases			Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened					
Decreases less than 15%	Increases more than 50%			Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who publishes about science... [often/rarely]					
	Increases more than 100%								

This figure represents the percentage of people across vulnerable groups and interactions that correctly identify the statement as science-based. It is important to mention that the impact of interactions with science in women, youth aged 25-34 and people from low SES is more accentuated than in the other groups. As abovementioned, the most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science.

Figure 6. Percentage of respondents who identify the statement “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education” as scientific evidence, across vulnerable groups

Finally, the following figure shows the increases in the respondents who identify the statement “Schools can overcome inequalities” as scientific evidence and in those who think it is a hoax. As abovementioned, generally the increases are higher in the identification of scientific evidence, especially when referring to interaction 2.often (following someone on social media who often publishes about science). The figure also represents the difference between the “scientific evidence” and the “hoax” responses, which is generally higher after interactions with science, pointing to the impact of interactions with science in the identification of scientific evidence in education.

Figure 7. Increases in the identification of the statement “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income and education” as scientific evidence and hoax (primary axis) and difference between “scientific evidence” and “hoax” (secondary axis), across vulnerable groups and interactions

Therefore, on the one hand interactions with science increase both, people who identify the hoax statement as a hoax and those who think it is an evidence-based statement. On the other hand, they increase the proportion of respondents who identify the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, contributing to the identification of evidence and hoaxes. People from low SES and youth aged 25-34 are the groups that benefits the most of interactions with science, with the highest increments in the identification of the hoax statement as a hoax and the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence. Following someone on social media who often publishes about science is the most effective interaction across vulnerable groups. In all vulnerable groups except for ethnic and religious minorities, the proportion of people who identify the hoax statement as a hoax is higher than the percentage of those who think it is an evidence-based statement. In the evidence-based statement the proportions of identification are generally higher than two-thirds.

5.4.2. Educational expectations

This section aims to deepen on the citizens’ perceptions about teachers’ educational expectations, and includes the following question:

- Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations.

Respondents are given the following response options: totally agree, tend to agree, totally disagree or tend to disagree.

Table 19. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations."

Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Totally disagree	276	3,7	3,7
More or less disagree	1275	17,0	20,7
More or less agree	3333	44,4	65,1
Totally agree	1296	17,3	82,3
I do not know	1277	17,0	99,3
Prefer not to answer	50	0,7	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The results show that more than half of the respondents (61.7%) agree to some extent with the affirmation that teachers who know act with high expectations.

Figure 8. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations."

RESPONSES BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

If we look closer at the data across vulnerable groups, we can observe how the proportion of people from ethnic and religious minorities, as well as youth who agree to some extent (including totally agree and more or less agree) with the question "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations" is slightly higher than the average (66.35%, 67.13% and 66.85%

respectively). Women and people from low SES obtain similar results than the average of respondents (61.34% and 61.43%), while the LGBTI+ community slightly lower percentage (50.98%).

Table 20. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you participated in any action to discuss scientific discoveries in education, in both face-to-face and online actions?"

Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minority	Religious minority	TOTAL
Totally disagree	3,93	3,92	5,15	4,52	4,62	7,07	6,20	3,68
More or less disagree	17,12	25,49	19,24	17,05	16,42	16,06	16,74	16,98
More or less agree	44,22	35,29	46,22	47,03	42,10	37,86	40,47	44,40
Totally agree	17,12	15,69	18,73	19,83	19,33	28,49	26,67	17,26
I do not know	17,06	17,65	10,14	10,55	16,86	9,56	9,46	17,01
Prefer not to answer	0,55	1,96	0,52	1,03	0,66	0,96	0,47	0,67
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This image represents how in all vulnerable groups, the proportion of people who agree to some extent (in blue colours) is significantly higher than those who disagree to some extent (in red colours). The highest difference is observed in youth 24-35 (with 21,57% who disagree and 66,85% who agree), while the smallest in the LGBTI+ with 21,57%.

Figure 9. Distribution of responses to the question “Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations” as scientific evidence, across vulnerable groups

Generally, the proportion of respondents from vulnerable groups that agree to some extent with the question “Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations” is higher than in the total of respondents. This is not the case of women and people from low SES, who get similar results than the total of respondents or the LGBTI+ who obtain lower percentages.

IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered “yes” to interaction 1 and “yes, often” and “yes, rarely” in interaction 2.

At first sight we can observe that due to interactions with science there is a general increase in all response options (“totally disagree”, “more or less disagree”, “more or less agree” and

“totally agree”), while the percentages of “I do not know” and “prefer not to answer” decrease more than 15%. One hypothesis behind these results may be that interactions with science provide citizens with skills and knowledge that made them feel more confident to answer this question. However, if we look closer to the data, we can conclude that the increase in those who agree to some extent (including totally agree and more or less agree) is higher than the increase in those who disagree to some extent (including totally disagree and more or less disagree). In this line, it is significant to point to the difference between those who agree to some extent and those who disagree to some extent across vulnerable groups and interactions. While among the total of vulnerable groups the difference between those who agree and those who disagree goes from 21.57% to 45.28%, among those who changed their mind because something happened to them or their families (interaction 1), it is comprised between 45.18% and 51.95%, among those who follow someone on social media who often publishes about science (interaction 2.often), it ranges from 42.05% to 56.33% and among when people follow on social media someone who rarely publishes about science, the difference is 39.13% to 53.69%.

To go to the results systematically, in interaction 1 the proportion of those who agree to some extent ranges from 69.00% (women) to 73.83% (ethnic minorities), and the group with the highest increase are people from low SES, with an increment of 14.84%. It is also relevant to point out that in people from ethnic minorities there is a decrease of 5.45% in those who disagree with the sentence “Teachers who know act with high expectations”.

In interaction 2, the results depend on the frequency of publication of scientific content on social media. This way, when scientific content is often shared, the percentages of those who agree to some extent with the importance of teachers’ expectations are comprised between 67.61% (people from low SES) and 74.68% (religious minorities). In this case, in all vulnerable groups there are increases of approximately 10%. If we look at the influence of interactions in those who disagree, we can see that in youth aged 16-24, ethnic minorities and religious minorities there are significant decreases of -7.64%, -15.96% and -20.01% respectively. Finally, when scientific content is rarely shared, the proportion of those who agree to some extent ranges from 66.60% (women) to 73.40% (youth aged 25-34), and the highest increase is again in people from low SES (+15.99%). Finally, due to the reduced number of responses from the LGBTI+ community (n=12, n=7 and n=7), their results have limited implications (see section 4).

Table 21. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations” across interactions by vulnerable groups

		Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve.							TOTAL
		Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	
INTERACTION 1	Totally disagree	4,61	0,00	3,55	5,42	5,59	6,25	6,71	4,26
	More or less disagree	18,91	33,33	22,34	18,72	17,37	15,63	16,25	18,55
	More or less agree	46,26	41,67	44,67	45,57	44,11	39,45	38,87	46,27
	Totally agree	22,74	16,67	26,40	24,63	26,44	34,38	32,51	23,56
	I do not know	7,29	8,33	3,05	5,17	6,50	4,30	5,30	7,20
	Rejected	0,19	0,00	0,00	0,49	0,00	0,00	0,35	0,16

	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Often	Totally disagree	5,41	14,29	5,63	5,23	9,09	7,64	6,33	4,70
	More or less disagree	17,26	0,00	16,90	17,77	16,48	11,81	12,03	17,30
	More or less agree	47,72	57,14	52,11	48,43	43,18	35,42	37,34	47,39
	Totally agree	22,34	14,29	20,42	25,44	24,43	38,19	37,34	22,87
	I do not know	7,28	0,00	4,93	3,14	6,53	5,56	6,33	7,57
	Rejected	0,00	14,29	0,00	0,00	0,28	1,39	0,63	0,17
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Totally disagree	5,30	0,00	5,22	2,96	4,38	10,31	8,09	4,28
	More or less disagree	19,65	0,00	22,61	16,75	17,81	15,46	16,18	18,37
	More or less agree	47,15	71,43	47,83	53,69	49,38	41,24	47,06	48,98
	Totally agree	19,45	28,57	19,13	19,70	21,88	27,84	22,79	20,60
	I do not know	8,25	0,00	5,22	6,40	6,56	4,12	5,15	7,48
	Rejected	0,20	0,00	0,00	0,49	0,00	1,03	0,74	0,29
	TOTAL	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Decreases more than 15%		Decreases less than 15%		Increases		Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened			
Increases more than 50%		Increases more than 100%		Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who [often/rarely] publishes about science					

The following figure presents the percentage of respondents who agree to some extent with the impact of teachers' expectations. As abovementioned, all interactions increase this percentage in all vulnerable groups and the most impactful interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science.

Figure 10. Percentages of respondents who agree to some extent with the impact of teachers' expectations, across vulnerable groups and interactions with science.

On the one hand, the following figure represents the increases in the responses of participants who agree to some extent with the impact of teachers' expectations across vulnerable groups and interactions with science. In this direction, the vulnerable group that benefits the most of interactions with science are people from low SES, who get the highest increases, followed by women. In general, the most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science.

Figure 11. Increases in the respondents who agree to some extent with the question “Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations” across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

On the other hand, the highest decreases are observed in ethnic and religious minorities who follow on social media someone who often publishes about science, with differences of -15.96% and -20.01% respectively.

Therefore, interactions with science increase all response options (including agreement and disagreement), while decrease “I do not know” and prefer not to answer”. The highest increases are found in the responses that agree to some extent with the importance of teachers' expectations (totally agree and more or less agree). The vulnerable group that benefits the most of interactions with science are people from low SES, who get the highest increases, followed by women. In general, the most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science.

5.4.3. Family participation in schools

This section includes the answers to the following question:

- Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey

Respondents are given the following response options: totally agree, tend to agree, totally disagree or tend to disagree.

More than half of the respondents (55.4%) agree to some extent (including totally agree and more or less agree) with the importance of families' participation in schools, while almost one-quarter of the respondents (24.9%) disagree to some extent with this question.

Table 22. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey"

Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Totally disagree	387	5,2	5,2
More or less disagree	1481	19,7	24,9
More or less agree	2922	38,9	63,8
Totally agree	1238	16,5	80,3
I do not know	1425	19,0	99,3
Prefer not to answer	54	0,7	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The following figure represents these results:

Figure 12. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey”

RESPONSES BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

When we look at the responses of people from vulnerable groups, we can observe that there are differences in the responses from vulnerable groups. While people from ethnic and religious minorities are more likely to agree to some extent with the importance of the participation of families in schools than the total of respondents (63.86% and 63.41% compared with 55.7%), LGBTI+ are less likely to agree (37.25%). Finally, there are not relevant differences in the responses of women, youth and people from low SES.

Table 23. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey” across vulnerable groups

Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey							
	Woman	LGBTI+	Youth	Low SES ⁸	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Totally disagree	4,98	13,73	9,28	5,31	6,12	6,12	4,96
More or less disagree	20,10	19,61	24,40	20,30	19,55	17,21	20,00
More or less agree	38,03	23,53	34,02	38,30	37,12	36,90	37,67
Totally agree	16,99	13,73	15,81	19,03	17,88	26,96	25,74
I do not know	19,27	29,41	14,95	15,86	18,71	12,05	11,01
Prefer not to answer	0,63	0,00	1,55	1,19	0,62	0,76	0,62
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

This figure presents the distribution of responses from people from vulnerable groups. In all cases, the proportion of respondents who agree to some extent (in blue colours) is notably higher than those who disagree to some extent (in red colours). In this case, the biggest difference is observed in ethnic minorities (23,33% who disagree and 63,86% who agree) and the smallest difference in the LGBTI+ community with 3,92%

⁸ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year

Figure 13. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey" across vulnerable groups

The proportion of people who agree to some extent with the importance of family participation in schools varies across vulnerable groups, ranging from 37.25% (LGBTI+) to 63.86% (ethnic minorities). In all vulnerable groups, people are more likely to agree to some extent than to disagree with the importance of family participation schools. The biggest difference is observed in ethnic minorities.

IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered "yes" to interaction 1 and "yes, often" and "yes, rarely" in interaction 2.

When we look at the results of citizens' interactions with science, we can observe that there is an increase in the proportion of those agree with that the question "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey" as well as in those who disagree. In general, this happens across all vulnerable groups and interactions with science. One hypothesis behind these results may be that interactions with science provide citizens with skills and knowledge that made them feel more confident to answer this question. This way, as we can see, generally the percentages of people who answer that they do not know or that refuse to answer decrease more than 15%.

In all vulnerable groups and interactions with science, the proportion of respondents who agree to some extent (including totally agree and ore or less agree) is higher than the proportion of those who disagree to some extent (totally disagree and more or less disagree). In addition, the difference between the percentages of those who agree and those who disagree are higher than with the total population when we introduce the impact of interactions with science. In this vein, among those who changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families (interaction 1), the proportion of those who agree to some extent ranges from 55,33% (youth 16-24) to 70,31% (ethnic minorities). In this case, the most notable increments are observed in people from low SES with 17.55%. The analysis by LGBTI+ individuals has limitations caused by the small size of the sample (n=12). Regarding interaction 2, the results point that following a scientist on social media who published scientific content has an impact on participants' respondents. Nevertheless, in this case the frequency of publication does not point to notable differences between the responses of those who follow someone who often publishes about science and those who follow someone who rarely publishes about science. Therefore, among those who follow someone on social media who often publishes about science, the proportion of those who agree to some extent with the question "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey" range from 51,41% (youth 16-24) and 72,92% (ethnic minorities) and in the case of those who follow someone who rarely publishes about science, from 53,91% (youth 16-24) to 70,10% (ethnic minorities). Also in this case, the analysis by LGBTI+ individuals has limitations caused by the small size of the sample (n=7 and n=7), more details are included in section 4.

Table 24. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey" across interactions and vulnerable groups

Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey									
		Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Totally disagree	4,70	16,67	9,64	4,93	6,04	5,08	3,89	5,28
	More or less disagree	23,42	13,33	25,89	20,44	19,94	16,80	20,14	21,22
	More or less agree	40,02	13,64	33,50	40,15	40,03	40,63	34,63	40,41
	Totally agree	22,46	3,33	21,83	25,12	24,62	29,69	32,51	22,97
	I do not know	8,93	11,76	9,14	8,37	8,91	7,03	7,42	9,49

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	Rejected	0,48	0,00	0,00	0,99	0,45	0,78	1,41	0,64
	TOTAL	100,00	28,57	100,0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Often	Totally disagree	6,26	14,29	11,97	7,32	7,67	6,25	8,86	6,26
	More or less disagree	24,03	28,57	29,58	23,00	22,44	15,28	13,92	22,35
	More or less agree	37,73	42,86	34,51	36,59	34,94	34,03	29,75	39,39
	Totally agree	22,84	0,00	16,90	24,74	26,14	38,89	41,14	23,30
	I do not know	8,80	14,29	6,34	8,36	7,95	4,86	5,06	8,35
	Rejected	0,34	0,00	0,70	0,00	0,85	0,69	1,27	0,35
	TOTAL	100,00	0	100,0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Totally disagree	4,72	14,29	7,83	3,45	4,38	2,06	2,21	4,28
	More or less disagree	22,20	14,29	24,35	24,14	23,44	18,56	25,00	22,06
	More or less agree	42,24	42,86	37,39	44,33	42,19	41,24	42,65	44,02
	Totally agree	18,47	0,00	16,52	18,72	20,63	28,87	23,53	18,76
	I do not know	12,18	28,57	13,91	8,87	9,38	9,28	5,88	10,59
	Rejected	0,20	0,00	0,00	0,49	0,00	0,00	0,74	0,29
	TOTAL	100,00	0	100,0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Decreases more than 15%	Decreases less than 15%	Increases	Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who [often/rarely] publishes about science
Increases more than 50%	Increases more than 100%		

The following figure represents the percentage of respondents who agree to some extent with the importance of family participation in schools across interactions and vulnerable groups. As abovementioned, interactions with science increase the proportion of respondents who agree in all vulnerable groups.

Figure 14. Increases in the respondents who agree to some extent with the question “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey” across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

The following figure represents the increases in the proportion of respondents of vulnerable groups who agree to some extent with the question “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey”, as a result of interactions with science. As we can observe, the group that benefits the most of all interactions with science are people from low socioeconomic status, who get the highest increases (17.55% for interaction 1, 11.06% for interaction 2-often and 14.21 for interaction 2-rarely). In general, the most effective interaction is interaction 1 (changing their mind because something happened to them or their families).

Figure 15. Increases in the respondents who agree to some extent with the question “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey” across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

We can conclude that after interactions with science, participants are more likely agree with the importance of family participation in schools. Across all vulnerable groups and interactions with science, the proportion of those who agree to some extent is higher than the proportion of those who disagree to some extent. In general, the most effective interaction is changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families. Finally, the group that is most benefitted from these interactions with science are people from low socioeconomic status, with increments in participation of approximately 18%, compared with the total of participants within their vulnerable group.

5.4.4. Segregation and diversity

This section aims to analyse respondents' identification of segregation and inclusive practices in schools and includes the following questions:

- Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning
- Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?

Regarding the first question, 31% of the respondents express that they know schools where students are separated according to their academic level, while 47.1% do not know school that separate students by academic level.

Table 25. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning"

Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes	2326	31,0	31,0
No	3534	47,1	78,1
I do not know	1581	21,1	99,1
Prefer not to answer	66	0,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The following figure show the distribution of responses:

Figure 16. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning"

As for the second question, almost 4 out of 10 of the respondents (39.6%) think that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for all students and 40.5% thinks the opposite.

Table 26. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?"

Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes	2975	39,6	39,6
No	3039	40,5	80,1
I do not know	1429	19,0	99,1
Prefer not to answer	64	0,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The following figure show the distribution of responses:

Figure 17. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?"

RESPONSES BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

When we look closer at the results of the first question (Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning) across vulnerable groups, we find that in all cases, people from vulnerable groups tend to know schools that separate students according to their academic level than the total of respondents. Ethnic and religious minorities are the groups that are more likely to know schools where students are segregated (50.10% and 45.12% respectively), while women and people from low socioeconomic status are less likely than the total of respondents (32.19% and 33.73% respectively).

Table 27. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning" across vulnerable groups

Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minority	Religious minority	TOTAL
Yes	32,19	37,25	40,72	39,18	33,73	50,10	45,12	30,98
No	46,11	41,18	45,19	44,01	44,25	34,61	37,52	47,08
I do not know	20,97	21,57	12,54	15,38	21,18	14,15	16,43	21,06
Prefer not to answer	0,73	0,00	1,55	1,43	0,84	1,15	0,93	0,88
	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure represents these results:

Figure 18. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning" across vulnerable groups

In the same line, the analysis of the second question (Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students) points to similar results. Vulnerable groups are more likely to have heard that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures benefits all students. The only exception is within the LGBTI+ community, with 23.53% of the respondents, compared to 39.63% of the total. The groups that are have heard the most that diversity in schools benefits all students are ethnic and religious minorities (57.47% and 54.11%).

Table 28. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students" across vulnerable groups

Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minority	Religious minority	TOTAL
Yes	40,42	23,53	39,52	41,79	40,42	57,74	54,11	39,63
No	38,37	47,06	43,81	42,59	40,03	30,98	33,95	40,48
I do not know	20,52	29,41	14,95	14,83	18,71	10,33	11,47	19,04
Prefer not to answer	0,68	0,00	1,72	0,79	0,84	0,96	0,47	0,85
	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure represents these results:

Figure 19. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students" across vulnerable groups

Therefore, in general, people from vulnerable groups are more likely to know schools that segregate students depending on their academic level and to have heard that it is scientifically proven that diversity in schools benefits all students (ranging from 32.19% to 50.10% in the first question and from 23.53% to 57.74% in the second). In both cases, people from ethnic and religious minorities are the groups with the highest percentages, while women (in the first case) and the LGBTI+ community (in the second) are the groups with the lowest percentages.

IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered “yes” to interaction 1 and “yes, often” and “yes, rarely” in interaction 2

The analysis of the impact of interactions with science points out that, when people from vulnerable groups interact with science, they are more likely to identify schools in their surroundings that implement segregation practices with students. In this line, we can see how in interaction 1 (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families), the proportions of identification of segregation practices in schools range from 41.67% (LGBTI+) to 58.98% (ethnic minorities), compared to the range obtained with the total of respondents from vulnerable groups (32.19% - 50.10%). Similar results are obtained in interaction 2.often (following someone on social media who often publishes about science) in all vulnerable groups except for the LGBTI+ community. In this case, the identification of segregation practices gets percentages between 42.47% (women) and 65.97% (ethnic minorities), which represent increases up to 50% compared with the total. However, when people followed on social media rarely publishes about science, the identification of segregation practices in schools are not so accentuated (38.11% - 50.52%). The results for the LGBTI+ community are limited by the reduced size of the sample (n=12, n=7 and n=7) (see section 4).

Table 29. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning” across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning									
		Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Yes	41,84	41,67	47,21	50,74	45,32	58,98	56,18	40,94
	No	44,63	33,33	45,18	37,68	42,75	30,86	35,34	46,59
	I do not know	13,34	25,00	7,61	10,59	11,63	8,98	8,13	11,89
	Rejected	0,19	0,00	0,00	0,99	0,30	1,17	0,35	0,59
	TOTAL	100,00	100,0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
I2. Often	Yes	42,47	28,57	47,89	44,60	47,44	65,97	63,29	39,57
	No	46,19	57,14	43,66	45,99	40,63	27,78	29,75	49,48
	I do not know	11,00	14,29	7,75	8,36	11,08	4,86	5,70	10,52
	Rejected	0,34	0,00	0,70	1,05	0,85	1,39	1,27	0,43
	TOTAL	100,00	100,0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
I2. Rarely	Yes	38,11	28,57	40,00	48,28	40,94	50,52	43,38	36,35
	No	49,51	71,43	50,43	42,86	48,75	36,08	41,91	51,21
	I do not know	12,38	0,00	9,57	8,37	10,31	13,40	14,71	12,15
	Rejected	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,49	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,29

TOTAL	100,00	0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Decreases more than 15%	Decreases less than 15%	Increases	Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened					
Increases more than 50%	Increases more than 100%	Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who [often/rarely] publishes about science						

The following figure shows the impact of interactions with science in the identification of schools that implement segregation practices with their students. In this line, changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families (interaction 1) has a notable impact in all vulnerable groups. However, the impact of following someone on social media (interaction 2) depends on the frequency of publication of scientific content. In this line, the scientific content is often published, respondents from vulnerable groups tend to identify segregation practices in schools to a greater extent, but when it is rarely published, the impact is not so accentuated.

Figure 20. Percentage of respondents who know schools that separate students according to their academic level across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

In this figure we can observe how, in all vulnerable groups except youth aged 25-34, the most effective interaction with science is following someone on social media who often publishes about science (interaction 2.often). The group that benefits the most of interactions with science are people from low socioeconomic status with increments of 36.40% (interaction 1), 60.24% (interaction 2.often) and 33.74% (interaction 2. Rarely). Again, the results from the LGBTI+ community are limited due to the small sample (n=12, n=7 and n=7) (see section 4).

Figure 21. Increases in the identification of schools that separate students according to their academic level across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

The analysis of the impact of interactions with science suggest when people from vulnerable groups interact with science, they tend to hear more that diversity in schools is beneficial for all students. This is true for all interactions and vulnerable groups. In this line, among those participants who have interacted with science through interaction 1 (changing their mind because something happened to them or their families), the proportion of those who have heard that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, benefits all students ranges from 49.24% (youth 16-24) to 70.31% (ethnic minorities), which represent increases of approximately 20-30%. When people interact with science through social media by following someone who often publishes about science, the responses are comprised between 49.30 (youth aged 16-24) to 76.58% (religious minorities), with increases of 40-60%. When those scientists followed on social media rarely publish about science, the percentages of those who have heard that diversity in school is beneficial for all students range from 41.74 (youth aged 16-24) to 60.82% (ethnic minorities). Finally, due to the reduced number of responses from the LGBTI+ community (n=12, n=7 and n=7), their results have limited implications.

Table 30. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students" across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students									
INTERACTION		Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
		1	Yes	53,74	25,00	49,24	55,42	55,14	70,31
	No	32,82	41,67	41,62	35,22	33,53	22,66	27,21	35,07
	I do not know	13,05	33,33	9,14	9,11	10,57	7,03	6,01	11,67

	Rejected	0,38	0,00	0,00	0,25	0,76	0,00	0,35	0,59
	TOTAL	100,00	0	0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
I2. Often	Yes	59,22	57,14	49,30	61,32	64,77	72,92	76,58	58,26
	No	30,12	14,29	44,37	31,71	27,27	20,14	17,09	31,65
	I do not know	10,32	28,57	6,34	6,27	7,67	6,94	6,33	9,57
	Rejected	0,34	0,00	0,00	0,70	0,28	0,00	0,00	0,52
	TOTAL	100,00	0	0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
I2. Rarely	Yes	52,06	28,57	41,74	48,77	54,06	60,82	53,68	51,51
	No	36,94	57,14	47,83	41,87	37,19	32,99	38,24	37,80
	I do not know	10,81	14,29	10,43	9,36	8,75	6,19	7,35	10,50
	Rejected	0,20	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,74	0,19
	TOTAL	100,00	0	0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Decreases more than 15%	Decreases less than 15%	Increases	Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who [often/rarely] publishes about science
Increases more than 50%	Increases more than 100%		

The following figure shows the proportion of respondents from vulnerable groups who have heard that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, benefits all students, across interactions. As we can see, all interactions have impact, but the highest impact is achieved when people follow on social media someone who often publishes about science (interaction 2.often).

Figure 22. Respondents who have heard that diversity in school benefits all students across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

Finally, in the following figure we can observe the increase (%) in the responses from vulnerable groups due to interactions with science. It is relevant to point that, in all interactions, the highest increases are found in people from low SES (36,40% in interaction 1, 60,24% in interaction 2.often and 33,74% in interaction 2.rarely), pointing out that they are the group that benefits the most from interactions with science.

Figure 23. Increases in the respondents who have heard that diversity in school benefits all students across vulnerable groups and interactions with science

Therefore, in both questions about segregation and diversity in schools, interactions with science increase the proportion of those who identify schools that segregate students depending on their academic level and also those who think that diversity in schools benefits all students. In both questions, the highest impact is achieved when people follow on social media someone who often publishes about science (interaction 2.Often) and the group that benefits the most of interactions with science are people from low socioeconomic status, with the highest increases.

5.5. Section 3 – Gender

This section aims to identify how citizens benefit from scientific research in gender. To do so, we have structured this part of the report in 4 sections 1) scientific evidence and hoax in gender (2 questions), 2) gender differences (1 question), 3) gender-based violence (2 question) and 4) isolating gender violence (1 questions).

5.5.1. Scientific evidence and hoax in gender

To analyze the impact of the interactions on the perception or recognition that respondents may have of the survey to distinguish between scientific evidence and hoax, we have introduced two phrases in the questionnaire: one of them is scientific evidence, while the other is a hoax. The sentences are:

- Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors
- Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors

In both cases, respondents are asked if those two statements are scientific evidence and hoax, or if they do not know. The results are distributed as follows:

Table 31. Distribution of respondents' answers to the two statements related to gender

Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Scientific evidence	2208	29,4	29,4
Hoax	642	8,6	38,0
I do not know	4538	60,5	98,4
Prefer not to answer	119	1,6	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0
Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Scientific evidence	929	12,4	12,4
Hoax	2230	29,7	42,1
I do not know	4194	55,9	97,9
Prefer not to answer	154	2,1	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

In both statements, approximately 6 out of 10 (60.5% in the hoax and 55.9% in the scientific evidence) express that they do not know if the statements are scientific evidence or hoaxes. Only 8.6% identify the hoax statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” as a hoax and 12.4% the evidence-based statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors” as scientific evidence. On the contrary, 29.4%

thinks that the first statement is scientific evidence and 29,7% that the second statement is a hoax.

Figure 24. Distribution of respondents' answers to the two statements related to gender

RESPONSES BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

The analysis across vulnerable groups point to the existence of differences across vulnerable groups in the identification of scientific evidence and hoax in gender. For example, while 15.66% of religious minorities and 13.19% of ethnic minorities identify the hoax statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” as a hoax, the proportions among LGBTI+, youth aged 25-34 and women are 7.84%, 7.93% and 7.97% in each case.

Table 32. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” across vulnerable groups

Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES ⁹	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Scientific evidence	30,17	17,65	37,80	37,99	32,36	45,89	41,71	29,41
Hoax	7,97	7,84	10,65	7,93	8,63	13,19	15,66	8,55
I do not know	60,24	70,59	49,48	52,42	57,51	40,15	40,78	60,45
Prefer not to answer	1,63	3,92	2,06	1,67	1,50	0,76	1,86	1,59
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

⁹ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year

As we can see in the following figure, most of the respondents across vulnerable groups do not know if the statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” is scientific evidence or hoax and in all cases, the proportion of those who think is scientific evidence is significantly higher than those who identify it as a hoax.

Figure 25. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” across vulnerable groups

Regarding the evidence-based statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors” we can see notable differences between vulnerable groups. In this line, while the proportion of youth (17.87% for those aged 16-24 and 17.21% for those aged 25-34) and ethnic and religious minorities (32.12 and 30.39%) is significantly higher than the average (12.38%), people from low socioeconomic status and women obtain similar results (14.80% and 12.29%) and the LGBTI+ community a slightly lower percentage (9.80%).

Table 33. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors” across vulnerable groups

Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES ¹⁰	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Scientific evidence	12,29	9,80	17,87	17,21	14,80	32,12	30,39	12,38
Hoax	29,57	23,53	29,21	29,66	28,97	27,92	24,81	29,71
I do not know	55,99	64,71	49,31	51,15	54,21	38,43	42,64	55,87

¹⁰ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year

Prefer not to answer	2,15	1,96	3,61	1,98	2,03	1,53	2,17	2,05
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure represents these results across vulnerable groups. In this case, it is relevant to point that, although in most vulnerable groups the proportion of respondents who think that the evidence-based statement "Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors" is a hoax is higher than those who identify it as scientific evidence, this is not the case of ethnic and religious minorities, where the result is the opposite. In all cases, the majority of respondents express that they do not know if the statement is scientific evidence or hoax.

Figure 26. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors" across vulnerable groups

Therefore, the majority of respondents express that they do not know if the statements are scientific evidence or hoaxes. In both statements, the proportion of people who identify the hoax-statement as a hoax and the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence is lower than those who think the contrary. In this line, between 7.84% and 15.66% identify the hoax statement as a hoax and 9.80%-32.12% identify the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence. Ethnic and religious minorities are the groups that more commonly identify scientific evidence and hoaxes in gender.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered “yes” to interaction 1 and “yes, often” and “yes, rarely” in interaction 2.

When we introduce interactions with science, we observe that as a result of these interactions, there is an increase in the proportion of those who think that the statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” is scientific evidence as well as in those who identify it as a hoax. This result is found generally, across all vulnerable groups and interactions with science. One hypothesis behind these results may be that interactions with science provide citizens with skills and knowledge that made them feel more confident to answer this question. This way, as we can see, generally the percentages of people who answer that they do not know or that refuse to answer decrease more than 15%.

Among those respondents who changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families, only between 10.17% (women) and 17.31% (religious minorities) identify the hoax statement as a hoax, with increases of 20% in average. On the contrary, approximately half of the respondents think that the statement is scientific evidence, with increases of 25% in average. Therefore, the difference between those who think that the statement is scientific evidence and those who correct identity it as a hoax, increases, suggesting that this interaction with science does not impact on the identification of evidence and hoax in gender.

Similar results are found in interaction 2. In this case, the proportion of respondents who identify the hoax-statement as a hoax is comprised between 7.67% (youth 25-34) and 15.19% (religious minorities), decreasing in youth and ethnic and religious minorities. Again, the increase (in percent) in those who think that Simone de Beauvoir fought against sexual relations with minors is higher than in those who know that this is a hoax, increasing the difference between both response options. These results also suggest that this interaction with science does not impact on the identification of evidence and hoax in gender. Finally, due to the reduced number of responses from the LGBTI+ community (n=12, n=7 and n=7), their results have limited implications (see section 4 for more details).

Table 34. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” across interactions and vulnerable groups

		Woma n	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Scientific evidence	39,06	33,33	45,69	46,55	41,54	54,69	53,36	39,07
	Hoax	10,17	0,00	12,69	11,33	10,27	14,84	17,31	10,45
	I do not know	49,62	50,00	41,12	41,13	46,68	29,69	27,56	49,15
	Rejected	1,15	16,67	0,51	0,99	1,51	0,78	1,77	1,33

		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
INTERACTION 2. Often	TOTAL	100,00	0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
	Scientific evidence	39,76	14,29	35,92	44,95	44,32	59,72	56,96	38,78
	Hoax	9,14	14,29	9,86	7,67	10,23	9,72	15,19	8,87
	I do not know	50,76	57,14	54,23	46,69	44,32	29,86	27,22	51,65
	Rejected	0,34	14,29	0,00	0,70	1,14	0,69	0,63	0,70
TOTAL		100,00	100,0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Scientific evidence	38,90	0,00	44,35	42,36	38,75	47,42	42,65	37,22
	Hoax	10,22	0,00	9,57	9,85	11,88	18,56	21,32	11,47
	I do not know	49,71	100,0	46,09	47,29	48,44	32,99	34,56	50,53
	Rejected	1,18	0,00	0,00	0,49	0,94	1,03	1,47	0,78
	TOTAL		100,00	100,0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Decreases more than 15%	Increases	Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened							
Decreases less than 15%	Increases more than 50%	Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who publishes about science... [often/rarely]							
	Increases more than 100%								

The following figure represents the identification of hoaxes in gender across vulnerable groups and interactions.

Figure 27. Identification of the statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” as a hoax across vulnerable groups and interactions.

In the following figure we can see the increases in the percentages of respondents who think that the statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors” is scientific evidence (in red colours) due to interactions with science and the increases in those who identify the statement as a hoax (in blue colours). In addition, we can observe the differences between those who respond “scientific evidence” and “hoax”. As we can see, this difference is higher when we introduce interactions with science, compared with the total of respondents (solid line compared to pointed lines).

Figure 28. Increase in respondents' answers to the following sentence "Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors" and difference between "scientific evidence" and "hoax" across interactions with science and vulnerable groups

With the introduction of interactions with science, we observe that there is an increase in the proportion of those who identify the statement "Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors" as scientific evidence as well as in those who think that it is a hoax. This result is found generally, across all vulnerable groups and interactions with science. One hypothesis behind these results may be that interactions with science provide citizens with skills and knowledge that made them feel more confident to answer this question. This way, as we can see, generally the percentages of people who answer that they do not know or that refuse to answer decrease more than 15%.

Among those respondents who changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families, between 17.27% (women) and 43.75% (ethnic minorities) identify the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, with increases of 30-40% in average. On the contrary, nearly one third of the respondents across vulnerable groups think that the statement is a hoax, with increases of approximately 10% in average. Therefore, the difference between those who think that the statement is a hoax and those who correctly identify it as scientific evidence, decreases.

Similar results are found in interaction 2. In this case, the proportion of respondents who identify the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence is comprised between 15.49% (youth 16-24) and 48.10% (religious minorities). In this case, the average increase is approximately 30%, with increases of more than 50% in people from low SES and from religious minorities. Also in this case, the increase (in percent) in those who know that Simone de Beauvoir defended sexual

relations with minors is higher than in those who think that it is the opposite, decreasing the difference between both response options. However, this is not the case of people who follow someone on social media who rarely publishes about science, since in this case the average increases in the those who identify the evidence-based statement and in those who think it is a hoax are approximately 10%. Finally, due to the reduced number of responses from the LGBTI+ community (n=12, n=7 and n=7), their results have limited implications (see section 4 for more details).

Table 35. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors" across interactions and vulnerable groups

		Woma n	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Scientific evidence	17,27	25,00	21,32	25,86	20,85	43,75	41,34	18,55
	Hoax	34,55	8,33	33,50	34,73	30,82	27,34	26,15	34,17
	I do not know	46,45	58,33	42,13	37,93	46,07	27,73	29,68	45,47
	Rejected	1,73	8,33	3,05	1,48	2,27	1,17	2,83	1,81
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Often	Scientific evidence	16,92	14,29	15,49	19,16	23,58	47,22	48,10	17,30
	Hoax	36,04	14,29	30,28	36,93	32,39	25,69	24,05	34,61
	I do not know	45,85	57,14	52,82	42,51	42,90	27,08	27,22	46,78
	Rejected	1,18	14,29	1,41	1,39	1,14	0,00	0,63	1,30
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Scientific evidence	15,91	0,00	18,26	19,21	16,88	34,02	31,62	15,16
	Hoax	36,15	14,29	33,04	28,57	35,31	32,99	29,41	35,86
	I do not know	46,95	85,71	47,83	51,72	46,56	31,96	38,24	48,30
	Rejected	0,98	0,00	0,87	0,49	1,25	1,03	0,74	0,68
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Decreases more than 15%	Increases		Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened						
Decreases less than 15%	Increases more than 50%		Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who publishes about science... [often/rarely]						
	Increases more than 100%								

The following figure represents the percentage of respondents from vulnerable groups who identify the statement "Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on

feminism, defended sexual relations with minors” as scientific evidence across interactions with science. As abovementioned, interactions with science generally increase the proportion of respondents who identify the evidence-based statement. In this line, respondents who changed their mind because something happened to them or their families obtain the highest increases in women and youth, while those who follow a scientist who often publishes about science on social media obtain the highest increases among people from low SES and ethnic and religious minorities.

Figure 29. Identification of the statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors” as a hoax across vulnerable groups and interactions.

In the following figure we can see the increases in the percentages of respondents who identify the statement “Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors” as scientific evidence (in blue colours) due to interactions with science and the increases in those who think that the statement is a hoax (in red colours). In addition, we can observe the differences between those who respond “hoax” and “scientific evidence”. As we can see, this difference is smaller in interactions 1 and 2 (often) with science, compared with the total of respondents (solid line compared to pointed lines in the secondary axis).

Figure 30. Increase in respondents' answers to the following sentence "Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors" (primary axis) and difference between "scientific evidence" and "hoax" (secondary axis) across interactions with science and vulnerable groups

Therefore, on the one hand interactions with science increase both, people who identify the hoax statement as a hoax and those who think it is an evidence-based statement. On the other hand, they increase the proportion of respondents who identify the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, contributing to the identification of evidence and hoaxes. Interactions with science not always have impact in helping people to distinguish scientific evidence from hoaxes in gender. In all vulnerable groups, the proportion of people who identify the hoax statement as a hoax is higher than the percentage of those who think it is an evidence-based statement. The same happens in the identification of the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, with the exceptions of ethnic and religious minorities.

5.5.2. Gender differences

This section aims to analyse citizens' identification of comments regarding gender differences in intellectual capacity and includes the following question:

- Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?

The response options include: yes, no, I do not know and prefer not to answer.

Almost 7 out of 10 respondents (69.3%) express that people around them do not argue that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers, while 19.2% affirm that in their contexts have heard this type of arguments.

Table 36. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?"

Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes	1444	19,2	19,2
No	5199	69,3	88,5
I do not know	801	10,7	99,2
Prefer not to answer	63	0,8	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The following figure represents the distributions of responses to the question "Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?"

Figure 31. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?"

RESPONSES BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

If we look closer at the results across vulnerable groups, we can observe that, although there are differences between vulnerable groups, in all cases, respondents are more likely to express that they have heard in their surroundings that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers. In this vein, between 22.50% (in people from low SES) and 43.98% (in ethnic minorities) identify people around them arguing that girls have less capacity for scientific and technological careers than boys, compared with the 19.24% of the total.

Table 37. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?" across vulnerable groups

Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES ¹¹	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Yes	22,36	23,5	29,73	25,54	22,50	43,98	36,12	19,24
No	66,11	58,8	58,59	61,30	64,77	47,23	52,71	69,26
I do not know	10,72	17,6	10,14	11,97	12,07	8,22	10,54	10,6
Prefer not to answer	0,81	0,00	1,55	1,19	0,66	0,57	0,62	0,84
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure represents the distribution of responses across vulnerable groups.

Figure 32. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?" across vulnerable groups

¹¹ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year

Therefore, people from vulnerable groups are more likely to identify people around them arguing that girls have less capacity for scientific and technological careers than boys. The results range from 22.50% (low SES) to 43.98% (ethnic minorities).

IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered “yes” to interaction 1 and “yes, often” and “yes, rarely” in interaction 2.

When we look at the responses of those participants from vulnerable groups who interact with science, we can identify increases in the identification of arguments regarding boys’ and girls’ capacity to perform scientific and technological careers. For example, among those who changed their mind because something happened to them or their families (interaction 1), the percentages of those who have heard this type of arguments range from 29.56% (women) to 55.47% (ethnic minorities), which represents increases of 25%-45%. Among those who follow someone on social media who often publishes about science, the increases are slightly higher (35%-60%), with percentages of identification of arguments about differences in intellectual capacity ranging from 30.12% (women) to 63.19% (ethnic minorities). When this person rarely publishes on social media, the impact of this interaction is not so accentuated (10-20%) and the percentages in this case are comprised between 26.13% and 49.48%.

Table 38. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?” across vulnerable groups and interactions

		It is argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?							
		Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Yes	29,56	25,00	37,56	35,96	32,63	55,47	49,82	28,04
	No	64,49	33,33	55,84	56,40	61,18	39,06	43,11	65,72
	I do not know	5,66	41,67	6,09	6,65	6,04	5,47	6,71	5,86
	Rejected	0,29	0,00	0,51	0,99	0,15	0,00	0,35	0,37
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Often	Yes	30,12	14,29	35,21	34,49	36,36	63,19	56,96	26,96
	No	64,97	71,43	56,34	59,23	56,53	29,86	36,08	67,74
	I do not know	4,40	14,29	7,75	5,92	6,82	5,56	5,70	4,96
	Rejected	0,51	0,00	0,70	0,35	0,28	1,39	1,27	0,35

	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Yes	26,13	14,29	29,57	28,57	27,81	49,48	39,71	24,10
	No	68,57	85,71	64,35	66,01	67,19	44,33	52,21	70,46
	I do not know	4,91	0,00	5,22	4,43	4,38	6,19	8,09	4,76
	Rejected	0,39	0,00	0,87	0,99	0,63	0,00	0,00	0,68
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Decreases more than 15%		Increases		Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened					
Decreases less than 15%		Increases more than 50%		Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who publishes about science... [often/rarely]					
		Increases more than 100%							

This figure represents how all interactions with science increase the identification of arguments regarding boys' and girls' capacity in scientific and technological careers across all vulnerable groups. Generally, the interaction with science with the highest impact is following someone on social media who often publishes about science. The only exception in this line is found in youth, where the most impactful interaction is changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families. The results from the LGBTI+ community are limited by the small size of the sample (see section 4).

Figure 33. Identification of arguments regarding boys' and girls' capacity to develop scientific and technological careers across vulnerable groups and interactions with science.

This figure presents the increases in the identification of arguments about boys' and girls' differences in scientific and technological capacity across interactions and vulnerable groups. In all interactions, the group that benefits the most of these interactions with science are people from low SES, with increases of 45.01%, 61.61% and 23.61%, respectively.

Figure 34. Increases of respondents' affirmative answers to the following sentence "Is it argued in your environment that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers?" across vulnerable groups and interactions

Therefore, interactions with science increase the proportion of people who identify people around them arguing that girls have less capacity than boys for scientific and technological careers. The most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science and the group that benefits the most are people from low SES.

5.5.3. Gender-Based Violence

This section aims to analyse citizens' perceptions about gender-based violence, including gender-based violence in partners and ex-partners, as well as in sporadic relationships. It includes the following questions:

- Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors?
- To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?

The first one includes four response options: yes, some people, no, I do not know and prefer not to answer, while the second: totally disagree, more or less disagree, more or less agree and totally agree.

For the first question (Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors?), the following table summarize the results obtained and show how nearly one third of the respondents (31.1%) express that people around them (also including some people) say that all men are potential aggressors, compared with the 61.4% who express the contrary.

Table 39. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors"

Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes, they do	323	4,3	4,3
Some people do	2014	26,8	31,1
No, they do not	4610	61,4	92,5
I do not know	506	6,7	99,3
Prefer not to answer	54	0,7	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The following figure presents the distributions of responses:

Figure 35. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors"

As for the second question "To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?" more than half of the respondents (54.3%) agree to some extent (including more or less agree and totally agree) that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships.

Table 40. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?"

To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Totally disagree	537	7,2	7,2
More or less disagree	1176	15,7	22,8
More or less agree	3175	42,3	65,1

Totally agree	903	12,0	77,1
I do not know	1650	22,0	99,1
Prefer not to answer	66	0,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0

The following figure also represents this trend:

Figure 36. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?"

RESPONSES BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

This section aims to look closer at the results across vulnerable groups. People from vulnerable groups are more likely to identify people around them saying that all men are potential aggressors. This is true for both response options "yes" and "some people". While the percentage of the total population who express that people around them say that all men are potential aggressors is 31.13% (including "yes" and "some people"), the proportion in vulnerable groups ranges from 30.69% to 57.93%. On one side we find women (30.69%), followed by people from low socioeconomic status (36.99%), and on the other side, we find ethnic minorities (57.93%), religious minorities (54.42%) and youth aged 25-34 (39,97%).

Table 41. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors" across vulnerable groups

Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors							
Wom en	LGBT I+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES ¹²	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOT AL

¹² Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year

Yes	4,33	3,92	7,39	8,01	6,03	20,08	17,21	4,30
Some people	26,37	5	40,72	31,96	30,96	37,86	37,21	26,83
No	61,21	52,9	44,33	51,78	55,26	37,48	39,22	61,41
I do not know	7,31	4	5,67	7,45	7,09	4,40	5,58	6,74
Prefer not to answer	0,79	0,00	1,89	0,79	0,66	0,19	0,78	0,72
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure shows the distribution of responses across vulnerable groups, compared with the total of respondents:

Figure 37. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors?" across vulnerable groups

Regarding the question "To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?" the results show notable differences across vulnerable groups. In this vein, the total proportion of respondents who agree with the statement (including totally agree and more or less agree) is 54.32%, compared with the 22.82% of those who disagree to some extent (including totally disagree and quite disagree). In vulnerable groups the proportion of those who agree to some extent ranges from 47.06% to 59.38%, being LGBTI+ (47.06%) and youth aged 16-24 (51.20%) the groups that are least likely to agree and religious minorities (59.38%) and ethnic minorities (57.17%) the most likely. On the other hand, the proportion of people from vulnerable groups who disagree to some extent ranges from 19.61% to 30.78%. Ethnic minorities (30.78%) and religious minorities (28.37%) are the groups that tend to disagree the most and LGBTI+ (19.61%) and youth aged 25-34 (23.63%) those who tend to disagree the least.

Table 42. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?" across vulnerable groups

To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Totally disagree	7,21	3,92	8,42	7,69	8,37	12,05	11,32	7,15
More or less disagree	16,49	15,69	19,42	15,94	16,07	18,74	17,05	15,67
More or less agree	41,52	33,33	40,38	42,90	42,49	37,48	40,16	42,29
Totally agree	12,42	13,73	10,82	13,16	12,81	19,69	19,22	12,03
I do not know	21,34	33,33	19,07	19,43	19,64	11,85	11,63	21,98
Prefer not to answer	1,02	0,00	1,89	0,87	0,62	0,19	0,62	0,88
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The following figure describes the distribution of responses across vulnerable groups:

Figure 38. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?" across vulnerable groups

Therefore, people from vulnerable groups are more likely to identify people around them saying that all men are potential aggressors, ranging from 30.69% to 57.93% (in comparison

with the 31.13% of the total of respondents. People belonging to ethnic and religious minorities are the most likely to identify this type of comments. In addition, between 47.06% and 59.38% of people from vulnerable groups agree to some extent that gender violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners and less frequently in sporadic relationships and between 19.61% and 30.78% thinks the opposite. Ethnic and religious minorities are the groups that tend to disagree the most.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered “yes” to interaction 1 and “yes, often” and “yes, rarely” in interaction 2.

When we analyse the impact of interactions with science, we can see that when people from vulnerable groups interact with science, they tend to identify more people saying that all men are potential aggressors. First, regarding interaction 1 (changing their mind about science because something happened), we can see increments of more than 50% in those who know people who say that all men are potential aggressors in all vulnerable groups and increments up to 50% in those who know some people who say so in all vulnerable groups, except for religious minorities. In this case, the total proportion of respondents who know people in their surroundings (including response options “yes” and “some people”) who say that all men are potential aggressors range from 38,96% (women) to 71,09% (ethnic minorities), compared with the 30,69% (women) to 57,93% (ethnic minorities) in the total of respondents.

Second, among respondents who follow on social media someone who often publishes about science (interaction 2-often), the proportion of those who know people who say that all men are potential aggressors increases between 108% and 198% in all vulnerable groups except youth aged 16-24 (with an increase of 81.1%). This time, the total proportion of respondents who know people in their surroundings (including response options “yes” and “some people”) who say that all men are potential aggressors range from 39,93% (women) to 75,69% (ethnic minorities), compared with the 30,69% (women) to 57,93% (ethnic minorities) in the total of respondents.

Finally, among those participants that follow on social media someone who rarely publishes about science, there is an increment in the identification of some people in their surroundings who say that all men are potential aggressors, although this impact is less accentuated than in previous interactions (13.18%-38.73%). This way, the total proportion of respondents who know people in their surroundings (including response options “yes” and “some people”) who say that all men are potential aggressors range from 39,88% (women) to 68,04% (ethnic minorities), compared with the 30,69% (women) to 57,93% (ethnic minorities) in the total of respondents. Also in this case, the results from the LGBTI+ community are limited by the small size of the sample (n= 12, n=7 and n=7), see section 4.

Table 43. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors” across vulnerable groups and interactions

		Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors?							
		Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
INTERACTION 1	Yes	6,91	8,33	12,69	13,79	10,27	30,47	27,56	8,16
	Some people	32,05	41,67	47,21	34,73	37,46	40,63	37,10	33,74
	No	57,39	50,00	35,53	47,78	48,49	26,17	31,45	54,53
	I do not know	3,26	0,00	2,54	3,20	3,32	2,34	2,47	3,14
	Rejected	0,38	0,00	2,03	0,49	0,45	0,39	1,41	0,43
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2: Often	Yes	10,49	14,29	13,38	16,72	17,90	44,44	39,24	10,87
	Some people	29,44	14,29	43,66	30,66	37,78	31,25	33,54	30,09
	No	57,19	71,43	39,44	49,13	41,48	22,22	25,32	56,17
	I do not know	2,54	0,00	2,82	3,48	2,84	2,08	1,90	2,70
	Rejected	0,34	0,00	0,70	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,17
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2: Rarely	Yes	3,54	0,00	7,83	6,90	6,25	19,59	14,71	4,57
	Some people	36,35	57,14	46,09	44,33	39,69	48,45	47,06	36,73
	No	57,37	42,86	42,61	44,33	51,25	27,84	36,76	55,88
	I do not know	2,55	0,00	3,48	3,94	2,50	4,12	1,47	2,72
	Rejected	0,20	0,00	0,00	0,49	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,10
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Decreases more than 15%		Decreases less than 15%		Increases		Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened			
Increases more than 50%		Increases more than 100%		Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who [often/rarely] publishes about science					

The following figure represents the increments in the percentages of participants who know people and some people in their surroundings who say that all men are potential aggressors. Across all interactions, the impact of interactions with science is more accentuated in people from low socioeconomic status, who get the highest percentages of increase. In all vulnerable groups except for youth, following someone on social media who often publishes about science is the interaction with the highest impact in the identification of people saying that all men are potential aggressors.

Figure 39. Increases in the proportion of respondents who answer “yes” and “some people do” to the following sentence “Do people around you say that all men are potential aggressors” across vulnerable groups and interactions

Regarding the impact of interactions with science in question “To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?” we can see that exist a general increase in both the people who agree to some extent and in those who disagree with the prevalence of gender violence in partners and ex-partners or in sporadic relationships. One hypothesis behind these results may be that interactions with science provide citizens with skills and knowledge that made them feel more confident to answer this question. This way, as we can see, generally the percentages of people who answer that they do not know or that refuse to answer decrease more than 15%. The results from the LGBTI+ community are limited by the small size of the sample (n= 12, n=7 and n=7), see section 4.

To go specifically through each interaction, in interaction 1 (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families), the total proportion of those who disagree to some extent (including totally disagree and more or less disagree) that gender violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners than in sporadic relationships ranges from 27.45% (women) to 34.77% (ethnic minorities) and the highest increase is found in youth 25-34 (19.86%). Regarding interaction 2 (following a scientist on social media), the results point to differences depending on the frequency of publication of scientific content. This way, when scientific content is often published, the proportion of those who disagree to some extent ranges from 22.54% (youth 16-24) to 32.64% (ethnic minorities). The highest increment in this case is found in people from low socioeconomic status, with approximately 15%. On the contrary, when scientific content is rarely published, the range of respondents who disagree to some extent is 24.75% (women) – 38.97% (religious minorities), compared with the 19.61%-30.78% of the total of respondents from vulnerable groups. The highest increase in this case is found in religious minorities with 37.36%.

Table 44. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?” across vulnerable groups and interactions

To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?									
	Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL	
INTERACTION 1	Totally disagree	9,40	8,33	9,14	10,10	11,18	14,84	12,37	9,17
	More or less disagree	18,04	33,33	23,86	18,23	16,92	19,92	16,96	17,16
	More or less agree	45,49	25,00	46,19	43,60	43,50	33,98	36,75	45,52
	Totally agree	13,53	16,67	8,63	16,26	15,86	23,83	25,09	14,39
	I do not know	12,86	16,67	11,17	11,58	11,93	7,03	7,77	13,22
	Rejected	0,67	0,00	1,02	0,25	0,60	0,39	1,06	0,53
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Often	Totally disagree	9,81	0,00	8,45	10,80	13,92	16,67	15,19	9,22
	More or less disagree	15,57	42,86	14,08	14,98	14,20	15,97	10,76	15,13
	More or less agree	43,15	14,29	41,55	43,90	39,20	27,78	32,28	43,22
	Totally agree	17,77	28,57	14,08	18,82	21,31	32,64	34,81	16,87
	I do not know	13,20	14,29	20,42	11,50	10,51	6,25	6,33	15,13
	Rejected	0,51	0,00	1,41	0,00	0,85	0,69	0,63	0,43
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Totally disagree	6,29	0,00	6,96	8,87	7,50	12,37	13,24	6,80
	More or less disagree	18,47	0,00	23,48	21,67	20,00	22,68	25,74	18,37
	More or less agree	50,88	85,71	48,70	48,28	50,31	41,24	41,18	49,85
	Totally agree	11,39	14,29	8,70	8,87	13,75	17,53	13,24	12,24
	I do not know	12,57	0,00	11,30	11,82	8,13	6,19	6,62	12,54
	Rejected	0,39	0,00	0,87	0,49	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,19
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Decreases more than 15%	Decreases less than 15%	Increases	Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who [often/rarely] publishes about science
Increases more than 50%	Increases more than 100%		

In this figure we can observe the total proportion of respondents from vulnerable groups who disagree to some extent with the question “To what extent do you agree with the statement

that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?” across vulnerable groups and interactions (primary axis), as well as the increases in the percentages due to interactions with science (secondary axis).

Figure 40. Increment of respondents who disagree to the following sentence “To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?” across vulnerable groups and interactions

Therefore, people from vulnerable groups are more likely to identify people around them saying that all men are potential aggressors when they interact with science. The highest increases are achieved when people follow on social media someone who often publishes about science and people from low SES are the group with the highest increments. In addition, people tend to disagree more with the idea that gender violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners and less in sporadic relationships when they interact with science.

5.5.4. Isolating Gender Violence

The final section aims to analyse to what extent citizens agree with the importance of overcoming Isolating Gender Violence (IGV) to overcome gender-based violence and includes the following question:

- Isolating Gender Violence refers to the attack against those who support the victims of direct gender violence. To what extent do you agree that, in order to promote active solidarity with victims of direct gender violence, it is necessary to protect those who support these victims?

The question includes the following response options: totally disagree, more or less disagree, more or less agree and totally agree, I do not know and prefer not to answer.

The results show that almost two thirds (65.0%) of the respondents agree to some extent (including totally agree and more or less agree) with the importance of overcoming IGV to end gender-based violence.

Table 45. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree that, in order to promote active solidarity with victims of direct gender violence, it is necessary to protect those who support these victims? "

To what extent do you agree that, in order to promote active solidarity with victims of direct gender violence, it is necessary to protect those who support these victims?			
	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Totally disagree	269	3,6	3,6
Quite disagree	606	8,1	11,7
Quite agree	2974	39,6	51,3
Totally agree	1906	25,4	76,7
I do not know	1601	21,3	98,0
Prefer not to answer	151	2,0	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,00

Figure 41. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree that, in order to promote active solidarity with victims of direct gender violence, it is necessary to protect those who support these victims? "

RESULTS BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

If we look at the responses across vulnerable groups, we can observe that despite the existence of small differences, all vulnerable groups obtain similar results compared with the total of respondents. This way, while among the total of respondents, those who agree to some extent (including totally agree and more or less agree) represent 65.01%, across vulnerable groups the proportion ranges from 52.94 (LGBTI+) to 68.26 (ethnic minorities). If we look at those who

disagree to some extent (including totally disagree and more or less disagree), we find similar results. In this case, the proportion in the total of respondents is 11.66%, and across vulnerable groups it is comprised between 7.84% (LGBTI+) and 21.09% (religious minorities).

Table 46. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree that, in order to promote active solidarity with victims of direct gender violence, it is necessary to protect those who support these victims?" across vulnerable groups

To what extent do you agree that, in order to promote active solidarity with victims of direct gender violence, it is necessary to protect those who support these victims?								
	Women	LGBTI+	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES ¹³	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
Totally disagree	3,56	3,92	7,90	4,12	4,71	7,27	6,67	3,58
More or less disagree	7,37	3,92	10,31	9,60	8,72	11,66	14,42	8,07
More or less agree	39,71	35,29	37,97	40,92	39,19	39,58	38,45	39,62
Totally agree	25,32	17,65	22,16	24,03	26,07	28,68	27,29	25,39
I do not know	22,07	37,25	18,73	18,79	19,51	11,85	12,40	21,33
Prefer not to answer	1,97	1,96	2,92	2,54	1,81	0,96	0,78	2,01
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

As abovementioned, people belonging to an ethnic or minority group are the most likely to agree with the importance of protecting those who support the victims of direct gender violence in order to promote active solidarity. The following figure represents this trend:

¹³ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year

Figure 42. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent do you agree that, in order to promote active solidarity with victims of direct gender violence, it is necessary to protect those who support these victims?" across vulnerable groups

Therefore, there are not notable differences in the results from people from vulnerable groups compared with the total of respondents. However, in people belonging to ethnic or religious minority groups, the proportion of those who agree to some extent with the importance of protecting victims of Isolating Gender Violence is slightly higher than the total of respondents.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

This section analyses the impact of two interactions with science in the responses of people from vulnerable groups. The interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Do the scientific people you follow share anecdotes or evidence about science?

In the analysis of the impact of these interactions, we have included the responses of those respondents who had interacted with science; thus, the responses in this section are those from participants who answered "yes" to interaction 1 and "yes, often" and "yes, rarely" in interaction 2.

In this case, we can observe that in general, interactions with science tend to increase the proportion of people from vulnerable groups who agree with the importance of protecting those who support the victims of gender violence to overcome gender-based violence. This way, in all vulnerable groups across the analysed interactions, more than 6 out of 10 of the respondents agree to some extent with this question.

Regarding interaction 1 (changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families), between 63.45% (youth aged 16-24) and 72.74% (women) of the respondents from vulnerable groups agree to some extent with the importance of protection those who support victims of gender violence, with increases up to 10%, compared with the total of respondents. The highest increase is found in women (11.86%).

When people interact with science by following on social media someone who often publishes about science (interaction 2.often), the proportion of those who agree to some extent is comprised between 66.90% (youth 16-24) and 76.84% (women), compared with the 52.94%-68.26% of the total. The increases in this case range from 8% to 18% approximately, with a maximum of 18.12% (women).

Finally, when people followed on social media rarely publishes about science, the percentage of agreement with the importance of protecting those who support the victims of gender violence range from 68.47 (youth 25-34) to 73.44% (low SES), with increases ranging from 2.70% (ethnic minorities) to 21.46% (youth 16-24).

Table 47. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent have you become aware of scientific evidence on education through information sources or from face to face or digital conversations with other persons?" across vulnerable groups and interactions

		Woman	LGBTI +	Youth 16-24	Youth 25-34	Low SES	Ethnic minorities	Religious minorities	TOTAL
To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships?									
INTERACTION 1	Totally disagree	4,99	8,33	10,66	5,91	6,65	10,16	7,77	4,96
	More or less disagree	8,25	8,33	11,68	10,10	9,37	12,89	16,25	9,22
	More or less agree	42,51	50,00	37,06	45,07	40,79	41,80	37,10	42,70
	Totally agree	30,23	8,33	26,40	25,86	31,42	28,91	31,80	29,64
	I do not know	12,76	16,67	11,68	12,07	9,97	5,47	6,36	12,05
	Rejected	1,25	8,33	2,54	0,99	1,81	0,78	0,71	1,44
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Often	Totally disagree	4,57	0,00	7,04	5,57	8,52	10,42	9,49	5,04
	More or less disagree	6,60	0,00	8,45	7,32	8,81	9,03	12,03	7,22
	More or less agree	41,79	42,86	35,21	43,90	35,80	37,50	36,71	41,13
	Totally agree	35,03	28,57	31,69	32,75	35,23	36,81	34,81	33,74
	I do not know	11,00	28,57	15,49	9,76	11,08	6,25	6,33	11,57
	Rejected	1,02	0,00	2,11	0,70	0,57	0,00	0,63	1,30
	TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
INTERACTION 2. Rarely	Totally disagree	4,32	0,00	6,09	4,93	5,63	8,25	8,09	3,79
	More or less disagree	7,27	0,00	6,96	11,33	9,06	10,31	11,76	9,52
	More or less agree	47,54	57,14	53,04	46,80	47,81	48,45	41,18	46,16

Totally agree	24,56	14,29	20,00	21,67	25,63	21,65	26,47	26,34
I do not know	15,13	28,57	13,04	13,30	10,31	10,31	11,76	12,83
Rejected	1,18	0,00	0,87	1,97	1,56	1,03	0,74	1,36
		100,0	100,0					
TOTAL	100,00	0	0	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Decreases more than 15%	Decreases less than 15%	Increases	Interaction 1: Changing their mind about science because something happened Interaction 2: Following on social media someone who [often/rarely] publishes about science
Increases more than 50%	Increases more than 100%		

This figure shows the impact of interactions with science in increasing the proportion of respondents who agree with the importance of protecting those who support the victims of gender violence (columns and primary axis). All interactions increase the proportion of respondents in all vulnerable groups who agree to some extent and, generally, the most impactful interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science. In addition, it represents the increases produced in the responses due to interactions with science (lines and secondary axis). As we can observe, the highest impact of interaction 1 and interaction 2.often is achieved in women and in interaction 2.rarely in youth 16-24.

Figure 43. Changes in the distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "To what extent have you become aware of scientific evidence on education through information sources or from face to face or digital conversations with other persons?" across vulnerable groups and interactions

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Therefore, interactions have an impact in increasing the proportion of people who agree to some extent with the importance of protecting those who support the victims of gender violence. In all vulnerable groups across the analysed interactions, more than 6 out of 10 of the respondents agree to some extent with this question. In general, the highest impact of interactions is found in women and the least in ethnic minorities. Finally, the results suggest that the most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science.

5.6. Section 4 – Analysis of associations related to education

To analyze the impact of the interactions on the perception or recognition that respondents may have of the survey to distinguish between scientific evidence and hoax, we have introduced two phrases in the questionnaire: one of them is scientific evidence, while the other is a hoax.

The sentences are:

- The academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities
- The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income.

5.6.1. Statement 1: Schools cannot overcome inequalities

Regarding the statement “the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities”, 43% of the respondents to the survey consider this to be a hoax.

RESULTS BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

As we have seen, almost half of the people interviewed when they read the phrase "the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities", they recognize that this is a hoax. If we look at whether or not vulnerable groups impact the perception of this phrase as a hoax, we see that, in general, this is not the case. For example, this ratio holds when looking at the responses of men and women. The variable "sex" does not impact the recognition (or not) of hoaxes. Of the 3839 women who participated in the survey, 1198 (31.4%) claim this is scientific evidence, while 1649 women (43.2% of the respondents) claim this is a hoax. Something similar also occurs when considering other genders: almost half of the people who define themselves as trans, non-binary, fluid, or other gender identities (other) usually recognize this phrase as a hoax. As we can see, the data is significant, which means that the differences among gender are meaningful.

Table 48. Chi square test for the statement “the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities”, by gender.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	36,824 ^a	18	,006
Likelihood ratio	29,030	18	,048
Linear-by-linear Association	,030	1	,862
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 13 cells (46.4%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

Also the analysis of the response by the low SES group of people reveals that differences among SES are significant.

Table 49. Chi square test for the statement “the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities”, by low level of SES.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	148,134 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	141,144	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	31,558	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.12.

When we compare the results by other vulnerable groups, such as ethnic minorities and religious minorities, the data obtained suggests a change in trend: people belonging to one of these vulnerable groups generally think that the phrase mentioned is more scientific evidence than a hoax. This is the case for people who claim to belong to an ethnic minority group: in this case differences among people belonging (or not) to minority groups are significant.

Table 50. Chi square test for the statement “the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities”, by minority groups.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	199,770 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	161,204	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	91,208	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (6.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.28.

The same happens when asking people who claim to belong to a religious minority group: they also no longer recognize that this phrase is a hoax (35.8%), and they tend to affirm that it is scientific evidence (42.6%). Again, data reveals that difference among people belonging (or not) to religious minority groups are significant.

Table 51. Chi square test for the statement “the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities”, by religious minority group.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	148,463 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	127,142	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	57,772	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (6.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.06.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

What happens when we take interactions into account, and can social interactions change the above results in any way?

When we compare these data to whether or not the people participating in the survey have (or do not have) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science, we see that the results do change. Those who say that they have someone close to them who is engaged in science tend to recognize the above statement as a hoax to a greater extent than those who do not have someone close to them engaged in science.

This is true for women and people who belong to one of the LGBTBI+ groups.

Table 52. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science and their opinion about the phrase “the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities” by gender.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				Total
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	
Women					
Scientific-evidence	35,6	28,8	30,1	37,5	31,4
Hoax	46,4	43,6	34,8	25,0	43,2
I do not know	16,3	25,9	31,3	30,0	23,3
Rejected	1,7	1,8	3,9	7,5	2,1
Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
LGTBI+					
Scientific-evidence	25,0	26,7	28,6	0,0	25,5
Hoax	50,0	43,3	42,9	50,0	45,1
I do not know	25,0	26,7	28,6	0,0	25,5
Rejected	0,0	3,3	0,0	50,0	3,9
Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer					
Scientific-evidence	33,3	18,8	40,0	33,3	27,3
Hoax	22,2	37,5	20,0	0,0	27,3
I do not know	44,4	37,5	40,0	0,0	36,4
Rejected	0,0	6,3	0,0	66,7	9,1
Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total					
Scientific-evidence	35,5	28,6	30,2	35,6	31,3
Hoax	46,2	43,5	34,7	24,4	43,1
I do not know	16,6	26,0	31,3	26,7	23,4
Rejected	1,6	1,8	3,8	13,3	2,2
Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

In the case of women, almost one in two recognize this phrase as a hoax (46.4%). The data also suggest that in the case of belonging to an LGBTBI+ group, if one has a close relationship with

someone engaged in or interested in science, one also tends to recognize the phrase "the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities" as a hoax (50%).

Table 53. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science and their opinion about the phrase "the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities", by SES level.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
SES (level 2 and below)					
Scientific-evidence	41,4	31,4	34,7	18,2	34,9
Hoax	44,3	41	27,9	36,4	39,9
I do not know	11,3	25,7	34,7	36,4	22,7
Rejected	2,9	1,9	2,6	9,1	2,4
Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

This change also occurs when we look at the responses of people who have low SES: those who have relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science are also more likely to recognize that the phrase "the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities" is a hoax.

Table 54. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science and their opinion about the phrase "the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities", for belonging to an ethnic minority group.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Ethnic minority group					
Scientific-evidence	47,7%	40,2%	38,9%	33,3%	44%
Hoax	38,6%	39,7%	38,9%	33,3%	39%
I do not know	11,6%	18,5%	20,4%	33,3%	15,1%
Rejected	2,2%	1,6%	1,9%	0%	1,9%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

However, when asking people who identify themselves as members of ethnic minority groups and say they have relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science, this fact does not produce a change in the trend: they continue to affirm that the phrase is scientific evidence in 47.7% of the cases, while 38.6% say it is a hoax.

Table 55. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science and their opinion about the phrase "the academic results depend on the economic and educational level of the families. Schools cannot overcome inequalities", for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Religious minority group					

Scientific-evidence	47,5%	37,6%	40,8%	40%	42,6%
Hoax	37%	34%	36,6%	20%	35,8%
I do not know	13,2%	27,1%	18,3%	40%	19,7%
Rejected	2,3%	0,8%	4,2%	0%	1,9%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

The trend remains the same for people who claim to belong to religious minority groups. Having acquaintances who work in or are interested in science does not seem to have any impact on whether they recognize (or not) the phrase as a hoax (37%) rather than as scientific evidence (47.5%).

5.6.2. Statement 2

Regarding the statement “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, we can see that 58.4% of the people who responded to the survey consider this to be scientific evidence.

RESULTS BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

According to the data, it appears that more than half of the respondents identify this second statement as scientific evidence. When we review the data according to gender, we see that this trend is reversed. The gender variable does change the results. In the case of women, 43.2% say that the statement "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income" is a hoax (compared to 31.4% who recognize it as scientific evidence). When zooming in on these data, considering the vulnerable gender groups, we see that this trend that we had already noticed in the previous table is accentuated: women tend to think that the phrase is a hoax (43%), compared to 31% who recognize it as scientific evidence; and in the case of people who declare themselves LGTBI+, the same thing happens: 45% say it is a hoax, compared to 25% who say it is scientific-evidence. Differences between women, LGTBI+ and people who do not want to specify their gender are statistically significant.

Table 56. Chi Square test of the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, by vulnerable gender groups.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	64,633 ^a	30	,000
Likelihood ratio	37,186	30	,172
Linear-by-linear Association	1,472	1	,225
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 24 cells (57.1%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

When we look at these data according to the SES group, the trend changes and it is just the other way around: the phrase is recognized as scientific evidence, not as a hoax. People with low SES tend to state that the phrase “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income” is scientific evidence (60,5%), well above the 17.6% who say it is a hoax. Again, the differences are statistically significant.

Table 57. Chi Square test of the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, by low SES

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	274,779 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	261,201	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	53,088	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.66.

The same happens when looking at the data according to the ethnic minority group: people tend to recognize this phrase as scientific evidence (63.5%) compared to 20.7% who say that it is a hoax. The differences among people who declares belonging to a ethnic minority group (or not) are significant.

Table 58. Chi Square test of the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, by ethnic minority groups.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	212,988 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	154,179	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	113,691	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (6.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.59.

This tendency is maintained when observing the data taking into account whether the respondents belong (or not) to a religious minority group. Again, data reveals that differences are significant.

Table 59. Chi Square test of the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, by religious minority groups.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	141,693 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	105,779	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	75,224	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (6.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.43.

Therefore, in all cases, people belonging to vulnerable groups tend to recognize that school does serve to overcome inequalities.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

Knowing someone close to you who is a professional in education has a strong impact on recognizing the school as a place that can help overcome inequalities and enable children from low-income families to achieve educational success. 64.4% of people who say they have a friend or relative in education think that school does contribute to overcoming inequalities, compared to 18.3% who think it is a hoax. This result is higher than that obtained from the responses of the total sample (58.4%), which means that social interactions impact the degree of the information we have to deal with hoaxes and/or recognize scientific evidence.

Table 60. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income.”

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				Total
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
Scientific evidence	64,4%	55,1%	44,0%	42,3%	58,4%
Hoax	18,3%	20,7%	13,5%	9,9%	19,2%
I do not know	15,9%	22,9%	38,5%	36,6%	20,8%
Rejected	1,4%	1,3%	4,1%	11,3%	1,6%
	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

When examining this result according to vulnerable groups, in the case of gender, the trend is the same; the same happens as in the previous case: women who have family members or friends who work in education also agree that school serves to overcome inequalities (62.1%), compared to 19.4% who believe that this is a hoax. In the case of LGTBI+ people, that proportion even increases: 78.6% agree that it is scientific evidence, compared to 14.3% who say it is a hoax.

Table 61. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, by gender.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				Total
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	
Women					
Scientific-evidence	62,1%	53,9%	43,7%	43,2%	56,9%
Hoax	19,4%	20,8%	16,4%	10,8%	19,9%
I do not know	17,3%	23,8%	36,1%	45,9%	21,8%
Rejected	1,2%	1,5%	3,8%	0,0%	1,4%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
LGTBI+					
Scientific-evidence	78,6%	54,5%	66,7%	0,0%	62,8%
Hoax	14,3%	22,7%	16,7%	0,0%	18,6%
I do not know	28,6%	59,1%	50,0%	0,0%	46,5%
Rejected	92,9%	59,1%	83,3%	100,0%	74,4%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
Prefer not to answer					
Scientific-evidence	22,2%	56,3%	60,0%	0,0%	42,4%
Hoax	33,3%	18,8%	0,0%	33,3%	21,2%

I do not know	44,4%	18,8%	40,0%	0,0%	27,3%
Rejected	0,0%	6,3%	0,0%	66,7%	9,1%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
Total					
Scientific-evidence	64,4%	55,1%	44,0%	42,3%	58,4%
Hoax	18,3%	20,7%	13,5%	9,9%	19,2%
I do not know	15,9%	22,9%	38,5%	36,6%	20,8%
Rejected	1,4%	1,3%	4,1%	11,3%	1,6%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

When looking to the chi-square test, data reveals that differences among gender are significant.

Table 62. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income", by vulnerable gender groups.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	36,824 ^a	18	,006
Likelihood ratio	29,030	18	,048
Linear-by-linear Association	,030	1	,862
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 13 cells (46.4%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

In the case of low SES people, it is confirmed that they see school as a resource to overcome the inequalities that families like them have to face in their everyday lives. This is true to a greater extent than in other vulnerable groups. In the case of low SES families, 66.6% agree that the statement "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income" is scientific evidence, compared to 17.4% who say it is a hoax.

Table 63. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income", by SES level.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				Total
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	
SES (level 2 and below)					
Scientific-evidence	66,6%	57,2%	51,7%	58,8%	60,5%
Hoax	17,4%	18,2%	12,5%	17,6%	17,6%
I do not know	15,0%	23,6%	30,0%	11,8%	20,6%
Rejected	1,1%	1,0%	5,8%	11,8%	1,4%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Differences among people in terms of their SES level are significant.

Table 64. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income", by low SES groups.

Chi-Square Test			
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	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	274,779 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	261,201	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	53,088	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.66.

The general trend is the same if we look at what happens with people who say they belong to ethnic minority groups. More than half (65%) agree with considering as scientific evidence that school serves to overcome inequalities (which is more than the percentage of the sample when not considering whether or not one belongs to a vulnerable group).

Table 65. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, for belonging to an ethnic minority group.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				Total
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	
Ethnic minority group					
Scientific-evidence	65,0%	60,8%	71,4%	33,3%	63,5%
Hoax	19,7%	23,1%	9,5%	33,3%	20,7%
I do not know	13,7%	14,1%	19,0%	33,3%	14,1%
Rejected	1,7%	2,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,7%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Differences among people belonging (or not) to ethnic minority groups are significant.

Table 66. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, for ethnic minorities.

	Chi-Square Test		
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	212,988 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	154,179	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	113,691	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (6.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.59.

The same trend is repeated in the case of people who say they belong to religious minority groups.

Table 67. Percentage of respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”, for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Having (or not) relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science				Total
	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	

Religious minority group					
Scientific-evidence	67,0%	58,5%	68,8%	25,0%	63,4%
Hoax	18,3%	18,8%	9,4%	25,0%	18,1%
I do not know	12,6%	21,9%	18,8%	25,0%	16,7%
Rejected	2,0%	0,8%	3,1%	25,0%	1,7%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Data also reveals that differences among people belonging to religious minority groups are significant.

Table 68. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income", for religious minorities.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	141,693 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	105,779	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	75,224	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (6.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.43.

Therefore, the data suggest that people generally agree that saying that school helps overcome inequalities is scientific evidence. Moreover, when interacting with someone who works in the educational field, more people agree with this statement. This is especially true in the case of families with low SES and for people who say they belong to religious minority groups. In both cases, more people say that it is scientific evidence to say that school serves to overcome inequalities than in any of the other vulnerable groups considered.

5.6.3. Impact of scientific research on academic performance

According to previous studies, the contributions of scientific research have a significant impact on students' academic outcomes. When education professionals have high expectations of their students, students tend to achieve better learning outcomes. More than half of the respondents are either more or less or totally agree with this statement (61.7%), compared to only 3.7% who say they totally disagree with this statement. These people claim to know teachers who act with high expectations.

RESULTS BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

If we look at the results according to membership in a vulnerable group, this trend holds in general. For example, when we consider the case of people according to the gender they declare, we see that both in the case of women, as well as in the case of people who register in one of the LGBTBI+ groups, they coincide in stating that they know teachers who act with high expectations. However, the case of trans people stands out, who gives a different opinion and

states that they generally disagree, i.e., that they do not know teachers who act with high expectations. In this case, 57.1% of the respondents' state that they disagree (more or less disagree).

Table 69. Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations, per gender.

	Woman	Trans	LGTBI+ (without trans)	Prefer not to answer	Total
Totally disagree	3,9	0,0	4,5	6,1	3,9
More or less disagree	17,1	57,1	20,5	24,2	17,3
More or less agree	44,2	14,3	38,6	27,3	44,0
Totally agree	17,1	14,3	15,9	9,1	17,0
I do not know	17,1	14,3	18,2	24,2	17,1
Prefer not to answer	0,6	0,0	2,3	9,1	0,6
Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Data is statistically significant.

Table 70. Chi Square test of the sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations", by gender.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	64,633 ^a	30	,000
Likelihood ratio	37,186	30	,172
Linear-by-linear Association	1,472	1	,225
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 24 cells (57.1%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

The analysis of the response by the low SES group of people show that differences in terms of SES level are statistically significant.

Table 71. Chi Square test of the sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations", by low SES.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	169,397 ^a	25	,000
Likelihood ratio	160,736	25	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	8,603	1	,003
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (2.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.42.

When we take into account membership (or not) of an ethnic minority group, we see that the trend is also maintained, and there are even more people who claim to know teachers who act with high expectations (66.4%), compared to 62.4% of people who, not belonging to an ethnic minority group, also claim to know teachers of this type. On the other side (people who do not know teachers who act based on high expectations), people who belong to ethnic minority groups also outnumber those who do not belong to any ethnic minority group (7.1% vs. 3.3%), which indicates that more people from ethnic minorities meet teachers who do not act based

on high expectations than people who do not belong to ethnic minorities. Data is statistically significant.

Table 72. Chi Square test of the sentence “Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations”, by ethnic minorities.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	350,530 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	196,206	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	33,086	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 4 cells (16.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .68.

In the case of people belonging to religious minorities, the results are similar.

Table 73. Chi Square test of the sentence “Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations”, by religious minorities.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	329,534 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	183,374	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	35,531	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 4 cells (16.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .68.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

When analyzing the impact that the interactions may have on the affirmation of knowing (or not) teachers who act based on high expectations, we can observe that, in general, the respondents to the survey affirm in a greater proportion that they do know this type of teachers. In the case of gender, this tendency is evident, as shown in the following table.

Table 74. Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations, per gender and “Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends”.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Woman	Totally disagree	4,1	3,1	11,5	0,0	3,9
	More or less disagree	17,8	17,1	12,6	10,8	17,1
	More or less agree	46,3	43,4	39,9	16,2	44,2
	Totally agree	20,0	15,1	13,7	16,2	17,1
	I do not know	11,4	20,9	21,9	43,2	17,1
	Prefer not to answer	0,4	0,5	0,5	13,5	0,6

	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
LGTBI+	Totally disagree	11,1	50,0	16,7	0,0	27,9
	More or less disagree	44,4	16,7	16,7	0,0	27,9
	More or less agree	27,8	27,8	33,3	0,0	27,9
	Totally agree	11,1	38,9	66,7	100,0	32,6
	I do not know	44,4	77,8	83,3	0,0	62,8
	Prefer not to answer	11,1	44,4	0,0	0,0	23,3
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer	Totally disagree	11,1	6,3	0,0	0,0	6,1
	More or less disagree	22,2	25,0	40,0	0,0	24,2
	More or less agree	44,4	25,0	20,0	0,0	27,3
	Totally agree	0,0	18,8	0,0	0,0	9,1
	I do not know	22,2	18,8	40,0	33,3	24,2
	Prefer not to answer	0,0	6,3	0,0	66,7	9,1
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total	Totally disagree	4,3	3,6	11,3	0,0	4,2
	More or less disagree	18,1	17,2	13,4	9,8	17,3
	More or less agree	46,1	43,1	39,2	14,6	43,9
	Totally agree	19,8	15,3	14,9	17,1	17,2
	I do not know	11,9	21,3	24,2	41,5	17,6
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,9	0,5	17,1	0,9
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Data is statistically significant, except for the LGTBI+ groups, because there is not enough responses (due to the simple size effect).

Table 75. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations", by gender.

		Chi-Square Test		
What is your gender		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Woman	Pearson Chi-square	236,412 ^b	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	139,261	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	32,243	1	,000
	N of valid cases	3815		
Man	Pearson Chi-square	158,820 ^c	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	144,999	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	28,465	1	,000
	N of valid cases	3608		
Trans	Pearson Chi-square	7,438 ^d	6	,282
	Likelihood ratio	8,881	6	,180
	Linear-by-linear Association	2,342	1	,126
	N of valid cases	7		
Non binary	Pearson Chi-square	24,000 ^e	6	,001
	Likelihood ratio	24,274	6	,000

	Linear-by-linear Association	1,419	1	,234
	N of valid cases	12		
Fluid	Pearson Chi-square	1,200 ^f	2	,549
	Likelihood ratio	1,588	2	,452
	Linear-by-linear Association	,059	1	,808
	N of valid cases	6		
Others	Pearson Chi-square	17,292 ^g	15	,302
	Likelihood ratio	19,362	15	,198
	Linear-by-linear Association	,928	1	,335
	N of valid cases	26		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	20,412 ^h	15	,157
	Likelihood ratio	18,080	15	,258
	Linear-by-linear Association	5,106	1	,024
	N of valid cases	33		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	386,778 ^a	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	268,598	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	67,636	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .47.

b. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .20.

c. 4 cells (16.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .21.

d. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.

and. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.

f. 6 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.

g. 24 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

h. 24 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

We can observe that in all groups, knowing a teacher who acts based on high expectations is higher if we compare having (or not) an acquaintance (or relative) who works in education. For example, in the case of women, we see that those who say that they have someone close (family member or friend) working in education say that they agree or strongly agree with that statement in 66.3% (compared to 58.5% of those who do not have people close to them who are education professionals).

However, in the case of people from one of the LGBTBI+ groups, the opposite is true: in this case, it is the people who have no acquaintances in the field of education who say more that they do know teachers who act based on high expectations (66.7% compared to 38.9% of those who do know someone in education).

Table 76. “Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations”, per low SES and “Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends.”

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends?				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Low SES	Totally disagree	5,6	3,2	13,3	0,0	4,6
	More or less disagree	15,4	17,8	8,3	23,5	16,4
	More or less agree	44,4	40,8	40,8	29,4	42,1
	Totally agree	24,6	16,2	15,0	23,5	19,3
	I do not know	9,7	21,2	20,8	17,6	16,9
	Prefer not to answer	0,2	0,8	1,7	5,9	0,7

	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
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Differences in terms of SES level are statistically significant.

Table 77. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations", by low SES.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	386,778 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	268,598	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	67,636	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .47.

The impact of knowing someone who works in education is much greater in the case of people who say they are low SES. In this case, those who say that they know teachers who act with high expectations are 69.1%, compared to 57% who say the same, among low SES people who do not know anyone working in education.

Table 78. Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations, per ethnic minority group and "Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends."

Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends?						
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Yes (ethnic m. group)	Totally disagree	7,7	5,0	19,0	0,0	7,1
	More or less disagree	13,3	21,6	4,8	0,0	16,1
	More or less agree	38,7	35,7	47,6	33,3	37,9
	Totally agree	31,3	25,6	19,0	0,0	28,5
	I do not know	8,7	11,1	4,8	33,3	9,6
	Prefer not to answer	0,3	1,0	4,8	33,3	1,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
No (ethnic m. group)	Totally disagree	3,3	2,9	9,1	5,7	3,3
	More or less disagree	17,3	17,5	13,4	20,0	17,3
	More or less agree	49,2	43,4	36,8	25,7	45,6
	Totally agree	19,6	14,5	16,7	17,1	16,8
	I do not know	10,3	21,1	23,9	31,4	16,7
	Prefer not to answer	0,3	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,4
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know (ethnic m. group)	Totally disagree	3,3	6,2	5,8	0,0	5,2
	More or less disagree	19,2	11,8	10,7	28,6	13,8
	More or less agree	40,0	41,0	35,5	14,3	38,8
	Totally agree	14,2	10,8	9,1	14,3	11,3

	I do not know	22,5	29,7	34,7	42,9	29,3
	Prefer not to answer	0,8	0,5	4,1	0,0	1,6
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (ethnic m. group)	Totally disagree	4,8	7,1	7,7	0,0	4,9
	More or less disagree	28,6	14,3	7,7	11,5	15,7
	More or less agree	33,3	28,6	30,8	23,1	28,4
	Totally agree	4,8	23,8	15,4	15,4	16,7
	I do not know	19,0	21,4	38,5	19,2	22,5
	Prefer not to answer	9,5	4,8	0,0	30,8	11,8
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (ethnic m. group)	Totally disagree	3,7	3,2	8,5	2,8	3,7
	More or less disagree	17,1	17,4	11,8	16,9	17,0
	More or less agree	47,7	42,8	36,8	23,9	44,4
	Totally agree	20,4	15,0	14,3	15,5	17,3
	I do not know	10,7	21,0	26,9	28,2	17,0
	Prefer not to answer	0,4	0,6	1,6	12,7	0,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Differences are significant in terms of belonging (or not) to an ethnic minority group.

Table 79. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations", by ethnic minorities.

Chi-Square Test				
Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	57,226 ^b	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	28,453	15	,019
	Linear-by-linear Association	,025	1	,875
	N of valid cases	523		
No	Pearson Chi-square	188,446 ^c	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	188,498	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	39,477	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6439		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	20,286 ^d	15	,161
	Likelihood ratio	19,820	15	,179
	Linear-by-linear Association	4,402	1	,036
	N of valid cases	443		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	21,653 ^e	15	,117
	Likelihood ratio	22,448	15	,097
	Linear-by-linear Association	6,937	1	,008
	N of valid cases	102		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	386,778 ^a	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	268,598	15	,000

Linear-by-linear Association	67,636	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

- a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .47.
- b. 12 cells (50.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.
- c. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.
- d. 9 cells (37.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .11.
- and. 17 cells (70.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .64.

Of those who do belong to an ethnic minority group and know someone close to them who is involved in education, 70% say they do know teachers who act based on high expectations, compared to 7.7% who disagree (i.e., they do not know teachers who act based on high expectations). When ethnic minorities who do not have anyone close to them in education respond, these percentages drop to 61.3% (those who say they do know teachers who act based on high expectations), and 5% (those who say they do not know such teachers). In other words, having someone in the family or in close friendships who is involved in education impacts whether or not they know teachers who have high expectations (or, in other words, that interactions have a great impact).

As we can see in the table below, in the case of people belonging to religious minority groups, the tendency is the same as in the previous case: those who have interactions with people involved in the world of education say to a greater extent that they know teachers who act based on high expectations than those who are not related to the field of education.

Table 80. Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations, per religious minority group and "Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends."

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close Friends?				Total
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
Yes (religious m. group)	Totally disagree	6,3	5,8	9,4	0,0	6,2
	More or less disagree	14,9	18,5	15,6	75,0	16,7
	More or less agree	41,5	38,8	43,8	25,0	40,5
	Totally agree	28,7	25,8	15,6	0,0	26,7
	I do not know	8,3	10,8	12,5	0,0	9,5
	Prefer not to answer	0,3	0,4	3,1	0,0	0,5
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
No (religious m. group)	Totally disagree	3,3	3,0	9,0	5,6	3,4
	More or less disagree	17,3	17,6	13,1	13,9	17,3
	More or less agree	48,7	43,1	38,0	22,2	45,2
	Totally agree	19,8	14,3	16,7	22,2	16,8
	I do not know	10,6	21,3	22,6	33,3	16,9
	Prefer not to answer	0,3	0,6	0,5	2,8	0,5
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know (religious m. group)	Totally disagree	4,8	1,5	7,5	0,0	4,3
	More or less disagree	16,9	12,8	7,5	40,0	12,5
	More or less agree	43,4	39,1	31,8	20,0	37,5
	Totally agree	8,4	12,8	9,3	0,0	10,4
	I do not know	25,3	33,8	40,2	40,0	33,8
	Prefer not to answer	1,2	0,0	3,7	0,0	1,5

	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (religious m. group)	Totally disagree	4,2	7,9	0,0	0,0	4,3
	More or less disagree	25,0	10,5	25,0	7,7	14,1
	More or less agree	45,8	47,4	50,0	26,9	41,3
	Totally agree	8,3	13,2	0,0	11,5	10,9
	I do not know	8,3	18,4	25,0	23,1	17,4
	Prefer not to answer	8,3	2,6	0,0	30,8	12,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (religious m. group)	Totally disagree	3,7	3,2	8,5	2,8	3,7
	More or less disagree	17,1	17,4	11,8	16,9	17,0
	More or less agree	47,7	42,8	36,8	23,9	44,4
	Totally agree	20,4	15,0	14,3	15,5	17,3
	I do not know	10,7	21,0	26,9	28,2	17,0
	Prefer not to answer	0,4	0,6	1,6	12,7	0,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

However, differences are **not** significant in terms of belonging (or not) to a religious minority group.

Table 81. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Scientific research shows that when teachers have high expectations of their students, results improve. Teachers who know act with high expectations", by religious minorities.

Chi-Square Test				
Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	20,679 ^b	15	,147
	Likelihood ratio	16,099	15	,376
	Linear-by-linear Association	,446	1	,504
	N of valid cases	645		
No	Pearson Chi-square	193,263 ^c	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	190,902	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	40,946	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6442		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	24,283 ^d	15	,060
	Likelihood ratio	25,725	15	,041
	Linear-by-linear Association	4,389	1	,036
	N of valid cases	328		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	21,435 ^e	15	,123
	Likelihood ratio	22,528	15	,095
	Linear-by-linear Association	12,054	1	,001
	N of valid cases	92		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	386,778 ^a	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	268,598	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	67,636	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .47.

b. 11 cells (45.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

c. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.

d. 11 cells (45.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.
and. 19 cells (79.2%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.

Therefore, and as a summary, the data indicate that interactions have to do with knowing (or not) teachers who act according to what scientific research says and that having high expectations improves student outcomes.

5.6.4. Dialogue between families and schools to foster learning

Another piece of evidence that has been proven by scientific research in education is that the relationship between families and schools, and specifically the participation of families in promoting their children's learning and their progress throughout their educational journey, results in improved academic results for these students. More than half of the people who participated in this survey agree with this statement (55.4%), compared to 5.2% who say they disagree and 19.7% who say they are more or less disagree.

RESULTS BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

When observing the results according to the gender variable, we can see that the trend we have detected in the aggregate data is maintained in the case of women, but not so in the case of people who belong to one of the LGBTI+ groups. In that case, they are more critical of the impact of the relationship between families and school. Differences are statistically significant.

Table 82. Chi Square test of the sentence “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey”, by gender.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	131,208 ^a	18	,000
Likelihood ratio	45,155	18	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	3,939	1	,047
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 13 cells (46.4%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

If we consider the socio-economic variable, people who place themselves in the low SES category also agree in their statements with the general data: only 6.1% are against the statement that the relationship between school and families contributes to the improvement of their children's academic results; 55% state that they are either totally agree or more or less agree. Differences are statistically significant.

Table 83. Chi Square test of the sentence “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey”, by low SES.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	149,730 ^a	25	,000

Likelihood ratio	138,562	25	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	13,775	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (2.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.61.

In the case of people who belong to an ethnic minority group and those who do not belong to any ethnic minority group, the differences are not very marked, and in any case, they coincide with the results for the general population. Those who belong to an ethnic minority group agree with the benefits of family participation in schools by 63.9%, compared to 55.1% of those who do not belong to any ethnic minority group. Differences are statistically significant.

Table 84. Chi Square test of the sentence “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey”, by ethnic minority.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	266,227 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	155,761	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	33,379	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .73.

The trend is repeated in the case of people who claim to belong to religious minority groups, where differences are also statistically significant.

Table 85. Chi Square test of the sentence “Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey”, by religious minority.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	309,948 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	158,789	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	34,014	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 4 cells (16.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .66.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

What happens when respondents to the question of whether or not they agree that family involvement in schools improves students' academic outcomes have someone they know - family or friend - who works in education? In the case of women, the tendency is the same as in the case of the sample in general: they tend to answer that this statement is true, and they do so more if they know someone who works in education than if they do not (60.3% vs. 51.1%).

On the other hand, when we look at the response of people who declare themselves to belong to one of the LGTBI+ groups, the answer is unclear. The LGTBI+ people who agree that families' involvement in schools improves student outcomes are much lower (22.9% of those who know someone in education; and 7.4% those who do not know anyone involved in education). On the

contrary, the predominant responses are either "I do not know" (11.4% of those who do know someone who works in education; and 31.5% of those who do not know anyone), or "I prefer not to answer" (48.6% and 35.2% respectively).

Table 86. Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey, by Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends and by gender.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Woman	Totally disagree	4,6	5,2	6,6	5,4	5,0
	More or less disagree	22,0	19,6	10,4	10,8	20,1
	More or less agree	39,3	37,4	38,3	13,5	38,0
	Totally agree	21,1	13,7	16,9	10,8	17,0
	I do not know	12,7	23,5	27,3	45,9	19,3
	Prefer not to answer	0,4	0,6	0,5	13,5	0,6
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
LGTBI+	Totally disagree	8,6	9,3	5,9	0,0	8,3
	More or less disagree	8,6	16,7	5,9	0,0	12,0
	More or less agree	14,3	5,6	5,9	0,0	8,3
	Totally agree	8,6	1,9	17,6	0,0	7,4
	I do not know	11,4	31,5	23,5	0,0	23,1
	Prefer not to answer	48,6	35,2	41,2	0,0	40,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	0,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer	Totally disagree	11,1	6,3	20,0	0,0	9,1
	More or less disagree	11,1	25,0	20,0	0,0	18,2
	More or less agree	44,4	25,0	20,0	0,0	27,3
	Totally agree	0,0	6,3	0,0	0,0	3,0
	I do not know	22,2	25,0	40,0	0,0	24,2
	Prefer not to answer	11,1	12,5	0,0	100,0	18,2
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total	Totally disagree	4,7	5,3	6,8	4,8	5,1
	More or less disagree	21,7	19,5	10,2	9,5	19,9
	More or less agree	38,8	36,5	35,1	11,9	37,1
	Totally agree	20,7	13,3	16,6	11,9	16,6
	I do not know	12,7	23,7	27,3	40,5	19,4
	Prefer not to answer	1,4	1,6	3,9	21,4	1,9
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Data is statistically significant, except for the LGTBI+ groups, because there is not enough responses (due to the simple size effect).

Table 87. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey", by gender.

Chi-Square Test				
What is your gender		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Woman	Pearson Chi-square	225,418 ^b	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	152,338	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	43,208	1	,000
	N of valid cases	3815		
Man	Pearson Chi-square	103,983 ^c	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	90,445	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	11,461	1	,001
	N of valid cases	3608		
Trans	Pearson Chi-square	7,000 ^d	6	,321
	Likelihood ratio	7,835	6	,250
	Linear-by-linear Association	1,429	1	,232
	N of valid cases	7		
Non binary	Pearson Chi-square	6,333 ^e	8	,610
	Likelihood ratio	8,318	8	,403
	Linear-by-linear Association	,184	1	,668
	N of valid cases	12		
Fluid	Pearson Chi-square	6,000 ^f	3	,112
	Likelihood ratio	5,407	3	,144
	Linear-by-linear Association	2,283	1	,131
	N of valid cases	6		
Others	Pearson Chi-square	29,618 ^g	12	,003
	Likelihood ratio	27,738	12	,006
	Linear-by-linear Association	2,535	1	,111
	N of valid cases	26		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	19,046 ^h	15	,212
	Likelihood ratio	16,666	15	,339
	Linear-by-linear Association	2,573	1	,109
	N of valid cases	33		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	369,509 ^a	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	238,177	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	55,645	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .51.

b. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .23.

c. 4 cells (16.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .20.

d. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.

and. 15 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .33.

f. 8 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.

g. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

h. 24 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

If we consider socioeconomic level, people who report belonging to the low SES also follow the same trend as women: those who know someone who works in education are more likely to say that family involvement does impact improving students' academic results.

Table 88. Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey, by Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends and by low SES.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
SES (level 2 and below)	Totally disagree	5,7	6,3	6,7	5,9	6,1
	More or less disagree	20,9	19,4	12,5	17,6	19,6
	More or less agree	37,7	36,6	40,0	23,5	37,1
	Totally agree	23,4	14,4	13,3	35,3	17,9
	I do not know	11,5	23,0	25,8	11,8	18,7
	Prefer not to answer	0,7	0,4	1,7	5,9	0,6
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Data reveals that differences in terms of SES group level are statistically significant.

Table 89. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey", by low SES.

		Chi-Square Test		
Household Annual Income in Euros		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Item 1	Pearson Chi-square	56,083 ^b	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	50,465	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	5,601	1	,018
	N of valid cases	1202		
Item 2	Pearson Chi-square	38,232 ^c	15	,001
	Likelihood ratio	38,258	15	,001
	Linear-by-linear Association	4,797	1	,029
	N of valid cases	1069		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	83,463 ^f	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	27,333	15	,026
	Linear-by-linear Association	4,760	1	,029
	N of valid cases	363		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	70,282 ^e	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	49,665	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	19,071	1	,000
	N of valid cases	1039		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	369,509 ^a	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	238,177	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	55,645	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .51.

b. 9 cells (37.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

- c. 10 cells (41.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.
- d. 10 cells (41.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.
- and. 10 cells (41.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.
- F. 10 cells (41.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .06.
- g. 5 cells (20.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .73.

Among people belonging to ethnic minority groups, 67.7% of those who know someone who works in education totally agree or more or less agree with the statement that schools that maintain dialogue with families and count on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey. In contrast, this percentage drops to 58.3% in the case of those who do not know anyone in education. In the case of those who do not belong to any ethnic minority group, the trend is similar, but the percentages are somewhat lower (60.4% and 51.2%, respectively).

Table 90. Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey, by Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends and by ethnic minority group.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends?				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Yes (ethnic minority)	Totally disagree	5,7	7,0	0,0	33,3	6,1
	More or less disagree	16,3	19,6	9,5	0,0	17,2
	More or less agree	35,7	37,2	57,1	0,0	36,9
	Totally agree	32,0	21,1	14,3	0,0	27,0
	I do not know	9,7	14,6	19,0	33,3	12,0
	Prefer not to answer	0,7	0,5	0,0	33,3	0,8
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
No (ethnic minority)	Totally disagree	4,6	5,3	8,6	8,6	5,2
	More or less disagree	21,4	20,5	11,5	17,1	20,5
	More or less agree	41,3	37,8	36,4	25,7	39,2
	Totally agree	19,0	13,4	17,2	17,1	15,9
	I do not know	13,2	22,4	25,8	31,4	18,7
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,0	0,5
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know (ethnic minority)	Totally disagree	2,5	4,1	5,0	14,3	4,1
	More or less disagree	16,7	10,8	9,1	0,0	11,7
	More or less agree	46,7	39,5	33,9	42,9	40,0
	Totally agree	14,2	12,8	9,1	0,0	12,0
	I do not know	19,2	31,8	40,5	28,6	30,7
	Prefer not to answer	0,8	1,0	2,5	14,3	1,6
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (ethnic minority)	Totally disagree	4,8	4,8	7,7	3,8	4,9
	More or less disagree	14,3	19,0	23,1	7,7	15,7
	More or less agree	33,3	33,3	30,8	11,5	27,5
	Totally agree	23,8	16,7	7,7	19,2	17,6
	I do not know	23,8	19,0	30,8	26,9	23,5
	Prefer not to answer	0,0	7,1	0,0	30,8	10,8
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (ethnic minority)	Totally disagree	4,6	5,4	6,9	8,5	5,2
	More or less disagree	20,7	19,9	11,0	11,3	19,7

More or less agree	40,9	37,8	36,5	21,1	38,9
Totally agree	20,1	13,8	14,0	15,5	16,5
I do not know	13,1	22,5	30,5	29,6	19,0
Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,6	1,1	14,1	0,7
Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Differences are statistically significant.

Table 91. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey", by ethnic minority.

Chi-Square Test				
Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	64,736 ^b	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	30,365	15	,011
	Linear-by-linear Association	,047	1	,829
	N of valid cases	523		
No	Pearson Chi-square	133,990 ^c	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	137,234	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	24,550	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6439		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	29,359 ^d	15	,014
	Likelihood ratio	26,202	15	,036
	Linear-by-linear Association	8,223	1	,004
	N of valid cases	443		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	21,183 ^e	15	,131
	Likelihood ratio	22,587	15	,093
	Linear-by-linear Association	7,078	1	,008
	N of valid cases	102		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	369,509 ^a	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	238,177	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	55,645	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

- a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .51.
- b. 12 cells (50.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.
- c. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.
- d. 11 cells (45.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .11.
- and. 17 cells (70.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .64.

In the case of religious minority groups, the tendency of the responses is very similar, as can be seen in the table below.

Table 92. Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey, by Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends and by religious minority group.

Is there an education professional among your relatives or close Friends?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Yes (religious minority)	Totally disagree	4,9	5,4	3,1	0,0	5,0
	More or less disagree	18,3	22,3	12,5	75,0	20,0
	More or less agree	37,0	36,9	53,1	25,0	37,7
	Totally agree	30,1	22,3	9,4	0,0	25,7
	I do not know	8,6	13,1	21,9	0,0	11,0
	Prefer not to answer	1,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,6
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
No (religious minority)	Totally disagree	4,6	5,5	6,8	8,3	5,2
	More or less disagree	21,2	20,2	12,2	8,3	20,2
	More or less agree	41,4	37,8	37,6	25,0	39,3
	Totally agree	18,9	13,2	16,3	19,4	15,8
	I do not know	13,5	22,8	26,2	38,9	19,1
	Prefer not to answer	0,4	0,6	0,9	0,0	0,5
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know (religious minority)	Totally disagree	4,8	2,3	7,5	40,0	5,2
	More or less disagree	18,1	11,3	7,5	0,0	11,6
	More or less agree	42,2	40,6	29,0	20,0	36,9
	Totally agree	16,9	12,0	11,2	20,0	13,1
	I do not know	16,9	32,3	43,0	0,0	31,4
	Prefer not to answer	1,2	1,5	1,9	20,0	1,8
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (religious minority)	Totally disagree	8,3	5,3	25,0	3,8	6,5
	More or less disagree	8,3	13,2	25,0	7,7	10,9
	More or less agree	37,5	36,8	50,0	15,4	31,5
	Totally agree	20,8	13,2	0,0	11,5	14,1
	I do not know	20,8	26,3	0,0	26,9	23,9
	Prefer not to answer	4,2	5,3	0,0	34,6	13,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (religious minority)	Totally disagree	4,6	5,4	6,9	8,5	5,2
	More or less disagree	20,7	19,9	11,0	11,3	19,7
	More or less agree	40,9	37,8	36,5	21,1	38,9
	Totally agree	20,1	13,8	14,0	15,5	16,5
	I do not know	13,1	22,5	30,5	29,6	19,0
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,6	1,1	14,1	0,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Differences are statistically significant.

Table 93. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Schools that know the scientific evidence practice maintaining a dialogue with families and counting on their participation to promote learning and progress throughout the educational journey", by religious minority.

Chi-Square Test				
Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	29,156 ^b	15	,015
	Likelihood ratio	30,105	15	,012
	Linear-by-linear Association	,624	1	,430

	N of valid cases	645		
No	Pearson Chi-square	137,605 ^c	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	140,611	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	31,350	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6442		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	46,026 ^d	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	36,154	15	,002
	Linear-by-linear Association	6,084	1	,014
	N of valid cases	328		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	22,819 ^e	15	,088
	Likelihood ratio	22,290	15	,100
	Linear-by-linear Association	6,498	1	,011
	N of valid cases	92		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	369,509 ^a	15	,000
	Likelihood ratio	238,177	15	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	55,645	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .51.

b. 11 cells (45.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

c. 3 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

d. 10 cells (41.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

e. 17 cells (70.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .26.

Therefore, we again find evidence that knowing someone who works in education impacts the interactions that are maintained, and that makes the answer to questions such as the one posted here about the involvement of families in schools to foster student learning positively answered.

5.6.5. Separation of students by learning levels

According to previous research, separating students by homogeneous level groups contributes to increasing educational inequalities. On the other hand, when the groups are diverse (heterogeneous), the results of all students improve. Participants were asked whether they were aware of schools that separate students by level groups in the survey. In general, almost half of the people who participated in the survey were no (47.1%); but one out of three people (31%) did know schools that do.

RESULTS BY VULNERABLE GROUPS

When we ask the same question by vulnerable groups, we see that the trend of the general sample is maintained. In the case of women, 46.1% say that the centers they know do not separate students by ability level, while 32.2% say that they do know centers that practice this practice. In the case of LGBTBI+ people, the response is very similar. When we explore the responses by the socio-economic level of the respondent, we obtain very similar data: 44.3%

state that they do not know of centers that separate students by ability level, compared to 33.7% who say they do.

In the case of people who belong to an ethnic minority group, the response is somewhat different. Half of them say that they do know of schools that group students by level (50.1%), compared to 34.6% who say that they do not know of schools that discriminate against students for this reason. On the contrary, only 29.8% of those who say they do not belong to any ethnic minority group say they know of schools that segregate students by ability level. The same trends is observed in religious minorities.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

What happens when you meet someone who works in education? In the case of women, when they know someone in education, 36.3% say that they segregate by level, compared to 29.3% of women who do not know anyone in education. On the contrary, 48.5% of women who do have someone they know in education say they do not know schools that segregate by level, compared to 45.5% of women who do not know anyone in education.

In the case of LGTBI+ people, the results are different. Among those who do have acquaintances in the world of education, 70% say that they know schools that segregate, compared to 66.7% in the case of people who have no contact with people in the educational field. In contrast, 20% of LGTBI+ people who know someone in education say that the schools they know do not segregate, and 50% of those who do not know anyone in education make the same claim.

Table 94. School segregation by educational level, according to whether or not someone is known to be in education, and by gender.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Woman	If they do it	36,3	29,3	27,3	27,0	32,2
	No, they do not do it	48,5	45,5	34,4	27,0	46,1
	I do not know	14,9	24,5	35,5	35,1	21,0
	Prefer not to answer	0,3	0,7	2,7	10,8	0,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
LGTBI+	If they do it	70,0	66,7	60,0	50,0	18,6
	No, they do not do it	70,0	100,0	40,0	0,0	20,6
	I do not know	20,0	50,0	60,0	0,0	10,8
	Prefer not to answer	160,0	216,7	160,0	50,0	50,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer	If they do it	44,4	37,5	40,0	33,3	39,4
	No, they do not do it	22,2	31,3	20,0	0,0	24,2
	I do not know	11,1	18,8	40,0	0,0	18,2
	Prefer not to answer	22,2	12,5	0,0	66,7	18,2
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total	If they do it	36,6	29,5	28,5	28,6	31,9
	No, they do not do it	48,5	45,8	34,2	23,8	45,3
	I do not know	14,9	24,6	36,3	31,0	20,7
	Prefer not to answer	1,4	2,1	6,7	16,7	2,2
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Data is statistically significant, except for the LGBTBI+ groups, because there is not enough responses (due to the simple size effect).

Table 95. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning", by gender.

		Chi-Square Test		
What is your gender		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Woman	Pearson Chi-square	154,344 ^b	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	114,129	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	80,078	1	,000
	N of valid cases	3815		
Man	Pearson Chi-square	137,580 ^c	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	107,824	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	64,469	1	,000
	N of valid cases	3608		
Trans	Pearson Chi-square	4,667 ^d	4	,323
	Likelihood ratio	5,742	4	,219
	Linear-by-linear Association	3,200	1	,074
	N of valid cases	7		
Non binary	Pearson Chi-square	3,310 ^e	4	,507
	Likelihood ratio	4,302	4	,367
	Linear-by-linear Association	2,386	1	,122
	N of valid cases	12		
Fluid	Pearson Chi-square	6,000 ^f	2	,050
	Likelihood ratio	5,407	2	,067
	Linear-by-linear Association	3,000	1	,083
	N of valid cases	6		
Others	Pearson Chi-square	5,327 ^g	6	,503
	Likelihood ratio	6,796	6	,340
	Linear-by-linear Association	,168	1	,682
	N of valid cases	26		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	8,463 ^h	9	,488
	Likelihood ratio	8,762	9	,460
	Linear-by-linear Association	,646	1	,422
	N of valid cases	33		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	318,746 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	227,100	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	146,178	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

- a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .62.
- b. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .27.
- c. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .27.
- d. 9 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.
- e. 9 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .33.
- f. 6 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.
- g. 11 cells (91.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .27.
- h. 15 cells (93.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .55.

If we take into account socio-economic level, low SES people who do know someone in education say that they mostly do not know schools that segregate by level (45.3%), compared to a similar number of people who do not have friends in the world of education (44.3%). The trend is the same for those who say they know schools that do segregate: 39.5% and 30.4% respectively.

Table 96. School segregation by educational level, according to whether or not someone is known to be in education, and by low SES.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				Total
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
SES (below level 2)	If they do it	39,5	30,4	28,3	29,4	33,7
	No, they do not do it	45,3	44,3	36,7	47,1	44,3
	I do not know	14,8	24,5	30,8	23,5	21,2
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,8	4,2	0,0	0,8
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Differences among SES groups are statistically significant.

Table 97. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning", by low SES

		Chi-Square Test		
Household Annual Income in Euros		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Item 1	Pearson Chi-square	61,245 ^b	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	48,614	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	32,365	1	,000
	N of valid cases	1202		
Item 2	Pearson Chi-square	23,969 ^c	9	,004
	Likelihood ratio	25,474	9	,002
	Linear-by-linear Association	10,847	1	,001
	N of valid cases	1069		
	Likelihood ratio	31,766	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	19,511	1	,000
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	87,328 ^f	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	44,294	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	19,828	1	,000
	N of valid cases	363		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	112,165 ^g	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	77,918	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	43,634	1	,000
	N of valid cases	1039		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	318,746 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	227,100	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	146,178	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .62.

b. 6 cells (37.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

- c. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.
- d. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.
- and. 5 cells (31.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.
- F. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.
- g. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .70.

In the case of persons belonging to ethnic minority groups, among those who do know someone in education, the majority say they do know schools that segregate (54.7%), compared to 42.2% of those who do not know anyone in education. On the other hand, in the case of schools that do not segregate, the percentages are 30.7% and 42.2%, respectively. This trend is reversed among those who do not belong to ethnic minority groups: more people say they do not know segregated schools than those who say the opposite (both for those who know someone in education and those who do not).

Table 98. School segregation by educational level, depending on whether someone is known in education or not, and by ethnic minority group.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Yes (ethnic minority)	If they do it	54,7	42,2	52,4	100,0	50,1
	No, they do not do it	30,7	42,2	23,8	0,0	34,6
	I do not know	13,7	14,1	23,8	0,0	14,1
	Prefer not to answer	1,0	1,5	0,0	0,0	1,1
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
No (Ethnic minority)	If they do it	32,7	27,6	28,2	25,7	29,8
	No, they do not do it	52,0	48,0	36,4	40,0	49,3
	I do not know	14,8	23,7	34,0	31,4	20,3
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,6	1,4	2,9	0,6
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know (ethnic minority)	If they do it	36,7	22,6	19,8	0,0	25,3
	No, they do not do it	35,0	42,1	24,8	42,9	35,4
	I do not know	28,3	34,4	50,4	42,9	37,2
	Prefer not to answer	0,0	1,0	5,0	14,3	2,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (ethnic minority)	If they do it	38,1	35,7	15,4	34,6	33,3
	No, they do not do it	33,3	23,8	23,1	7,7	21,6
	I do not know	28,6	31,0	46,2	30,8	32,4
	Prefer not to answer	0,0	9,5	15,4	26,9	12,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (ethnic minority)	If they do it	35,0	28,2	26,4	29,6	31,0
	No, they do not do it	49,2	47,2	31,3	26,8	47,1
	I do not know	15,3	23,9	39,3	31,0	21,1
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,8	3,0	12,7	0,9
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Data reveals that differences are significant among people declaring that they do not belong to an ethnic minority group, but for people who does, the differences are not significant.

Table 99. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence

“Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning”, by ethnic minority.

Chi-Square Test				
Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	14,067 ^b	9	,120
	Likelihood ratio	15,238	9	,085
	Linear-by-linear Association	1,571	1	,210
	N of valid cases	523		
No	Pearson Chi-square	114,353 ^c	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	112,490	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	73,025	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6439		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	38,675 ^d	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	38,001	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	24,206	1	,000
	N of valid cases	443		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	13,358 ^e	9	,147
	Likelihood ratio	15,856	9	,070
	Linear-by-linear Association	4,780	1	,029
	N of valid cases	102		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	318,746 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	227,100	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	146,178	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

- a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .62.
- b. 8 cells (50.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.
- c. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .21.
- d. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.
- and. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.66.

The percentages for those who belong to a religious minority group are similar but even more marked. In the case of those who belong to a religious minority group, 49.9% of those who do know people in education say they know schools that segregate, compared to 40.4% of those who do not know anyone in education. In contrast, fewer people (in both cases) say that the schools they know do not segregate. When they do not belong to a religious minority group, the majority option (both for those who know someone in education and those who do not) is schools that do not segregate.

Table 100. School segregation by educational level, according to whether or not someone is known to be in education, and by religious minority group.

Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends						
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
		Yes (religious minority)	If they do it	49,9	40,4	37,5
No, they do not do it	37,5		38,1	31,3	50,0	37,5
I do not know	12,0		20,4	28,1	50,0	16,4
Prefer not to answer	0,6		1,2	3,1	0,0	0,9
Total	100,0		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

No (religious minority)	If they do it	32,9	27,5	29,0	30,6	29,9
	No, they do not do it	51,2	48,3	36,2	38,9	49,1
	I do not know	15,4	23,6	33,0	27,8	20,5
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,6	1,8	2,8	0,6
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know (religious minority)	If they do it	37,3	21,8	18,7	40,0	25,0
	No, they do not do it	37,3	42,9	20,6	20,0	33,8
	I do not know	25,3	33,8	55,1	20,0	38,4
	Prefer not to answer	0,0	1,5	5,6	20,0	2,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (religious minority)	If they do it	41,7	31,6	0,0	30,8	32,6
	No, they do not do it	37,5	21,1	50,0	7,7	22,8
	I do not know	20,8	39,5	50,0	34,6	33,7
	Prefer not to answer	0,0	7,9	0,0	26,9	10,9
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (religious minority)	If they do it	35,0	28,2	26,4	29,6	31,0
	No, they do not do it	49,2	47,2	31,3	26,8	47,1
	I do not know	15,3	23,9	39,3	31,0	21,1
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,8	3,0	12,7	0,9
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Differences are statistically significant.

Table 101. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Think about the schools you know best. Students are separated according to their level of learning", by religious minority.

Chi-Square Test				
<i>Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group</i>		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	20,064 ^b	9	,018
	Likelihood ratio	20,153	9	,017
	Linear-by-linear Association	15,990	1	,000
	N of valid cases	645		
No	Pearson Chi-square	102,567 ^c	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	100,165	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	64,452	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6442		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	41,438 ^d	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	39,792	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	21,822	1	,000
	N of valid cases	328		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	19,561 ^e	9	,021
	Likelihood ratio	22,414	9	,008
	Linear-by-linear Association	6,901	1	,009
	N of valid cases	92		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	318,746 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	227,100	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	146,178	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

- a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .62.
- b. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.
- c. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .23.
- d. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.
- and. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .43.

In summary, it seems that in vulnerable groups, what is more, important is the vulnerability factor, not so much whether they know someone (or not) who works in education. Their perception of school segregation (by level) is more marked by their status as a "vulnerable group" than their interactions.

5.6.6. Analysis of diversity at school

Another scientific evidence we can find in the research is that diversity, with appropriate actions, is beneficial for students' academic results.

According to the data collected, the people who participated in the survey are evenly divided between those who have heard of this evidence and those who have not heard of it before (39.6% vs. 40.5%, respectively).

RESULTS BY VULNEABLE GROUPS

Looking at the responses taking into account whether the respondent is from a vulnerable group, we see that in the case of women, the trend is similar to the overall sample: 40.4% had heard of this evidence, while 38.4% did not know that diversity is beneficial when appropriate educational actions are used. In the case of LGTBI+ people, the data indicate that, in general, respondents were not aware of this evidence (47.1%), compared to 23.5% who were aware of it. Differences are statistically significant.

Table 102. Chi Square test of the sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?", by gender.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	124,982 ^a	18	,000
Likelihood ratio	66,202	18	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	9,264	1	,002
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 15 cells (53.6%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

In the case of low SES people, the sample is completely evenly divided: 40.4% had heard of it, compared to 40% who did not know about it. Differences are statistically significant.

Table 103. Chi Square test of the sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?", by low SES.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	131,630 ^a	15	,000
Likelihood ratio	124,179	15	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	28,144	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 1 cells (4.2%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.09.

The trend changes for people from minority groups. In the case of ethnic minority groups, 57.7% of survey respondents who said they were from an ethnic minority group said they had heard that diversity is beneficial (compared to 31% who said they had not). On the other hand, if you are not from an ethnic minority group, only 39.2% had heard that diversity is beneficial (and 41.9% did not know). Differences are statistically significant.

Table 104. Chi Square test of the sentence “Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?”, by ethnic minority.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	465,150 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	249,733	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	185,040	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 3 cells (18.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .87.

In the case of people who say they belong to a religious minority group, the situation is very similar: those who do belong to a religious minority group say that they have heard that diversity is beneficial (54.1%), compared to 34% who have not heard anything about it. On the other hand, among people who say they do not belong to a religious minority group, the percentages are 39.2% and 41.4%, respectively. Differences are statistically significant.

Table 105. Chi Square test of the sentence “Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students?”, by religious minority

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	456,827 ^a	9	,000
Likelihood ratio	219,228	9	,000
Linear-by-linear Association	174,655	1	,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .78.

This indicates that belonging to a vulnerable minority group does affect whether or not diversity is considered beneficial to learning.

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

For people who report knowing someone who works in education, the effect is that they tend to respond to a greater extent that they did know that diversity is beneficial to learning. For women, 49.8% say they have heard of it, compared to 34.6% who have not. On the other hand, when they do not have friends in the world of education, these percentages drop to 33.6% and 42.5%, respectively (i.e., the number of those who had heard of it decreases, and the number of those who had not heard of it increases). In the case of LGTBI+ people, the trend is the same, but with much lower percentages in both cases.

Table 106. Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students? by “Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends” and by gender.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Woman	Yes i heard it	49,8	33,6	32,2	27,0	40,4
	No I haven't heard	34,6	42,5	31,7	24,3	38,4
	I do not know	15,2	23,6	33,9	32,4	20,5
	Prefer not to answer	0,5	0,4	2,2	16,2	0,7
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
LGTBI+	Yes i heard it	15,6	11,5	6,3	0,0	11,8
	No I haven't heard	25,0	26,9	6,3	50,0	23,5
	I do not know	9,4	11,5	37,5	0,0	14,7
	Prefer not to answer	50,0	50,0	50,0	50,0	50,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer	Yes i heard it	11,1	37,5	0,0	0,0	21,2
	No I haven't heard	33,3	25,0	20,0	0,0	24,2
	I do not know	44,4	31,3	80,0	0,0	39,4
	Prefer not to answer	11,1	6,3	0,0	100,0	15,2
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total	Yes i heard it	48,9	33,0	29,4	23,8	39,5
	No I haven't heard	34,4	41,9	29,4	23,8	37,9
	I do not know	15,2	23,3	35,3	28,6	20,5
	Prefer not to answer	1,5	1,7	5,9	23,8	2,1
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Data is statistically significant, except for the LGTBI+ groups, because there is not enough responses (due to the simple size effect).

Table 107. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence “Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students”, by gender.

		Chi-Square Test		
What is your gender		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Woman	Pearson Chi-square	272,303 ^b	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	164,653	9	,000

	Linear-by-linear Association	126,779	1	,000
	N of valid cases	3815		
Man	Pearson Chi-square	194,775 ^c	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	151,069	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	110,360	1	,000
	N of valid cases	3608		
Trans	Pearson Chi-square	7,438 ^d	4	,114
	Likelihood ratio	8,881	4	,064
	Linear-by-linear Association	2,535	1	,111
	N of valid cases	7		
Non binary	Pearson Chi-square	2,117 ^e	4	,714
	Likelihood ratio	2,634	4	,621
	Linear-by-linear Association	1,696	1	,193
	N of valid cases	12		
Fluid	Pearson Chi-square	2,400 ^f	2	,301
	Likelihood ratio	2,634	2	,268
	Linear-by-linear Association	1,690	1	,194
	N of valid cases	6		
Others	Pearson Chi-square	7,897 ^g	6	,246
	Likelihood ratio	9,936	6	,127
	Linear-by-linear Association	1,516	1	,218
	N of valid cases	26		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	24,754 ^h	9	,003
	Likelihood ratio	20,564	9	,015
	Linear-by-linear Association	3,858	1	,049
	N of valid cases	33		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	539,907 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	331,366	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	253,000	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .61.

b. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

c. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .27.

d. 9 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.

and. 9 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .50.

f. 6 cells (100.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.

g. 11 cells (91.7%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .15.

h. 15 cells (93.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .45.

When we consider the socio-economic level, people of low SES who do know someone in education tend to affirm in a much higher percentage that they have heard that diversity is beneficial for learning (54.2%) than people who do not have friends in the field of education (32.2%). The opposite is also true: 32.2% of those who know someone in education say that they have not heard that diversity is beneficial for learning, while if they do not know anyone in education, this percentage rises to 45.9%. In other words, having a relationship with someone who works in education makes it easier to learn about this scientific evidence.

Table 108. Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students? by “Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends” and by low SES.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
SES (below level 2)	Yes i heard it	54,2	32,2	31,7	29,4	40,4
	No I haven't heard	32,2	45,9	32,5	41,2	40,0
	I do not know	12,4	21,4	34,2	23,5	18,7
	Prefer not to answer	1,2	0,5	1,7	5,9	0,8
	Total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Differences are statistically significant.

Table 109. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students", by low SES.

		Chi-Square Test		
Household Annual Income in Euros		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Item 1	Pearson Chi-square	82,758 ^b	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	75,486	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	40,254	1	,000
	N of valid cases	1202		
Item 2	Pearson Chi-square	64,070 ^c	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	64,549	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	46,093	1	,000
	N of valid cases	1069		
Item 3	Pearson Chi-square	62,897 ^d	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	49,695	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	35,292	1	,000
	N of valid cases	1180		
Item 4	Pearson Chi-square	78,378 ^e	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	61,905	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	49,138	1	,000
	N of valid cases	2654		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	157,856 ^f	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	55,242	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	27,138	1	,000
	N of valid cases	363		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	111,349 ^g	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	60,197	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	26,727	1	,000
	N of valid cases	1039		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	539,907 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	331,366	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	253,000	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .61.
 b. 6 cells (37.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .10.
 c. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.
 d. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

and. 5 cells (31.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.
 F. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.
 g. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .70.

In the case of people belonging to minority groups, this trend is repeated, but with even higher percentages. People belonging to ethnic minority groups, who have friends or relatives working in education, say that they have heard that diversity is beneficial for learning in 65.7%. On the other hand, if they do not have friends or family members in education, the percentage drops to 47.2%. In either case, it is much higher than the percentage of those who say they did not know that diversity is beneficial to learning (24.3% and 40.2%, respectively).

Table 110. Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students? by "Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends" and by ethnic minority group.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Yes (ethnic minority)	Yes i heard it	65,7	47,2	47,6	33,3	57,7
	No I haven't heard	24,3	40,2	38,1	33,3	31,0
	I do not know	8,7	12,6	14,3	0,0	10,3
	Prefer not to answer	1,3	0,0	0,0	33,3	1,0
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
No (ethnic minority)	Yes i heard it	48,0	32,9	31,1	28,6	39,2
	No I haven't heard	37,5	45,5	39,7	40,0	41,9
	I do not know	13,9	21,1	27,8	25,7	18,3
	Prefer not to answer	0,6	0,5	1,4	5,7	0,6
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know (ethnic minority)	Yes i heard it	35,8	29,7	16,5	28,6	27,8
	No I haven't heard	34,2	37,9	24,8	28,6	33,2
	I do not know	28,3	31,8	57,0	28,6	37,7
	Prefer not to answer	1,7	0,5	1,7	14,3	1,4
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (ethnic minority)	Yes i heard it	28,6	23,8	23,1	26,9	25,5
	No I haven't heard	33,3	38,1	38,5	15,4	31,4
	I do not know	28,6	28,6	30,8	23,1	27,5
	Prefer not to answer	9,5	9,5	7,7	34,6	15,7
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (ethnic minority)	Yes i heard it	49,1	33,3	26,9	28,2	39,6
	No I haven't heard	36,1	44,8	34,6	29,6	40,5
	I do not know	14,1	21,3	36,8	23,9	19,0
	Prefer not to answer	0,8	0,5	1,6	18,3	0,9
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Differences are statistically significant.

Table 111. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students", by ethnic minority.

Chi-Square Test

<i>Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group</i>		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	55,677 ^b	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	30,295	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	11,671	1	,001
	N of valid cases	523		
No	Pearson Chi-square	192,019 ^c	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	180,159	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	146,331	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6439		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	39,139 ^d	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	33,332	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	19,376	1	,000
	N of valid cases	443		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	11,389 ^e	9	,250
	Likelihood ratio	10,677	9	,298
	Linear-by-linear Association	2,674	1	,102
	N of valid cases	102		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	539,907 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	331,366	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	253,000	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

- a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .61.
- b. 8 cells (50.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.
- c. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .20.
- d. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.
- and. 6 cells (37.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.04.

The same results are repeated in the case of people who say they belong to religious minority groups, as can be seen in the table below.

Table 112. Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students? by "Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends" and by religious minority group.

		Is there an education professional among your relatives or close friends				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Yes (religious minority)	Yes i heard it	63,3	43,5	43,8	25,0	54,1
	No I haven't heard	27,2	42,7	31,3	75,0	34,0
	I do not know	8,9	13,5	25,0	0,0	11,5
	Prefer not to answer	0,6	0,4	0,0	0,0	0,5
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
No (religious minority)	Yes i heard it	48,0	33,1	29,9	30,6	39,2
	No I haven't heard	37,2	45,1	36,7	33,3	41,4
	I do not know	14,3	21,4	32,1	30,6	18,8
	Prefer not to answer	0,6	0,5	1,4	5,6	0,6
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
I do not know	Yes i heard it	32,5	24,8	15,0	20,0	23,5
	No I haven't heard	34,9	44,4	30,8	60,0	37,8
	I do not know	27,7	30,8	51,4	0,0	36,3

(religious minority)	Prefer not to answer	4,8	0,0	2,8	20,0	2,4
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Prefer not to answer (religious minority)	Yes i heard it	25,0	18,4	50,0	26,9	23,9
	No I haven't heard	45,8	36,8	50,0	11,5	32,6
	I do not know	16,7	36,8	0,0	23,1	26,1
	Prefer not to answer	12,5	7,9	0,0	38,5	17,4
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Total (religious minority)	Yes i heard it	49,1	33,3	26,9	28,2	39,6
	No I haven't heard	36,1	44,8	34,6	29,6	40,5
	I do not know	14,1	21,3	36,8	23,9	19,0
	Prefer not to answer	0,8	0,5	1,6	18,3	0,9
		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

The differences among people who declares belonging to a ethnic minority group (or not) are significant.

Table 113. Chi Square test of the respondents according to whether they have (or do not have) relatives or close friends who are education professionals and their opinion about the sentence "Have you heard that it has been scientifically proven that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for the academic results of all students", by religious minorities

Chi-Square Test				
<i>Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group</i>		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Yes	Pearson Chi-square	33,538 ^b	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	32,686	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	19,342	1	,000
	N of valid cases	645		
No	Pearson Chi-square	199,706 ^c	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	186,107	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	154,708	1	,000
	N of valid cases	6442		
I do not know	Pearson Chi-square	32,933 ^d	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	33,214	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	9,951	1	,002
	N of valid cases	328		
Prefer not to answer	Pearson Chi-square	20,404 ^e	9	,016
	Likelihood ratio	21,638	9	,010
	Linear-by-linear Association	3,145	1	,076
	N of valid cases	92		
Total	Pearson Chi-square	539,907 ^a	9	,000
	Likelihood ratio	331,366	9	,000
	Linear-by-linear Association	253,000	1	,000
	N of valid cases	7507		

a. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .61.

b. 8 cells (50.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

c. 2 cells (12.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .21.

d. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

and. 6 cells (37.5%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .70.

5.7. SECTION 5 – ANALYSIS OF THE ASSOCIATIONS RELATED TO GENDER

Concerning gender issues, the respondents showed a certain lack of knowledge about the figure of Simone de Beauvoir. When asked if this feminist author had fought against sexual relations with minors, 60.5% said they did not know, or if, on the contrary, she had defended them, 55.9% did not know. Among those who did speak out, 29.4% of those surveyed thought that the feminist author had taken a stand against sexual relations with minors was scientific evidence, while 8.6% thought it was a hoax. When asked whether the author defended sexual relations with minors, 29.7% thought it was a hoax, and the percentage regarding whether it was scientific evidence increased to 12.4%.

About the environment that surrounds the people encountered in terms of gender, it is observed that most people do not have people around them who think, for example, that girls have less capacity than boys to develop technological and scientific careers. 69.3% of the surveyed affirm this. The 19.2% say that they have people around them who think so. Similarly, when asked whether the people around the respondents think that all men are potential aggressors, only 4.3% said yes. It should also be noted that 26.8% say that some people around them do think so. Above all, 61.4% say that they do not have people around them who think that way.

Finally, concerning questions on gender-based violence and isolating gender violence, more than half of the respondents (54.3%) totally agree or quite agree with the fact that such violence occurs more between partners and ex-partners than in sporadic relationships. Some 22.9% disagreed with this statement. In turn, 65% know what isolating gender violence means in the fight against gender violence. In any case, both in the case of whether gender-based violence occurs more between partners and ex-partners than in sporadic relationships and about knowing what isolating gender violence means, the percentages of not knowing about these issues is high in both cases, with 22% and 21.3% respectively.

Face-to-face and social media interactions can play an essential role in the social impact of scientific research on gender and education in the citizenry, especially on young people and vulnerable groups. Some observations emerge when analyzing the questions related to gender by interactions and attending to the vulnerable groups' variable.

5.7.1. Minority ethnic groups

Concerning the ethnicity variable, 523 respondents (7% of the total) claim to belong to a minority ethnic group.

Of those belonging to a minority ethnic group, 61.3% stated that they had a relative or close friend who had worked or was working on gender equality issues who thought that Simone de Beauvoir fought against sexual relations with minors. The same percentage was lower without considering the variable of belonging to an ethnic minority group; it was 46.1%.

Table 114. Practices or has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality (by belonging to a minority ethnic group in %)

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors</i>	Scientific evidence	61,3	34,4	43,8	100	45,9
	Hoax	20,1	9,2	8,3	0	13,2
	I do not know	17,6	55,7	47,9	0	40,2
	Rejected	1	0,7	0	0	0,8
	Total	100	100	100	100	100

In this specific case, having a family member or close friend who practices or has practiced or has a position in the promotion of gender equality has not impacted this issue being considered less as scientific evidence. On the other hand, the percentage of people who consider it a hoax increased from 8.6% of people who considered it a hoax to 15% when the respondents also stated that they had a family member with professional experience in gender equality issues.

Among people belonging to ethnic minority groups, the percentage rises again to 20.1%. Therefore, the detection of this statement as a hoax increases positively, although it is also considered scientific evidence. It is worth noting that the percentage of people who answer "I do not know" decreases drastically, going from 60.5% to 37.6% when they have had a family member or currently have one working professionally on gender equality issues. Again, this percentage drops when people belong to an ethnic minority group to 17.6%.

Thus, interactions play an essential role since the detection of the hoax varies as much as considering it as scientific evidence when a family member or close friend with professional experience in the field of gender equality intervenes.

[Table 115. Practices or has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality.](#)

<i>Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality</i>		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors</i>	Scientific evidence	422	1581	183	22	2208
	Hoax	46,1%	27,2%	25,5%	31,0%	29,4%
	I do not know	137	439	56	10	642
	Rejected	15,0%	7,6%	7,8%	14,1%	8,6%
	Total	344	3706	458	30	4538
	Rejected	37,6%	63,9%	63,8%	42,3%	60,5%
		12	77	21	9	119
		1,3%	1,3%	2,9%	12,7%	1,6%
Total		915	5803	718	71	7507
		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

It happens similarly about the second of the statements regarding Simone de Beauvoir to discern whether scientific evidence is a hoax. In this case, the statement about the feminist author is scientific evidence. Without considering interactions and the variable ethnicity, 12.4% responded that it is scientific evidence, compared to 29.7% who believe it is a hoax, and a high

percentage of people who did not know (55.9%). If the respondents have a family member or close friend working on gender equality issues, the percentage who consider it scientific evidence rises to 28.6%, and the same percentage for people belonging to an ethnic minority group rises to 51.8%. The percentage that considers it a hoax practically does not vary in any of the cases, and what does vary considerably is the percentage of people who say they do not know since it drops from 55.9% to 36.2%, and in the specific case of people from other minority ethnic groups, it drops to 15.6%.

Table 116. Practices or has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality (by belonging to a minority ethnic group in %)

	Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality				
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, Scientific evidence</i>	51,8	19,4	22,9	33,31	32,1
<i>author of one of the best-known books on feminism, I do not know</i>	30,7	24,5	33,3	66,7	27,9
<i>defended sexual relations with minors</i>	15,6	54,9	41,7	0	38,4
Rejected	2	1,1	2,1	0	1,5
Total	100	100	100	100	100

Table 117. Practices or has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality.

	Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality				Total
	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, Scientific evidence</i>	262	551	100	16	929
<i>author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors</i>	28,6%	9,5%	13,9%	22,5%	12,4%
Hoax	295	1767	155	13	2230
I do not know	32,2%	30,4%	21,6%	18,3%	29,7%
Rejected	331	3390	444	29	4194
	36,2%	58,4%	61,8%	40,8%	55,9%
	27	95	19	13	154
	3,0%	1,6%	2,6%	18,3%	2,1%
Total	915	5803	718	71	7507
	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

It is also interesting to note how the mere fact of having a family member or close friend engaged in or interested in science impacts the detection of scientific evidence and hoaxes among respondents belonging to an ethnic minority group. In the case of considering the statement that Beauviour fought against sexual relations with minors, the differences between answering the question without applying the crossover with the variable of having a family member or close friend engaged in or interested in science and applying it are minimal. We went from 29.4% to 33.7% who consider it scientific evidence and 8.6% to 10.3% who consider it a hoax. A wider variation is observed when applying the filter of belonging to an ethnic minority group since

54.2% consider it scientific evidence and 14.4% think it is a hoax. There is also a drop from 55.1% to 30.7% of people who say they do not know.

Table 118. Is anyone among your relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science.

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

			Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors</i>	Scientific evidence		912	1006	266	24	2208
			33,7%	26,9%	27,0%	29,6%	29,4%
	Hoax		278	283	72	9	642
			10,3%	7,6%	7,3%	11,1%	8,6%
	I do not know		1493	2387	622	36	4538
			55,1%	63,9%	63,2%	44,4%	60,5%
	Rejected		25	58	24	12	119
			0,9%	1,6%	2,4%	14,8%	1,6%
Total			2708	3734	984	81	7507
			100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Table 119. Is anyone among your relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science (by belonging to a minority ethnic group in %)

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

			Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors</i>	Scientific evidence		54,2	34,4	44,4	33,3	45,9
	Hoax		14,4	12,7	9,3	0	13,2
	I do not know		30,7	52,4	46,3	33,3	40,2
	Rejected		0,7	0,5	0	33,3	0,8
Total			100	100	100	100	100

In the case of the statement regarding whether it defended sexual relations with minors, there are not many differences between having a scientific relative or friend and not having one. From 12.4% to 14.9% consider it scientific evidence, and from 29.7% to 33.5% consider it a hoax. Once again, it increases when the ethnicity variable is included, with 42.6% considering it scientific evidence and 30% a hoax (in this case, it remains the same).

Table 120. Is anyone among your relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science.

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

			Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known</i>	Scientific evidence		404	379	128	18	929
			14,9%	10,1%	13,0%	22,2%	12,4%
	Hoax		906	1080	227	17	2230
			33,5%	28,9%	23,1%	21,0%	29,7%

<i>books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors</i>	I do not know	1349	2213	597	35	4194
		49,8%	59,3%	60,7%	43,2%	55,9%
	Rejected	49	62	32	11	154
		1,8%	1,7%	3,3%	13,6%	2,1%
Total		2708	3734	984	81	7507
		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Table 121. Is anyone among your relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science (by belonging to a minority ethnic group in %)

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors</i>	Scientific evidence	42,6	19	24,1	33,3	32,1
	Hoax	30	25,9	24,1	33,3	27,9
	I do not know	26,4	52,9	50	33,3	38,4
	Rejected	1,1	2,1	1,9	0	1,5
	Total	100	100	100	100	100

The role of interactions should also be highlighted about two key questions related to gender issues. The first focuses on respondents' opinions regarding whether GBV occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners and less frequently in causal relationships. The second focuses on respondents' knowledge of isolating gender-based violence.

Regardless of the role of interactions, 22.9% disagreed with this statement, with 54.3% in favor. When the interactions variable comes into play, in this case, through the variable related to whether the respondents follow people in social networks who are scientists or interested in science, the percentage of those who disagree rises to 25%, and those who agree 59.9%. When incorporating the variable ethnicity, the percentage of people who disagree rises to 33.5%, and the percentage who agree is 59.3% (practically identical).

Thus, following a scientific person on social networks slightly influences the fact that people reject this statement, and it is significantly clearer when incorporating the variable of ethnicity, where people who follow scientific people on social networks are positioned to a greater extent in disagreement with this statement.

Table 122. Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science.

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based</i>	Totally disagree	207	228	91	11	537
		8,3%	6,8%	5,9%	8,7%	7,2%
	Quite disagree	418	516	225	17	1176
		16,7%	15,4%	14,7%	13,5%	15,7%

<i>violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships</i>	Quite agree	1139	1421	571	44	3175
		45,5%	42,5%	37,2%	34,9%	42,3%
	Totally agree	360	379	155	9	903
		14,4%	11,3%	10,1%	7,1%	12,0%
	I do not know	372	774	474	30	1650
		14,8%	23,2%	30,9%	23,8%	22,0%
	Prefer not to answer	10	23	18	15	66
		0,4%	0,7%	1,2%	11,9%	0,9%
Total		2506	3341	1534	126	7507
		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Table 123. Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science (by belonging to a minority ethnic group in %)

		<i>Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality</i>				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships</i>	Totally disagree	37	21	5	0	63
		14,1%	11,8%	6,3%	0,0%	12,0%
	Quite disagree	51	30	16	1	98
		19,4%	16,9%	20,3%	33,3%	18,7%
	Quite agree	87	80	28	1	196
		33,1%	44,9%	35,4%	33,3%	37,5%
	Totally agree	69	26	8	0	103
		26,2%	14,6%	10,1%	0,0%	19,7%
	I do not know	18	21	22	1	62
		6,8%	11,8%	27,8%	33,3%	11,9%
	Prefer not to answer	1	0	0	0	1
		0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%
Total		263	178	79	3	523
		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

5.7.2. Minority religious groups

Out of the total of 7507 people in the sample, 645 reported belonging to a religious minority group, representing 8.6%. As in the case of persons belonging to ethnic minority groups, belonging to a religious minority group generates differences concerning how interactions affect the delimitation of scientific evidence or a hoax. About the incidence of having a close person or a family member in professional gender equality activities to identify hoaxes, 59% place the first of the statements (that it is a hoax) about Beauvoir as scientific evidence, by 23.6% who establish it as a hoax. Without considering the vulnerable group, out of the total number of participants, 46.1% said it was evidence, and 15% said it was a hoax. Therefore, there is an increase in the responses in both cases, which is directly related to the decrease in the number of people who say they do not know, from 37.6% to 16.5%. Therefore, people who have a family member or

friend in a gender equality position respond to a greater extent, either stating that it is evidence or a hoax.

Table 124. Practices or has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality (by belonging to a religious minority in %)

		Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors</i>	Scientific evidence	125	118	24	2	269
		59,0%	32,2%	38,7%	40,0%	41,7%
	Hoax	50	41	8	2	101
		23,6%	11,2%	12,9%	40,0%	15,7%
	I do not know	35	198	29	1	263
		16,5%	54,1%	46,8%	20,0%	40,8%
	Rejected	2	9	1	0	12
		0,9%	2,5%	1,6%	0,0%	1,9%
	Total	212	366	62	5	645
		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

In the second statement, which is scientific evidence, there is an increase in the number of people who identify it as evidence. Without considering the variable of belonging to a minority religious group, 28.6% identify it as evidence, and this percentage increases to 52.4% among people who belong to a minority religious group. In the same way, the percentage of religious people who consider it a hoax is also reduced from 32.2% to 25%. It is also noteworthy that the percentage of people who say they do not know is reduced from 36.2% to 20.3%.

Table 125. Practices or has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality (by belonging to a religious minority group in %)

		Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors</i>	Scientific evidence	111	66	16	3	196
		52,4%	18,0%	25,8%	60,0%	30,4%
	Hoax	53	85	20	2	160
		25,0%	23,2%	32,3%	40,0%	24,8%
	I do not know	43	207	25	0	275
		20,3%	56,6%	40,3%	0,0%	42,6%
	Rejected	5	8	1	0	14
		2,4%	2,2%	1,6%	0,0%	2,2%
	Total	212	366	62	5	645
		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Having a family member or close friend working on scientific issues or interested in them does not affect the case of identifying the first of the statements related to Beauvoir as a hoax and not considering it as scientific evidence. It does impact when we incorporate the variable of belonging to a minority religious group. The first of these statements, that it is a hoax, is

identified as such by 8.6% without taking into account the subject of interactions and increases to 10.3% when introducing, for example, the interaction of having a family member or friend who is a scientist or interested in science. This percentage rises to 16.2% in the case of people belonging to the religious minority group. On the other hand, what also happens is that the percentage of people who consider it as evidence increases to 50.2%.

Table 126. Is anyone among your relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science (by belonging to a religious minority group in %)

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, fought against sexual relations with minors</i>	152	85	30	2	269
Scientific evidence	50,2%	32,0%	42,3%	40,0%	41,7%
Hoax	49	39	11	2	101
I do not know	16,2%	14,7%	15,5%	40,0%	15,7%
Rejected	98	135	29	1	263
	32,3%	50,8%	40,8%	20,0%	40,8%
	4	7	1	0	12
	1,3%	2,6%	1,4%	0,0%	1,9%
Total	303	266	71	5	645
	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Differences were observed in the second statement, with 29.4% considering it scientific evidence without taking interactions into account and 14.9% considering it a hoax. The same happens when it is considered a hoax, from 8.6% to 33.5%. In other words, interactions, such as having a family member or friend who is a scientist or interested in science, impact considering it a hoax. When we include the variable of belonging to a minority religious group, the percentage of people who consider it a hoax decreases to 23.8%, and the percentage who consider it scientific evidence increases to 41.3%. The percentage of people who say they do not know decreases from 49.8% to 32.3%.

Table 127. Is anyone among your relatives or close friends engaged in or interested in science (by belonging to a religious minority group in %)

Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
<i>Simone de Beauvoir, author of one of the best-known books on feminism, defended sexual relations with minors</i>	125	49	19	3	196
Scientific evidence	41,3%	18,4%	26,8%	60,0%	30,4%
Hoax	72	71	16	1	160
I do not know	23,8%	26,7%	22,5%	20,0%	24,8%
Rejected	98	141	35	1	275
	32,3%	53,0%	49,3%	20,0%	42,6%
	8	5	1	0	14
	2,6%	1,9%	1,4%	0,0%	2,2%
Total	303	266	71	5	645
	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

As in the case of the ethnicity variable, belonging to a minority religious group also impacts the view as to whether gender-based violence occurs more in the environment of the partner and ex-partner than in sporadic relationships. People who state that they belong to a religious minority group have a higher percentage concerning disagreeing with this statement. Precisely 32.7% would strongly or somewhat disagree. The percentage who agree is also very high, standing at 60.6%. What does have a clear impact on following a scientist or someone interested in science on social networks is the percentage of not knowing what to say, which is reduced from 14.8% to 6.4%. Being more aware of what is scientific seems to impact positioning oneself when responding to planted claims positively.

Table 128. Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science (by belonging to a religious minority group in %)

		<i>Has any person in your family or close friends practiced any profession or position in the promotion of gender equality</i>				
		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	
<i>To what extent do you agree with the statement that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships</i>	Totally disagree	47	21	5	0	73
		14,4%	10,2%	4,9%	0,0%	11,3%
	Quite disagree	60	33	13	4	110
		18,3%	16,0%	12,6%	44,4%	17,1%
	Quite agree	118	92	46	3	259
		36,1%	44,7%	44,7%	33,3%	40,2%
	Totally agree	80	28	16	0	124
		24,5%	13,6%	15,5%	0,0%	19,2%
	I do not know	21	31	21	2	75
		6,4%	15,0%	20,4%	22,2%	11,6%
Prefer not to answer	1	1	2	0	4	
	0,3%	0,5%	1,9%	0,0%	0,6%	
Total	327	206	103	9	645	
	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	

5.8. Conclusions

<p><i>Scientific evidence and hoax</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 43% of the participants identifies the hoax in education (Schools cannot overcome inequalities), while 58.4% identifies the evidence-based statement “The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income”- In gender, approximately 6 out of 10 of the respondents express that they do not know if the statements are scientific evidence or hoaxes. Only 8.6% identify the hoax and 12.4% the evidence-based statement.
<p><i>Educational expectations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 61.7% of the participants agree to some extent with the affirmation that teachers who know act with high expectations
<p><i>Family participation in schools</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- More than half of the respondents (55.4%) agree to some extent with the importance of families’ participation in schools
<p><i>Segregation and diversity</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Almost one third of the respondents (31%) express that know schools where students are separated according to their academic level.- Almost 4 out of 10 of the respondents (39.6%) think that diversity in schools, with the appropriate measures, is beneficial for all students.
<p><i>Gender differences</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Almost 7 out of 10 respondents (69.3%) express that people around them do not argue that girls have less capacity than boys to develop scientific and technological careers
<p><i>Gender-based violence</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Nearly one third of the respondents (31.1%) identify people around them saying that all men are potential aggressors- More than half of the respondents (54.3%) thinks that gender-based violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners, and less frequently in sporadic relationships.
<p><i>Isolating Gender Violence</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Almost two thirds (65.0%) of the respondents think that it is important to protect those who support the victims of gender violence to end gender-based violence
<p><i>Vulnerable groups</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The proportion of people who identify scientific evidence and hoaxes in education varies across vulnerable groups. Youth aged 16-24 are more likely to identify scientific evidence and hoaxes in education, while ethnic and religious minorities are the groups that more commonly identify scientific evidence and hoaxes in gender.

- Vulnerable groups tend to agree more with the importance of teachers' high expectations, compared with the total of respondents. Women and people from low SES get similar results than the total of and LGBTI+, lower.
- The proportion of people who agree to some extent with the importance of family participation in schools varies across vulnerable groups (from 37.25% in LGBTI+ to 63.86% in ethnic minorities). In all vulnerable groups, people are more likely to agree to some extent than to disagree with the importance of family participation schools. The biggest difference is observed in ethnic minorities.
- Vulnerable groups are more likely to know schools that segregate students depending on their academic level and to have heard that it is scientifically proven that diversity in schools benefits all students (ranging from 32.19% to 50.10% in the first question and from 23.53% to 57.74% in the second). In both cases, people from ethnic and religious minorities are the groups with the highest percentages.
- Vulnerable groups tend to identify more people around them arguing that girls have less capacity for scientific and technological careers than boys. The results range from 22.50% (low SES) to 43.98% (ethnic minorities).
- Vulnerable groups are more likely to identify people around them saying that all men are potential aggressors, ranging from 30.69% to 57.93%. People belonging to ethnic and religious minorities are the most likely to identify this type of comments.
- Between 47.06% and 59.38% of people from vulnerable groups agree that gender violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners and less frequently in sporadic relationships.
- There are not notable differences in the results from people from vulnerable groups compared with the total of respondents in the importance of protecting victims of Isolating Gender Violence.

The role of interactions

- On the one hand interactions with science increase both, people who identify the hoax statement as a hoax and those who think it is an evidence-based statement. On the other hand, they increase the proportion of respondents who identify the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, contributing to the identification of evidence and hoaxes.
- In education, people from low SES and youth aged 25-34 are the groups that benefits the most of interactions with science. Following someone on social media who often publishes about science is the most effective interaction in education. Interactions with science not always have impact in helping people to distinguish scientific evidence from hoaxes in gender.
- In general, the proportion of people who identify the hoax statement as a hoax is higher than the percentage of those who think it is an evidence-based statement. The same happens in the identification of the evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, with some exceptions.

- Interactions with science increase all response options, but the highest increases are found in the responses that agree to some extent with the importance of teachers' expectations. The vulnerable group that benefits the most of interactions with science are people from low SES, who get the highest increases, followed by women. In general, the most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science.
- After interactions with science, participants are more likely agree with the importance of family participation in schools. The most effective interaction is changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families and the group that is most benefitted from these interactions with science are people from low socioeconomic status, with increments of approximately 18%.
- Interactions with science increase the proportion of those who identify schools that segregate students depending on their academic level and also those who think that diversity in schools benefits all students. In both questions, the highest impact is achieved when people follow on social media someone who often publishes about science and the group that benefits the most of interactions with science are people from low socioeconomic status, with the highest increases.
- Interactions with science increase the percentage of people who identify people around them arguing that girls have less capacity than boys for scientific and technological careers. The most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science and the group that benefits the most are people from low SES.
- People from vulnerable groups are more likely to identify people around them saying that all men are potential aggressors when they interact with science. The highest increases are achieved when people follow on social media someone who often publishes about science and people from low SES are the group with the highest increments. In addition, people tend to disagree more with the idea that gender violence occurs more frequently between partners and ex-partners and less in sporadic relationships when they interact with science.
- Interactions have an impact in increasing the proportion of people who agree with the importance of protecting those who support the victims of gender violence. In all vulnerable groups across the analysed interactions, more than 6 out of 10 of the respondents agree to some extent with this question. The highest impact of interactions is found in women and the least in ethnic minorities. The most effective interaction is following someone on social media who often publishes about science.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this report was to identify in both, face to face interactions and social media interactions, how societal actors, including young citizens and vulnerable groups, benefit from the social impact of scientific research in the framework of two Sustainable Development Goals –Quality Education and Gender Equality. In order to do so, the main elements facilitate (transformative dimension) and obstacles hinder (exclusionary dimension) the targeted impacts have been identified.

Using a mixed method approach, this report has been informed by a literature review in top-ranked journals published in Journal Citation Reports and Scopus, analytics of social media (SMA) on four different networks -Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and Reddit -- communicative focus groups (FG) and an international survey. Among the main elements that facilitate scientific, political and social impact there are co-creation of scientific knowledge, egalitarian dialogue with all sectors of society (including those that have traditionally been excluded from science), interactions with science and social media interactions.

The main results respond to the objective of how societal actors, including young citizens and vulnerable groups, benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education by identifying four key elements that facilitate and foster this impact: 1) Research with social impact has co-creation at the core of the intervention, 2) Egalitarian dialogue involving all sectors of society contributes to the social impact of research, 3) Interactions with science contribute to the identification of scientific evidence and hoax in gender and education and 4) Social media is an effective agora to share and discuss about science.

Research with social impact has co-creation at the core of the intervention

Social impact of research is achieved when, when once the results of research have been published, disseminated and transferred, they improve citizens' lives in relation to the objectives such as the Sustainable Development Goals¹⁴. After an in-depth analysis of existing scientific articles about the topic of this report, the results point out that actions that give importance to the **co-creation of knowledge and combine scientific evidence and local knowledge provided by communities achieve greater impact**. This finding was observed in diverse educational contexts, including schools, high schools, universities, and informal learning centres, as well as in the promotion of effective evidence-based programs on preventive socialisation of gender-based violence. Therefore, in order to build fair and sustainable societies, researchers should create spaces for the co-production of knowledge with the participation of all sectors of society, **including those that have traditionally been excluded from scientific processes**. Then,

¹⁴ Reale, E., Avramov, D., Canhial, K., Donovan, C., Flecha, R., Holm, P., ... & Van Horik, R. (2018). A review of literature on evaluating the scientific, social and political impact of social sciences and humanities research. *Research Evaluation*, 27(4), 298-308. <http://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvx025>
Soler-Gallart, M. (2017). *Achieving social impact: sociology in the public sphere*. Springer. <http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60270-7>
IMPACT-EV. (2015). *Research Briefing. Social Impact of Research*. Recuperat de http://impact-ev.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/research_briefing.pdf

interactions between scientific knowledge provided by universities and experience-based knowledge provided by citizens will produce better research outcomes and relevant that respond to citizens' needs and the challenges of society.

Some examples in this regard can be found in SMA, where the messages that contained **real examples of social impact of research** consisted of actions promoted by NGOs involving **all members of communities** and were explicitly **linked to the achievement of SDGs**, or Wikipedia, as an accurate and reliable encyclopaedia that has its basis on certified scientific sources and co-creation of knowledge. Another example is found in the FG, where participants remarked that Dialogic Scientific Gatherings -one of the Successful Educational Actions that is based on the co-creation of knowledge through reading and discussing scientific works- promoted scientific literacy among participants, as well as interest towards science, empowerment and self-confidence. In addition, Dialogic Scientific Gathering promoted the participation in scientific events (gatherings, talks or conferences) in the associations/schools, encouraged teachers to make new scientific activities inside their school and improve the atmosphere among teachers of the same school.

Egalitarian dialogue involving all sectors of society contributes to the social impact of research

Existing scientific evidence analysed in the literature review points that changes in legislation improve education for all when they have two key characteristics: are based on scientific evidence in the field of education and give high priority to the engagement of an egalitarian dialogue with community members. Therefore, the scalability and transference of educational practice depends on the characteristics of the dialogue shared during the process between all stakeholders. In the same direction, on SMA, a common finding across social networks and strategies is that within the examples of real cases of social impact of research there were messages that share the impact achieved by specific actions in the promotion of women political participation, black women health, access to water, financial and technical women empowerment, and COVID-19 gender labour gap, among others. These messages provided examples of how NGOs, partnerships of NGOs, educational settings, companies, citizens' platforms and universities in dialogue with communities benefit from specific research outcomes that were improving citizens' lives and responding to the challenges of society. In this line, the following figure represents how in the **bottom-up strategy** in which hashtags and messages emerged directly from the interests of society, **there is a greater proportion of messages in which citizens benefit from social impact of research**, in contrast with the top-down strategy.

Impact across strategies

Figure 1. Proportion of messages with scientific, political and social impact on social media across strategies

Another related example is obtained from the qualitative data of the FG, where participants expressed that **the egalitarian dialogue shared in the Scientific Dialogic Gatherings** encourages people to be curious, to **increase the knowledge of scientific vocabulary and provides the motivation for people to transform their environment**, while improving the educational practices of the teachers.

Interactions with science contribute to the identification of scientific evidence and hoax in gender and education

Qualitative and quantitative data point to the same direction. On the one hand, participants from FG expressed that the use of social media for research dissemination purposes was very important, as it contributes to teach people how to identify verified content from fake news. Therefore, participants believe that science and scientific research must occupy as much space as possible, in order to prevent fake news or not verified information to spread and reaching the population in general. Quantitative data from the survey points to the same direction. The results show that interactions with science increase both, people who identify a hoax statement as a hoax and the proportion of respondents who identify an evidence-based statement as scientific evidence, contributing to the identification of evidence and hoaxes. The following figure that **interactions with science increase the proportion of people from vulnerable groups who distinguish scientific evidence and hoxes** in gender and education.

Figure 2. Increases in the identification of scientific evidence in gender and education across vulnerable groups and interactions with science¹⁵

One example of the identification of scientific evidence and hoaxes can be found in SMA, especially on Twitter and Reddit where **users are more likely to interact with those messages that are based on scientific evidence than with those without it**. In this line, in one of the analysed reddit communities, the average punctuation of those posts and comments without scientific evidence was 23.95, compared with the 238.55 points of those with certified scientific evidence and 25.04 of those with supposed scientific evidence.

Social media is an effective agora to share and discuss about science.

Social media has gained an undeniable presence in citizens' lives and it has become a space not only for social interactions among citizens from around the world. The analysis of the qualitative and quantitative data in this report concludes that social media has also become an effective agora for the exchange and discussion on scientific topics. On the one hand, women participants and especially youth express in the FG that they learn and benefit from the scientific, political and social impact of research through social media. They remarked that social media may boost scientific research due to the conversations running through different timelines and platforms. In this sense, social networks are perceived as an input for researchers about the topics that interest social media users and population in general, and which could result in new researches or studies. For this reason, scientific research should use social media in order to disseminate results

¹⁵ I1 (Interaction 1)- Changing their mind about science because something happened to them or their families
 I2.often- Following someone on social media who often publishes about science
 I2.rarely – Following someone on social media who rarely publishes about science

The SMA enabled to identify how researchers succeed at reaching citizens when sharing their research on social media and also how users adopt scientific concepts and arguments and discuss about scientific topics on the different social networks. Although the four analysed networks (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and Reddit) have different characteristics and purposes, all of them are used for any of these purposes. In addition, citizens value scientific contributions on social media, use them in discussions on social media and in some cases ask for scientific evidence, which are examples of how citizens benefit from scientific research. The following figure shows how **in the bottom-up strategy more than half of the messages contained some type of scientific evidence.**

Figure 3. Presence of scientific evidence on social media across strategies

Quantitative results from the survey also support this finding as identified that **following someone on social media who often publishes about science is the most effective interaction** with science in the promotion of scientific literacy and identification of evidence and hoaxes. In addition, **the impact of this interaction tends to be higher in people from low socioeconomic status and women.** Finally, participants in the SMCO expressed that social media allowed them to reflect, argue, motivate them to learn more and to engage in virtual dialogue with other users about what they have found in scientific articles, their experiences, or their point of view.

This report explored how citizens benefit from scientific research in gender and education, by identifying what elements facilitate (transformative dimension) and what obstacles hinder (exclusionary dimension) scientific, political and social impact. This way, by promoting these transformative elements and overcoming exclusionary barriers, it will be possible to maximise scientific, political and social impact. On the one hand, among the main elements that facilitate scientific, political and social impact there are co-creation of scientific knowledge, egalitarian dialogue with all sectors of society (including those that have traditionally been excluded from science), interactions with science and social media interactions. On the other hand, the main obstacles that were identified were language barriers and that scientific outcomes do not always reach all sectors of society, leaving behind those who are more in need of the benefits of scientific research. Therefore, scientific research must ensure an inclusive dissemination of science that promotes not only scientific impact, but political and social as well.